

Copyright 2023 Alexander Thomas Gagliano

BUILDING A COMPREHENSIVE PICTURE OF STELLAR DEATH
FOR THE ERA OF SYNOPTIC SURVEYS

BY

ALEXANDER THOMAS GAGLIANO

DISSERTATION

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Astronomy
in the Graduate College of the
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, 2023

Urbana, Illinois

Doctoral Committee:

Professor Brian Fields, Chair

Assistant Professor Gautham Narayan, Director of Research

Associate Professor Yue Shen

Assistant Professor Ryan Foley, University of California, Santa Cruz

Abstract

Nearly a century after their interpretation as the terminal stages of stellar evolution, countless questions still surround the physics powering supernovae. Without the ability to observe a star at the precise moment of its demise, our efforts to trace observed phenomenology back to nature of the terminal progenitor system are limited. This thesis attempts to clarify this connection through a detailed analysis of an explosion’s local environment and signatures of interaction detected within the first few days of an explosion. We emphasize the value of these early-signatures through a comprehensive analysis of the nearby SN Ic 2020oi, and reveal its nature as the detonation of a low-mass ($\sim 9.5 M_{\odot}$) binary progenitor enshrouded with $\sim 0.1 M_{\odot}$ of circumstellar material. To quantify the statistical leverage offered by a transient’s host galaxy, we construct the Galaxies HOsting Supernovae and other Transients (GHOST) catalog of 16,175 supernovae and the photometric properties of their associated host galaxies from the first Data Release of the Pan-STARRS 3- π survey. We use a random forest classification model to distinguish between Type-Ia and Type-II SNe with $\sim 68\%$ accuracy, and release a series of software tools that can be used to improve host-galaxy association at scale. Next, we forecast the host-galaxy correlations that will be revealed in deep upcoming surveys extending to $z < 3$, and release the Simulated Catalog of Optical Transients and Correlated Hosts (SCOTCH) for benchmarking upcoming classification algorithms. We use this catalog to train a ‘First Impressions’ classifier, consisting of a recurrent neural network trained on synthetic samples and validated on supernovae from the Zwicky Transient Facility Bright Transient Sample (ZTF BTS). This classifier achieves a total accuracy of 83% within the first three days, a first in the literature; at thirty days, the precision and recall achieved are comparable to full-phase networks in the literature with more complex architectures. On the precipice of the Vera C. Rubin Observatory’s unprecedented discovery rates, computational techniques able to leverage physical correlations will be essential for further clarifying progenitor physics and identifying objects of interest for targeted follow-up campaigns.

For my family, whose rich expanse of interests and everlasting support have affirmed my conviction that every facet of this world (and of those beyond it) is worthy of dedicated study.

Acknowledgments

This work would not have been possible without countless people who, in ways both obvious and imperceptible, supported my growth as an astronomer and as a human being over the past decade. This dissertation is an investigation into the environment that shapes a star and its demise. I view my trajectory through a similar lens of interconnection (hopefully with a cheerier outcome, though time will tell).

Eternal thanks to my adviser, Gautham Narayan, who offered steady guidance at all hours as I translated my enthusiasm for a scientific question into a rigorous methodology for chipping away at its answer. His descriptions of himself as a ‘recovering SN Ia cosmologist’ did little to deter me from working with him, nor did the umpteen Slack channels he proudly displayed; his tireless advocacy on my behalf over the past four years proved that I made the right call. My committee members deserve additional thanks: Brian Fields, Yue Shen, and Ryan Foley each offered sustained encouragement, as did the suite of additional mentors with whom I have been lucky to have collaborated throughout my graduate career - Renée Hložek, Dan Foreman-Mackey, Gaby Contardo, and Ashley Villar. Each of these researchers established a tradition of careful and kind analysis to which I have continually aspired.

Long before graduate school, mentors cemented in my mind the pleasure of extracting insight from observation. My research trajectory began with George Wolfe, Duke Writer and Jeremy Schnittman at the Loudoun Academy of Science, and the torch was passed to, among others, Colonel Dave Miller and Mark Embree at Virginia Tech. A short stint at the Cerro-Tololo Inter-American Observatory brought me to the study of globular clusters alongside Juan Madrid, who led me to a terminal after lamenting my inexperience with Linux/Unix with the quip that ‘Bill Gates has ruined you’. Kevin Govender at the International Astronomical Society’s Office of Astronomy for Development instilled in me a lasting consideration for the societal impacts of my work after a night in Sutherland marked by the brightest stars I have ever seen, and my time with Joe Smidt and Ayçin Aykutalp at Los Alamos National Laboratory pushed me to articulate and defend my ideas (both astronomical and metaphysical). I’m grateful for each of these experiences.

The transition from studying computational modeling in my undergraduate years to astrophysics in my graduate ones was an abrupt one. My programming language of choice was R and not Python, and I couldn’t figure out why every problem was being solved with Monte Carlo sampling. What kept me motivated in those early years gaining foundational knowledge was how much *fun* I was having. I attribute much of that excitement to my close-knit cohort: Cassidy Wagner, Melanie Archipley, Colin Burke, Patrick Aleo, Frank

Fu, Cail Daley, and Amelia Mangian. Debating the nuances of radiative processes at the dry-erase board in my apartment at 2 am is one of the fondest memories I have of the past five years. Chris Tandoi and Bre Lucero were and forever will be honorary members of this cohort. Thank you all for making it so much fun.

The University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign supported this work through an Illinois Distinguished Fellowship, as did the National Science Foundation through a Graduate Research Fellowship (DGE-1746047), and the Center for AstroPhysical Surveys through a Survey Science Fellowship. The Flatiron Institute allowed me to continue my foray into neural networks as a Pre-Doctoral Fellow at the Center For Computational Astrophysics.

A lifetime of thanks goes to my loving parents, siblings, and friends, and the constellation of collaborators scattered across the University of Illinois, the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration, the Flatiron Institute, astro[*sound*]bites, and the Young Supernova Experiment. Their encouragement has strengthened my resolve to leave a community better than I found it. This mission continues in spite of the closing of Clever Moose, my favorite coffee shop in Champaign, in the final semester of my program. Much of my research was completed there long after close while I was fueled by discount lattes.

Finally, my completion of this dissertation and the final year of my studies were vastly enriched by the support of my partner Abigail, who reminded me that it is possible to strive for great things while retaining a kind heart and investing in simple pleasures.

Despite the obstacles that have arisen in completing this dissertation through a global pandemic and years of lockdown, I have never felt alone.

Table of Contents

List of Abbreviations	viii
Chapter 1 Introduction	4
1.1 Background: The Landscape of Time-Domain Surveys	4
1.2 Supernova Physics	5
1.3 The Value of Host-Galaxy Information	16
1.4 Transient Classification Techniques	21
Chapter 2 An Early-Time Optical and Ultraviolet Excess in the type-Ic SN 2020oi	25
2.1 Introduction	25
2.2 Observations	27
2.3 Host Galaxy Extinction	33
2.4 Bolometric Light Curve Fitting	34
2.5 Explosion Kinetics from Bolometric Fitting	37
2.6 Inferences on the Pre-Explosion Mass-Loss History	41
2.7 Spectral Analysis	42
2.8 The Very Early Spectrum of SN 2020oi	44
2.9 Characterizing the Early-Time Emission of SN 2020oi	45
2.10 Properties of the Stellar Cluster Coincident with 2020oi	51
2.11 Host-Galaxy Properties from MUSE Spectroscopy	52
2.12 Deducing the Properties of the SN 2020oi Progenitor	55
2.13 Conclusions	56
Chapter 3 Galaxies Hosting Supernovae and Other Transients (GHOST)	77
3.1 Introduction	77
3.2 Host Galaxy Identification	78
3.3 Data and Software Products	93
3.4 Dimensionality Reduction	95
3.5 Supernova Classification	103
3.6 Supernova Siblings	113
3.7 Conclusions	114
Chapter 4 The Catalog of Optical Transients and Correlated Hosts (SCOTCH)	117
4.1 Introduction	117
4.2 Methodology Overview	119
4.3 Galaxy Data	120
4.4 Generating Transients with the SNANA Simulation	123
4.5 Host Library Creation (HOSTLIB)	131

4.6	Transient-Host Galaxy Correlations (WGTMAP)	137
4.7	Offsets from the Host Center	146
4.8	Validation of Host Galaxy Correlations	148
4.9	Catalog Access and Intended Use	154
4.10	Conclusions	159
4.11	Data Availability	162
Chapter 5 First Impressions: Early-Time Classification of Supernovae using Host Galaxy Information and Shallow Learning		
		163
5.1	Introduction	163
5.2	Data	165
5.3	Data Pre-Processing	170
5.4	Model Architecture	176
5.5	Primary and Adaptive Training	179
5.6	Results	180
5.7	Conclusions	186
Chapter 6 Conclusions and The Road Ahead		
		193
Appendix A Details Concerning the Construction and Use of the SCOTCH Catalog		
		198
A.1	Approximate Nearest-Neighbours Matching of GHOST and CosmoDC2 Galaxies with ANNOY	198
A.2	Using the SCOTCH Catalog	199
Appendix B Consolidated Optical and UV Photometry of SN Ic 2020oi		
		207
References		
		238

List of Abbreviations

SN	Supernova
CSM	Circumstellar Material
SESN	Stripped-Envelope Supernova
CCSN	Core-Collapse Supernova
YSE	Young Supernova Experiment
GP	Gaussian Process
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SCE	Shock-Cooling Emission
GHOST	Galaxies HOsting Supernovae And other Transients (catalog of 16,000 observed SNe and their host galaxies)
SCOTCH	Synthetic Catalog of Optical Transients and Correlated Hosts (catalog of 5 million synthetic transients and their host galaxies)
AUROC	Area Under the Receiver Operator Characteristic Curve
AUPRC	Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve

Foreword

This dissertation is laid out as follows. In Chapter 1 I provide a historical overview into the study of supernova host galaxies and their early-time signatures. In Chapter 2, I analyze the physics and environment of SN 2020oi, a nearby (d 17 Mpc) type Ic supernova whose early photometry revealed flux in excess of comparable events of its class. This chapter is based upon the publication “An Early-Time Optical and Ultraviolet Excess in the type-Ic SN 2020oi” [165]. In chapter 3, I consolidate the photometric properties of 16,176 supernova host galaxies and investigate the value of this information for the binary classification problem. This chapter is based upon the publication “GHOST: Using Only Host Galaxy Information to Accurately Associate and Distinguish Supernovae” [164]. I then discuss my work to construct a homogeneous, volume-limited sample of synthetic transients with realistic host-galaxy properties for training upcoming analysis pipelines in Chapter 4. This chapter is based upon the publication “The Simulated Catalogue of Optical Transients and Correlated Hosts (SCOTCH)” [306]. I then construct a physically-motivated real-time transient classifier in Chapter 5, which is based on the publication “First Impressions: Early-Time Classification of Supernovae using Host Galaxy Information and Shallow Learning” (Gagliano et al., 2023, in review). I present my conclusions and provide an overview of my upcoming work in Chapter 6.

In addition to these first and co-first-author publications, I have collaborated on a number of co-author publications during the completion of my dissertation. Some of these are discussed throughout this dissertation where relevant; all are listed below for completeness:

- P. D. Aleo, K. Malanchev, S. Sharief, D. O. Jones, G. Narayan, R. J. Foley, V. A. Villar, C. R. Angus, V. F. Baldassare, M. J. Bustamante-Rosell, D. Chatterjee, C. Cold, D. A. Coulter, K. W. Davis, S. Dhawan, M. R. Drout, A. Engel, K. D. French, A. Gagliano, C. Gall, et al. “The Young Supernova Experiment Data Release 1 (YSE DR1): Light Curves and Photometric Classification of 1975 Supernovae”. *arXiv e-prints*, doi:10.48550/arXiv.2211.07128.
- C. R. Angus, V. F. Baldassare, B. Mockler, R. J. Foley, E. Ramirez-Ruiz, S. I. Raimundo, K. D. French, K. Auchettl, H. Pfister, C. Gall, J. Hjorth, M. R. Drout, K. D. Alexander, G. Dimitriadis, T. Hung, D. O. Jones, A. Rest, M. R. Siebert, K. Taggart, G. Terreran, et al. “A fast-rising tidal disruption event

from a candidate intermediate-mass black hole”. *Nature Astronomy* 6.

- Francisco Förster, Alejandra M. Muñoz Arancibia, Ignacio Reyes-Jainaga, *Alexander Gagliano*, Dylan Britt, Sara Cuellar-Carrillo, Felipe Figueroa-Tapia, Ava Polzin, Yara Yousef, Javier Arredondo, Diego Rodríguez-Mancini, Javier Correa-Orellana, Amelia Bayo, Franz E. Bauer, Márcio Catelan, Guillermo Cabrera-Vives, Raya Dastidar, Pablo A. Estévez, Giuliano Pignata, Lorena Hernández-García, et al. “DELIGHT: Deep Learning Identification of Galaxy Hosts of Transients using Multiresolution Images”. 164.5, 195.
- W. V. Jacobson-Galán, L. Dessart, D. O. Jones, R. Margutti, D. L. Coppejans, G. Dimitriadis, R. J. Foley, C. D. Kilpatrick, D. J. Matthews, S. Rest, G. Terreran, P. D. Aleo, K. Auchettl, P. K. Blanchard, D. A. Coulter, K. W. Davis, T. J. L. de Boer, L. DeMarchi, M. R. Drout, N. Earl, et al. “Final Moments. I. Precursor Emission, Envelope Inflation, and Enhanced Mass Loss Preceding the Luminous Type II Supernova 2020tlf”. *ApJ*, 924.1, 15.
- D. O. Jones, R. J. Foley, G. Narayan, J. Hjorth, M. E. Huber, P. D. Aleo, K. D. Alexander, C. R. Angus, K. Auchettl, V. F. Baldassare, S. H. Bruun, K. C. Chambers, D. Chatterjee, D. L. Coppejans, D. A. Coulter, L. DeMarchi, G. Dimitriadis, M. R. Drout, A. Engel, K. D. French, et al. “The Young Supernova Experiment: Survey Goals, Overview, and Operations”. 908.2, 143 (Feb. 2021), p. 143. doi: 10.3847/1538-4357/abd7f5.
- Juan P. Madrid, Conor R. O’Neill, *Alexander T. Gagliano*, and Joshua R. Marvil. “A Wide-field Map of Intracluster Globular Clusters in Coma”. *ApJ*, 867.2, 144.
- Samaporn Tanyanont, Stan E. Woosley, Kirsty Taggart, Ryan J. Foley, Lin Yan, Ragnhild Lunnan, Kyle W. Davis, Charles D. Kilpatrick, Matthew R. Siebert, Steve Schulze, Chris Ashall, Ting-Wan Chen, Kishalay De, Georgios Dimitriadis, Dillon Z. Dong, Christoffer Fremling, *Alexander Gagliano*, Saurabh W. Jha, David O. Jones, Mansi M. Kasliwal, et al. “Supernova 2020wnt: An Atypical Superluminous Supernova with a Hidden Central Engine”. *arXiv e-prints*, doi:10.48550/arXiv.2212.00177.
- Sam M. Ward, Stephen Thorp, Kaisey S. Mandel, Suhail Dhawan, David O. Jones, Kirsty Taggart, Ryan J. Foley, Gautham Narayan, Kenneth C. Chambers, David A. Coulter, Kyle W. Davis, Thomas de Boer, Kaylee de Soto, Nicholas Earl, *Alex Gagliano*, Hua Gao, Jens Hjorth, Mark E. Huber, Luca Izzo, Danial Langeroodi, et al. “SN 2021hpr and its two siblings in the Cepheid calibrator galaxy NGC 3147: A hierarchical BayeSN analysis of a Type Ia supernova trio, and a Hubble constant constraint”. *arXiv e-prints*, doi:10.48550/arXiv.2209.10558.
- Yossef Zenati, Qinan Wang, Alexey Bobrick, Lindsay DeMarchi, Hila Glanz, Mor Rozner, Armin Rest, Brian D. Metzger, Raffaella Margutti, Sebastian Gomez, Nathan Smith, Silvia Toonen, Joe S.

Bright, Colin Norman, Ryan J. Foley, *Alexander Gagliano*, Julian H. Krolik, Stephen J. Smartt, Ashley V. Villar, Gautham Narayan, et al. “Evidence for Extended Hydrogen-Poor CSM in the Three-Peaked Light Curve of Stripped Envelope Ib Supernova”. *arXiv e-prints*, doi:[10.48550/arXiv.2207.07146](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2207.07146).

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background: The Landscape of Time-Domain Surveys

Dramatic advancements in both software and strategy have shifted the landscape of time-domain astrophysics. Surveys spanning wide swaths of the night sky have grown increasingly ambitious in recent years, driven by the success of the archetypal Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS; [520]) and building on the serendipitous discovery and high-cadence, multi-wavelength coverage of the nearby supernova (SN) 1987A [see 22, for a comprehensive review]. These surveys have balanced sky coverage and depth, and can be broadly grouped into two categories: low-redshift and wide-field searches, including the Nearby SN Factory [SNFactory; 7], the Texas SN Search [398], the Pan-STARRS Survey for Transients [PSST; 230], the All-Sky Automated Survey for SNe [ASAS-SN; 280], the Foundation Supernova Survey [144, 245], the Asteroid Terrestrial-impact Last Alert System [ATLAS; 486], the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF; [40]), and the Young SN Experiment [YSE; 246]; and targeted, high-redshift, and narrow-field searches, including the Sloan Digital Sky Survey-II SN Survey [427], SN Cosmology project [379], Deep Lens Survey [37] and the Pan-STARRS Medium Deep survey [MDS; 497]. These complementary campaigns have culminated in an ($\mathcal{O}(5000 \text{ yr}^{-1})$) transient discovery rate that has increased exponentially since the turn of the century. The Vera C. Rubin Observatory [Rubin Observatory; 233] is slated to annually discover 10^6 transients¹ beginning at first light in 2025, single-handedly surpassing this exponential scaling and offering our first window into the dynamic sky spanning $0 < z < 1$.

The scientific value of these endeavors has been validated by the panoply of perplexing transient behavior that has been discovered. Extant samples now encompass rapidly-evolving transients, with the first statistical samples recovered from the Pan-STARRS (PS1; [487]) Medium-Deep survey [124]; Fast Blue Optical Transients with decay timescales incompatible with the radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni ; and kilonova emission from the merging of neutron stars, which has been definitively associated with a short-duration

¹https://www.lsst.org/sites/default/files/docs/sciencebook/SB_11.pdf

gamma-ray burst [2] (and, more recently, a long-duration gamma-ray burst [403]). The high-cadence photometric and spectroscopic coverage that has unveiled these short-duration phenomena has spurred complementary advancements in our understanding of common supernovae and their behavior in the first few days of an explosion (although, at the level of current surveys, these signals are often plagued by degeneracies).

The data-rich era of wide-field surveys and multi-messenger astrophysics demands automated techniques for prompt event filtering and analysis. A algorithmic ecosystem has flourished of alert brokers (including ANTARES; [334]; ALeRCE; [149]; Fink; [350]; and Lasair; [455]), systems which process raw data, perform preliminary analyses (ranging from photometric redshift estimation to anomaly detection), and consolidate results into a high-level overview for human consumption. These results inform marshals, platforms for automated coordination of telescope follow-up [291, 253, 107] (and, soon, real-time automatic target selection [467]). Once brokers have reduced the stream of alerts and marshals have prioritized targets for observation, these objects are sent to Target and Observation Managers (TOMs; [470]) for scheduling.

Our understanding of the physics underlying transient behavior, and of the computational infrastructure relevant for their analysis, are in continual co-evolution. Real-time classifiers now leverage advances in Recurrent and Convolutional Neural Networks [355, 349, 395] as well as variational auto-encoders [501, 48], while the detection of astrophysical anomalies has seen the use of isolation forests and the Local Outlier Factor of each event (sometimes only after projection into a locality-sensitive latent space of lower dimensionality; see [303] for an overview of common techniques). To ensure both their interpretability and performance across diverse observing conditions, these algorithms should be designed and specialized for targeted science cases. The ‘ideal’ analysis algorithm both codifies our prior understanding of the relevant astrophysical systems (including their characteristic timescales and most significant features), while being pliable enough to allow for serendipitous discoveries. We present an overview of these astrophysical systems, their observational characteristics, and the environments where they occur (their ‘host galaxies’) below.

1.2 Supernova Physics

Background: Discerning the Nature of Stellar Death from Early Observations

Following the recognition of a supernova (SN) as an astrophysical phenomenon distinct from traditional novae by Baade and Zwicky in 1934 [28], campaigns began to systematically observe these events in local galaxies. Many of the searches were led by Baade and Zwicky with the 100-inch Schmidt Telescope at Palomar Observatory. Three SNe were observed in a period of ~ 1.5 years between 1936 and 1938, leading to a local rate determination of ~ 1 SN per galaxy per 600 years [525]. During this same period, spectroscopy of the Crab nebula had confirmed its expansion; its sky location suggested an association with a ‘guest

star' observed in the year 1054 [310]. By comparing the angular expansion rate of the nebula from photographic plates spanning 11 years with the expansion velocity inferred from doppler-shifted spectral lines, an estimated distance of 5,000 light years was deduced. The observability of the event at these distances revealed its nature as an SN, showing conclusively that significant masses of stellar material were ejected in the phenomenon.

The Zwicky-Minkowski classification taxonomy was introduced shortly thereafter [343]. Events were categorized as *Type II* whose spectra featured hydrogen absorption lines, and as *Type I* whose spectra lacked them. By the 1940's, it was known that type I SNe had peak-light spectra that were remarkably homogeneous between events (significantly more so than observed novae). Only oxygen lines had been conclusively identified in the SN I spectrum. These spectra were later (correctly) interpreted to be a composite of a hot thermal background and heavily doppler-broadened lines from expanding ejecta [510]. Type II SNe, noted for their heterogeneity, were observed to lie nearly exclusively in spiral galaxies despite the relative dearth of them among the low-redshift galaxy population [343]. Lower limits were placed on an explosion's effective temperature on the assumption that the intrinsic luminosity was at least four times what could be observed in visible light (hydrogen recombination was known to emit ultraviolet photons with at least three times the energy of optical photons; [524]). The linear decline rate of SN I photometry was thought to reflect the radioactive decay of *some* element, potentially Californium-254 [29] (an argument ostensibly supported by the Californium-254 detected in the ground-based thermonuclear explosion of the 'Mike' device in 1952 on the Enewetak Atoll [104]); a decade later the true decay chain responsible, starting with ^{56}Ni , was identified [103]).

As the mathematical implications of late-stage stellar evolution were resolved in the literature, physical explanations for these enigmatic events began to grow. Milne in 1930 [342] proposed that stars undergoing collapse inevitably produced novae, and in 1940 the role of neutrinos in carrying massive amounts of energy from a system and permitting a gravitational collapse was realized [174] (despite the neutrino having been only theorized). Among the dramatic theoretical leaps made during this time were those introduced in [29] in 1956. It was proposed that an SN I marked the implosion of a star with a sub-solar radius and a CNO core in an 'advanced evolutionary stage.' The implosion was believed to cause a corresponding temperature increase sufficient to unbind the stellar envelope and trigger explosive nucleosynthesis. In the following year, [65] noted that this implosion would occur in a star as it exceeded the Chandrasekhar mass limit. They additionally note that stars above $M_* > 10 M_\odot$ could meet a similar fate before a significant fraction of their nuclear energy had been spent (explaining the hydrogen-rich spectra in SNe II). Hoyle and Fowler in 1960 [229] completed the push toward a concordant picture of SNe I in predicting that explosive unbinding of a low-mass evolved star could take place *without* being preceded by an implosion, instead being caused by ignition of unstable degenerate stellar material. The early recognition of SNe I (comprising only SNe Ia at this time) as being caused by runaway burning, and of SNe II as being implosion-driven, remains our broad conceptual picture of stellar death to this day.

Core-Collapse SNe: Observational Properties and Progenitor Systems

A supernova marks the runaway detonation of a star unable to maintain hydrodynamic stability. Through the vast majority of a star’s lifetime, gravitational contraction is held at bay by gas pressure generated by nuclear fusion in the stellar core (in a white dwarf, the balance is maintained through electron degeneracy pressure). The irrevocable disruption of this interplay culminates in one of two physical scenarios. In a *core-collapse supernova* (CCSN), a star of zero-age main sequence mass $M_* > 8 M_\odot$ collapses following iron/nickel fusion in the stellar core and rebounds when finally counteracted by the nuclear strong force, generating a shock wave that unbinds the stellar envelope. This shock wave triggers the explosive nucleosynthesis of substantial quantities of additional ^{56}Ni , which then decays by $^{56}\text{Ni} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Co} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Fe}$. It is the emission from this radioactive decay that marks a primary contributor to the optical emission observed in CCSNe. The supernova ejecta, once comprising a core of mass $\sim M_\odot$ compacted into a radius of $\sim R_\oplus$, then expands outward at roughly the escape velocity of the system:

$$v_{\text{ej}} \approx \sqrt{GM_\odot/R_\oplus} \approx 10^4 \text{ km s}^{-1} \quad (1.1)$$

CCSNe comprise the dominant pathway toward stellar detonation. In the other, the carbon-oxygen core of a white dwarf approaches the Chandrasekhar limit and ignites, detonating as a *thermonuclear supernova* (SN Ia).

In recent years, supernova taxonomy has swelled to encompass nearly a dozen sub-classes differing in spectral character (Fig. 1.2) and occurrence rate (Fig. 1.1). SNe II, CCSNe characterized by the presence of strong hydrogen lines with P-Cygni profiles from the emitting ejecta, exhibit the most diversity. The most common class of CCSN, SNe IIP, exhibit a photometric plateau lasting for months following the initial explosion. This behavior can be understood as the roughly constant energy output from a tenuous shock-heated stellar envelope ionized shortly after its accelerated expansion by the supernova shock. During the plateau phase of the explosion, the ejecta opacity is dominated by electron scattering. The ionized envelope expands homologously and cools. This continues until the outer edge of the envelope cools to the hydrogen recombination temperature ($\sim 5 \text{ K}$) and a recombination front forms, which propagates inward and rapidly decreases the opacity of the ejecta. Energy injection from radioactive ^{56}Ni and ^{56}Co can also contribute to the observed luminosity, at first negligibly and soon a major producer of photons (although this is dependent upon the properties of the progenitor system). This evolving contribution serves to extend the observed plateau and alter its decline rate [285].

In contrast, SNe IIL exhibit a linear dimming rate of \sim hundredths of a magnitude per day before settling into a tail dominated by radioactive decay [173]. They are more luminous at peak and exhibit higher expansion velocities than their plateau counterparts. It has long been assumed that these two classes differ in the degree of stripping of the stellar envelope that takes place prior to detonation. This conceptual framework has been supported by radiation-hydrodynamic models of the red supergiants responsible for

Figure 1.1: Relative proportions of common SNe in a volume-limited sample. Core-collapse rates are consolidated from [444] (in which SNe IIP and SNe IIL are grouped due to the debate as to whether or not they arise from distinct phenomena); thermonuclear rates are consolidated from [300].

these explosions [351], suggesting that these two classes naturally arise from differences in pre-explosion mass-loss, and consequently, the density profile of surrounding CSM at the time of detonation.

The question of pre-explosion stripping looms large over the remaining major branch of CCSNe, deemed Stripped-Envelope Supernovae (SESNe). This observational family consists of SNe Ib, which lack clear hydrogen lines in their classification spectra; SNe Ic, which lack both hydrogen and helium lines; and the transitional SNe IIb, which are characterized by weak hydrogen lines that fade with time. The observational characteristics of these groups can be cleanly explained by a continuum in envelope loss, with SNe Ib at one end being only partially stripped and SNe Ic nearly completely stripped ([173] and Fig. 1.3). We note, however, that stripping may not be complete in the case of SNe Ic: spectroscopic modeling of observed events suggests the presence of trace helium abundances at early phases [511, 165], although direct observational support has been elusive and may reflect abundances below detectability limits. Further, this framework leaves room for a wide range of physical mechanisms *driving* the mass-loss, and raises an interesting ‘chicken and egg’ problem at the heart of ongoing debates: do the properties of the underlying progenitor star determine the mechanism and strength of pre-explosion stripping, or does the pre-explosion mass-loss mechanism alter the properties of the stellar progenitor, which drive the observed diversity? In which direction does the arrow of causality point?

In the case of SNe Ic, the stripping mechanism is intrinsically tied to the binarity of the progenitor

Figure 1.2: Diagram illustrating the observational diversity of SN classification today. Spectral properties used to classify SNe are listed in rounded rectangles with dashed edges, photometric properties used are listed in rounded rectangles with solid edges, and derived properties used are listed in parallelogram boxes. Thermonuclear SNe (SNe Ia) are listed in red, SNe II are listed in blue, and SESNe are listed in green. Notes provide additional observational properties. Data consolidated from [50, 166, 145, 361, 491, 51, 167, 448, 235, 478, 216, 281, 184, 225, 377, 185].

Figure 1.3: Canonical model for explaining the diversity of SESNe among binary progenitors. Decreased separation increases the envelope stripping rate and strength of subsequent winds, resulting in the loss of the H and He-rich envelope in the most extreme cases and explosion as an SN Ic. Reproduced from [477] with permission.

system. In a binary system, Roche-lobe overflow onto a stellar companion removes the outermost hydrogen layer [517]; observational evidence suggesting that the majority of massive stars occur in binaries that will interact during their lifetimes lends support for this channel [429]. Stripping may also take place without a companion; here, stripping begins through strong stellar winds originating from a Wolf-Rayet progenitor [459, 518]. Regardless of how the stripping begins, however, these two formation pathways converge with a Helium star that loses its remaining envelope through metal line-driven winds [458, 519]².

The progenitor mass required for detonation as an SN Ic is lower for binary than for single systems, and constraints have often favored the low-mass solution [126, 72, 167]; further, the dearth of progenitor detections disfavors single massive stars whose comparatively bright flux should be detectable above the magnitude limit of the observations [130, 196, 257]. Nevertheless, detailed investigations into individual explosions have revealed unique exceptions: precursor photometry obtained by Cao et al. [73] for the type-Ib SN iPTF13bvn was found to be consistent with models for a single massive Wolf-Rayet [although this interpretation has been challenged; see 141]. Further complicating these efforts, the nature of the SN Ic progenitor system is often ambiguous from pre-explosion photometry, as exemplified by the coincident stellar cluster at the explosion site for type-Ic SN 2017ein [271, 495].

Higher-energy broad-lined SNe Ic, with expansion velocities reaching (or exceeding)

²Binary models have predicted more residual helium left at the time of explosion than single-star models, which may provide an observational means for distinguishing between progenitors in the future.

$v_{\text{exp}} \sim 20,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ at peak light, are the only SNe to be unambiguously associated with long-duration gamma-ray burst jets, following the association of GRB 980425 with the broad-lined type Ic SN 1998bw [168]. Early spectroscopic evidence for a choked jet in the GRB-SN SN2017iuk [235] indicates that the properties of the surrounding circumstellar material at the time of explosion play a critical role in the formation and evolution of relativistic jets in these events. For these reasons, clarifying the terminal mass-loss behavior associated with SESNe is essential to explain the observed diversity of these phenomena, and whether they arise via distinct progenitor channels or signify realizations along a continuum.

We contribute to these studies by inferring the progenitor properties of SN 2020oi, an exceptionally well-covered SN Ic in the local Universe ($d \sim 17 \text{ Mpc}$) whose pre-explosion photometry also revealed a coincident stellar cluster. We discuss this transient, its likely progenitor, and its unusual early-time behavior in Chapter 2.

Thermonuclear SNe: Observational Properties and Progenitor Systems

The thermonuclear detonation of a white dwarf is observed as an SN Ia. The identification of the white dwarf as the SN Ia progenitor was a natural consequence of the explosion mechanism: because degenerate stellar material is unable to maintain thermal equilibrium through contraction or expansion, accretion that increases the system beyond a critical temperature *must* undergo runaway temperature increase accompanied by a catastrophic state change [336]).

Due to the lack of a stellar envelope in the terminal progenitor, the radioactive emission of ^{56}Ni can be seen nearly as soon as it is produced (the diffusion timescale is low), resulting in a light curve roughly matching that of the half-life of the isotope (rising to peak light in ~ 10 days), a peak brightness 2-3 mag greater than traditional CCSNe, and a second near-infrared maximum occurring when the recombination front marking the transition from double to single ionization reaches the iron-rich core (which decreases the opacity of the ejecta and increases its efficiency in reprocessing UV/blue radiation from the explosion; [250]). Spectroscopically, these events are characterized by a dearth of helium and hydrogen and strong lines of intermediate-mass elements near peak (including carbon, oxygen, neon, and silicon).

Despite their discovery preceding the creation of the charge-coupled device by thousands of years, the physical trigger for most thermonuclear explosions is actively debated. The discovery of SNe Ia in elliptical galaxies seemed impossible, if these galaxies were solely populated by low-mass ($\sim 1 M_{\odot}$) stars and thermonuclear detonation was to take place only at or near the Chandrasekhar limit. To resolve this issue, it was proposed in [509] that binary accretion from a stellar companion could push a primary star to this mass threshold, triggering runaway burning in the core and the subsequent unbinding of stellar material.

The progenitor systems of SNe Ia are now believed to be exclusively binaries. Two primary contenders are commonly invoked: that of a single white dwarf accreting from a non-degenerate companion (the single-degenerate case; [203]); and that of two white dwarfs merging (the double-degenerate case; [370]). Double-degenerate mergers are more closely able to reproduce the event rate and the inferred ages of pro-

genitor systems [328, 489, 472], but evidence strongly suggests that both scenarios occur in nature with some frequency (the upcoming gravitational-wave detections made by the Laser Interferometer Space Antenna will revolutionize our understanding of binary white-dwarf demographics, and place new constraints on the merger contribution to the total observed rate). Adding significant complexity to our observational picture, these progenitors may trigger a detonation in a variety of ways, with some mechanisms possible in both types of systems. Double-degenerate systems, for example, undergo both stable and unstable mass transfer (with unstable mass transfer dominating low-mass He+CO white-dwarf binaries prior to merging; [60]), which may trigger a helium-shell detonation that leads to a carbon-core detonation prior to a merger, deemed the ‘dynamically-driven double-degenerate double-detonation’ (D⁶) SN Ia model [441]³.

The light curve rise time of an SN Ia correlates strongly with its peak-light luminosity and color, a relationship deemed the ‘Phillips relation’ [381]. By this relationship, brighter events evolve over longer timescales than dimmer ones. The source of this correlation may arise naturally from the explosion: higher masses of synthesized ⁵⁶Ni produce brighter events at peak, and are also associated with higher masses of intermediate-mass elements that increase the opacity of the ejecta and slow the timescales of emission. Alternatively, it could reflect aspects of the explosion trigger, such as the transition point from deflagration (subsonic C/O burning) to detonation (supersonic burning) [329]. Regardless of the mechanism that triggers and regulates runaway nuclear burning, the resultant emission as an SN Ia is so reliable that the use of these explosions as standardizable candles have cemented them at the bedrock of near-field cosmology.

The above picture holds true for most, but not all, thermonuclear events. Multiple sub-classes of SNe Ia have now emerged that do not obey the Phillips relation (Fig. 1.4). Among them are SNe Iax, exemplified by the prototypical member of the class SNe 2002cx and codified as a distinct observational group a decade ago [145]. SNe Iax are extremely low-luminosity phenomena (>2 mag below their Branch-normal counterparts at peak), a fact that has led to their interpretation by some as the partial deflagration of a white dwarf near the Chandrasekhar limit: the shock wave onset by burning remains sub-sonic and does not fully destroy the stellar material (this leaves the curious possibility that an SN Iax may not be a terminal explosion, and that multiple events may be associated with the same star; [293]). Sub-Chandrasekhar models have also been proposed [484]. SNe-Ia-91bg-like, also named after the category’s archetypal member SN 1991bg and dimmer than traditional thermonuclear events, are identified by their rapidly-declining light-curves (owing to extremely low synthesized ⁵⁶Ni masses of < 0.1 M_⊙; [476]) and their low photospheric temperatures. ‘SNe Ia-CSM’ have now also been discovered, paradoxically exhibiting narrow-line hydrogen lines from the surrounding circumstellar medium similar to SNe IIn [152]. There is debate about whether these objects are even thermonuclear explosions at all.

At the higher-energy end of the thermonuclear spectrum are SNe Ia 91T-like, whose strong pre-peak Fe spectral signatures suggest high surface-level ⁵⁶Ni masses relative to traditional events. If the thermonu-

³The discovery of hypervelocity stars with inflated envelopes strongly suggests that a companion degenerate donor may survive a D⁶ SN Ia explosion and be ejected from the system (as with LP 398-9; [86]).

Figure 1.4: The photometric diversity of thermonuclear explosions, parameterized by the absolute B-band maximum brightness and the B-band decline rate. The Phillips relation among Branch-normal SNe Ia is shown as a black line, while peculiar SNe Ia deviate from this relationship. Spectral differences also exist between Ia sub-types (see text for details). Data obtained from <https://zenodo.org/record/5727583>.

clear explosion begins through sub-sonic C/O burning (deflagration) and transitions to a detonation as is proposed in the delayed-detonation model [268], it may permit a configuration for rapid surface synthesis of iron-group elements in the subsequent detonation (though simulations have yet to reproduce this behavior; [484]).

Further challenging the canonical picture of a homogeneous population of white dwarfs approaching the Chandrasekhar mass, SNe Ia have been discovered whose maximum luminosity implies synthesized ^{56}Ni masses of $> 1 M_{\odot}$. The total mass associated with these explosions seems to exceed the mass limit, leading to their designation as ‘Super-Chandrasekhar SNe Ia’ (SNe Ia-SC). SN 2003cv [227] and SN 2007fg [434] are two well-studied examples of the class. Although the enhanced luminosity of SNe Ia-SC has been attributed to an accreting white dwarf supported by rapid differential rotation as it surpasses the mass-limit, simulations of these systems have so far been unable to form progenitors at the highest-mass end (as the efficiency of the accretion is inversely proportional to the rate of rotation; [91]). Interactions with surrounding circumstellar material may contribute to the observed luminosity, but the narrow lines that typically reveal the presence of this material (as in SNe Ia-CSM) are not detected [317]. Strong magnetic fields may play a role in regulating the equation of state of the progenitor in these events, potentially altering the mass limit [116].

The landscape of observational diversity continues to expand, with many overluminous and short-duration phenomena hinting at additional central engines or variations in explosion mechanism. These include superluminous SNe, thought to be associated with newly-formed magnetars; and Fast Blue Optical Transients, with timescales more compatible with a hydrodynamic than a radioactive heating source. Complicating our traditional taxonomy, the number of transitional objects detected has grown in recent years (e.g., in the luminosity gap between SLSNe and traditional CCSNe; [184]); this suggests that weak magnetar engines may contribute to the energy output of supernovae powered primarily by ^{56}Ni . Even the explosion energies of Branch-normal SNe Ia have now been found to vary by ~ 4 . The mapping between our observational classes and the progenitor physics behind them may not be one-to-one, and increased samples in the coming decade will help reveal where the degeneracies lie.

Phases of Emission and Early-Time Signatures

The electromagnetic emission observed in an SN commences with shock breakout. When the optical depth of the plasma at the shock front moving at velocity v_{shock} drops below $\tau \sim c/v_{\text{shock}}$, it produces a short-duration burst of X-ray, UV, and optical photons. In a pristine stellar environment, shock breakout takes place at the stellar surface, and thus places direct constraints on the size of the progenitor star. If the terminal system is enshrouded by dense circumstellar material, the emission signature is delayed. Detection of this emission has been elusive as a result of the short timescales involved; nevertheless, serendipitous discoveries with exceptionally high-cadence instruments such as the Kepler Space Telescope [228] are possible, as evidenced by the first unambiguous optical detection of shock-breakout in the type II SN KSN 2011d

[177].

Following shock-breakout emission comes shock-cooling emission (SCE) from either the extended stellar envelope (as with SNe II) or surrounding CSM. These produce distinct observational signals, and the availability of simple parametric models for this emission (whose flux is proportional to the radius of the progenitor star; see [384, 385, 431]) has allowed us to place additional constraints on the mass and the radius of a progenitor envelope (or CSM) from early high-cadence photometry. Early spectroscopy may also exhibit narrow lines of ‘flash-ionization’ from the recombination of shock-ionized and low-velocity CSM. Analysis of these lines can constrain the composition of the CSM, lending support for pre-explosion mass-loss rates [267].

The SN shock is followed by its slower-moving ejecta, whose presence and evolution can lead to distinct optical signatures. Early flux emission in excess of the canonical $f \propto t^2$ ‘fireball model’ may result from ejecta interaction with a stellar companion [251]. Here, the optically-thick stellar ejecta collides with a close-in companion (either a giant or a main sequence star) along the line of sight of the observer. This collision creates a rarefied cavity behind the companion, where radiation from the explosion ‘leaks’ through and is detected above the bulk emission. In principle, the occurrence rate of this interaction offers a potential means of distinguishing between formation pathways of SNe Ia; in practice, however, the degeneracies between these and other signatures from optical photometry alone has challenged interpretations [68].

Finally, the supernova ejecta can also collide with surrounding CSM, leading to hydrodynamic emission across a broad range of the electromagnetic spectrum.

The evolution of an explosion’s color in the first few days, as discrete tracers of its underlying spectral energy distribution (SED), can even unveil an atypical radial distribution of nucleosynthetic products, such as an overabundance of heavy elements on the surface of the progenitor star [360].

A comprehensive understanding of supernovae links pre-explosion stellar properties to post-explosion phenomenology, but confounding factors prevent our ability to identify stars immediately prior to their demise. An inescapable trade-off exists between data quality and quantity: individual stars are only resolved in the very local Universe (typically within our own galaxy, although luminous stars within ~ 20 Mpc have been resolved in deep *Hubble Space Telescope* imaging; [481], within which the likelihood of observing SNe during a multi-year survey is low (< 1 SN Ia yr^{-1} is expected using the local volumetric rate calculated by [160]). Further, we lack the ability to distinguish between ‘terminal’ and ‘non-terminal’ variability, and any terminal variability that does occur will only supersede detection limits for the few closest events detected (e.g., for SN2020tlf; [236]). Most importantly, pre-explosion electromagnetic variability is only expected in a fraction of events, and with the characteristic timescales relative to explosion still unknown (in theory, gravitational waves from LISA can be used to identify the pre-merger inspiral phase of binary WD evolution; [521]). Instead, wide-field coverage of the night sky to sufficient depth has permitted archival searches for the stellar progenitors of observed explosions. These searches have achieved limited but important successes [6, 453, 454, 496, 451, 273, 279, 495, 271, 368, 270], beginning with the type-II SN 1987A

[508]. Comparable fervor has characterized the search for an SN Ia progenitor, but not a single progenitor has been found⁴. Despite this, the search has yielded valuable progenitor constraints (as with SN 2011fe, for which a red giant or massive $> 1 M_{\odot}$ main-sequence companion was rejected on the basis of imaging from the *Hubble Space Telescope*).

In the absence of direct progenitor detections, the early interaction signatures outlined above offer our most direct probes of the stellar surface and its surroundings at the time of detonation. The precise reconstruction of this ecosystem is paramount to inferring the terminal mass-loss behavior of a star and conclusively linking late-stage stellar evolution to our observational studies.

The value of these early interactions has motivated the Young SN Experiment (YSE), a multi-band, 1512 deg² survey conducted with the Pan-STARRS telescopes (supplemented by data from the Blanco 4m telescope at Cerro Tololo-Inter-American Observatory) [246]. Since its inception in 2020, YSE has observed the sky with a nominal cadence of ~ 3 days. When augmented with public photometry from ATLAS, ZTF, and a complementary observing program on the Dark Energy Camera (DECam), YSE achieves an effective observing cadence of ~ 1 day, dramatically improving our ability to discover and characterize these early signatures among supernovae in the local Universe. The first data release of the survey has recently been published [8], and contains the photometry and host-galaxy properties of 1,975 SNe discovered since November 2019 (despite losses due to weather, instrument downtime, and the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic).

1.3 The Value of Host-Galaxy Information

Background and Summary of Global Correlations

In August of 1885, a bright, short-lived event was observed in the Andromeda galaxy. Deemed ‘S. Andromedae’, the event found itself thrust to the center of contemporaneous discussions concerning the nature of our Universe. Novae had been detected previously in the Milky Way; if this phenomenon was of the same nature, its detectability seemed to reveal that resolved spirals were structured nebulae residing within our own Galaxy. If Andromeda was indeed a distant galaxy of similar spatial extent to that of the Milky Way, “the star which suddenly shone out in the midst of it in August 1885 should have been equivalent to...nearly *fifty million such suns as our own!*” [102] A similar argument was made by Shapley during the famous Curtis-Shapley debate of 1920 to disfavor the existence of other ‘island universes’, with Curtis countering that “a division into two classes [of novae] is not impossible” [224].

The theory of multiple classes was soon borne out. The team of astronomers (Zwicky and Baade) to coin the now-common name for the extragalactic and extra-energetic ‘super-novae’ were also instrumental

⁴The possibility has been raised that, following the double-degenerate merger of two CO white dwarfs, angular momentum may support the rotating remnant against collapse for multiple Myrs [488]; this latency would explain the lack of companions detected in pre-explosion imaging.

in their interpretation, suggesting in [28] that they signified the terminal stages of stellar evolution leading to the creation of a neutron star (the neutron had been discovered only a year earlier). These prescient predictions were driven by a sample of only two well-studied objects - S. Andromedae, whose spectroscopic properties were inferred from disparate firsthand descriptions spanning at least a dozen observers [373]; and B. Cassiopeiae, whose light curve was documented qualitatively by Tyco Brahe four hundred years prior [27].

SNe had been used to confirm the existence of other galaxies, and as SN discovery rates grew, their nature was similarly inferred through information from the local environment. SNe II were found to cluster toward the spiral arms of late-type galaxies [405, 243], and the SN rate for all types was found to increase roughly linearly with both the luminosity and the star-formation rate of the host galaxy [482]. Prior to the spectroscopic confirmation that SNe Ib/c were the core-collapse explosions of stripped massive stars, studies of nearby stellar populations indicated short-lived progenitors (a preliminary classification scheme was proposed of I(y) and I(o) to distinguish between hydrogen-poor young-star explosions and hydrogen-poor old-star explosions, respectively; [112]).

Decades of studies have since clarified the correlation between the global properties of a galaxy and the transients that occur within it. Because of the short-lived (< 50 Myr) massive stars involved, the rate of CCSNe is tightly coupled to the star formation rate of a galaxy [194], and SESNe rates are suppressed in galaxies below $10^{10} M_{\odot}$ [195]. Among SESNe, the hosts of both SNe Ic-BL and SNe with an associated GRB are lower-metallicity the hosts of SNe Ic [345], suggesting enhanced pre-explosion line-driven winds. The SN Ia rate per unit mass correlates with global specific star-formation rate [459]⁵, although non-negligible populations inhabit early-type galaxies as well. In both early- and late-type hosts, the SN Ia rate correlates with stellar mass, although the strength of the correlation may differ between populations [326, 475]. Global correlations are not limited to dominant classes: all but a single SN Iax to date have been discovered in late-type galaxies [314], and Rapidly-Evolving Transients (RETs) similarly prefer galaxies with high specific star-formation rates [514]. The opposite holds true for SNe 91bg-like; these events are discovered primarily in red E and E/Sa galaxies [493], although extant samples are small. Hydrogen-deficient SLSNe (SLSNe I) occur primarily in faint dwarf galaxies [295] that are exceptionally blue [359] and have low gas-phase metallicities [90] (the hosts of hydrogen-rich SLSNe II exhibit substantially greater diversity, but extend to lower-luminosity hosts than CCSNe; [19]).

Comparative Studies of Local Correlations

Global correlation studies attempt to bridge dramatically different spatial scales, taking advantage of broad statistical correlations to investigate transient phenomena by proxy. While the stellar progenitors of explo-

⁵The preference of SNe Ia for highly star-forming galaxies may reflect the interaction of the progenitor with a non-degenerate companion, although significant differences in the peak brightness and decline rates of SNe Ia hosted by active and passive galaxies suggest different rates of progenitor channels between host galaxy types.

Figure 1.5: Matrix of the most-likely Galaxy-Zoo-labeled morphology [301] of host galaxies for transients in the Transient Host Exchange Catalog [394]. The sample contains $\sim 3,300$ events after cross-matching between the two catalogs. The preference of CCSNe for spiral galaxies can be clearly observed, as well as the preference of SNe Ia for high-mass ellipticals. SNe Iax are found to occur exclusively in spiral galaxies and merger systems, while SNe Ia-91bg-like are found nearly exclusively in spirals.

sive transients remain unresolved (both in serendipitous pre-explosion imaging and in our understanding of their nature), we can further improve our inference of parsec-scale physics through studies of the local environment. On this front, synoptic sky catalogs with data from SDSS for its spectroscopic coverage and the *Hubble Space Telescope* for its spatial resolution have been invaluable. These datasets have shown that SNe Ic-BL and SNe IIb occur in extremely blue locations [258], and SNe Iax have been conclusively associated with young stellar populations [481]. The explosion sites of other SN II sub-types (including SN IIP, SN IIIn, and SN IIL) do not exhibit statistically significant differences. Nevertheless, the selection function introduced in consolidating heterogeneous archival datasets limits these analyses.

Trading data quantity for quality, targeted programs have employed integral-field unit (IFU) spectroscopy to further clarify the local environment. Due to the challenges in resolving individual stellar populations, insights gleaned from targeted spectroscopic surveys are typically qualitative and comparative: the Calar Alto Legacy Integral Field Area (CALIFA) survey of ~ 100 low-redshift ($0.005 < z < 0.03$) SN host galaxies found that SNe Ib/c most closely traced their galaxy’s star-forming regions, followed by SNe II and with SNe Ia exhibiting the weakest correlation. More recently, the PMAS/PPAK Integral-Field Unit Supernova Hosts Compilation (PISCO) of 272 explosion sites reported the highest local metallicities for SNe Ic [170], lending support for their final mass-loss episodes being governed by metallicity-driven winds. IFU

spectroscopy has also confirmed the association of SNe 91bg-like with old stellar populations averaging ~ 10 Gyr and exhibiting little ongoing star formation [372]. Additional multi-object spectroscopy will soon be collected for thousands of SN sites by the 4-metre Multi-Object Spectroscopic Telescope (4MOST) survey on the VISTA telescope following first light in late 2023, driving new studies in resolved explosion-site correlations.

Higher-redshift host galaxies challenge our ability to resolve the explosion site, but systematic studies comparing the radial offsets of different classes are still possible. This is motivated by the existence of radial age gradients in a galaxy’s underlying stellar populations [52], and has now become a common technique for comparing SNe. While the association of CCSNe with stellar arms is well-established, attempts to identify this population by offset alone have been surprisingly challenging (likely because the radial distribution of star-forming HII regions is poorly-constrained - where H-alpha emission is available, its radial distribution closely follows that of observed CCSNe; [15]). Some studies suggest that the events are rarely found within the innermost galaxy [243, 206], while others derive a CCSN rate within the innermost kpc of spiral galaxies to be at least as high as those in the outer regions [507]. Others suggest that the radial concentration of CCSNe are a function of the galaxy’s stellar luminosity [206], or the host galaxy’s spiral sub-type [20]. Part of the difficulty lies in the associated observational biases: dust profiles are exponential as a function of galactocentric radius in late-type galaxies [352], so dust-obscured nuclear transients are often extinguished beyond detectability or explicitly cut from SN searches (surveys of Ultra-Luminous Infrared Galaxies (ULIRGs) have forecasted that *most* SNe may occur within the host nucleus, [150], and the SPitzer InfraRed Intensive Transients Survey [238] forecasts as many as $\sim 40\%$ of local CCSNe are missed by optical surveys; the enhanced resolution and infrared sensitivity of *JWST* will provide the tightest constraints to date on this dust-obscured population). Other limitations include the potential confusion of SN light with a bright galactic bulge, and the myriad definitions in the literature for a galaxy’s radius (which limit comparative studies between host samples).

The question of whether a transient’s host galaxy impacts its observed evolution is relevant to precision cosmology (despite being subdominant to systematic uncertainties from redshift biases, MW extinction correction, light curve fitting; [55]). Following standardization, residuals in the distance moduli calculated with SN Ia samples have been found to correlate with a broad range of global host-galaxy properties, including stellar mass, star-formation rate, and local stellar age and metallicity [288, 476, 95, 416]. The physics driving this correlation is actively debated, with some suggesting that distinct dust distributions between early and late-type hosts play a major role [54] and others attributing the effect to the mean age of the SN Ia progenitor [95]. Despite the confusion, most cosmological analyses now rely on an additional host-galaxy stellar-mass step to account for this correlation. An additional term associated with systematic differences in the local environment has also been proposed [413].

Transient classification from photometry alone can directly benefit from the inclusion of these correlations. The majority of extant classifiers consider host-galaxy information only implicitly, as in the case of

Figure 1.6: **Left:** Cumulative fraction of star formation at the SN site (estimated from normalized H- α maps) relative to the total star-formation of the host galaxy. Fractions are shown for five classes of SNe, and sample sizes are provided in the legend (one object is designated ‘IIb/Ib’ and considered in both samples). Results suggest that SNe Ic are most likely to trace active star-forming regions, and have the shortest-lived progenitors; whereas SNe Ia are least likely, and likely have old progenitors. Reproduced from [17] with permission. **Right:** Cumulative fraction of SN Ia sub-types as a function of host galaxy morphology. SNe Ia-91bg-like are most likely to be found in late-type (E and E/SO) host galaxies, suggesting relatively old progenitors; SNe Ia are found nearly exclusively in structured spirals active in star formation. Reproduced from [205] with permission.

postage-stamp classifiers processed by convolutional neural networks [79] or ‘real-bogus’ classifiers which distinguish true astrophysical events from imaging artifacts [e.g., 269, 127, 4]. Even if contextual information is not directly provided as input, many rely on redshifts derived from host-galaxy photometry and some include pre-explosion non-detections in the classification of partial-phase transient light curves [355].

The first systematic investigation into the value of host-galaxy information for SN classification was conducted by [142], who found that a Naïve Bayes classifier (one that assumes independent features) using *only* host galaxy morphology, absolute magnitude, color, galactic offset and pixel rank could classify supernovae as accurately as the then-leading light curve classification methods. More recently, [31] showed that selection cuts on host galaxy star formation estimated by photometry can increase the purity of SN Ia and CCSN samples by 10% and 20% from random guessing, respectively. The same year, [182] built a random-forest classifier to classify SLSNe using transient photometry combined with host radius and brightness. We build upon these prior works by training a classifier to distinguish between SNe Ia and SNe II using host properties, which we discuss in Chapter 3. This analysis was later extended by [276] who, by consolidating optical and infrared host-galaxy photometry, were able to classifying eight classes of transient at purities above random (seven classes of SNe, and tidal disruption events).

1.4 Transient Classification Techniques

Transient typing is a fundamental component of many time-domain analyses: it facilitates comparisons between statistical samples, the identification of anomalous events, and the design of relevant programs for follow-up observations. First attempts at automating this process consisted of comparing observed spectra to expert-labeled spectra, with the Generic cLAssification TOol (GELATO; [76]) attempting to minimize the mean distance between the observed rest-frame spectrum and a set of templates across discrete wavelength bins. The Supernova Identification code (SNID; Blondin & Tonry, [46]) later improved upon this technique by maximizing the cross-correlation between observed spectrum and template, and simultaneously constraining the redshift that maximizes this correlation.

Non-parametric fitting has recently become popular for spectroscopic classification, driven by improvements in the scalability of neural networks to large datasets and highly non-linear problems. The fundamental building block for all neural networks is the perceptron. For a set of inputs \mathbf{x} , a linear transformation is applied by computing the dot product with a weight vector \mathbf{w} :

$$y = f(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}) \quad (1.2)$$

An activation function f is then applied to the output. Although the initial conception for the perceptron implemented the Heaviside step for binary classification, alternative activation functions have since been introduced which allow for continuous outputs and introduce nonlinear complexity to a network’s capabilities [408]. In a neural network, multiple perceptrons (or artificial neurons) are linked in a layer. Each neuron processes the full input sequence and their output can be ingested by multiple hidden layers. The output of the algorithm is that of the final layer in the network. The weights of each neuron are updated through backpropagation⁶ [420], in which the gradients of an objective function quantifying the distance between output and target vectors are calculated with respect to the neuron weights in training. Weight updates are then computed - in the widely-used *Adam* optimizer, a custom learning rate is calculated from first and second moments of the objective [275]. Adaptive learning rates, neuronal drop-out during training, and batch normalization have further contributed to the rapid convergence of modern neural networks for diverse astrophysical applications.

The breadth of neural network architectures continues to grow. Neural networks can now combine inputs by convolution kernel (as in a convolutional neural network, common for processing images with pixel correlations) or simultaneously process both input data and node output from earlier input (as in a recurrent neural network), thus allowing for the fitting of temporal correlations. These techniques have found significant success applied to spectroscopic transient classification. The binned spectral intensity at the locations of prominent lines can be ingested by multi-layered perceptrons [347], or the full spectrum

⁶Alternative approaches to weight updates have been considered, as it has been deemed implausible that backpropagation is used in biological learning [215].

can be processed by neural network to predict the event’s type and approximate phase [354]. These algorithms are significantly faster than traditional template-matching techniques and can be tailored in training to reach performance thresholds relevant for science-specific analyses (as in the demand for negligible false positive rates in photometric SN Ia typing; [157]).

Spectroscopic capabilities have stagnated relative to transient discovery rates: by 2010, less than half of discovered SNe had spectroscopic confirmation [264], and that number has dropped to 10% today. Consequently, the need for low-latency transient typing from photometry alone has grown increasingly urgent. Template-matching was again employed in early efforts, but with a significant distinction: because of the the substantial degeneracies that exist at the photometric level, large libraries of *synthetic* events were generated and used as templates. The photometric SN Identification (pSNid; [425]) package⁷, developed to classify the SNe observed during the SDSS-II SN Survey (2005 – 2007), calculated the Bayesian Evidence of belonging to a given class by comparing a light curve to a model grid varying in redshift, host-galaxy extinction, time of maximum brightness, distance modulus, and decline rate (parameterized by Δm_{15} , the difference between the apparent brightness from peak to 15 days later). The SN photometric classification challenge (SNphotCC; [264]) launched concurrently to spur additional developments, with pSNid achieving the highest overall figure of merit. SNphotCC established a tradition of photometric classification challenges that continued with the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge (PLAsTiCC; [263, 322, 217]) and the Extended LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge (ELAsTiCC⁸; Fig. 1.7). ELAsTiCC data now serves as the latest standard in synthetic transient photometry.

Photometric classification techniques that employ neural networks are now commonplace. Many methods take advantage of temporal correlations encoded within discrete multivariate time-series data (spectral correlations are often leveraged to build a latent representation of each event in pre-processing, [e.g., 501, 395], which is valuable for overcoming challenges in training caused by irregular sampling; efforts to embed a continuous representation of the underlying phenomenon directly into a neural network are ongoing [418, 209]. Classifiers have been built using both RNNs [355, 349, 383] and CNNs [395]. The flexibility of these non-parametric methods is advantageous for recovering subtle correlations between input and output, but significant data volumes are required for robust training.

Synthetic data continue to be an essential element in training and validation of classification algorithms, underscoring the need for realistic simulations and an *a-prior* understanding of the dominant physics governing transients and their dominant feedback mechanisms. Furthermore, the lack of interpretability from input to final classification poses a challenge for identifying outliers and failure modes. Architectures are slowly being introduced which attempt to embed physically-relevant information, as with the photometric classifier parSNIP: a variational autoencoder is used to encode a series of multi-band light curves, and the

⁷sas.upenn.edu/~gladney/html-physics/psnid/psnidII/

⁸https://portal.nersc.gov/cfs/lsst/DESC_TD_PUBLIC/ELASTICC/

Figure 1.7: A phase-space comparison of the transients simulated in the SN photometric classification challenge (SNphotCC; red) and the Extended LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge (ELAsTiCC; blue). Major simulated classes are labeled in black and non-simulated phenomena are italicized. Timescale has been measured as the time above 50% maximum observed brightness, estimated from a best-fit gaussian profile. Limits from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory between the wide-fast-deep main survey and the deep drilling fields nightly deep stacks will be placed on events in the shaded purple region [192]. The full SNphotCC dataset is shown; only 10% of the ELAsTiCC training dataset is plotted. Figure adapted from [70] and [254].

latent variables are decoded into an internal representation of the transient’s underlying time-dependent spectrum [48]. The learned latent features are used in a decision tree classifier, and the recovered spectral series can be inspected for individual events. Physical constraints may also be introduced through a custom loss function, but this can make the problem significantly more ill-conditioned [286]. The trade-off between flexibility and interpretability will continue to influence the design of next-generation transient classification algorithms for years to come.

The data collected by Rubin will shift the paradigm in SN classification and analysis not only for its staggering discovery rates, but for the deep multi-band imaging it will provide for SN host galaxies. This precisely-calibrated photometry will be three magnitudes deeper in g than a Pan-STARRS (PS1) single-visit exposure and greater than four magnitudes deeper over the ten-year survey than the PS1 3π co-add

depth. Extant low- z host-galaxy samples are insufficient for training automated analysis techniques for first light, but we lack on the other end the physically-motivated progenitor models that would allow us to reproduce observed correlations between transient and host in hydrodynamic simulations. An intermediate step toward investigating transient behavior and the feedback processes that govern it is to develop an empirical, data-driven methodology for embedding observed correlations into simulated datasets. These simulations can then be used to rapidly triage phenomena observed at first light, with encoded correlations becoming more realistic as larger samples are obtained. To more effectively prepare for Rubin first light, we design and rigorously validate a pipeline of this sort for simulating a range of extragalactic transients and the correlated properties of their host galaxies. We discuss this pipeline in Chapter 4, and train an early-time SN classifier using the dataset in Chapter 5. The resultant framework serves as a model for consolidating incomplete datasets from diverse sources into a comprehensive picture of stellar death.

Chapter 2

An Early-Time Optical and Ultraviolet Excess in the type-Ic SN 2020oi

This chapter is based on: Gagliano, Izzo, Kilpatrick, Mockler, et al., 2022, *ApJ*, 924, 2.

2.1 Introduction

The data consolidated for SN 2020oi, a nearby SN Ic, is uniquely suited to shed light on the question of pre-explosion mass-loss in SESNe. SN 2020oi was discovered by the Automatic Learning for the Rapid Classification of Events (ALeRCE) transient broker on January 7th, 2020 at 13:00:54.000 UTC [148] from the alert stream of the Zwicky Transient Facility [ZTF; 40]. It was classified as a type-Ic SN two days later using the Goodman Spectrograph at the Southern Astrophysical Research Telescope [446]. The event occurred at $\alpha, \delta = 185.7289^\circ, 15.8236^\circ$ (J2000), $\sim 4.67''$ North from the nucleus of the SAB(s)bc spiral galaxy Messier 100 (M100/NGC 4321) presiding at a distance of 17.1 ± 1.8 Mpc [153]. SN 2020oi is the seventh SN discovered in M100, preceded by the unclassified SNe 1901B, 1914A, and 1959E; and the type-IIL SN 1979C [78], type-Ia SN 2006X [397], and calcium-rich transient SN 2019ehk [237]. As the most recent in this series of observed M100 explosions spanning over a century, SN 2020oi has been continuously monitored since its discovery, and a wealth of pre-explosion data have been collected on its local environment. For these reasons, SN 2020oi represents an ideal event for constraining SN Ic progenitor properties and explosion physics.

We have observed a bump lasting ~ 1 day and beginning ~ 2 days from the time of explosion in nearly all bands of our optical and UV photometry. In *gri* bands, we observe a brief increase and decrease in flux; in *u* band, we observe only a flux decrease (see Fig. 2.1). The coincidence of this phenomenon across bands suggests a high-temperature component to the early-time photometry of SN 2020oi above the standard SN rise.

Early-time bumps such as the one observed in the SN 2020oi photometry are extremely rare among

spectroscopically-standard SNe Ic, particularly when observed in multiple bands and across multiple epochs. Early-time ATLAS data revealed emission in excess of a power-law rise for SN 2017ein, which was interpreted as the cooling of a small stellar envelope that was shock-heated [516]. A decrease in V -band flux in the first photometric observations of SN LSQ14efd [32] was similarly attributed to shock-cooling. An extended ($> 500 R_{\odot}$), low-mass ($0.045 M_{\odot}$) envelope, potentially ejected by a massive Wolf-Rayet progenitor pre-explosion, was proposed to explain the luminous first peak in SN iPTF15dtg [479]. The multi-wavelength coverage of the SN 2020oi bump, coupled with the classification spectrum obtained immediately following its decline, together comprise a rich dataset for investigating the early-time behavior of SNe Ic.

Here, we describe the photometric and spectroscopic coverage of SN 2020oi spanning ~ 1 year of observations and the corresponding constraints that these data provide for the progenitor of this SN Ic. Further, we provide a detailed spectroscopic analysis of M100 and the region immediately surrounding SN 2020oi using pre-explosion Integral Field Unit (IFU) spectroscopy with the Multi Unit Spectroscopic Explorer (MUSE) mounted on the European Southern Observatory Very Large Telescope. By presenting a comprehensive picture of the most rapidly fading SN Ic observed to date, this work will shed additional light on the full diversity of stripped-envelope explosions and their origins.

Three prior works have investigated this SN: Horesh et al. [223], who reported evidence of dense circumstellar material from radio observations; Rho et al. [409], who modeled near-IR spectroscopy to derive the presence of carbon monoxide and dust; and Tinyanont et al. [485], who presented spectropolarimetric observations suggesting SN 2020oi is unlikely to be an asymmetric explosion. None of these studies investigated the early-time excess reported here, nor did they attempt an analysis of the explosion environment from host-galaxy spectroscopy.

This chapter is laid out as follows. In §2.2, we outline the photometric and spectroscopic observations collected for SN 2020oi, which span optical, UV, and X-ray wavelengths. We use the notation δt to refer to the number of days from the explosion time of MJD 58854.0, which is determined using a fireball rise model outlined in §2.5. We estimate the host-galaxy reddening in §2.3 and use Gaussian Process Regression to derive the bolometric light curve for the explosion in §2.4. §2.5 is devoted to the explosion parameters of SN 2020oi, which are estimated using three different models of the event in the photospheric phase and compared to previous stripped-envelope explosions. Next, we constrain the mass-loss rate of the progenitor from our X-ray observations in §2.6. We model our spectral sequence near peak light using a radiative transfer code to characterize the ejecta in §2.7, and independently fit the unique early-time spectrum in §2.8. In §2.9, we consider physical interpretations for the early-time optical and UV excess. §2.10 is devoted to fitting the *HST* pre-explosion photometry of the stellar cluster coincident with the explosion (see §2.2 for details). We then analyze the stellar population within SN 2020oi’s local environment using MUSE IFU spectroscopy in §2.11, and derive a final age for the SN progenitor in §2.12. We conclude by summarizing our major findings in §2.13.

2.2 Observations

HST Pre- and Post-Explosion Observations

We obtained archival *Hubble Space Telescope* (*HST*) images of the central region of M100 using the Hubble Legacy Archive¹ and the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST)². These observations span nearly three decades, beginning with the calibration of the Wide Field/Planetary Camera 2 (WFPC2) [56] for the *Hubble Space Telescope*'s Key Project [154, 214] and ending with a study (Proposal ID 16179; PI: Filippenko) into the host environments of nearby SNe. We present a false-color composite of *HST* pointings of M100 post-explosion in Figure 2.2, in which we have marked the location of SN 2020oi. The diversity of studies involving M100, particularly concerning the dynamics and stellar populations immediately surrounding its nucleus, provide ample context for studying the pre-explosion environment. We present a detailed summary of the *HST* observations in Table 2.1. As in Kilpatrick et al. [271], we use the `astrodrizzle` and `drizzlepac` packages [187] to reduce these archival images in the python-based *HST* imaging pipeline `hst123`³. We performed all *HST* photometry using a circular aperture fixed to a 0.2'' width and centered on the location of SN 2020oi as inferred from post-explosion F555W observations. Using the python-based `photutils` package [49], we extracted an aperture in each drizzled frame and estimated the background contribution from the median value within an annulus with inner and outer radii of 0.4'' and 0.8'', respectively, and centered on the circular aperture. We derived the AB magnitude zero point within each frame from the PHOTPLAM and PHOTFLAM keywords in the original image headers⁴.

Although no progenitor is immediately evident in the pre-explosion imaging, a marginally-extended brightness excess likely corresponding to a stellar cluster is nearly coincident with the SN explosion. We calculate the nominal offset between the cluster and the explosion in *HST*/WFC3 UVIS imaging to be 0.55 px, corresponding to a physical separation of less than 2.3 parsecs. This cluster is also visible in the most recent *HST* images obtained (MJD 59267, $\delta t \approx 413$ days). We analyze the photometric properties of this source in §2.10.

¹<https://hla.stsci.edu/>

²<https://archive.stsci.edu/>

³<https://github.com/charliekilpatrick/hst123>

⁴i.e., following the standard formula for WFPC2, ACS, and WFC3 zero points as in <https://www.stsci.edu/hst/instrumentation/acs/data-analysis/zeropoints>

Table 2.1: *HST* Pre-Explosion Cluster and SN 2020oi Photometry.

MJD	Phase ^a (days)	Filter	Exposure (s)	Magnitude	Uncertainty	3 σ Limit	ID
49352.6	-9501.4	F555W	1800.0	19.419	0.062	26.242	5195
49352.6	-9501.4	F439W	1920.0	19.460	0.114	24.857	5195
49352.7	-9501.3	F702W	2400.0	19.657	0.057	25.990	5195
49359.5	-9494.5	F555W	1668.5	19.443	0.048	26.228	5195
49359.5	-9494.5	F439W	1920.0	19.444	0.041	24.839	5195
49359.6	-9494.4	F702W	2318.5	19.630	0.095	25.833	5195
51212.0	-7642.0	F218W	1200.0	19.668	0.059	22.845	6358
53155.8	-5698.2	F814W	1200.0	19.837	0.005	25.430	9776
53155.9	-5698.2	F555W	1200.0	19.432	0.005	25.886	9776
53761.4	-5092.6	F330W	1200.0	19.271	0.005	25.728	10548
54469.8	-4384.2	F555W	2000.0	19.409	0.009	25.965	11171
54469.9	-4384.1	F439W	1000.0	19.454	0.022	24.502	11171
54469.9	-4384.1	F380W	1000.0	19.449	0.019	24.824	11171
54469.9	-4384.1	F702W	1000.0	19.614	0.013	25.512	11171
54470.0	-4384.1	F791W	1000.0	19.712	0.021	24.920	11171
55147.1	-3707.0	F775W	270.0	19.734	0.010	24.951	11646
55147.1	-3706.9	F475W	970.0	19.326	0.005	27.050	11646
55147.1	-3706.9	F555W	970.0	19.422	0.005	27.040	11646
58153.7	-700.6	F814W	500.0	19.849	0.007	25.252	15133
58153.7	-700.3	F475W	700.0	19.328	0.005	26.500	15133
58153.8	-700.3	F160W	596.9	20.133	0.007	24.627	15133
58626.8	-227.2	F814W	2128.0	19.823	0.004	26.526	15645
58877.9	23.9	F814W	836.0	15.821	0.004	25.695	15654
58877.9	23.9	F438W	1050.0	16.783	0.004	26.150	15654
58877.9	23.9	F336W	1110.0	18.453	0.004	26.286	15654
58877.9	23.9	F275W	2190.0	19.114	0.005	26.535	15654
58877.9	23.9	F555W	670.0	16.421	0.004	26.426	15654
58923.6	69.6	F814W	836.0	16.943	0.004	25.672	15654
58923.6	69.6	F438W	1050.0	17.770	0.004	26.177	15654
58923.6	69.6	F336W	1110.0	18.928	0.005	26.150	15654
58923.6	69.6	F275W	2190.0	19.215	0.005	26.350	15654
58923.6	69.6	F555W	670.0	17.372	0.004	26.283	15654
58990.6	136.6	F110W	1211.8	19.853	0.005	25.873	16075
58990.6	136.6	F160W	1211.8	20.050	0.006	25.088	16075
58990.7	136.6	F814W	900.0	18.984	0.005	25.943	16075
58990.7	136.6	F555W	1500.0	19.027	0.004	27.071	16075
59267.0	412.9	F625W	780.0	19.475	0.005	26.231	16179
59267.0	413.0	F438W	710.0	19.244	0.005	25.931	16179

^a Phase is relative to the time of explosion (MJD = 58854.0).

Note: Magnitudes are in AB and have not been corrected for host extinction. Shaded rows denote pre-explosion photometry.

Figure 2.1: Host-galaxy subtracted photometry for SN 2020oi relative to the calculated time of explosion ($MJD = 58854.0$). Markers are colored by filter and shapes indicate the instrument used to take the observation. Shaded light curves indicate the Gaussian-process fits integrated to construct the bolometric light curve for the event. Red dotted lines mark the phases where spectra were obtained and the grey shaded region spans the early-time optical and UV excess (shown in zoom at left). Late-time upper limits are shown at right. *Swift* UV (optical) upper limits are plotted in the top (center) panel. The magnitude uncertainty from the reported distance to M100 is shown in black top-right, and the median uncertainty in magnitude due to uncertainty in host-galaxy extinction across all bands is shown in purple. Uncertainty in the time of explosion between our models is shown bottom left. Observations with photometric errors above 0.5 mag are not shown. Suspicious observations due to poor seeing and errors in background subtraction are outlined in red.

Figure 2.2: A false-color *HST* image of the nucleus of M100 post-explosion. The location of SN 2020oi is circled, and the physical scale is given bottom right.

Ground-Based Optical Photometry

We observed SN 2020oi with the Las Cumbres Observatory Global Telescope Network (LCO) 1m telescopes and LCO imagers from 8 Jan. to 5 Feb. 2020 in $g'r'i'$ bands. We downloaded the calibrated BANZAI [335] frames from the Las Cumbres archive and re-aligned them using the command-line blind astrometry tool `solve-field` [289]. The images were also recalibrated using DoPhot photometry [435] and PS1 DR2 standard stars observed in the same field as SN 2020oi in gri bands [140]. We then stacked $g'r'i'$ -band frames obtained from 31 Jan. to 7 Feb. 2021 as templates and reduced them following the same procedure using SWarp [45]. The template images were subtracted from all science frames in hotpants [38], and finally we performed forced photometry of SN 2020oi on all subtracted frames using DoPhot with a point-spread function (PSF) fixed to the instrumental PSF derived in each science frame.

SN 2020oi was also observed with the Nickel 1m telescope at Lick Observatory, Mt. Hamilton, California in conjunction with the Direct $2k \times 2k$ camera ($6.8' \times 6.8'$) in $BVr'i'$ bands from 31 Jan. to 8 Aug. 2020. All image-level calibrations and analysis were performed in photpipe [407, 271] using calibration frames obtained on the same night and in the same instrumental configuration. We then aligned our images using 2MASS astrometric standards in the image frame, then each image was regridded to a corrected frame using SWarp [45] to remove geometric distortion. All photometry was performed using a custom version of DoPhot [435] to construct an empirical PSF and perform photometry on all detected sources. We then calibrated each frame using PS1 DR1 sources [140] in ri bands and transformed to BV bands using transformations in Tonry et al. [487].

Observations of SN 2020oi were also obtained with the Thacher 0.7m telescope located at Thacher

Observatory, Ojai, California from 14 Jan. to 21 Dec. 2020 in *griz* bands. The imaging reductions followed the same procedure described above for our Nickel reductions and in Dimitriadis et al. [121].

We further observed SN 2020oi with the Swope 1m telescope at Las Campanas Observatory, Chile starting on 21 Jan. 2020 through 15 Mar. 2020 in *uBVgriz* bands. Our reductions followed a procedure similar to the one outlined above for the Nickel telescope and described in further detail in Kilpatrick et al. [272].

In addition to the photometry listed above, we include observations obtained from the forced-photometry service [333] of the Zwicky Transient Facility [ZTF; 40, 191]. These data, which begin on 7 Jan. 2020 ($\delta t = 2$ days) and continue through 26 April 2020 ($\delta t = 111$ days), were obtained using the Palomar 48-inch telescope and reduced according to the methods outlined in Bellm et al. [40].

Swift Ultraviolet Observations

To obtain ultraviolet (UV) photometry for SN 2020oi, we leverage the extensive observations made of M100 by the Neil Gehrels *Swift* Observatory [178]. The earliest of these was obtained in November 2005. The follow-up campaigns of SN 2006X and SN 2019ehk, acquired with the Ultraviolet Optical Telescope [UVOT; 414], provide excellent UV and *UBV*-band template images for SN 2020oi, spanning a total of 22 pre-explosion epochs. Indeed, the first 2 post-explosion UVOT epochs come from the follow-up campaign of SN 2019ehk, which serendipitously observed SN 2020oi only ~ 2.45 days after explosion. Observations were collected for SN 2020oi from 2 to 53 days post-explosion.

We performed aperture photometry with the `uvotsource` task within the `HEASOFT v6.22`⁵, following the guidelines in Brown et al. [58] and using an aperture of $3''$. Using the 22 pre-explosion epochs obtained, we have estimated the level of contamination from the host-galaxy flux. In doing so, we assume that excess flux contributions from the progenitor system (as in the case of outbursts or flares), if present, are negligible. This assumption is supported by our measurements of a consistent flux at the location of SN 2020oi across all pre-explosion observations. As a result, we averaged the photon count-rate across the 22 epochs for each filter and then subtracted this from the count rates in the post-explosion images, following the prescriptions in Brown et al. [57].

To further constrain the host-galaxy contamination within our UVOT images, we perform the same aperture photometry described above at three other locations along the star-forming ring of M100 and equidistant from the nucleus. After host-galaxy subtraction, we find an unexplained flux increase at the same post-explosion epoch across all apertures. It is likely that this is a systematic effect in the *Swift* instrumentation, but at present we are unable to validate this hypothesis. To eliminate the possibility of contaminating our photometry with systematics at other epochs, and because of the strong UV contamination from the M100 nucleus, we have replaced our *Swift* photometry with upper limits derived prior to host

⁵We used the calibration database (CALDB) version 20201008.

subtraction.

We present our complete optical and ultraviolet light curve for the explosion in Figure 2.1, where we have removed all observations with photometric uncertainties above 0.5 mag. Our full photometric dataset is listed in Table B.1.

Chandra X-ray Observations

We obtained deep X-ray observations of SN 2020oi with the Advanced CCD imaging spectrometer (ACIS) instrument onboard the *Chandra X-ray Observatory* (CXO) on February 15, 2020 and March 13, 2020, 40 and 67 days since explosion, respectively (PI Stroh, IDs 23140, 23141) under an approved DDT program 21508712. The exposure time of each of the two observations was 9.95 ks, for a total exposure time of 19.9 ks. These data were then reduced with the CIAO software package [version 4.13; 161], using the latest calibration database CALDB version 4.9.4. As part of this reduction, we have applied standard ACIS data filtering.

We do not find evidence for statistically significant X-ray emission at the location of the SN in either observations or in the co-added exposure. Using Poissonian statistics we infer a 3σ count-rate limit of $\sim 4.02 \times 10^{-4} \text{ c s}^{-1}$ and $\sim 5.02 \times 10^{-4} \text{ c s}^{-1}$ for the two epochs of CXO observation (0.5 - 8 keV). The Galactic neutral hydrogen column density in the direction of the transient is $NH_{MW} = 1.97 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ [247]. Assuming a power-law spectral model with spectral photon index $\Gamma = 2$, the above count-rate limits translate to 0.3-10 keV unabsorbed flux limits of $F_x < 6.3 \times 10^{-15} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (first epoch), and $F_x < 7.9 \times 10^{-15} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (second epoch). We note the presence of diffuse soft X-ray emission from the host galaxy at the SN site, which prevents us from achieving deeper limits on the X-ray emission of the explosion.

Optical Spectroscopy

We have obtained 12 spectra from $\delta t \approx 3.3$ to $\delta t \approx 41.0$ days post-explosion. Two spectra, including the classification spectrum ($\delta t \approx 3.3$ days from explosion), were obtained with the Goodman High Throughput Spectrograph [101] at the Southern Astrophysical Research (SOAR) Telescope. Six were obtained with the FLOYDS spectrograph on the Faulkes 2m telescopes of the Las Cumbres Observatory Global Telescope Network [LCOGT; 59], two with the Low-Resolution Imaging Spectrometer [LRIS; 367] on the Keck I telescope, and two with the Kast spectrograph [341] on the 3m Shane telescope at Lick Observatory. The FLOYDS spectra were reduced using a dedicated spectral reduction pipeline⁶ and the remaining ones with standard IRAF/PYRAF⁷ and python routines [447]. All of the spectral images were bias/overscan-subtracted and flat-fielded, with the wavelength solution derived using arc lamps and the

⁶https://github.com/LCOGT/floyds_pipeline

⁷IRAF is distributed by the National Optical Astronomy Observatories, which are operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation.

final flux calibration and telluric line removal performed using spectro-photometric standard star spectra [449]. We provide a summary of our full spectral sequence, which spans 38 days of explosion, in Table 2.2, and plot each obtained spectrum in Figure 2.3.

In addition to those described above, two optical spectra were obtained that did not contain obvious SN emission. The first was obtained using the Keck Observatory’s Low Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (LRIS) on December 10th, 2020, ~ 336 days from the explosion’s maximum brightness in r band. After reducing the data, it was determined that the spectrum was dominated by galaxy light. The second spectrum, which was obtained with the FLOYDS spectrograph on the Faulkes 2m telescope of the LCOGT in Siding Springs, Australia, was affected by poor seeing.

Table 2.2: Optical Spectroscopic Observations of SN 2020oi.

Date (UT)	MJD	Phase ^a (days)	Telescope	Instrument	Wavelength Range
2020-01-09	58857.3	+3.3	SOAR	Goodman	4000–9000
2020-01-12	58860.5	+6.6	Shane	KAST	3800–9100
2020-01-16	58864.6	+10.6	Faulkes North	FLOYDS	4800–10000
2020-01-20	58868.6	+14.6	Faulkes North	FLOYDS	4800–10000
2020-01-22	58870.5	+16.5	Faulkes North	FLOYDS	4800–10000
2020-01-24	58872.4	+18.4	Faulkes North	FLOYDS	4800–10000
2020-01-27	58875.0	+21.0	Keck I	LRIS	3200–10800
2020-01-31	58879.4	+25.4	Faulkes North	FLOYDS	4800–10000
2020-02-01	58880.3	+26.3	SOAR	Goodman	4000–9000
2020-02-01	58880.4	+26.4	Faulkes North	FLOYDS	4800–10000
2020-02-13	58892.0	+38.0	Shane	KAST	3500–11000
2020-02-16	58895.0	+41.0	Keck I	LRIS	3200–10800

^a Phase is given relative to time of explosion (MJD = 58854.0).

2.3 Host Galaxy Extinction

We estimate the host-galaxy extinction along the line of sight to the SN first using the empirical relation between the reddening and the equivalent width of the spectrum’s Na $\lambda\lambda 5889, 5895$ doublet [388]. Using our de-redshifted high resolution Keck/LRIS spectrum obtained on January 27, a pseudo-continuum is defined as a line at the edges of the absorption feature and the spectrum is then normalized at the feature’s position. We then fit the sodium doublet, which we approximate as two Gaussians with their widths forced

to be the same and their relative strengths constrained according to their oscillator strengths (obtained from the National Nuclear Data Center⁸). This process is repeated 10,000 times for different choices of the pseudo-continuum. We estimate a combined equivalent width of $0.88 \pm 0.05 \text{ \AA}$, corresponding to a host reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.15 \pm 0.03 \text{ mag}$ [using equation 9 from 388]. This is comparable to the value provided by Horesh et al. [223], who estimates $E(B - V) = 0.14 \pm 0.05 \text{ mag}$ of reddening using this procedure. Assuming $R_V = 3.1$, this corresponds to a V band extinction of $A_V \approx 0.47$.

We additionally estimate the line-of-sight host-galaxy reddening by comparing the observed color evolution of SN 2020oi during the first 20 days following peak luminosity to the type-Ic color templates provided in Stritzinger et al. [471]. First, we sample a range of A_V and R_V values across a uniformly-spaced grid spanning $[0.0, 1.0] \text{ mag}$ and $[1.0, 6.0]$, respectively. By interpolating the spectra spanning this range in phase, we obtain extinction corrections for each photometric band and calculate the χ^2 value of our corrected color curve. Because we find R_V to be poorly constrained from our photometry, we choose A_V to be the value with the smallest χ^2 value for a fixed $R_V = 3.1$ (corresponding to a Galactic extinction curve). We note that infrared observations of SN 2020oi are needed to conclusively determine R_V [471].

We find a best-fit host-galaxy extinction of $A_V = 0.35 \text{ mag}$ for $R_V = 3.1$, corresponding to a reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.11 \text{ mag}$. We estimate the error on A_V to be 0.03 mag by calculating the standard deviation of the best-fit values across each of our sampled R_V values. We adopt this value as our host-galaxy extinction instead of the value derived from the Na doublet fitting due to the large dispersion associated with the latter relationship. A slightly higher host reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.13 \text{ mag}$ was adopted by Horesh et al. [223] from a comparison of the same color templates as we have used. We also report a Galactic reddening value of $E(B - V) = 0.0227 \pm 0.0002 \text{ mag}$ in the direction of the SN based upon the maps of Schlafly et al. [436], leading to a combined reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.133 \pm 0.03 \text{ mag}$. This is consistent with the 0.153 mag of total reddening reported by Horesh et al. [223], who find a comparable Galactic value of $E(B - V) = 0.023 \text{ mag}$ in the direction of M100. In the following sections, we adopt a combined reddening of $E(B - V) = 0.133$.

2.4 Bolometric Light Curve Fitting

To consolidate our panchromatic observations obtained at different epochs into a consistent bolometric light curve, we seek to construct a non-parametric model for the photometric evolution of the explosion in each filter using Gaussian Process Regression [GPR; 401]. GPR is an approach to functional approximation that assumes that observations are realizations sampled from a latent function with Gaussian noise. The model is constrained by a kernel function that describes the similarity between observations using a length scale over which our observations are correlated. By conditioning a chosen kernel, which characterizes our prior, on the observations, we can generate a posterior distribution for a class of functions that

⁸<https://www.nndc.bnl.gov/>

describe the data. This procedure can additionally consider a mean model for the observations, and this further conditions the subsequent model predictions. We use the GPR implementation in George [13].

The mean model we construct for our light curve in each band must be sensitive to the early-time bump observed within the first five days, but insensitive to late-time galactic contamination from the bright nucleus. We use Scipy’s `splrep` function, which determines a basis (B-) spline representing a one-dimensional function, to construct this model [120]. The basis calculated by this method is determined both by the degree of the spline fit and the weights imposed on each observation. The observations with highest relative weighting most tightly constrain the B-spline, allowing us to determine the light-curve features captured in the mean model and those smoothed in it.

First, we calculate a B-spline for our r -band photometry with polynomial order five. Observations taken before MJD 58858.0 ($\delta t \approx 4.0$ days) are given a weight of 60, those within 3 days of the r -band peak are given a weight of 50, and all other points are given a weight of 10. We then construct a mean model for our GPR according to the following equation:

$$\bar{m}(t) = \begin{cases} B(t + \alpha) + \beta + \gamma & \text{for } t < 58858.0 \\ B(t + \alpha) + \beta, & \text{for } t \geq 58858.0 \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

Where t is the time in MJD, B is the r -band B-spline interpolation function, α is a parameter that shifts the entire curve forward in phase, β is a parameter that shifts the model in magnitude, and γ is a parameter that determines the height of the early-time brightness excess relative to the rest of the light curve. Although this model was constructed from only our r -band photometry, it serves as the mean model for all our passbands. The parameters described above allow the model to account for the difference in light curve properties between r and the other fitted bands.

These three free parameters, in addition to a fourth to account for the intrinsic photometric dispersion, are then fit in each band independently using an exp-sine-squared kernel of length-scale $\Gamma = 0.9$ and period $\ln(P) = 5$ to smoothly predict the rise and decay of the luminosity. The period was chosen to be approximately twice the duration of the photometry (~ 70 days), ensuring that the rise and fall to the light curve corresponds to the first half-wavelength of the model. The value for Γ was determined empirically; larger Γ values resulted in a mean model that overfit the observations and preserved small-scale correlations. This results in a set of 500 interpolated observations in $UBgVriz$ bands spanning MJD 58854-58919 (corresponding to the first 65 days of the explosion). We present the posterior distributions obtained from this method in Figure 2.1.

Next, we use the `Superbol` package⁹ [362] to calculate the integrated bolometric luminosity of SN 2020oi. After shifting to the rest frame and correcting for the combined Milky Way and host-galaxy extinction, we model the explosion at each epoch as a black-body (a good approximation during the photospheric phase

⁹<https://github.com/mnicholl/superbol>

owing to the optically thick ejecta) and use the `curve_fit` routine within the Python package `Scipy` to determine the photospheric temperature and radius that best describe each interpolated observation. These curves are then integrated to account for the unobserved far-UV and near-IR flux from the event and calculate the bolometric luminosity at each epoch. We present the final bolometric light curve in Figure 2.4, along with those reported by Lyman et al. [313] and Taddia et al. [480] for previous SN Ic and SN Ic-BL events.

We find SN 2020oi to be less luminous than nearly all previous SNe Ic from Lyman et al. [313] for the majority of its evolution. Roughly 10 days before peak, the explosion is the second-dimmest type-Ic event for which data are available. Similarly, at the end of the photospheric phase ($t \approx 30$ days, after which point the SN ejecta can no longer be approximated as a black-body due to its decreasing opacity as it expands), SN 2020oi is dimmer than all but two SN Ic reported [the tail of the SN 1994I is slightly less luminous, although the extinction in the direction of SN 1994I remains highly uncertain; see 432]. Interestingly, although we find the event to be dimmer than most other SNe Ic at early- and late-times, at peak SN 2020oi rises to within less than half a standard deviation of the mean peak luminosity for the SN Ic sample.

An event with a lower luminosity pre- and post-maximum but reaching comparable brightness at peak to other type-Ic explosions must necessarily exhibit rise and decline rates greater than other type-Ic events. Indeed, as is reported in Horesh et al. [223] and visible in Fig. 2.4, the slope of the bolometric luminosity of SN 2020oi after maximum is steeper than most previously observed SNe Ic. The overall bolometric evolution can be seen to roughly match that of SN 1994I. We can parameterize the decline rate of SN 2020oi by $\Delta m_{15,\text{bol}}$, the difference in the absolute bolometric magnitude from peak brightness to 15 days following peak. We find a value of $\Delta m_{15,\text{bol}} \approx 1.63 \pm 0.14$, higher than any other stripped-envelope SN reported by either Lyman et al. [313] or Taddia et al. [480] and ~ 1 mag higher than the median for type-Ic events. The wide scatter in SN Ic decline rates was reported in Li et al. [300] in a study of eight events, although of the SNe considered only the decline of SN 1994I was characterized as rapid. Larger type-Ic samples are needed to determine whether these rapidly-declining events are intrinsically rare. We present the peak absolute magnitudes and $\Delta m_{15,\text{bol}}$ values for SN 2020oi and other stripped-envelope events in Figure 2.5.

Photospheric Properties of SN 2020oi

We now leverage our best-fit black-body model from `Superbol` to estimate the radius and temperature of the photosphere of the SN as it explodes, which we present in Figure 2.6 for the first 60 days of the explosion. Due to the unknown nature of the flux excess, we consider only the radius and temperature estimates following $\delta t \sim 3$ days from the time of explosion.

Following the observed flux excess, the first photospheric radius observed is $R = 5.1 \pm 0.9 \times 10^{14}$ cm at $\delta t \approx 3$ days from explosion. The corresponding effective temperature at this epoch is $T_{\text{eff}} = 6300 \pm 600$ K. As the ejecta expands, the temperature of the ejecta probed by the photosphere decreases and so does its scattering opacity. At $\delta t = 11.7$ days, the photosphere radius reaches a maximum of

$2.1 \pm 0.6 \times 10^{15}$ cm, or 140 AU, and a temperature of $T_{eff} = 5800 \pm 600$ K. The opacity of the external layers of expanding ejecta has now decreased sufficiently to allow central radiation to escape, causing the photosphere to recede inward. Past $\delta t = 11.7$ days, the radius of the photosphere decreases gradually until $\delta t = 20$ days (10 days following peak luminosity) and then remains roughly constant for the following 30 days considered.

For comparison, we have also estimated the photospheric properties of the explosion as derived from the classification spectrum and the five spectra proceeding it. At each spectral epoch, we obtain an upper limit on the photospheric velocity from the minimum of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ line. Assuming homologous expansion, the radius is then estimated as $R(\delta t) = v_{exp} \delta t$. We caution that this estimate is highly sensitive to our estimated time of explosion. The effective temperature is calculated from the bolometric luminosity as

$$T_{eff}(\delta t) = \left(\frac{L_{bol}(\delta t)}{4\pi R_{ph}(\delta t)^2 \sigma_{SB}} \right)^{1/4} \quad (2.2)$$

where σ_{SB} is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant. We find systematically higher temperatures and lower radii using the spectroscopic indicators for the epochs studied, although the overall evolution is similar.

We also plot the best-fit spectroscopic estimates of the photospheric temperature and radius for the similar type-Ic SN 1994I in Fig. 2.6. We note a more gradual temperature evolution for SN 2020oi compared to SN 1994I when derived from the event photometry; this difference is less prominent in the spectroscopic indicators, and may be a reflection of the method used rather than an intrinsic difference in the two explosions.

The evolution provided by the black-body fits excluding the early excess closely mimics that of the stripped-envelope SNe considered in both Prentice et al. [391] and Taddia et al. [480]. The maximum photospheric radius for SN 2020oi is in agreement with the range reported by Taddia et al. [480] of $0.6 - 2.4 \times 10^{15}$ cm⁻¹, and the SNe in both samples also exhibit a maximum photospheric temperature of $T = 4000 - 8000$ K followed by a cooling phase to roughly ~ 5000 K 10 days following maximum light. We similarly note an apparent increase in temperature following this leveling off, as is reported in Prentice et al. [391] and Taddia et al. [480]; however, this is most likely nonphysical and instead a consequence of non-thermal effects following the photospheric phase of the explosion (as we mention above, the explosion is not well-characterized by a black-body following $\delta t \approx 30$ days).

2.5 Explosion Kinetics from Bolometric Fitting

The rapid brightening of the explosion as observed in Fig. 2.4 indicates a short diffusion time for photons produced by the radioactive decay of synthesized ⁵⁶Ni and ⁵⁶Co. We derive this timescale along with other explosion parameters for the SN using three independent methodologies, which we describe and compare below.

The Arnett (1982) Model Applied to the Bolometric Light Curve of SN 2020oi

In this section, we use a modified one-component Arnett model [21] to constrain $M_{\text{Ni}56}$, the mass of ^{56}Ni synthesized in the explosion; t_{exp} , the time of explosion; and t_d , the diffusion timescale. We further derive the total kinetic energy E_k and the total mass ejected in the explosion M_{ej} from these estimates. The Arnett model contains a number of assumptions which are applicable during the photospheric phase of most standard SN explosions ($t \lesssim 30$ days): that the ejecta undergo homologous expansion and are both optically thick and radiation-pressure dominated; that the energy density of the ejecta is most concentrated at its center; and that the explosion exhibits spherical symmetry. This formalism has proven valuable for characterizing the bolometric evolution of both type-Ia SNe and stripped-envelope events [see e.g., 382, 143, 434, 126, 313, 422, 33]. In this work, we adopt the modified Arnett model developed by Valenti et al. [492] in which the emission of the SN is assumed to be dominated by the radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni into ^{56}Co early in the explosion and from ^{56}Co to ^{56}Fe at late times.

We iteratively fit our bolometric light curve excluding the early-time flux excess, first for t_d and next for t_{exp} . This procedure requires an estimate of the ejecta velocity at peak bolometric luminosity, which we estimate spectroscopically using the Si line to be $v_{\text{exp}} = -12750 \pm 250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. We limit our search for t_{exp} to within 5 days of our earliest observation but no later than MJD 58855.54 (the date of the first explosion detection) and our search for t_d to (0, 20) days. We also assume an optical opacity of $\kappa_{\text{opt}} = 0.07 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ as is typically adopted for hydrogen-poor CCSNe [479]. Using this routine, we find a diffusion timescale for the event of $t_d = 8.41 \pm 0.28$ days and a predicted time of explosion of $t_{\text{exp}} = 58855.4 \pm 0.2$ (MJD). The uncertainties reported are propagated from our photometric and spectroscopic uncertainties, and do not include uncertainty in the host-galaxy extinction or the distance to the SN. From this procedure, we further derive a total kinetic energy of $E_k = 0.97 \pm 0.13 \times 10^{51} \text{ erg}$, comparable to the estimate of $1 \times 10^{51} \text{ erg}$ provided in Rho et al. [409].

Because the unusual early-time photometric evolution of the explosion can bias the Arnett estimates for t_0 toward later epochs, we derive the time of explosion by fitting the SN rise (excluding epochs of optical and UV excess) to an expanding-fireball model. We elaborate on this model in §2.9. We impose an assumption of zero flux at MJD 58852.55 corresponding to the epoch of the last r -band non-detection from ZTF. From our best-fit model, we predict an explosion time of MJD 58854.0 ± 0.3 . We adopt this value throughout this work. We note that this estimate is consistent with the MJD date of 58854.0 ± 1.5 estimated by Rho et al. [409] and that of 58854.50 ± 1.46 predicted by Horesh et al. [223]. Further, taking the mean between the last ZTF non-detection and the time of the first explosion detection (on MJD 58855.54), we obtain a comparable MJD date of 58854.05.

Constraining the Ejecta Mass of SN 2020oi Using the Khatami and Kasen (2019) Formalism

In addition to the Arnett prescription, we use the model described in Khatami et al. [266] to constrain M_{ej} and $M_{\text{Ni}56}$. Although the Arnett model provides an estimate for the mass of synthesized ^{56}Ni , the model assumes that the peak luminosity of the event is equal to the heating rate at peak. This ignores radiative diffusion originating from the central engine and extending to the surface of the ejecta, which can lead to the true peak luminosity being underestimated if the heating source is centrally concentrated and overestimated if the heating source is highly mixed. For stripped-envelope supernovae such as the one considered here, this can have a large effect on the reported ^{56}Ni mass [266]. By parameterizing the degree of mixing for different classes of explosions with a factor β , the Khatami & Kasen model attempts to account for this diffusion and provide a more accurate estimate of the nickel mass.

With an estimate for the peak luminosity of the event L_{peak} , the time of peak light t_{peak} , and the mixing parameter β , $M_{\text{Ni}56}$ can be determined by re-arranging equation A.13 from Khatami et al. [266]:

$$M_{\text{Ni}56} = \frac{L_{\text{peak}}\beta^2 t_{\text{peak}}^2}{2\varepsilon_{\text{Ni}} t_{\text{Ni}}^2} \left(\left(1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{Co}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{Ni}}} \right) \times \right. \\ \left. (1 - (1 + \beta t_{\text{peak}}/t_{\text{Ni}})e^{-\beta t_{\text{peak}}/t_{\text{Ni}}}) + \right. \\ \left. \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{Co}} t_{\text{Co}}^2}{\varepsilon_{\text{Ni}} t_{\text{Ni}}^2} (1 - (1 + \beta t_{\text{peak}}/t_{\text{Co}})e^{-\beta t_{\text{peak}}/t_{\text{Co}}}) \right)^{-1} \quad (2.3)$$

where $t_{\text{Ni}} = 8.77$ days is the timescale for the radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni into ^{56}Co , $t_{\text{Co}} = 111.3$ days is the timescale for the radioactive decay of ^{56}Co into ^{56}Fe , and ε_{Ni} and ε_{Co} are the amount of energy per unit mass released from these decays. We adopt a value of $\beta = 0.9$ that has been empirically calibrated from a sample of well-studied SNe Ic [5]. The diffusion timescale t_d can be calculated from the rise time by numerically solving the equation

$$\frac{t_{\text{peak}}}{t_d} = 0.11 \ln \left(1 + \frac{9t_s}{t_d} \right) + 0.36 \quad (2.4)$$

and, from the diffusion timescale, the total ejecta mass is then found by

$$M_{\text{ej}} = t_d^2 v_{\text{ej}} \frac{c}{\kappa_{\text{opt}}} \quad (2.5)$$

As in the Arnett treatment, we derive the kinetic energy from the ejected mass:

$$E_k = \frac{3}{10} M_{\text{ej}} v_{\text{exp}}^2 \quad (2.6)$$

where v_{exp} is the velocity of the explosion at peak (found spectroscopically with the Si line).

We report a synthesized ^{56}Ni mass of $M_{\text{Ni}56} = 0.08 \pm 0.02 M_{\odot}$ and a total ejecta mass of $M_{\text{ej}} = 0.81 \pm 0.03 M_{\odot}$ from this method. These estimates are slightly higher than the $M_{56\text{Ni}} = 0.07 M_{\odot}$ and $M_{\text{ej}} = 0.7 M_{\odot}$ values reported by Rho et al. [409], where they are estimated by comparing photometric observations of the event to a library of explosion models. The best-fit values from our one-component Arnett model are $M_{\text{Ni}56} = 0.16 \pm 0.02 M_{\odot}$ and $M_{\text{ej}} = 1.00 \pm 0.08 M_{\odot}$. The larger M_{ej} values derived with the Arnett model is a direct consequence of their distinct treatments of the diffusion timescale; by considering the additional contributions from radiative diffusion, the timescale calculated using the Khatami et al. [266] method is significantly higher than is found using the Arnett method. Khatami et al. [266] also note that the Arnett model yields less-accurate parameter estimates for lower values of $M_{56\text{Ni}}$, in some cases deviating from the true mass by a factor of two (as is shown for the type-II SN 1987A relative to the value determined from late-time light curve fits). Because of the limitations of the Arnett model, we adopt the Khatami et al. [266] estimates for the nickel and ejecta masses, as well as the kinetic energy of the explosion.

The ejected nickel mass estimated for SN 2020oi from both the Arnett and the Khatami & Kasen formalisms is lower than the median for SNe Ic presented in Anderson [14]. Similarly, Taddia et al. [480] suggest that the mass of nickel synthesized in SN Ic events is $\sim 0.09 - 0.17 M_{\odot}$, and our estimates occupy the lower end of this distribution. Because the radioactive decays $^{56}\text{Ni} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Co}$ and $^{56}\text{Co} \rightarrow ^{56}\text{Fe}$ are the dominant energy sources powering the emission at early and late times, respectively, this finding is consistent with the low luminosity of the bolometric light curve observed in Fig. 2.4. The estimated mass of synthesized ^{56}Ni is comparable to the $0.07 M_{\odot}$ value reported for SN 1994I [234], explaining their similar bolometric evolution. We compare the best-fit explosion parameters for SN 2020oi to other stripped-envelope SNe in Figure 2.7, and report the derived explosion properties in Table 2.3.

The MOSFiT type-Ic Model Applied to the Optical/UV Photometry of SN 2020oi

In addition to estimating the properties of SN 2020oi from the bolometric light curve, we use the SN Ic model within the Modular Open Source Fitter for Transients [MOSFiT; 198] to validate the SN explosion parameters and constrain the photospheric properties of SN 2020oi. In this framework, a forward model for the emission of an explosive transient is constructed by specifying its central engine and emission SED. In the default SN Ic model, energy from ^{56}Ni decay is deposited following the rates provided in Nadyozhin [356]. This produces black-body radiation that diffuses from the SN ejecta according to Arnett [21]. MOSFiT is implemented using a Bayesian framework for iteratively sampling the SN parameter space and approximating the solution with maximum likelihood. As in the models described in previous sections, MOSFiT constrains M_{ej} and $M_{\text{Ni}56}$ (parameterized by the fraction of M_{ej} comprised of nickel, f_{Ni}) and assumes homologous expansion of the ejecta. We additionally solve for the γ -ray opacity κ_{λ} of the ejecta, which controls the degree of trapping of γ -rays generated from ^{56}Ni and ^{56}Co decay; as well as T_{min} , the temperature floor of the model photosphere. We exclude photometry after $\delta t > 30$ days from our fit. We use the dynamic nesting sampling method in *dynesty* [465], with a burn-in phase of 500 and a chain

length of 2000, to sample our parameter space. We have verified that we obtain comparable results using MCMC sampling with `emcee`, a Python-based application of an affine invariant Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC) with an ensemble sampler [147].

We list our best-fit MOSFiT parameters in Table 2.3. We also compare the bolometric light curves associated with our MOSFiT and Arnett models in Fig. 2.8, and present the corner plot from our MOSFiT run in Fig. 2.9. We have found during this analysis that, by fitting the model band-by-band under the assumption of black-body radiation (as opposed to our Arnett fit to the bolometric light-curve), the MOSFiT model is more sensitive to deviations from black-body. This was particularly evident later in the event’s evolution, where the inclusion of photometry > 30 days from explosion resulted in a best-fit MOSFiT model whose bolometric light-curve was under-luminous relative to that of SN 2020oi.

We can now compare the photospheric evolution of our MOSFiT model to that derived photometrically and spectroscopically. We plot the black-body radius and temperature for the first 60 days of the model in Fig. 2.6. The temperatures predicted by the model within the first ~ 6 days are higher than those derived from photometry and spectra, but the plateau starting 20 days following explosion is consistent. The photospheric radius suggested by the model is lower than the photometric estimates before 20 days and consistent thereafter.

Table 2.3: SN 2020oi Explosion Parameters Derived Using Multiple Models.

Method	M_{Ni} (M_{\odot})	M_{ej} (M_{\odot})	t_{exp} (MJD)	t_{d} (days)	E_k 10^{51} erg
Arnett [21]	$0.16^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	$1.00^{+0.08}_{-0.08}$	$58855.4^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	$8.41^{+0.28}_{-0.28}$	$0.97^{+0.13}_{-0.13}$
Khatami et al. [266]	$0.08^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	$0.81^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	–	$19.88^{+0.36}_{-0.36}$	$0.79^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$
Guillochon et al. [MOSFiT; 198]	$0.107^{+0.003}_{-0.003}$	$0.79^{+0.06}_{-0.07}$	$58853.99^{+0.08}_{-0.07}$	$8.08^{+0.23}_{-0.29}$	$0.77^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$
Final Values	$0.08^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	$0.81^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	$58854.0^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	$19.88^{+0.36}_{-0.36}$	$0.79^{+0.09}_{-0.09}$

Note: The adopted explosion time was determined by fitting the early-time rise to a fireball explosion model.

2.6 Inferences on the Pre-Explosion Mass-Loss History

The X-ray emission from H-stripped SNe exploding in low-density environments is dominated by Inverse Compton (IC) radiation for $\delta t \lesssim 40$ days [e.g., 93]. In this scenario, the X-ray emission is generated by the upscattering of seed optical photospheric photons by a population of relativistic electrons that have been accelerated at the SN forward shock. We followed the IC formalism by Margutti et al. [330] modified for a massive stellar progenitor density profile as in Margutti et al. [331]. Specifically, we assumed a wind-like environment density profile $\rho_{\text{CSM}} \propto r^{-s}$ with $s = 2$ as appropriate for massive stars [85], an

energy spectrum of the accelerated electrons $N_e(\gamma) \propto \gamma^{-p}$ with $p = 3$ as commonly found from radio observations of Ib/c SNe [e.g., 463, 461, 462, 460] and as observed at late times in SN 2020oi [223], and a fraction of postshock energy into relativistic electrons $\epsilon_e = 0.1$. We further adopted the explosion parameters $M_{\text{ej}} = 0.81 M_{\odot}$ and $E_k = 0.79 \times 10^{51}$ erg inferred from the modeling of the bolometric light curve in §2.5. Under these assumptions, our deep X-ray upper limits from §2.2 lead to a mass-loss rate limit of $\dot{M} \approx 1.5 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$ for a wind velocity of $v_w = 1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

In an earlier analysis on SN 2020oi by Horesh et al. [223], radio observations obtained with the Karl G. Jansky Very Large Array (VLA) beginning on day 5 of the explosion [222] were explained as radiation originating from a shock-wave interaction between the SN ejecta and surrounding circumstellar material. These data were then modeled using the synchrotron self-absorption (SSA) formalism derived in Chevalier [94]. In this model, the microphysics of the interaction are parameterized by the ratio between ϵ_e , the fraction of energy from the shock-wave injected into relativistic electrons; and ϵ_B , the fraction of energy converted to magnetic fields. The best-fit model found by Horesh et al. [223] suggests a strong departure from equipartition, with $\frac{\epsilon_e}{\epsilon_B} \geq 200$. Further, Horesh et al. [223] predict an X-ray emission from Inverse Compton of $L_x \approx 1.2 \times 10^{39} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. This corresponds to a flux of $F_x \approx 5.1 \times 10^{-14} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for their estimated distance of 14 Mpc.

We find no evidence for statistically significant X-ray emission using Chandra and infer a 0.3-10 keV unabsorbed flux limit of $F_x < 6.3 \times 10^{-15} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ at $\delta t = 40$ days (see §2.2). Their derived progenitor mass-loss rate of $\dot{M} = 1.4 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ is comparable to the value calculated in this work; however, our deeper flux limit indicates either different microphysical parameters (ϵ_e and ϵ_B) than the ones adopted by Horesh et al. [223] or suppression of the X-ray emission due to photoelectric absorption by a thick neutral medium.

2.7 Spectral Analysis

We have used the 1D Monte Carlo radiative transfer code TARDIS¹⁰ [262, 261] to estimate the composition of the SN ejecta from the obtained spectra. This requires us to assume a density distribution for the SN ejecta and a bolometric luminosity for each spectrum. For the bolometric luminosities corresponding to each spectral epoch, we have evaluated the bolometric light curve derived in §2.4. Given the similarity of the explosion to SN 1994I, we have adopted the density distribution model corresponding to a carbon-oxygen core of mass $M_f = 2.1 M_{\odot}$ immediately before explosion [CO21, 365, 234]. Each spectrum has been computed within a given range of velocities, in which we have assumed the ejecta undergo homologous expansion. The minimum ejecta velocity for each spectrum was derived from the P-Cygni profile associated with its primary absorption features. Elemental abundances are assumed to be uniform within the velocity range considered. We concentrate our analysis on the four spectra measured closest to peak

¹⁰<https://tardis-sn.github.io/tardis/index.html>

luminosity ($\delta t = 10.6, 14.6, 16.5,$ and 18.4 days from explosion).

Our models are able to reproduce the dominant features identified in the observed spectra: we replicate the profiles of the Si II $\lambda 6355$ feature, the near-IR Ca II triplet, the Fe II contributions and the Mg II $\lambda 4481$ lines. Some discrepancies remain; for example, the simulated O I line predicts a slightly larger absorption than the observed line [similar to what is shown in 511]. We have identified the C II $\lambda 6540$ line in the day 10.6 spectrum, and in order to simulate this feature, we have increased the abundance of carbon in the corresponding velocity regime. We have also included a non-negligible sodium abundance to reproduce the absorption observed around 5600 \AA . This feature may include some contribution from He I $\lambda 5876$, which is excited by non-thermal processes originating from the decay of nickel generated in the explosion [309]. A similar line of reasoning applies for the C II $\lambda 6540$ feature, which can be contaminated by residual absorption from He I $\lambda 6678$. We do not identify clear He I features in our spectral series, such as the triplet 2p-3s transition He I $\lambda 7065$ that is usually observed in the spectra of type-Ib SNe. The other optical He I $\lambda 4471$ feature is located in a region contaminated by other absorptions, mainly from Mg and Fe. Unfortunately, our spectral data do not cover the near-IR range where the bright lines He I $\lambda \lambda 10830, 20580$ are visible from the 2s-2p singlet/triplet transitions, and as a result we are unable to conclusively verify contributions from helium.

To further investigate the presence of a non-negligible helium abundance, we have also used the `recomb-nlte` option in TARDIS. For the day 11 spectrum, we have considered an amount of $\sim 0.01 M_{\odot}$ of helium in our simulated ejecta, and we obtain slightly stronger agreement with the observed spectrum. Nevertheless, we are unable to unambiguously confirm the presence of helium in the SN 2020oi ejecta. We note that the potential presence of helium was also considered in the case of the type-Ic SN 1994I [see e.g., 137, 34] and previously for SN 2020oi [409].

In Figure 2.10, we show the spectral series obtained near peak with the FLOYDS spectrograph along with the results of our spectral synthesis simulations. As an additional comparison, we plot three spectra corresponding to the type-Ic SN 1994I at comparable epochs in its explosion [137]. The two events show notable similarities in their evolution and in the presence of Ca II, Mg II, Fe II, Si II, and O I features. SN 2020oi shows slightly higher ejecta velocities than SN 1994I [340], as estimated from the minima of the P-Cygni absorptions lines (in particular, from the Si II $\lambda 6355$ transition). This result is also consistent with the higher kinetic energy found for this SN (see §2.5) compared to SN 1994I ($0.6 - 0.8 \times 10^{51}$ erg; see [340]), and also its higher bolometric peak in Figure 2.4.

The dominant species recovered from the TARDIS [262, 261] simulations of the peak spectra are shown in Figure 2.11, and the full abundance pattern found for each spectrum is presented in Table 2.4. The abundance pattern varies only marginally across the epochs that we have simulated and within the velocity range considered, suggesting mixing within the ejecta. Our simulated composition is also similar to that reported

for other type-Ic SNe for which element mixing has been discussed [432]. A more detailed analysis of these spectra considering a stratified abundance distribution is planned for an upcoming work, allowing us to further investigate mixing signatures.

Table 2.4: Fractional Abundances [$\times 10^{-2}$] of Best-Fit SN 2020oi Spectra.

Phase	X_{He}	X_C	X_O	X_{Ne}	X_{Na}	X_{Mg}	X_{Si}	X_S	X_{Ca}	X_{Ni}	X_{Fe}	X_{Co}	X_{Cr}	X_{Ti}	X_{Ar}
3.3	65.0	10.0	16.8	0.0	0.0	3.0	4.0	0.0	0.5	0.01	0.10	0.0	0.001	0.001	0.0
10.6	14.0	5.0	60.0	10.0	0.1	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.05	0.05	0.10	0.01	0.01	0.01	2.0
14.6	1.0	5.0	65.0	19.0	1.0	0.5	0.4	0.1	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.0	0.005	0.005	4.0
16.5	0.0	2.0	75.0	20.0	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.0	0.005	0.005	2.0
18.4	0.0	1.0	75.0	20.0	1.0	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.07	0.15	0.0	0.006	0.006	3.0

2.8 The Very Early Spectrum of SN 2020oi

We now consider the peculiar features of the SN 2020oi spectrum obtained at $\delta t = 3.3$ days. This spectrum is one of the earliest obtained for a type-Ic SN.

This spectrum shows considerable absorption features from Si-burning elements, including Si II $\lambda 6355$ and the Ca II NIR triplet jointly expanding at a velocity of $v_{\text{exp}} = -24,000 \pm 500$ km s $^{-1}$. At the same velocity, we have identified the feature at ~ 4500 Å as Fe II (multiplet 42), although this feature is likely blended with other fainter absorptions of Fe-peak elements [e.g., $\lambda = 4508.29$ Å; see 9]. The lack of a substantial absorption from O I $\lambda 7773$ indicates that the line-forming region of this spectrum is located in the most external layers of the ejecta, where the abundance pattern is enriched in lighter elements such as carbon and helium. Indeed, we find evidence for He I $\lambda 5876$ and C II $\lambda 6580$, and cannot rule out a potential contribution from He I $\lambda 6678$. Unfortunately, our spectrum does not cover the near-IR region where the He I $\lambda 10830$ line is typically prominent in the presence of a helium-rich gas.

To characterize this early spectrum, we undertake the same composition modeling using TARDIS as was done for the peak spectra. However, we are unable to reproduce the observed spectrum using the same SN 1994I CO21 density distribution [365, 234] that was adopted for the peak spectra; in particular, we cannot reproduce the blue excess observed at wavelengths ≤ 5000 Å. Consequently, we have considered deviations from the pure CO21 model for this spectrum caused by the presence of a gas excess at larger radii. We note that a similar approach has been recently adopted in Williamson et al. [511] in an analysis of SN 1994I. We find that our observed spectrum can be reproduced by an excess of $\sim 0.2 M_{\odot}$ of material composed of a large amount of carbon, helium, oxygen, and traces of heavy element signatures (Ca, Si, S, Fe) at the highest velocities ($v_{\text{exp}} \approx -24000$ km s $^{-1}$), roughly corresponding to $\sim 10^{14}$ cm at the time the spectrum was obtained (assuming homologous expansion). We show this best-fit spectrum, as well

as those predicted by the CO21 composition and density models, in Fig. 2.12. *Our fits suggest that the blue excess of the day 3.3 spectrum can be explained by an additional-mass component with a composition distinct from the ejecta near peak.* However, we note that our final simulation does not precisely reproduce the continuum at bluer wavelengths (e.g. $\lambda \ll 5000 \text{ \AA}$).

If the blue excess observed in the day 3.3 spectrum is the result of emission from material present at the highest explosion velocities, any additional signatures within the day 6.6 spectrum will better constrain its mass and composition. This analysis is beyond the scope of this work but is planned for a separate publication.

2.9 Characterizing the Early-Time Emission of SN 2020oi

Evidence for Flux in Excess of an Expanding-Fireball Explosion Model

We now consider the evidence for a bump in the photometry at day $\delta t \approx 2.5$ in excess of the emission expected for traditional SN explosions.

We fit the extinction-corrected flux spanning 3 to 10 days post-explosion in each band (excluding the early-time bump) to a canonical expanding-fireball model ($f \propto (t - t_{\text{exp}})^2$, where t_{exp} is the time of explosion). We have also fit a $(t - t_{\text{exp}})^n$ model where we allow n to vary between 1.0 and 3.0, finding reasonable agreement with the rise across all bands for $n = 1.7$. We present both models in Fig. 2.13 along with the associated photometry. Although neither model perfectly captures the early-time rise of the SN due to their simplicity, the $n = 1.7$ model more accurately describes the gradual increase in explosion flux past $\delta t \approx 6$ days. The models most closely fit the data between 4 and 6 days, which is unsurprising given the higher photometric uncertainties for data obtained at later epochs. We calculate the reduced- χ^2_ν Goodness-of-Fit across all bands for our analytic fireball models, where ν quantifies the degrees of freedom in our early-time dataset.

We find a χ^2_ν value of 1.9 for the $n = 2$ model and 0.5 for the $n = 1.7$ model. Next, we calculate the reduced- χ^2 across all bands for the values between 2.2 and 2.7 days (comprising the early bump). We find a χ^2_ν value of 15.0 for the $n = 2$ model and 4.7 for the $n = 1.7$ model, indicating significantly worse fits for these observations than for the rest of the data composing the rise. Further, the consistency of the flux in excess of the best-fit models between bands (which is not captured by our χ^2_ν metric) and within photometry taken at multiple observatories indicates a physical origin. We investigate potential explanations for this excess in the following sections.

Emission from Shock Cooling

To characterize the excess flux observed in the pre-maximum UV and optical photometry, we first consider four distinct shock-cooling models. In the first two models, we apply the Sapir et al. [431] treatment using

two values for the polytropic indices of the progenitor star. These models assume a progenitor composed of a uniform density core of mass M_c and a polytropic envelope in hydrostatic equilibrium. Immediately following shock breakout, the emission is assumed to be dominated by the outermost layers of the envelope; in subsequent epochs, the emission from successively deeper layers dominate. We adopt polytropic indices of $n = 3/2$ and $n = 3$, appropriate for a red super-giant with a convective envelope and a blue super-giant with a radiative envelope, respectively. Although these extended hydrogen envelopes have been stripped in the case of SNe Ic such as SN 2020oi, this is one of the only shock-cooling treatments in the literature that attempts to account for the density profile of the progenitor (by the ability to change the polytropic index of its envelope). As a result, it remains a valuable probe of the shock breakout kinetics of stripped-envelope events.

For the third model, we consider the one-zone analytic solution described in Piro [384]. This model considers shock-cooling from surrounding circumstellar material and is independent of the chemical composition and density profile of the material. The fourth model uses a revised treatment for this emission from Piro et al. [385], which differs from the original formalism with the addition of a power-law dependence of the luminosity with time during the rise of the early emission.

Each of these models allows us to constrain the mass (M_{env}) and the radius (R_{env}) of extended material surrounding the progenitor; the shock velocity v_s ; and the time between the early excess and the time of explosion t_{exp} . As in Jacobson-Galán et al. [237], we use the package `emcee` to sample our model parameter space and obtain the fit with the smallest χ^2 value.

Adopting the procedure outlined above, none of the four models successfully converged to a solution that accurately characterized the early-time photometry. The reason for this lies in the first photometric observation for the event (see Fig. 2.13) in r band, which was originally reported in the ZTF alert stream [40]. If the explosion occurred within an environment free of surrounding material, the emission during shock-breakout of the progenitor’s photosphere should be the earliest optical emission observed. The initial r band observation occurs > 0.5 days earlier than the rest of the photometry and agrees with the continuum predicted by the analytic rise models outlined in the previous section. This suggests that shock breakout from the stellar surface occurred earlier than the optical excess at $\delta t \approx 2.5$ days, and the models considered are unable to reconcile these two phases of early-time photometry. The timescale of these observations disfavors shock-cooling of surrounding material as the cause of the flux excess; nevertheless, we caution that these simplified models have been validated against prominent early emission signatures and may be unsuitable for more subtle excesses.

To account for the possibility that the first ZTF observation was not caused by the explosion, we manually fit our shock-cooling models to the early-time bump excluding this point to estimate the properties of the resulting progenitor photosphere. Both these parameters and those corresponding to the full MCMC fit are presented in Table 2.5. From the manual fits, which are shown in Fig. 2.14, we derive $M_{\text{env}} \approx 0.5 - 70 \times 10^{-2} M_{\odot}$, $R_{\text{env}} \approx 4 - 14 R_{\odot}$, and $v_{\text{env}} \approx 2 - 4 \times 10^4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Although

the range in shock velocities found is consistent with the value of $2.4 \pm 0.2 \times 10^4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ estimated spectroscopically for the photosphere at $\delta t \approx 3.5$ days, binary evolution models from Yoon et al. [517] (Fig. 12) predict larger radii for a progenitor of final mass $2.1 M_{\odot}$ as is suggested by the spectroscopic analysis detailed in Section 2.7. Although these results suggest that only a small amount of mass located at the photosphere of the progenitor is needed to explain this emission, additional analysis is required to reconcile the characteristics of the observed bump with the initial ZTF detection.

Although shock-heating of dense CSM has been proposed to explain the VLA radio observations of SN 2020oi [223], the first radio emission was detected at $\delta t = 4.9$ days. This is ~ 2.5 days later than the early-time optical and UV excess. If both emission is caused by shock-heated media, the radio-emitting material must either exist at significantly higher radii than the optically-emitting material or the same material must be dense enough to explain the delay (in which case the material would likely be optically thick to the radio emission in the first place). This suggests that the SN 2020oi radio observations are uncorrelated with the optical excess, and that the two signatures are probing distinct environments. Without radio observations closer to the epoch of the photometric bump, we are unable to use the VLA data to verify the presence of nearby CSM.

Table 2.5: Shock Cooling Models.

Model	R_{env} (R_{\odot})	M_{env} ($\times 10^{-2} M_{\odot}$)	v_{env} ($\times 10^4 \text{ km s}^{-1}$)	t_{exp} (MJD)	χ^2_{ν}	DOF
P15	~ 6	~ 1.5	~ 2.2	–	–	–
P15 ^a	$7.23^{+2.33}_{-0.45}$	$0.82^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$	$2.45^{+0.10}_{-0.20}$	$58855.9^{+0.08}_{-0.03}$	51.7	21
P20	~ 18	~ 0.9	~ 3.6	–	–	–
P20 ^a	$13.6^{+1.31}_{-1.24}$	$0.47^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	$4.03^{+0.10}_{-0.10}$	$58856.1^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	53.7	20
SW17 [n=3/2]	~ 7.1	~ 6	~ 1.6	–	–	–
SW17 ^a [n=3/2]	$4.3^{+0.4}_{-0.3}$	$2.4^{+0.3}_{-0.2}$	$2.36^{+0.11}_{-0.11}$	$58856.2^{+0.1}_{-0.1}$	50.6	20
SW17 [n=3]	~ 7.2	~ 70	~ 1.8	–	–	–
SW17 ^a [n=3]	$5.7^{+1.1}_{-1.1}$	$67.0^{+1.5}_{-2.3}$	$2.04^{+0.20}_{-0.21}$	$58856.1^{+0.1}_{-0.1}$	52.9	20

^a Fitting only the flux excess i.e., $2 < t < 3$ days after explosion.

Emission from Companion Interaction

The ejecta mass derived in §2.5 and the agreement of the CO21 composition model with peak spectra in §2.7 both suggest that SN 2020oi originated in a binary system. For systems with low binary separations, the explosion of the primary star will affect the secondary, and it has been theorized that the presence of a

companion can be deduced by the signature it imprints on the earliest moments of an SN explosion.

The study by Kasen [251] in connection with SNe Ia is illustrative. In the conceptual framework presented, the presence of the companion blocks the expansion of the explosion ejecta and carves out a cavity behind it. Thermal diffusion from the heated ejecta, which is typically unable to escape at early times because of the high optical depths involved, then leaks into this rarefied space as radiation. This emission, which varies in intensity based on the binary separation a and the viewing angle θ , can be observed as an optical and UV excess at $\delta t < 8$ days above the broad continuum dominated by synthesized ^{56}Ni .

For the type-Ia simulated by Kasen, the emission timescale associated with companion interaction varies from ~ 2 days for highly inclined viewing angles to ~ 8 days for an interaction along the line of sight. The lower end of this timescale range agrees more with the inclusion of the early ZTF observation than the timescales associated with the shock-cooling models in the previous section, although we caution that this range may differ for SN Ic progenitor interactions. In addition, as is detailed in §2.8, interaction with material at $\geq 10^{14}$ cm can explain the blue excess in the day 3.3 spectrum.

Interaction of the explosion with a binary companion, proceeding in a manner similar to that outlined in Kasen [251], should produce additional early-time signatures. When the initial SN shock collides with the surface of the companion, the post-shock energy is released as an X-ray burst spanning the first few hours of the event in advance of the UV/optical emission. Further, because the SN ejecta are distorted by the presence of the companion, the subsequent emission should show polarization indicative of ejecta asymmetries. Observations of SN 2020oi taken using the WIRC+Pol instrument at Palomar Observatory [485] near peak found a broadband polarization of $p = 0.37 \pm 0.09\%$, low enough to be explained by interstellar dust scattering and not asymmetry within the explosion itself. Because the flux-excess timescale agrees more closely with the highly-inclined interactions simulated in Kasen [251], and the polarization measurements were taken long after any potential interaction, early asymmetry may be difficult to detect; further, the polarization signature of companion interaction at peak light (or lack thereof) remains unconstrained in the literature.

Nevertheless, the question remains as to whether the interaction of a type-Ic explosion with a binary companion would produce a similar flux excess to that predicted for SNe Ia. The analysis in Kasen [251] considered a low-mass companion with radius between 10^{11} cm (for an evolved sub-giant) and 10^{13} cm (for a red giant). In contrast, most companions of stripped-envelope supernovae should reside on or near the ZAMS [523], and so the signatures of binary interaction should be relatively faint [302] except for rare close-binary systems [411]. The stellar cluster coincident with SN 2020oi limits our ability to constrain the brightness of a companion and derive its physical properties. The majority of binary evolution models in BPASS that agree with our derived ejecta mass (see §2.12) feature a companion with radius immediately pre-explosion below 2×10^{11} cm and an orbital separation below 10^{12} cm. 80% of these systems feature radial separations higher than the close-binary systems considered in Rimoldi et al. [411]. Further, the optical bump occurs ~ 0.7 days after the first ZTF detection. Estimating the ejecta velocity as $-23,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

at early times, this corresponds to a distance of $\sim 10^{14}$ cm. As a result, the likely binary separation for this system is lower than suggested by the timescale of the excess if caused by companion interaction and higher than the necessary separation for a bright signature.

Emission from Hydrodynamical Interaction of the Ejecta with Circumstellar Material

The rapidly-expanding shock wave from an SN is followed by its more slowly-moving ejecta. For progenitor systems surrounded by CSM, the collision of the ejecta with this material creates a high-temperature interface whose multi-wavelength emission is re-processed and re-emitted. Although many stripped-envelope supernovae (SE SNe) for which CSM interaction has been proposed have been SNe IIb [e.g., 1993J and ZTF18aalrxas; 437, 156], there is increasing evidence that this process can also occur in SNe Ib/c [339, 115, 464].

The presence of local CSM as inferred from an early-time signature indicates a mass-loss episode concurrent with or immediately preceding the explosion. It has been recently realised that SNe can occur even for the fraction of stripped stars that are stably transferring mass onto a binary companion [290], potentially providing fresh CSM with which the ejecta could collide.

Current models [290, 189, 323] indicate that significant expansion of the progenitor star occurs only at sub-solar metallicity, ~ 50 kyr before the explosion and once again a few kyr before the explosion (although different progenitor mass-loss histories may allow for expansion at higher metallicities, as is suggested by [179]). During the latter interaction phase, the radius of the SN progenitor exceeds several R_{\odot} , thus creating a CSM cloud of at least 10^{13} cm. Much less mass ($< 0.1 M_{\odot}$) is shed during this secondary pre-explosion interaction relative to the first. Given that the envelope mass will be continuously ejected over the few kyr before the SN, and assuming a characteristic ejection velocity of 100 km s^{-1} (comparable to the orbital velocity at such separations), one may realistically expect a tenuous cloud extending up to $10^{17.5}$ cm around the system by the explosion time. Such clouds are sufficient to produce an early excess [92]. Because the density of this material strongly decreases with radius, a flux excess from CSM interaction would originate in the inner layers ($10^{14} - 10^{15}$ cm) of the cloud and the collision shock would accelerate as it expanded into the outermost low-density media. This distance is consistent with the timescale for the optical bump observed. The SN energy, in turn, would decrease due to the mass loss in the preceding binary interactions but remain comparable to typical type-Ic SN energies as an upper limit.

The main prediction of this scenario is that the event must have originated in a location with sub-solar metallicity, which supports the findings both from *HST* photometry in §2.10 and from MUSE spectroscopy in §2.11. Further, the explosion of the progenitor into CSM composed of its own lost envelope should lead to early-time spectroscopic signatures of the light elements shed, as is strongly suggested by the spectroscopic analysis in §2.8. Radiative diffusion through asymmetrically-distributed or clumpy CSM

may also explain the offset of the excess relative to the initial ZTF observation.

Another interesting line of evidence that may indicate CSM interaction lies in the rising K band continuum found by Rho et al. [409] 63 days from MJD 58854, which can be attributed to infrared emission from dust. Rho et al. [409] suggest that this signature may be produced by dust condensing directly from the SN ejecta, pre-existing CSM dust heated by SN radiation, newly formed dust from CSM interactions with the explosion, or an infrared echo from dust in the galaxy’s interstellar medium. A dusty pre-existing CSM shell heated by the SN shock at the time of explosion should be located at a distance of $10^{16} - 10^{17}$ cm to generate infrared (IR) emission ~ 60 days post-explosion. This distance is in general agreement with the limits placed on the sizes of previously-observed dust shells [151], but it remains unclear whether any CSM surrounding SN 2020oi at these radii would be dense enough to produce the day-63 IR emission. Additional analysis is therefore necessary to determine whether the most-likely CSM density structure created by type-Ic SNe undergoing Roche-lobe overflow could be responsible for both optical and IR signatures.

Emission caused by Asymmetric ^{56}Ni

It is possible that the presence of decaying ^{56}Ni in the outer layers of the SN ejecta is the source of the early flux excess, as has been proposed for stripped-envelope events with multiple light curve peaks [125] and other type-I events with less-prominent photometric excesses [318]. An asymmetric or shallow distribution, in comparison to the centrally concentrated ^{56}Ni ejecta assumed by the Arnett model, would power an event that is blue at early times and red at late times as the outer layers are locally heated [319]. We do not find significant evidence for this trend in our spectral sequence relative to that for SN 1994I in §2.7.

It is possible that a jet can deposit ^{56}Ni into the outermost, high-velocity ejecta of an SN, as was proposed for the type-Ib SN 2008D [44]; however, we have detected no X-ray emission associated with SN 2020oi as would be expected for a jet. In theory, the mass of nickel-rich material needed to explain our early-time emission is likely small [318]. However, as we note in earlier sections, significant asymmetry in the ejecta is at odds with the negligible polarization at peak light observed by Tinyanont et al. [485]. Further, we have found in §2.8 that by including C and He at significantly higher radii than the rest of the ejecta, we are able to reproduce the day 3.3 spectrum more faithfully than by considering an excess contribution of Ni and Fe.

Conclusions on the Photometric Excess

The above considerations lead us to the conclusion that the early-time flux excess may be the emission from ejecta interaction with CSM at large radii. We illustrate this scenario in Fig. 2.15. We note that the interpretation of CSM interaction is not inconsistent with the absence of narrow photoionization features in the day 3.3 spectrum from §2.8, as these may have been detectable at earlier epochs [267]. We caution that given the limited number of predictive excess models available in the literature for stripped-envelope events, other interpretations are possible. Further, at present we are unable to constrain whether CSM

surrounding the SN is the result of late-stage Roche-lobe overflow, the tenuous remnant of a previous mass-transfer episode, or an eruptive mass-loss event [e.g., 443].

2.10 Properties of the Stellar Cluster Coincident with 2020oi

In this section, we derive the properties of the stellar cluster associated with SN 2020oi from pre-explosion photometry obtained with the *Hubble Space Telescope* (*HST*).

We use the code *Prospector* [294] to generate synthetic integrated Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs) corresponding to a series of Simple Stellar Populations (SSPs, which are assumed to be created instantaneously). The *Prospector* package allows for both MCMC sampling in *emcee* [147] and dynamic nested sampling in *Dynesty* [465] to generate posterior estimates for a set of model parameters. In addition, it provides an interpolation scheme for generating SEDs spanning an arbitrarily fine grid in parameter space.

To characterize the stellar cluster associated with the SN, we first calculate its extinction-corrected flux in each *HST* filter prior to explosion. We then develop an SED model in *Prospector* parameterized by the age of the stellar cluster t_{Clust} ; the cluster metal mass fraction $\log_{10}(Z/Z_{\odot})$; and the cluster mass M_{Clust} . We implement top-hat priors for $\log_{10}(Z/Z_{\odot})$ and t_{Clust} spanning $[-2, 0.2]$ and $[0.1, 300]$ Myr, respectively, informed both by our later MUSE analysis and the stellar populations predicted in Allard et al. [11]. For our prior on M_{Clust} , we impose a log-uniform distribution spanning $[10^4, 10^{11}] M_{\odot}$. We then sample the posterior distribution of each SED model marginalized by our *HST* observations using *emcee*, where we have chosen 128 walkers for two rounds of burn-in of length 25 and 50, respectively, and a run length of 1000 iterations.

For comparison, we have additionally calculated the results obtained using *dynesty* and from a targeted brute-force grid search of the parameter space, in which we have sampled 200 values each of M_{Clust} , $\log_{10}(Z/Z_{\odot})$, and t_{Clust} within $[10^{4.5}, 10^{6.5}] M_{\odot}$, $[-2, 0]$, and $[1, 100]$ Myr, respectively. For each of our SSPs, we assume the Chabrier log-normal stellar IMF [83] and a Milky-Way curve for extinction of starlight from dust surrounding old stars [77]. We have verified that the use of the Calzetti et al. [71] extinction law does not alter our results.

We present a corner plot of our posterior estimates from both *emcee* and grid search in the right panel of Figure 2.16. Both methods predict a best-fit median cluster mass of $\log(M_{\text{Clust}}) = 5.86_{-0.26}^{+0.14} M_{\odot}$, a cluster metallicity of $\log(Z/Z_{\odot}) = -1.58_{-0.31}^{+0.35}$, and a cluster age of $t_{\text{Age}} = 40_{-20}^{+30}$ Myr. Our *dynesty* values are consistent with these estimates.

Knapen et al. [278] undertakes a similar analysis in the innermost region of M100 by fitting spatially-averaged optical and IR observations of dominant star-forming regions to stellar population models. For the region coincident with SN 2020oi, the authors find a best-fit model composed of multiple stellar populations but dominated by stars of age ~ 40 Myr, in close agreement with our estimate. A further study by

Allard et al. [11] derived an age of 10 – 30 Myr for the stellar population associated with SN 2020oi. These studies, coupled with our *Prospector* results from above, suggest that the SN progenitor is coincident with a young (~ 40 Myr) stellar cluster. Although we do not find evidence for multiple populations of stars as a direct consequence of our simplified SSP treatment, we do not have the wavelength coverage to constrain a more complex star formation history.

2.11 Host-Galaxy Properties from MUSE Spectroscopy

The inner region of NGC 4321/M100 was observed with the European Southern Observatory Very Large Telescope [211] with the Multi Unit Spectroscopic Explorer (MUSE) in the wide-field mode with adaptive optics configuration (WFM-AO) on April 28, 2019 (Prog. ID 1100.B-0651, PI: Schinnerer). Using the code described in Fusco et al. [162] to reconstruct the atmospheric conditions at the epochs observed, we derive PSF FWHM values of $0.677''$, $0.509''$, and $0.375''$, for 5000 \AA , 7000 \AA , and 9000 \AA , respectively, for our MUSE data. MUSE data have been reduced using standard *esorex* recipes that were embedded in a general python-based script. The final data cube covers $\sim 90\%$ of the *HST/ACS F814W* image, corresponding to the bright star-forming ring surrounding the center of the galaxy as can be seen in Fig. 2.17.

To analyze the MUSE data cube, we have first corrected for the Galactic reddening in the direction of the galaxy and then reported each single spaxel in the rest-frame, assuming a redshift of $z = 0.0052$. Then, we have applied the Voronoi spatial binning method [74] assuming a signal-to-noise value of 40 in a wavelength range characterized by an absence of spectral features ($\Delta\lambda = 5600 - 5700 \text{ \AA}$). After this binning, we use our analysis tools to study the properties of the underlying stellar component and nebular gaseous emission in each spectral bin. For each specific physical property we aim to study, we obtain a detailed spatially-resolved map across the full data cube and in the immediate surroundings of SN 2020oi.

Stellar Populations within M100

To distinguish the underlying stellar continuum from the gaseous emission, we have applied the stellar population synthesis code *STARLIGHT* [100] to each spectral bin. *STARLIGHT* allows us to fit an observed spectrum to a combination of template spectra, which can be composed of either individual stellar spectra or distinct stellar population models obtained from evolutionary codes. In the current work, we have used the stellar population synthesis models described in Bruzual et al. [61]. This library consists of 150 stellar templates generated with a Chabrier initial mass function [83] with ages varying between 10^6 yrs and 1.8×10^{10} yrs, and with metallicity spanning from $Z = 0.0001$ to $Z = 0.05$ in six bins (where $Z_{\odot} = 0.02$). This allows us to generate best-fit estimates for the age and metallicity distribution of M100, according to the input templates. A caveat is given by the wavelength range provided by MUSE: with a rest-frame range of $4675\text{-}9300 \text{ \AA}$, we miss the bluest region of stellar spectra where important indicators for the star formation history are present (e.g., Mg and Ca H&K absorption lines). As a result, the values provided are mainly

based on indicators available in the wavelength range covered by MUSE at $z = 0.0052$, e.g. the Ca II near-IR triplet.

We plot the light fraction contributions for young ($t < 500$ Myr), intermediate age ($500 \text{ Myr} < t < 5 \text{ Gyr}$), and old ($t > 5 \text{ Gyr}$) stellar populations in Fig. 2.18. Most evident is an anti-correlation of old stellar light with the spiral arms that comprise the nuclear ring. This anti-correlation is not evident in either of the two other maps, suggesting that the nuclear ring is comprised primarily of a combination of young and intermediate-age stars. Light from all three of these populations can be seen near the location of the SN, and because of the limited resolution of the IFU data we are unable to definitively associate it with a single stellar population.

SN 2020oi as Evidence for Cold Gas Dynamics in M100

M100 has been extensively studied due to its close proximity and its active star formation sites [424, 175, 81, 26, 132]. To date, seven SNe have been discovered within M100, but only SN 2020oi occurred within its central $5''$. This makes it possible to leverage previous analyses to further characterize the progenitor system and its formation as a consequence of the dynamical evolution of its host galaxy.

SN 2020oi exploded within a “nuclear ring” of radius $\sim 5''$ where the majority of star formation within M100 occurs [421]. Allard et al. [10] used SAURON IFU spectroscopy to probe the ring’s $H\beta$ emission and gas dispersion. In their model of nuclear ring formation, cold gas is channeled inward along the dust lanes of the spiral arms under the gravitational influence of the central bar. This gas settles near the inner Lindblad resonances for the galaxy at the contact points between the nuclear ring and the innermost spiral arms. At the trailing edge of the spiral arms, where the velocity gradient is smaller than at the shock fronts, cold gas clumps and star formation is induced. These locations are predicted to contain the youngest stellar populations within the nuclear ring. The connection between core-collapse progenitors and the clumping of atomic gas by the motion of spiral arms has also been explored in the galaxy M74 [337]. We illustrate this mechanism in the left panel of Fig. 2.16.

Because the SN took place within the co-rotation radius for M100, the gas and dust at the radius of SN 2020oi is rotating more rapidly than the pattern speed of the spiral arms. If the SN 2020oi progenitor formed from the action of the spiral arms, we can obtain a rough estimate for its age from the time over which the newly-formed stellar cluster underwent roughly circular motion from within a spiral arm to its current location. We first use a PS1 *gri*-band composite pointing of M100 to estimate the coordinates of a point along the leading edge of each of the inner dust lanes, such that they are roughly the same distance from the nucleus as SN 2020oi (~ 4.5 arcsec). Assuming the cluster undergoes circular rotation, we evaluate the rotation curve for M100 from Knapen et al. [277] at $4.5''$ (using both the $H\alpha$ and CO-derived estimates) and determine the differential speed between the matter at this radius and the pattern speed of the spiral arms from Hernandez et al. [212]. We then calculate the length of the circular arc connecting SN 2020oi to each of the dust lanes, accounting for an extinction with respect to our line of sight of

$i = 30$ *Ph.D.* [277]. From these estimates, we derive an upper limit to the age of the progenitor cluster of $t_{\text{Age}} \approx 9 - 17$ Myr, if it formed from the passage of the nearest spiral arm; and $t_{\text{Age}} \approx 14 - 26$ Myr if it formed from the furthest arm. The second age range overlaps both with our earlier stellar cluster age estimate and with the age provided by Knapen et al. [278] (who estimates an age of ~ 15 Myr for the majority of stars in the star-forming region coincident with SN 2020oi). Although neither of these estimates alone is conclusive evidence for the age of the SN 2020oi progenitor (and earlier passes of the material through the spiral arms could have equally triggered star formation events), in conjunction with the cluster age estimates from *Prospector* they present a consistent picture for its formation.

Using population synthesis models, Allard et al. [11] finds that the spectral emission from the nuclear ring is equally well-explained by two models. In the first, an initial period of star formation ($t \sim 3$ Gyr ago) concludes and is followed only by the starburst event currently observed. In the second, the period of initial formation was followed by multiple continuous starburst events occurring every ~ 100 Myr and starting $t \sim 500$ Myr ago. Allard et al. [11] favors the latter hypothesis, which is consistent with a continuous inflow of gas under the gravitational pumping action of the central bar. While we are unable to distinguish between these two scenarios, our estimate of ~ 40 Myr for the age of the SN 2020oi cluster suggests that its formation corresponds to the most recent burst of star formation.

Metallicity and Star Formation at the Supernova Site

Because our IFU data span the inner region of M100, we can use traditional emission-line flux indicators to estimate the metallicity at the location of the SN. We employ the empirical relations derived by Marino et al. [332] to estimate the metallicity at the SN 2020oi spectral bin location based on the $(\text{O III } \lambda 5007/\text{H}\beta)/(\text{N II } \lambda 6583/\text{H}\alpha)$ and $(\text{N II } \lambda 6583)/(\text{H}\alpha)$ line ratios (the O3N2 and N2 indices, respectively), as is appropriate for low-redshift HII regions:

$$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.743 + 0.462 \times \log(\text{N2}) \quad (2.7)$$

$$12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.753 - 0.214 \times \log(\text{O3N2}) \quad (2.8)$$

Line fluxes have been measured on the spectrum obtained by the subtraction of the composite stellar population best-fit spectrum obtained from *STARLIGHT* with the observed spectrum (see Fig. 2.19). Using the N2 and O3N2 indices, we find a metallicity at the location of SN 2020oi of $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.50 \pm 0.01$ (± 0.18 sys), and $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.57 \pm 0.03$ (± 0.18 sys), respectively. Averaging these, we find $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.55 \pm 0.03$. Assuming a value for solar metallicity of $12 + \log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 8.69$

[23], the metallicity at the position of SN 2020oi is found to be slightly sub-solar. Another estimate for the metallicity comes from the final results of the STARLIGHT fits, where we have averaged the metallicities of each stellar base with its corresponding stellar mass weighted by the eigenvalues of the results obtained. From the analysis of the spectral bin corresponding to the location of SN 2020oi we find $\langle Z \rangle = 0.015$, where the Solar value is $Z_{\odot} = 0.02$. We conclude that the stellar metallicity inferred from the analysis of the stellar population underlying the SN is consistent with the metallicity obtained from the analysis of the nebular gas. Both values are also consistent with the average values for the gas-phase and stellar metallicities found from the analysis of a IFU-data sample of type-Ic SN host galaxies [169].

We have also estimated the star-formation rate at the location of SN 2020oi using the method delineated in Kennicutt [259], which is based on the luminosity of the extinction-corrected $H\alpha$ recombination line, $L_{H\alpha} = 6.9 \pm 1.4 \times 10^{37} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$: we obtain an effective star-formation rate of $\text{SFR} = 6.0 \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-3} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$. This value is lower than the average SFR value found in a systematic analysis of type-Ic SN local environments [170].

2.12 Deducing the Properties of the SN 2020oi Progenitor

The estimated mass ejected in the explosion has strong implications for its progenitor system. We evaluate these implications by comparing our results to events simulated using the binary and single-star models from v2.2 of the Binary Population And Spectral Synthesis (BPASS) code¹¹, which are described in detail in Eldridge et al. [129]. We constrain BPASS simulations to those consisting of a primary star with a CO-core mass greater than $1.38 M_{\odot}$ and a total mass greater than $1.5 M_{\odot}$ immediately pre-explosion, as progenitors less massive than this are unlikely to undergo core-collapse [129]; and to only those systems containing a primary star with a hydrogen mass of less than $10^{-3} M_{\odot}$ immediately prior to explosion (the threshold reported in BPASS as corresponding to a stripped-envelope event). The resulting models span stellar metallicities from $Z = 10^{-5}$ to $Z = 0.04$. We plot the ejected mass for a fiducial SN explosion energy of 10^{51} erg (roughly corresponding to the energy of SN 2020oi) against the progenitor mass of the system at the beginning of the simulation in Figure 2.20. We find the M_{ej} value estimated for SN 2020oi near the lowest end of estimates for a system of initial mass $M_{\text{ZAMS}} \approx 6.5 - 13.0 M_{\odot}$, which occurs only in the simulated binary progenitor systems. The mean and median of initial progenitor masses within this subset of models are both $9.5 M_{\odot}$. Adopting this value and calculating the standard deviation across all viable models, we obtain a most-likely progenitor mass of $M_{\text{ZAMS}} = 9.5 \pm 1.0 M_{\odot}$. This value is lower than the initial mass predicted by Rho et al. [409], who reports a value of $13 M_{\odot}$. As is also noted in Rho et al. [409] (see their Table 2), the most likely initial progenitor mass predicted for SN 1994I, whose bolometric properties are similar to those of SN 2020oi, is $13 - 15 M_{\odot}$ [234, 432]. Adopting our higher Arnett estimate of $M_{\text{ej}} = 1.00 M_{\odot}$ results in a higher progenitor mass of $M_{\text{ZAMS}} = 10 M_{\odot}$. This strongly

¹¹<https://bpass.auckland.ac.nz/>

suggests a low-mass binary progenitor origin for SN 2020oi.

Because we have derived a likelihood surface for the properties of our SN cluster from *HST* pre-explosion photometry in §2.10, we can combine our results with the derived properties of the explosion to extract a most likely age for the SN 2020oi progenitor.

From our likelihood surface, we first marginalize over the cluster metallicity and mass to obtain a probability density function for the age of the cluster. We then obtain a histogram of likely progenitor ages from BPASS by considering the ages of only the stellar models that result in a stripped-envelope explosion within the M_{ej} range predicted by the Khatami and Kasen fit to our bolometric light curve. As we note above, these models are all low-mass binary systems. We generate a kernel density estimate associated with this histogram, and then multiply our probability densities and normalize the result to obtain a combined probability density function for the age of the explosion. The resulting distribution is shown in Figure 2.21. The most likely age for the SN 2020oi progenitor is found by calculating the peak of the probability density function, and the uncertainty is reported by taking its standard deviation.

From these estimates, we calculate a final progenitor age of $t_{\text{Age}} = 27 \pm 7$ Myr. Although none of the previous SN 2020oi studies constrained the age of the progenitor, this estimate is in general agreement with simulations of stripped-envelope SNe from binary systems (a $3 M_{\odot}$ helium core pre-explosion is expected to be ~ 19 Myr old, compared to our $2.1 M_{\odot}$ density distribution; see [411]). Combined with the explosion parameters from previous sections and the derived progenitor mass of $M_{\text{ZAMS}} = 9.5 \pm 1.0 M_{\odot}$, our analysis strongly disfavors a single massive Wolf-Rayet as progenitor for the explosion [111, 118].

2.13 Conclusions

We have presented photometric and spectroscopic observations of the type-Ic SN 2020oi, which resides in the grand-design spiral galaxy M100. Our observations were obtained using Keck, SOAR, and other ground-based telescopes and span ~ 400 days of the event, allowing us to characterize the explosion in detail. Additional pre-explosion *HST* photometry and MUSE IFU spectroscopy has permitted a detailed investigation of the underlying stellar population at the location of the SN. Table 2.6 lists the properties of both the SN and its host environment derived in previous sections.

Table 2.6: Derived Properties of SN 2020oi.

System	Property	Units	Value
Explosion Site	Star-Formation Rate	$M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-2}$	$6.0 \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$
	Metallicity ($\langle Z_{*} \rangle$)	Z_{\odot}	~ 0.75
	Reddening ($E(B - V)$)	mag	0.133 ± 0.03
Cluster	Age (t_{Clust})	Myr	40^{+30}_{-20}
	Mass (M_{Clust})	M_{\odot}	$7.24^{+2.33}_{-4.33} \times 10^5$
	Metallicity (Z_{Clust})	Z_{\odot}	0.03 ± 0.02
SN	Time of Explosion (t_{exp})	MJD	58854.0 ± 0.3
	Decline Rate ($\Delta m_{15, \text{bol}}$)		1.63 ± 0.14
	Kinetic Energy (E_k)	10^{51} erg	0.79 ± 0.09
	Ejecta Mass (M_{ej})	M_{\odot}	0.81 ± 0.03
	^{56}Ni Mass ($M_{\text{Ni}56}$)	M_{\odot}	0.08 ± 0.02
Progenitor	ZAMS Mass (M_{ZAMS})	M_{\odot}	9.5 ± 1.0
	Pre-Explosion Mass (M_f)	M_{\odot}	~ 2.1
	Mass-Loss Rate (\dot{M})	$M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	$\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$
	Age (t_{Age})	Myr	27 ± 7

Below, we summarize the primary conclusions associated with our analysis:

1. Using the bolometric light curve code `Superbol` in tandem with a Gaussian Process routine to interpolate our photometric observations, we find SN 2020oi to be dimmer than the majority of SNe Ic and with a photometric evolution similar to that of the type-Ic SN 1994I. We calculate a luminosity decline rate of $\Delta m_{15, \text{bol}} \approx 1.6$, higher than all stripped-envelope SNe analyzed in both Lyman et al. [313] and Taddia et al. [480].
2. We separately model the bolometric luminosity of the event in the photospheric phase using the modified one-component Arnett model described in Valenti et al. [492] and following the Khatami et al. [266] treatment for stripped-envelope SNe. We further use the `MOSFiT` code [198] to model the photoemetry of the event in each observed band. Adopting the results from Khatami et al. [266], we find a mass of synthesized nickel of $M_{\text{Ni}56} = 0.08 \pm 0.02 M_{\odot}$ and a total ejecta mass of $M_{\text{ej}} = 0.81 \pm 0.03 M_{\odot}$. These values fall at the lowest end of the range reported by Taddia et al. [480] for SNe Ic, a result consistent with the faint bolometric light curve and the rapid decline of the explosion. We derive an explosion time of MJD 58854.0 ± 0.3 using a fireball rise model applied to the first 10 days of photometry.

3. Detailed 1D spectral modeling using the radiative transfer code TARDIS reveals a composition near peak in strong agreement with the CO21 model developed to explain the spectral sequence of SN 1994I. We find evidence of Ca II, Mg II, Fe II, Si II, and O II features and a best-fit composition that remains roughly consistent across the epochs simulated, indicating at least partial ejecta mixing.
4. The earliest spectrum obtained ($\delta t = 3.3\text{d}$) features an enhanced blue continuum that cannot be explained by the SN 1994I CO21 composition model. Further, we find evidence of Fe II $\lambda 4500$ but not O I $\lambda 7773$, indicating that this material is associated with the outermost layers of the ejecta but contains higher-mass elements typically observed at later epochs. We have obtained reasonable fits to this spectrum by considering an additional high-velocity ($< -23000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) gas component ($0.1 M_{\odot}$) to the emission, with a distinct composition to the primary ejecta that includes carbon and potentially helium.
5. The optical and UV photometry near $\delta t \approx 2.5$ days reveals emission in excess of the expanding-fireball model. This excess is present in data obtained with Las Cumbres Observatory and with *Swift*. We have considered several physical scenarios to explain this emission, including shock-cooling, binary interaction, CSM interaction, and an asymmetric distribution of nickel synthesized from the explosion. We slightly favor the interpretation of ejecta interaction with CSM material, potentially from wave-driven mass-loss or mass transfer onto the companion at the time of the explosion. Nevertheless, until a more complete picture of the diversity of possible signatures from each of these phenomena is known, we cannot rule out alternative interaction mechanisms. The flux excess could also potentially be explained by properties intrinsic to the type-Ic explosion; early observations of a statistical sample of events are needed to investigate this possibility.
6. We have identified a marginally-extended source, likely a stellar cluster, coincident with the explosion in *HST* pre-explosion imaging. By combining stellar evolution models from BPASS with modeling of the cluster photometry in *Prospector*, we derive an age for the SN 2020oi progenitor of $27 \pm 7 \text{ Myr}$. This age is consistent with values predicted from previous starburst evolution models [278, 11], and with the conceptual picture of the progenitor forming from dynamical interaction of the innermost spiral arms with cold gas in M100's nuclear ring. This is the sole SN of seven discovered in M100 whose location has allowed us to validate the mechanism underlying star formation in the nuclear ring.
7. Our age constraints, coupled with an initial mass of $M_{\text{ZAMS}} \approx 9.5 M_{\odot}$ predicted from BPASS models and a pre-explosion mass of $M_f \approx 2.1 M_{\odot}$ estimated from spectral modeling in TARDIS, present a consistent picture of a low-mass binary progenitor system for SN 2020oi. An explanation for the optical/UV excess and early spectrum of the explosion must be consistent with a binary progenitor system.

The results of this study highlight the value of early-time observations in constraining the nature of SN progenitors. From its initial discovery, SN 2020oi was closely monitored by the Young Supernovae Exper-

iment [YSE; 246], which surveys 1,512 deg² of sky in *griz* bands using the Pan-STARRS telescopes to a median 5- σ depth of 21.5 mag. Although surveys such as the Vera Rubin Observatory’s Legacy Survey for Space and Time [LSST; 233] will vastly expand our discovery rate of stripped-envelope SNe, high-cadence photometry and spectroscopy from additional surveys such as YSE will be critical for distinguishing between progenitor models and expanding our sample of observed short-duration phenomena [as in the case of the type-Ia SN 2018oh, observed by *TESS*; 121].

SN 2020oi’s relatively late excess (relative to the time of explosion), coupled with the tentative finding of a non-negligible helium abundance (corroborated by the listing of SN 2020oi as a transitional object between SNe Ib and SNe Ic in Fig. 16 of [409]), make it a particularly useful addition to our sample of observed SNe Ic. The object is only the fourth spectroscopically-standard SN Ic with excess flux detected pre-maximum, and the dearth of sufficient analogues for comparison challenges our ability to conclusively characterize this emission.

In a volume-limited sample, SNe Ic comprise $\sim 7\%$ of all CCSNe [444]. To resolve early excesses among these rare phenomena and clarify its connection to pre-explosion stripping, young SNe in the local Universe need to be classified in real-time and scheduled for high-cadence follow-up. We consider the value of global host-galaxy photometry in facilitating this early classification in the following chapter.

Figure 2.3: The full sequence of optical spectra obtained for SN 2020oi. Spectrographs used for observations are listed at right, along with the phase of the spectra relative to the time of explosion. Prominent absorption lines are listed in red and the spectrum taken within one day of the early-time photometric excess is highlighted in blue at top.

Figure 2.4: The bolometric light curve for SN 2020oi (blue), plotted alongside the type-Ic/Ic-BL SN samples from Lyman et al. [313] and Taddia et al. [480]. Light curves have been aligned at peak and the shaded regions correspond to 1- σ confidence intervals for the SNe in Lyman et al. [313], which incorporate only uncertainty in the bolometric corrections for each event. Uncertainties in distance modulus and extinction along each line of sight are not shown and may affect this comparison. For clarity, we plot only SNe with pre-maximum observations. The rise and decline rate of SN 2020oi is similar to that of the characteristic type-Ic event SN 1994I (shown in violet), which is identified as a rapidly declining event in Lyman et al. [313]. SN 2020oi appears more luminous than SN 1994I, but unaccounted-for extinction toward SN 1994I may also account for this difference [410]. The bolometric contribution from the SN 2020oi early-time bump can be seen in the first day of observations.

Figure 2.5: Light curve absolute magnitude at peak (M_{peak}) and linear decline rates ($\Delta m_{15,bol}$) for stripped-envelope SNe from Lyman et al. [313]. The location of SN 200oi is denoted by a star at right. Error in the value of $\Delta m_{15,bol}$ is propagated from photometric uncertainties, and error in M_{peak} combines uncertainty in event photometry, distance, and extinction. The decline rate for SN 200oi from peak to 15 days following is ~ 1 mag higher than the median for type-Ic events shown and ~ 0.3 mag higher than the decline rate of the next-closest type-Ic event, SN 1994I [although the decline of SN 1994I may have been higher than is shown here due to uncertainty in extinction estimates in the direction of the SN; see 410]. Figure adapted from Lyman et al. [313].

Figure 2.6: Temperature and radius estimates of the SN photosphere from black-body fits to the photometry at each interpolated epoch in green. Spectra-derived black-body values for SN 2020oi are shown in violet. The spectra-derived photospheric properties of the type-Ic SN 1994I [432] are shown as blue points. The photospheric properties of the best-fit MOSFiT model (described in §2.5) are given in black. Shaded regions denote 1- σ confidence intervals. The difference between spectroscopic and photometric estimates of these properties are not physical, but instead reflect the approximate nature of each indicator.

Figure 2.7: The total ejecta masses and explosion energies for the stripped-envelope SNe in Lyman et al. [313] and Taddia et al. [480] derived using a semi-analytic Arnett model [21]. The star denotes the parameter values derived for SN 2020oi in this study using an Arnett model, whereas the diamond denotes the values adopted from the Khatami et al. [266] prescription (see text for details). The location of SN 1994I is labeled bottom left. SN 2020oi was more energetic than the well-studied SN 1994I but the two explosions ejected similar masses of material.

Figure 2.8: Best-fit bolometric light curve models for the photospheric phase of SN 2020oi. The Arnett model calculated in §2.5 is shown as a blue dashed line, and the black shaded region describes the fit determined using the code MOSFiT (§2.5). The derived bolometric light curve for SN 2020oi is shown in green. Derived parameters are presented in Table 2.3. The bolometric luminosity of the explosion is not well-described by either model 30 days after explosion due to the rapidly decreasing opacity of the ejecta.

Figure 2.9: Corner plot of the model parameters for the SN 2020oi explosion found using the nested-sampler implementation in MOSFiT. Marginal distributions from the nested chains are shown at top along with the median parameter values and their $1\text{-}\sigma$ uncertainties. The parameter t_{exp} indicates the date of explosion relative to the first ZTF observation at MJD 58855.54.

Figure 2.10: The spectra observed at $\delta t \approx 11, 15, 17,$ and 18 days from explosion (black), along with the corresponding best-fit models (green). The spectra of SN 1994I are shown in violet for comparison. Mutual features associated with the presence of Ca, Mg, Fe, Si, and C are shown. The similarity between spectral sequences suggests similar ejecta composition and photospheric evolution for the two SNe.

Figure 2.11: The best-fit ejecta composition for the four epochs corresponding to the modeled peak spectra. The epochs relative to the explosion date are listed at top, and the velocity values adopted for each epoch are shown at bottom. The best-fit composition for the SN 1994I ejecta at similar epochs [432] is also shown. Although the composition of the SN 2020oi ejecta varies between epochs, the comparable abundances of O and Ne across the 8-day evolution indicates partial ejecta mixing.

Figure 2.12: The early-time spectrum for SN 2020oi (violet) compared to three composition models: One in which a best-fit composition distinct from the CO21 model was used (black, dashed); one in which additional mass was added at the highest velocities with composition matching that of CO21 model (green); and one in which high-velocity mass was added with a composition distinct from CO21 (red). The model with a distinct composition (Table 2.4) of additional mass at high velocities provides the best fit to the day 3 spectrum.

Figure 2.13: The early-time normalized flux of SN 2020oi. The dashed line corresponds to a canonical expanding-fireball model $f \propto (t - t_{\text{exp}})^2$ applied to days 3 – 10 of the photometry in each band, while the dotted line describes a model with $f \propto (t - t_{\text{exp}})^{1.7}$ to more accurately capture the photometry in *gri* bands following 7 days. Flux in excess of that predicted by both models can be seen at $\delta t \approx 2.5$ days from explosion for the majority of bands.

Figure 2.14: The best-fit shock-cooling models for SN 2020oi excluding the first ZTF observation in r band, shown along with the optical and UV photometry corresponding to the first five days of explosion. Four analytic fits were considered to characterize the early-time observations: Piro [384]; Piro et al. [385]; and Sapir et al. [431] using polytropic indices of $n = 3/2$ and $n = 3$.

Figure 2.15: Diagram illustrating flux excess from ejecta interaction with asymmetric CSM. In this scenario, the SN ejecta collide with an asymmetric cloud and the thermal emission of the material as it cools is observed at distinct epochs (t_1 and t_2 corresponding to the epoch of the first ZTF point and the epoch of the photometric bump, respectively) based on its optical depth. From simulations of similar binary systems, the minimum semi-major axis of the cloud predicted is $\geq 10^{14}$ cm, which would agree with the presence of material as is inferred in §2.8.

Figure 2.16: **Left:** Schematic diagram illustrating the proposed star formation mechanism associated with M100’s nuclear ring. Cold gas flows inward along the spiral arms (turquoise channels) and collects between the Outer Inner and Inner Inner Lindblad resonances (OILR and IILR, indicated as red circles at ~ 1 kpc and ~ 0.7 kpc, respectively), and then sinks toward the nucleus from gravity. This material then sweeps past the spiral arm shock fronts in its rotation and collapses, forming new stars. Two possible paths for the SN 2020oi progenitor from formation to explosion are shown in violet and used to provide an independent estimate for the age of the system (see §2.11). **Right:** Corner plot corresponding to our best-fit parameters for the *HST* pre-explosion photometry of the stellar cluster associated with SN 2020oi. Emcee results are shown in black contours and posterior probabilities derived from a manual grid search is shown in color (where yellow corresponds to the highest-probability parameters and blue corresponds to the lowest). Marginal histograms are plotted at top, with median posterior values marked by light blue lines and first and third quartiles marked by red lines.

Figure 2.17: *Hubble Space Telescope* images of the host galaxy of SN 2020oi. The left image corresponds to a Wide-Field Camera observation in the F814W filter, which covers almost the entire galaxy, while the right panel shows the inner region of M100 as observed by the Advanced Camera for Surveys (ACS) in the F555W filter. The position of SN 2020oi is shown as a red circle. On the WFC image, the corresponding field of view of the ACS, as well as the region covered by MUSE observations, are over-plotted with cyan and red squares, respectively.

Figure 2.18: Light fraction contributions for three populations of stars within the nucleus of M100 as derived from MUSE spectroscopy. The location of SN 2020oi is marked with a circle in the upper left corner of each map.

Figure 2.19: The spectrum at the bin of SN 2020oi as observed by MUSE (in violet). The composite stellar population spectrum obtained from STARLIGHT is shown in green. Emission-line fluxes have been measured from the residual spectrum, calculated by subtracting the synthetic spectrum by the observed spectrum. Host-galaxy extinction has been calculated internally from emission-line fluxes.

Figure 2.20: **Left:** The Zero-Age Main Sequence (ZAMS) mass of the progenitor star M_{ZAMS} versus the ejecta mass M_{ej} following explosion for single (green) and binary (violet) progenitor systems in BPASS. The blue shaded region captures the models in BPASS with predicted M_{ej} values within the range estimated for SN 2020oi. These models are weighted by the initial mass function with properties determined by Moe et al. [348] to reproduce observed binary populations. **Right Upper Panel:** The distribution of M_{ZAMS} values for the models within the blue shaded region at left. Considering only these models, the most likely mass for the SN progenitor is $9.5 M_{\odot}$. **Right Lower Panel:** The range of M_{ej} values for the same set of models as above.

Figure 2.21: The probability density functions (PDFs) associated with the age of the SN 2020oi progenitor. The estimates derived from pre-explosion cluster photometry are given in green, and those derived from comparing explosion parameters to stellar evolution models are given in violet. The normalized probability density found by combining these two estimates are given as the black PDF at center, and the age with highest posterior probability is reported at right along with the standard deviation of the combined PDF.

Chapter 3

Galaxies Hosting Supernovae and Other Transients (GHOST)

This chapter is based on: Gagliano, Narayan, Engel, & Carrasco Kind, 2021, *ApJ*, 908, 2.

3.1 Introduction

Finding and studying nearby stripped-envelope systems such as SN 2020oi in the present day presents unique challenges. As SN discovery rates swell beyond our ability to spectroscopically characterize them, photometric SN classification algorithms have arrived on the scene en masse. These classifiers employ template fitting methods on real or simulated light curves (e.g. [389, 248]), novel machine learning algorithms ([231, 274, 355, 349]), or a combination of the two [304]. Community-wide challenges have also drawn upon expertise from outside of the astronomical community, starting with the Supernova Photometric Classification Challenge (SNPhotCC; [264]) in preparation for the Dark Energy Survey (DES) and closely followed by the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge (PLAsTiCC; [263]) in preparation for The Vera C. Rubin Observatory (Rubin). Despite the accuracy of these previously developed methods, many classifiers are validated on simulated or archival photometry spanning the full phase of each event; during Rubin operations, however, massive data volumes demand us to operate algorithms in real time and on incomplete light curves.

To enable classification when explosion photometry is incomplete or unreliable, we now explore the use of host galaxy information in classifying supernovae when photometry from the explosion is incomplete or unreliable. We extend the work done by [142] by constructing a database of host galaxy-supernova pairs greater than an order of magnitude larger than the Lick Observatory Supernova Search (LOSS; [299]) sample they use. We also consider > 140 additional host galaxy features. In addition to our data products, we have developed a new method for identifying transient host galaxies in deep surveys using postage stamps of the field. This method achieves accuracies superior to the commonly used directional light radius method

at low- z , and with greater completeness at high- z where little morphological information is available.

We provide a schematic overview of our analysis framework in Figure 3.1. In §3.2, we describe our methodology for constructing and validating our database of supernovae and their host galaxies. In §3.3 we outline the data and accompanying software products. These products can be used to query the released database and identify the host galaxies of new transients. We compare PS1-derived brightness and morphology features of host galaxies using Principal Component Analysis in §3.4. We then compare the host galaxies of underrepresented supernova classes using t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (tSNE) in §3.4. Next, we introduce our algorithm to classify supernovae and present results in §3.5. Section §3.6 is devoted to the analysis of supernovae originating in the same host galaxy. We conclude by summarizing our results in §3.7.

3.2 Host Galaxy Identification

To construct a dataset of supernova host galaxies, we first assemble a dataset of spectroscopic supernovae. We have downloaded all spectroscopically classified supernovae from the Transient Name Server (TNS; <https://wis-tns.weizmann.ac.il/>) and the Open Supernova Catalog (OSC; <https://sne.space/>). After removing events with identical names and positions, we are left with 20,736 events. We then implement a series of quality cuts and a novel matching algorithm to identify the host galaxies of supernovae in our sample. Our final database contains host galaxy information for 16,175 supernovae – just over 78% of all spectroscopically classified events at the time of writing. We outline our methodology for matching supernovae with their host galaxies below.

PS1 Querying for Host Candidates

We use the first data release of Pan-STARRS (PS1; [84]) to search for candidate host galaxies due to its survey depth ($5\sigma < 23.3$ in g -band) and extensive list of sources ($>3\text{B}$ unique objects). We have chosen Pan-STARRS data over SDSS for its superior sky coverage and comparable depth (SDSS has a median 5σ depth of 23.13 in g), and over alternative sky surveys for its resolution ($0.25^\circ/\text{px}$, two orders of magnitude higher than the $21^\circ/\text{px}$ resolution of the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite). We opt for the first data release to take advantage of the *bestDetection* flag, which was corrupted in DR2.

To first order, a host galaxy can be found by cross-matching the redshift of the event with the redshifts of nearby sources; however, the majority of supernovae discovered prior to 2010 do not list a spectroscopic redshift in TNS, and the NASA Extragalactic Database (NED¹) is only 75% complete for redshifts of galaxies at $z \leq 0.05$. The catalog is even less complete at higher redshifts [287]. For these reasons, supernovae and their host galaxies cannot be associated by redshift alone. Instead, we construct a table of potential host

¹<https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/>

Figure 3.1: An outline of the analysis completed, with corresponding sections labeled. The primary data sources for our supernova sample are given at the top of the flowchart, and major steps within our pipeline are indicated with text.

galaxies for each transient event using the following procedure:

1. Query Pan-STARRS for all catalogued objects within 30° of the supernova. If a host galaxy has been reported in TNS or OSC, we instead take its coordinates as the center of our cone search. The resultant table is likely to contain artifacts and other objects that are irrelevant to this analysis, such as HII regions.
2. Use the PS1 *primaryDetection* = 1 flag to remove duplicate detections of the same source. This is common in fields containing a single large galaxy with a spatially resolved core or many associated HII regions. We identified multiple faint galaxies without a *primaryDetection* = 1 entry at this stage, and so we caution that this cut may preferentially associate supernovae with nearby large galaxies.
3. Remove any object not detected in *gri*. We have found that the number of artifacts in our candidate host galaxy list increases dramatically without this cut, but we do not cut on *z* or *y* bands so that we retain high-*z* host galaxies in our sample.
4. Remove sources with *bestDetection* = 0 if at least one source with *bestDetection* = 1 is present in the field. If no best detection sources exist, do not eliminate any potential host galaxies for that supernova. We had initially removed all sources with *bestDetection* = 0, but found that this removed a non-negligible fraction of plausible host galaxies.
5. Remove sources with *qualityFlag* = 128 (indicating a poor-quality stack object).

We list the fraction of supernovae removed at each of these steps in Table 3.1. After removing the majority of artifacts from our table, we eliminate the PS1 sources corresponding to stars.

Star/Galaxy Separation for Deep Surveys

A useful feature for distinguishing point-like and extended sources is brightness measured in different apertures [450]. The total flux of an unresolved source can be captured equally well by a point-spread function (PSF) model or by a more complicated aperture model such as Kron, which defines the radius of its aperture as $2.5\times$ the first radial moment of a source [320]. To first order, stars can be separated from galaxies with a horizontal cut in $m_{\text{PSF}} - m_{\text{Kron}}$ space (See section 6.3 of [84]), where stars will cluster around $m_{\text{PSF}} - m_{\text{Kron}} = 0$. This cut introduces a bias against distant high-redshift galaxies, which are well-mixed with stars in this space faintward of $m_{\text{PSF}} \sim 21$. Further, stars brighter than $m_{\text{PSF}} \sim 15$ will shift above this line because of saturation, and a horizontal cut will not capture these bright sources.

To more accurately distinguish stars from potential host galaxies, we query the PS1-Source Types and Redshifts with Machine learning (PS1-STRM) catalog from Beck et al. [36] for every source within our candidate list. The PS1-STRM catalog uses a neural network to label sources as stars, galaxies, and QSOs.

Figure 3.2: **Left.** Postage stamps for a few RF-identified stars in our dataset using a decision threshold of 50% (above) and 80% (below). Although the 50% model achieves high accuracies across the full dataset, it is more likely to erroneously identify bright galactic nuclei as stars. By increasing the decision threshold to 80%, the RF model becomes less likely to flag these sources. **Right.** The precision-recall curves for our RF model. The points top right indicate our final decision threshold. The green (purple) line corresponds to the full (masked) sample, where the masked sample contains only sources with low photometric uncertainty ($MagErr < 0.02$) and greater than 3 detections in *griz*. With a star/galaxy decision threshold of 80%, we achieve a recall and precision of 92% for the full sample and 95% and 96%, respectively, for the masked sample. The inset confusion matrix presents our final classification results on the full sample. Because we have biased our algorithm against removing potential hosts, we achieve a 2% false negative rate for our galaxy classification with negligible impact on the mean accuracy, precision, and recall of the model.

Out of $\sim 49,500$ unique sources, nearly 48,000 belong to one of these categories, whereas the remaining 1,500 are listed as ‘unknown’. To classify this remaining subset, and to avoid querying this database each time our pipeline is run, we implement a Random Forest (RF; [53]) algorithm to separate stars from galaxies and QSOs using features of PS1-STRM-classified sources. A Random Forest is a supervised learning algorithm composed of an ensemble of decision trees. In the classification problem, a random subset of input features is used to construct each decision tree and predict the class of a sample. Once the trees are constructed, the algorithm assigns a final class with a majority vote of the output from each tree. We use the random forest implementation in `sklearn`. For our final model, we require at least 8 observations to split a branch, two features per split, and a minimum of two observations per leaf (the end of each tree). We train our RF model on the aperture magnitude (m_{Ap}) of our potential host galaxies in g , r , and i ; $m_{Ap} - m_{Kron}$ in the same bands; and the 4-dimensional color distance in $g - r$, $r - i$, $i - z$, and $z - y$ from the PS1 stellar locus, the path traced by stars in color-color space. Because of its generality, the stellar locus is a valuable tool for photometric calibration of large surveys [213]. We can also use it to help distinguish stars and galaxies, since stars within our sample should closely trace the locus whereas galaxies will not. Aperture magnitude is determined by integrating over the analytic PSF aperture, then extrapolating the PSF model to estimate the flux that was missed. We have chosen this measurement in place of m_{PSF} because it ac-

Figure 3.3: The residuals in $g - r$ and $i - z$ colors calculated between the PS1 stellar locus and identified stars within our candidate host galaxy table. Colors have been corrected for extinction using the reddening values and extinction coefficients from Schlafly et al. [436].

counts for local variations in the PSF, and as a result its values have less dispersion (see Fig. 3.3). We adopt a cubic spline with knots given by Tonry et al. [487] and an $r - i$ bin width of 0.001 as our PS1 stellar locus. To calculate the 4-dimensional distance of each source from this locus, we use the equation [108]:

$$4DCD = \min_k \sum_{i=0}^4 \frac{(C_i - t_{i,k})^2}{\sigma_i^2} \quad (3.1)$$

where C_i represents the i th color of a source, $t_{i,k}$ represents each value along the stellar locus for that color, and σ_i represents the PS1 uncertainty in the source's color (calculated by combining the magnitude uncertainties in quadrature). The $4DCD$ is the minimum value of this equation calculated between all k points along the stellar locus. This value approaches the orthogonal distance between a source and the stellar locus in 4D space as the number of discretized locus points approaches infinity.

We considered the use of Gaia DR2 parallaxes as an additional feature within our RF model, as it would allow us to distinguish between galactic stars and distant galaxies; however, the depth of the survey (with a limiting magnitude of $G = 21$) limits its completeness for a significant number of our sources. Further, the parallaxes reported in DR2 have significant uncertainties, and training our RF to identify stars by their large parallaxes would remove a non-negligible fraction of galaxies from our sample as well.

To quantify the performance of our star-galaxy separator, we divide our STRM-classified data into 70% training and 30% testing sets, respectively. Next, we re-balance the training set using the Python package `Imbalanced-learn`. This prevents our algorithm from improving accuracy by classifying every source as the most populous class in the training data. Our training set consists of 12,560 stars and 12,560 galaxies/QSOs after re-balancing, and our testing set consists of 5,345 stars and 6,351 galaxies/QSOs. This brings our train and test fractions to 68.2% and 31.8%, respectively.

We now consider the accuracy, precision, and recall of our model. The accuracy describes the total

fraction of the test sample that is correctly labeled, and for a given class the precision is defined as

$$p = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3.2)$$

where the true positive rate TP describes the number of objects correctly identified in this class and the false positive rate FP describes the number of objects incorrectly labeled as members of this class. Recall is defined as

$$r = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3.3)$$

where the false negative rate FN denotes the number of objects incorrectly labeled as *not* belonging to this class.

Our model achieves a mean precision, mean recall, and mean accuracy of 93% each distinguishing stars and galaxies/QSOs from this test set. We also create an “ideal” sample of stars and galaxies by removing from our dataset any sources with missing brightness information, $ApMagErr > 0.02$, $ApMag > 20$, or fewer than 3 detections in *griz*. For the STRM-classified stars, we also remove sources with $psfQfPerfect < 0.9$, which would indicate that a non-negligible fraction of pixels were masked in the stack detection of this source. After splitting into training and testing samples and re-balancing the training set as before, this curated sample consists of 2,569 galaxies/QSOs and 2,569 stars in the training set, and 2,559 galaxies/QSOs and 1,101 stars in the testing set. Using the same model as before, our mean precision, mean recall, and mean accuracy each increase to 96%.

While this model achieves high accuracies on both our full and curated samples, the precision and recall of stars and galaxies should not be weighted equally. Retaining host galaxy candidates is significantly more important than removing all stars, since remaining stars may be removed by later cuts but it is highly unlikely that a galaxy will be added back to the data once it is removed. For this reason, we only remove sources that are classified as stars to $>80\%$ probability by our RF model (instead of the fiducial 50% cut). With this threshold, our mean accuracy on the full dataset decreases to 92% (a decrease of 2%), but our precision for stars rises to 98% and our recall for galaxies reaches 99%. Our mean precision on the curated sample is now 95% (a decrease of 1%) but our mean precision is unchanged. By minimizing the number of galaxies misidentified as stars, we achieve a classifier that is both accurate and conservative. We show the precision-recall curve for our classifier in Fig. 3.2, along with the final confusion matrix after increasing our decision threshold.

We then remove the STRM-identified stars and the RF-predicted stars from our table of potential host galaxies. Galaxies with the smallest separation from the stellar locus and the stars with the largest locus separation were inspected using PS1 postage stamps, but no manual re-association was done at this stage. The RF-identified galaxies with smallest separation to the locus were nearly point sources, but were kept in the dataset due to the likelihood that they were QSOs.

The Directional Light Radius for Host Galaxy Association

Supernovae are often associated with a host galaxy using the directional light radius (DLR) prescription outlined in Gupta et al. [199], where the angular separation θ is scaled by the radius of the host galaxy in the direction of the event d_{DLR} . A supernova embedded in a large galaxy is more likely to be found further from its host galaxy's nucleus than a small galaxy, and this normalized distance permits a direct comparison of supernova separations between host galaxies with vastly different scales. Normalized separation metrics have already been adopted by the Supernova Legacy Survey (SNLS; [475]) and the SDSS-II Supernova Survey (SDSS-SNS; [426]). As the rate of supernova detections continues to increase, the success of the DLR method at low- z and in crowded fields has made it the preferred method for automated host galaxy association (see [199] for a detailed review).

The DLR method proceeds as follows. For a supernova located at (x_{SN}, y_{SN}) and a potential host galaxy located at (x_{Gal}, y_{Gal}) , the Stokes parameters U and Q of the galaxy are given by its flux-weighted second order moments in PS1:

$$U = M_{XY}; \quad Q = M_{XX} - M_{YY} \quad (3.4)$$

The angular tilt ϕ of the galaxy relative to celestial north is then found with

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1}(U/Q) \quad (3.5)$$

Next, we calculate the aspect ratio of the host galaxy with

$$r_{a/b} = \frac{(1 + \kappa + 2\sqrt{\kappa})}{1 - \kappa} \quad (3.6)$$

where κ is derived from the two Stokes parameters:

$$\kappa = Q^2 + U^2 \quad (3.7)$$

The angle γ , describing the angle of the supernova position relative to the galactic center and celestial north, is then found with

$$\gamma = \tan^{-1} \frac{y_{SN} - y_{Gal}}{x_{SN} - x_{Gal}} \quad (3.8)$$

Finally, we arrive at the angle β subtended by the galactic semi-major axis and the vector connecting the supernova to the galactic center:

$$\beta = \phi - \gamma$$

The DLR is found with these parameters and the galaxy’s semi-major axis r_a using the equation

$$d_{DLR} = \frac{r_a}{\sqrt{(r_a/b \sin \beta)^2 + (\cos \beta)^2}} \quad (3.9)$$

The scaled directional light radius is found by θ/d_{DLR} , where θ is the Great Circle distance of a supernova from the center of its host galaxy in arcseconds. An illustration of this method is given in Figure 3.4.

The DLR method uses second-order moments for estimating U and Q , which are model independent; however, estimating the host galaxy’s semi-major axis r_a may require us to adopt a light profile model. We have selected the Kron radius, defined as $2.5 \times$ the first radial moment of a candidate host galaxy’s surface brightness profile, in the band which has the highest SNR, as our value for r_a to minimize this dependence. The mean r -band Kron radius for all potential host galaxies at this stage is 7.5° .

Gupta [200] estimates that 7% of matches in his sample found using this method are erroneous, with an additional 3% of SNe left unassociated due to unreported second order moments. Using a naive DLR association, we find our fraction to be significantly higher. This is due to a combination of non-galaxy sources in our database and multiple PS1 entries for a single source, both of which were only partially removed in previous steps. To mitigate this issue, we have modified the DLR method outlined above. For each supernova in our sample, we complete the following steps:

1. Find the Kron radius of each potential host galaxy in the band with highest SNR. Then, calculate d_{DLR} . If either the Kron radius or the second-order moments are not provided, remove this source from the list of potential host galaxies. Repeat for all potential host galaxies.
2. Eliminate host galaxies with $\theta/d_{DLR} > 5$. If no host galaxies remain after this step, the supernova is reported to be hostless and added to the sample of hostless events.
3. Rank-order the host galaxies by ascending values of θ/d_{DLR} .
4. If the remaining list contains at least one NED-identified galaxy, select the galaxy with the lowest θ/d_{DLR} as host. If not, select the source with the lowest θ/d_{DLR} .

Limitations in the DLR Methodology Applied to PS1 Data

The depth of PS1 has allowed us to construct a complete list of supernova host galaxies, but several issues can arise in a survey as complete as PS1. First, de-blending errors plague many of the low- z host galaxies in our sample. These galaxies are often characterized by several overlapping PS1 “sources”, and neither the *primaryDetection* nor the *bestDetection* flags are able to unambiguously identify the PS1 entry closest to the true galaxy center.

Second, deep PS1 imaging is able to resolve dim host galaxy features that would be missed in other surveys. This introduces additional “sources” to the list of candidate host galaxies for a supernova, further

crowding low-redshift fields. Because of the de-blending errors associated with highly extended sources, we also find non-physical Kron radius measurements for the majority of these sources. We often find a PS1 source near the true galactic center with an uncharacteristically low Kron radius, if one is reported at all. Conversely, sub-structures such as HII regions and bright stars may “adopt” the light profile of an entire galaxy and report uncharacteristically high Kron radius values. These issues bias the DLR algorithm *away* from large host galaxies where visual association would be trivial.

Third, high-redshift host galaxies can easily be mistaken for imaging artifacts, and are preferentially removed by the *bestDetection* flag. The Kron radius for these objects is often (understandably) not reported. This leads to an overabundance of unassociated supernovae in sparse fields.

We have attempted to develop a pipeline that is fault-tolerant to these limitations in PS1 data, but accurate radius estimates are critical to the success of the DLR method in crowded fields. Gupta [200] uses an upper limit of $\theta/d_{DLR} = 4$ as a balance between sample purity and efficiency. We have extended this value to 5 to account for the low Kron radius estimates associated with low-redshift host galaxies; we note that a similar threshold is used for associating host galaxies in SNLS [475].

By visually inspecting a subset of associated host galaxies, we predict our overall misassociation rate with the full pipeline to be $\sim 5\%$; however, for low-redshift objects this rate can be as high as 30% for the reasons given above. When DLR fails to find the true host galaxy, a supernova is often matched to an HII region or bright star. To maintain the accuracy of our associations at low redshift, we have developed a novel host galaxy association algorithm using the light profiles of sources near the supernova of interest. We provide a detailed description of this method below.

Host Galaxy Association using Background Image Gradients

While deep imaging of extended host galaxies in PS1 makes source de-blending difficult, it makes visual association of SN host galaxies easier. We can rapidly identify a host galaxy by eye by first determining if the supernova is embedded within a galaxy’s light profile and, if so, by tracing this profile from the location of the supernova to the host galaxy’s center.

We have automated this process with a gradient ascent method able to accurately locate the center of the host galaxy in which a cataclysmic event is embedded. We release this code with the rest of the GHOST software.

For each transient, we have downloaded an 800x800 pixel ($200^\circ \times 200^\circ$) postage stamp of the field in *gri*. We have also downloaded the corresponding PS1 image stack masks and number counts. We use the stack masks to remove saturated pixels, and the counts mask to remove pixels created from fewer than two stack images. To remove stars that have not saturated the detector and any remaining starlight from those that have, we use the `DAOStarFinder` routine within the `photutils` package. We identify and remove sources matching a gaussian light profile with $\text{FWHM} \sim 3$ at a threshold of 20 standard deviations above the median pixel intensity. We have intentionally set our threshold high to prevent us from masking AGN at

Figure 3.4: The PS1 postage stamp for SN 2014dp, with host galaxy candidates circled. We show the radius of each candidate in the direction of the transient, calculated using the Kron radius of the host galaxy and the DLR method in §3.2. Despite the center of the true host galaxy lying further from the transient event than other spurious candidates, the true host galaxy (magenta) is correctly identified using our modified DLR method. The match is verified using redshift information from NED.

the centers of galaxies, as these provide meaningful gradient information. We then remove each identified star using a circular mask with a 5 pixel radius.

Once we have removed stars from the field, we use `Scipy` to construct a two-dimensional cubic spline interpolation over the pixels that were previously masked. We apply zero-points to these *gri* images, average them together in magnitude space, and convert back to flux to generate a PS1-averaged image *A*. Next, we use the `Background2D` function within `photutils` to create an image dominated by the light profiles of galaxies within the field. This function is typically used to estimate spatially-varying background noise from a crowded field and study smaller sources in detail. Because a galaxy halo can be conceptualized as background noise to the structure within the halo, we can use this same function to create a version of image *A* dominated by the light profiles of galaxies in the field and with minimal remaining effects from dust and HII regions. This smoothed image, which we call *B*, forms the basis for our gradient ascent method.

To estimate the sky background, `Background2D` divides a pointing into evenly sized smaller regions,

Figure 3.5: **a.** The gradient ascent algorithm applied to SN2017erp. The red circles correspond to the positions of PS1 sources eliminated before the DLR calculation, while the blue circles (scaled by d_{DLR}) denote potential host galaxies at the DLR stage. The dark magenta dashed circle denotes the DLR-selected host galaxy, while the smaller dashed gold circle at center denotes the PS1 source selected by gradient ascent. The position of the supernova is given by the yellow star. Despite numerous spurious detections in the field, the gradient ascent algorithm is able to rapidly identify the true host galaxy, which was later verified by redshift. **b.** The estimated background light profile of the central host galaxy, found by dividing the postage stamp into squares and applying a median filter to each of these sub-regions. We give the background pixel gradients, in blue, at every 20th pixel for clarity. The path traversed by the gradient ascent method is marked in dark magenta, and the black circle marks the final host galaxy. By masking saturated pixels and point-sources, we recover the light profile from the true host galaxy.

applies a median filter across each smaller region, then interpolates the resulting pixels back to the resolution of the original postage stamp. This smoothing requires a careful selection of both the size of each sub-region, or box, and the size of the median filter. Ideally, the size of each box should be larger than the galactic structure comprising the host galaxy of interest, and small enough to capture its radial light profile. A large sub-region and median filter will smooth local brightness variations; a small sub-region and median filter will preserve them. As a result, the size of the sub-region needed to resolve a host galaxy’s light profile will change drastically from field to field. We have empirically determined a set of criteria for predicting whether the true host galaxy will fall into one of three size categories - “small”, “medium”, or “large”. These criteria determine the sizes of the image boxes and the median filter. A box of 75x75 pixels is used for large host galaxies, while boxes of 40x40 and 15x15 px are used for medium and small host galaxies, respectively. The median filter used for large and medium host galaxies is 3x3 pixels; for small host galaxies, no filter is

applied to the data.

The estimated size of the true host galaxy is based upon four measurements:

1. \tilde{I} : The sigma-clipped median count of the image. This metric attempts to characterize the flux of non-stellar light across the full postage stamp. A high value of \tilde{I} suggests a large host galaxy in the field, but can also indicate bright stars that were not completely removed.
2. f_{IM} : The fraction of pixels in the 800x800 pixel image with a photon count of at least unity. This metric provides additional evidence for a single extended source dominating the field, and is less biased by stellar saturation.
3. f_{SN} : The fraction of pixels within a 200x200 pixel box centered on the supernova with a photon count of at least unity. This provides strong evidence for the spatial extent of the true host galaxy. If both f_{SN} and f_{IM} are near unity, a host galaxy is deemed large; if f_{SN} is large but f_{IM} is small, a medium host galaxy is assumed.
4. I_{SN} : The image count at the location of the supernova. If this value is above a certain threshold, the host galaxy is deemed “small”. This may appear counterintuitive, but this designation suggests that the supernova occurred near its host galaxy center. It is important that we use a small filter in this case to preserve the precise location of the host galaxy center.

A large filter can shift the location of a host galaxy center due to a combination of AGN masking and edge effects. To recover the local peak, we normalize and combine images A and B into a weighted average (image C). The weights applied to A and B are determined by the magnitude of I_{SN} and the number of masked pixels in image A . Image B is given the dominant weighting in the resulting image unless I_{SN} is above a threshold, for the same reason described above. If more than 15% of the image has been masked, the cubic interpolation of the image becomes unreliable and artificial photon counts from interpolated masked stars contaminate A . If this occurs, the reference image A is given a weight of 0 and $C = B$.

Once we have our final profile-dominated image C , we estimate the two-dimensional gradient at each pixel using the numpy package. We use second-order central differencing at the interior points of each image and first-order differencing at the boundaries. We begin at the location of our supernova $(x_i, y_i) = (x_{SN}, y_{SN})$ in pixels and update the position according to the image gradient $\nabla C(x_i, y_i)$, using a forward Euler updating scheme:

$$(x_{i+1}, y_{i+1}) = (x_i, y_i) + h\nabla C(x_i, y_i) \quad (3.10)$$

Here h represents a chosen step size. After completing a step, we round our updated position coordinates to the nearest pixel. By tracing the local gradient in the postage stamp, the algorithm “crawls” to local areas of increased brightness. For spatially extended sources, the gradients will cause the step to terminate at or near the center of the supernova’s host galaxy. The algorithm iterates until the calculated position has reached

the edge of the postage stamp or for 1000 steps, whichever comes sooner. If the algorithm reaches a region of the image with a gradient smaller than a pixel, we use the `numpy` `random` function to randomly perturb its location by one pixel in any direction. This feature, combined with the large number of total iterations, prevents the algorithm from getting trapped in a local maximum. After the algorithm terminates, we conduct a PS1 cone search at the terminated position. The radius of this search is 5° for “small” or “medium” host galaxies (see above criteria), and 20° for “large” host galaxies. We eliminate sources with only one PS1 detection, and then select the non-stellar source closest to the terminated position. We illustrate this algorithm in Figures 3.5a and 3.5b.

For this algorithm to be successful, we must select a physically relevant step size h . This must be large enough to “overlook” remaining deviations from a smooth light profile, and small enough to prevent overshooting the true center of a host galaxy. For a given field, We calculate h by multiplying the mean Kron radius for all potential host galaxies by an empirical scale factor based on the four criteria outlined above. We use a large scale factor when the supernova occurs within a large galaxy dominating the postage stamp, and a small scale factor when the supernova occurs within a small extended source. This allows our step sizes to vary with the scale of the most likely host galaxy even when the true host galaxy is unknown. This scale factor also accounts for unrealistically low PS1 Kron radius values, as is described in greater detail in 3.2. If we adopt a scale factor of unity, the algorithm terminates in a majority of fields before the galactic center is reached.

Table 3.1: Quality Cuts to Spectroscopic Sample During Association.

Pipeline Step	Fraction Removed	Total Fraction
PS1 30° cone search for nearby host galaxies	7.3%	92.7%
Removal of sources not detected in <i>gri</i>	3.2%	89.5%
Removal of sources with <i>qualityFlag</i> = 128, <i>primaryDetection</i> = 0, <i>bestDetection</i> = 0	<0.1%	89.5%
Star, galaxy separation with SVM	3.6%	85.9%
Directional light radius host galaxy association	10.3%	75.6%
Gradient ascent host galaxy association	-3.9%	79.5%
Redshift mismatch	1.9%	77.6%
Manual reassociation	-0.4%	78.0%

We trigger this algorithm when a host galaxy is not found using DLR, and when a candidate host galaxy is missing the morphology information necessary for the DLR method. There are 2,137 supernovae matching the first criterion, and 3,129 matching the second. We find by visual inspection that the gradient ascent

method achieves a 12% misassociation rate for the incomplete morphology sample, compared to 16% for the DLR method. We additionally find a $\sim 3\%$ misassociation rate for the “hostless” sample, which generally consists of less crowded fields. More importantly, our method recovers 800 host galaxies from the hostless sample. This is nearly half of the supernovae removed by the DLR method and roughly 4% of all spectroscopic supernovae. We have included these matches in our final database.

Our gradient ascent method reliably recovers transient host galaxies at low-redshifts when a large galaxy dominates the field, and at high-redshifts with sparse fields. When the host galaxy is large and the field is crowded, the large filter selected can blend multiple galaxies and shift the peak of the true host galaxy’s light profile. This causes the algorithm to terminate at an artificial maximum, and can lead to incorrect associations.

To be useful for early-time classification, our host association pipeline must be fast. We have timed our complete pipeline for five low- z ($z < 0.001$) events and five high- z ($z > 0.4$) events from TNS. We find a median of 85 ± 4 s per event for the low- z sample and a median of 73 ± 37 s per event for the high- z sample. The large spread in association times at high- z is caused by the gradient ascent method, which is only triggered when the DLR method fails. More low- z events triggered gradient ascent because the large physical projections involved makes it harder to find the center of the true host galaxy. The majority of time elapsed during the gradient ascent method is spent querying PS1 for postage stamps of the field; if images are provided in advance (or the association is done over a faster internet connection), latency will likely decrease.

After incorporating host galaxies matched with the gradient ascent method, we manually re-associate an additional 425 supernovae ($\sim 2.6\%$ of our table) by eye that were mismatched in our sample and another 69 low- z supernovae (0.4% of our table). These low- z supernovae were the events from TNS with $z < 0.014$ ($d_L \approx 60$ Mpc) that were not successfully associated by our pipeline. In the majority of cases, the hosts of these supernovae were either $> 30^\circ$ from the event or reported unphysical radius information in PS1 and dropped at the DLR stage. We further identify misassociations by plotting the redshift of each supernova as a function of its angular separation θ from its host galaxy. Multiple associations indicate $\theta > 15^\circ$ and $z > 0.1$, corresponding to a physical separation of > 30 kpc. Although supernovae have been discovered as far as 80 kpc from their host centers from tidal interactions with other galaxies [134], events at this separation are probably uncommon (see Figure 2 of [171]). To confirm this sample as misassociated, we identify the matches where the supernova redshift differs from its host galaxy’s redshift by greater than 50%. We plot this sample in Figure 3.6a. These ~ 300 events occur predominantly at $z_{SN} > 0.1$ and comprise the majority of our high- z matches with large separation. We have removed these events from our database. We estimate the misassociation rate of our final database to be $< 3\%$, lower than the misassociation rate reported by Gupta et al. [199]. We list the fraction of total supernovae dropped from our sample at each stage of the pipeline in Table 3.1.

Our final database contains host galaxies for 78% of all spectroscopically classified supernovae, higher

Figure 3.6: **a.** The redshifts of supernovae in our sample as a function of angular separation from their host galaxy. Small points are colored by the host galaxy’s r -band Kron radius. We find a θ distribution roughly matching that given in Galbany et al. [171] but with multiple high- z host galaxies with $\theta > 15^\circ$. In most of these high- z cases, the host galaxy’s Kron radius is too small to reasonably explain this wide separation. By flagging the systems where the host galaxy’s redshift differs by more than 50% of the supernova’s redshift (the large points in red), we confirm that this high- z sample is composed of predominantly misassociated systems. **b.** The distribution of spectroscopic redshifts for supernovae with associated host galaxies in GHOST and those without identified host galaxies. The median of each distribution is shown. Assuming a standard cosmology ($H_0=67.8$, $\Omega_0 = 0.3$) and a flat Universe, the supernovae in our sample lie at a median luminosity distance of ≈ 318 Mpc, while the unassociated sample lies at a median luminosity distance of ≈ 1.7 Gpc. We are able to associate the majority of supernovae within $z < 0.62$; the supernova sample analyzed in Gupta [200] spanned the range $0.01 \leq z \leq 0.46$.

than the completeness reported by Gupta [200] (73%, or 15,826/21,787 candidates) and spanning a significantly wider range in redshift. We have associated the majority of spectroscopic supernovae within $z < 0.62$; the furthest supernova candidate in Gupta [200] was at $z = 0.46$. 33.2% of events within our unassociated sample occurred at declinations below $-30^{\text{Ph.D.}}$, where a host galaxy search was excluded because no PanSTARRS 3PI survey images would be available. Excluding these events brings the fraction of associated supernovae to 84%. The remaining unassociated supernovae are located at significantly higher redshifts than the supernovae in the associated sample, as is shown in Fig. 3.6b. It is possible that even PS1 depths are insufficient to resolve these host galaxies.

43 supernova pairs in our final table have the same redshift, similar discovery dates (within 100 days of each other), and coordinates within 1 arcsecond of each other. These duplicates were removed. Two supernovae within 1 arcsecond of each other have discovery dates greater than one year apart. This pair of events is SN007ie, a type Ia supernova discovered on May 9th, 2007 at an RA and Dec (J2000) of

Figure 3.7: A screenshot of the GHOST Viewer, which consolidates 16, 175 host galaxy postage stamps and basic information about the supernovae they host into a streamlined GUI. A pop-up sidebar provides spectra for both supernova and host galaxy, if they are available. Light curve data from the Open Supernova Catalog is also presented. By viewing many identified host galaxies simultaneously, incorrect associations can be rapidly identified and population statistics can be studied in greater detail.

334.4029°, 0.6133° ; and PS1-11aqj, a type II supernova discovered on February 9th, 2011 at an RA and Dec of 334.4028°, 0.6134°.

3.3 Data and Software Products

The GHOST Database

The Galaxies HOsting Supernova Transients (GHOST) database contains 16, 175 spectroscopically classified supernovae and the photometric properties of their host galaxies. The full table can be downloaded as a CSV, and the host galaxy data for OSC supernovae have been added to the JSON data files and re-released for convenience. We have also included 1,436 masses estimated from host galaxy photometry (Foundation, [144]; PS1COSMO, [440], [244]), Hubble residuals of 124 SNe Ia (Kaepora, [445]), host galaxy and transient spectra (Sloan Digital Sky Survey, [520]; TNS), and transient light curves. In addition, we have developed software for querying the database and associating new host galaxies. We describe the functionality of the code in the following sections.

Analysis Tools for the GHOST Database

We have developed and released a Python package called `astro_ghost` to analyze the GHOST data products. It can be found at the repository for this work. The package also contains our full DLR and gradient ascent association pipelines. We list several functions for parsing the database below, along with a basic description of their use:

- `getTransientHosts`: Inputs the name and location of a transient or list of transients. If the transient is not found in the database by name or location, the association pipeline is run and the most likely host galaxy (one per transient) is returned.
- `getHostStatsFromTransientCoords`: Inputs the location of the transient as an `astropy SkyCoord` object, and returns basic statistics about a host galaxy (including other associated transients in the database).
- `getHostStatsFromTransientName`: Inputs the TNS name of a transient, and returns basic statistics about a host galaxy.
- `getTransientStatsFromHostName`: Generates basic statistics for a transient (or a series of transients) based on the NED-reported name of its host galaxy.
- `getTransientStatsFromHostCoords`: Generates basic statistics for a transient, based on host galaxy location as a `astropy SkyCoord` object.
- `getHostImage`: Inputs a transient TNS name and returns a postage stamp of the most likely host galaxy in one of the PS1 bands - g, r, i, z, y - as a fits file, and plots the image in gri as a color image.
- `getTransientSpectra`: Plots the spectrum of the transient from TNS, if it is available.
- `getHostSpectra`: Plots the spectrum of the host galaxy from SDSS or NED.
- `coneSearchPairs`: Completes a cone search for all transient-host pairs whose transient location falls within a certain radius, returned as a pandas dataframe. Useful for identifying supernovae associated with the same system where the NED name in the database is that of an HII region or star within the galaxy.
- `fullData`: Returns the full GHOST database.

Sample code outlining the usage of each of these functions is provided at the link above.

The GHOST Viewer

We have also created a website for simultaneously viewing all host postage stamps in our database. This website is hosted at the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA). Postage stamps are dynamically scaled in real time so that the user may rapidly view many host galaxies or individual systems of interest. Host galaxy images are color-coded by the class of the supernova matched to them. After selecting a postage stamp, a basic summary of both the supernova and its host galaxy are provided in a sidebar. Users may interactively search the database for a specific supernova by name, spectral class, or by the name of its host galaxy. Interactive plots showing the spectra of both host galaxy and supernova are also presented, and this data can be downloaded as a CSV. Both GHOST and its associated viewer will be updated as new supernovae are reported.

3.4 Dimensionality Reduction

Our final dataset contains 317 features of 16, 175 PS1 sources, along with the following seven features of their associated supernovae: right ascension, declination, class, name, redshift, angular offset θ , and scaled angular offset θ/d_{DLR} . Nearly half of the host galaxy features characterize the source’s detection in PS1. These include the pixel coordinates of the source in each filter, the number of source detections, and the detection ID in each band. Nevertheless, the large number of remaining features prohibits a brute-force search for supernova correlations. Further, galaxy features are highly correlated with each other, leading to empirical relationships such as the color-magnitude relation [39] and the Fundamental Plane for ellipticals [122]. These properties can reveal similar information about a galaxy’s position along an evolutionary track. As a result, these features likely do not provide unique information about the class of a supernova.

To test this hypothesis, we construct a correlation matrix, given in Figure 3.8, for the galaxy features in GHOST. We use Spearman’s rank correlation over the Pearson correlation because the latter describes only linear relationships, whereas the former quantifies the ability of a relationship to be described by any monotonic function. For features present in each band, we have only shown those features in g . We find that over half of our single-band features are $> 80\%$ correlated, and the same features across multiple bands are even more strongly correlated. The strong correlations between magnitude, flux, and radial moments of host galaxies in GHOST appear as blocks within the full correlation matrix. These blocks form a regular grid across our matrix due to the strong correlations between brightness features in each band. Aperture radius is not strongly correlated with our other photometric features, and therefore appears as a gap in the correlation blocks.

Figure 3.8: The Spearman rank correlation between PS1 source features in a single band (g), with blue corresponding to negatively correlated features and red corresponding to positively correlated features. Over half of the features are strongly correlated, particularly the magnitude of the host galaxy in different apertures and its first and second order radial moments. Strong correlations can also be seen in the same features across multiple bands (inset at right), leading to the block structure of the matrix.

Identifying Dominant Host Galaxy Features with Principal Component Analysis

To reduce our list of host galaxy parameters without reducing their predictive power, we undertake a principal component analysis (PCA) of our galaxy data. In PCA, a dataset is transformed to a set of orthogonal components with the first principal component containing the most uncorrelated variance. A dataset composed of highly correlated features will be well-characterized by a single principal component, which is a linear combination of the original features.

We begin by re-scaling our host galaxy features so that each has a mean of 0 and a variance of 1. Each of our features is continuous instead of categorical, rendering one-hot encoding unnecessary. Re-scaling is necessary to directly compare features whose values may differ in both magnitude and range. If a single feature contains a wide range of values, the first calculated principal component will capture most of the variance in this feature alone and not across all features. Next, we transform our GHOST database to its first two principal components using the `sklearn` package in Python. These principal components capture over half (55%) of the total variation in host galaxy features, confirming the degeneracy shown in Fig. 3.8.

By reducing the dimensionality of our dataset, we can visually identify differences between classes of supernovae. We present a biplot of our principal component model in Figure 3.9 along with the transformed distributions of SN Ia, SN Ib/c, and SLSN host galaxies. Because the principal components are linear combinations of the galaxy features, we can represent the initial galaxy features as vectors in this reduced space. The loading of each vector is defined as its projected length along each PCA axis; this quantifies the weight assigned to that feature in calculating a principal component. Highly linearly correlated features are given similar weights along the two axes, and we can see a clustering of magnitude, flux, and morphological features forming the dominant contributions to this PCA space. The first principal component, which explains 44.5% of the variation in host galaxy information, is determined nearly equally by the Kron radius of a source and its PSF, Kron, and Aperture magnitudes. The second principal component, which explains 10.4% of the variation, is determined mainly by the PSF flux, $momentRH$ (the square root of the first radial moment) and $ExtNSigma$ in each band (a PS1 derived feature extremely similar to our $m_{AP} - m_{Kron}$ mag, $ExtNSigma$ is defined as the difference between PSF and Kron magnitude of a source subtracted by the stellar median value and divided by the error combined in quadrature; see [320] for more information). SN Ia host galaxies are widely distributed in this space, with two peaks at separate locations along both principal components. The two highest-density contours for host galaxies of SNe Ib/c span a significantly smaller range in PCA space than the highest-density contours for host galaxies of SNe Ia, although with a smaller sample size (591 SNe Ib/c vs. 6,279 SNe Ia) this homogeneity may be unphysical. These three classes are also centered at different locations in PC space, providing a useful diagnostic tool for distinguishing classes of supernovae without any information from their explosions.

The multimodal distribution of SN Ia host galaxies in this PCA space suggests multiple distinct populations, particularly given the large sample size of this class. In addition, the strong overlap with the two other groups suggests that SN Ia host galaxies are photometrically similar to galaxies hosting SNe Ib/c and

Figure 3.9: The PCA-transformed distribution of host galaxy parameters for three supernova classes in our data: SN Ia, SN Ib/c, and SLSN. For clarity, we plot in black the feature vectors in r with highest loading along the two principal component axes. The SN Ib/c and SLSN distributions are centered at different positions along the first principal component, suggesting host galaxies with different size and brightness properties. The distribution of SN Ia host galaxies is bimodal, suggesting multiple host galaxy populations. A distinct group of SLSNe can also be seen top center. These galaxies host unusually energetic SNe (see text) – an indication that SN anomalies can be found by the properties of their host galaxies. Postage stamps correspond to the peak of the SN Ib/c distribution (orange border) and the peaks of the SN Ia distribution (green borders)

SLSNe. By embedding postage stamps corresponding to each peak in Fig. 3.9, we can see that one SN Ia mode aligns with bright spiral galaxies (which are similar to SN Ib/c hosts), whereas the other aligns with faint, featureless hosts (which are similar to SLSN hosts). The bimodality of SN Ia host galaxies also presents a challenge for classification. SN Ia residing within host galaxies at the left peak are likely to be misclassified as SLSNe, and SNe Ia within host galaxies at the right peak are likely to be misclassified as SNe Ib/c. Despite this overlap, the separation along the first principal component suggests that type information is revealed by host information alone.

By reducing the dimensionality of our host galaxy features, we can also rapidly identify outliers within GHOST. Fig. 3.9 reveals a sub-sample of SLSN host galaxies that are well-separated from the rest of the dis-

tribution in PCA space. This population is comprised of four supernovae in our dataset. Two of these are SN2213-1745 and SN2016aps, events whose hyper-energetic explosions make them strong candidates for pair-instability or pulsational pair-instability supernovae ([106, 363]). SN2016aps is the brightest supernova ever discovered, with peak absolute magnitude of -22.35 ± 0.09 in i . Another supernova in this sample is SN2017gci, which was listed in the original AT report as a candidate cataclysmic variable; and LSQ14fxj, which has been alternatively classified as a SLSN, SN Ic, and an unusually bright Ia by different groups. From the feature loadings in Fig. 3.9, it is possible that some of these events correspond to the faintest SLSN host galaxies in our sample; indeed, SN2017gci was initially listed as hostless, and the estimated redshift of SN2213-1745 is $z = 2.0458 \pm 0.0005$ [106], making it the most distant SN in our sample. The fact that these rare supernovae are associated with outliers in our host galaxy sample suggests a strong correlation between transient and host galaxy. Studying these host galaxies in more detail will likely shed light on these enigmatic events.

Because significantly more variance from our full table is captured by the first PCA component, we can better distinguish SN classes by projecting the data along only this axis. We show Gaussian kernel density estimates (KDEs) for our SNe along the first principal component in Fig. 3.10. Because sample sizes vary dramatically between classes, the spread may not be representative of the true underlying populations; however, the medians of each distribution are illustrative.

Broadly categorizing this principal component as “size and brightness” and the second principal component as “light profile” in alignment with the loadings from Figure 3.9, we can now identify systematic physical differences between classes. The host galaxy distributions for type II, Ib/c, and IIb supernovae peak at nearly the same location and feature a heavy rightward skew, a strong indication that these supernovae are found in host galaxies with similar brightness and Kron radius. These hosts are distinct from SLSN host galaxies, which have a strong leftward skew; and host galaxies of Ia supernovae, which are not strongly skewed in either direction. By visually inspecting a subset of postage stamps corresponding to these populations, we find our SN Ib/c and SN II host galaxies to consist mainly of large spirals, whereas our SLSNe are hosted in smaller galaxies with a range of different morphologies. Visual inspection of our SN Ia host galaxy sample did not reveal any consistent trends with respect to size or morphology, potentially explaining the wide spread of the SN Ia KDE. This suggests that the horizontal axis in Figure 3.10 corresponds roughly to brighter, larger galaxies toward the right and smaller, fainter galaxies toward the left. These results are in agreement with previous findings that SLSNe-I are found almost exclusively in low-mass dwarf galaxies with low star formation rates ([375, 295, 312, 19]) and core-collapse supernovae occur predominantly in late-type galaxies with high star formation rates ([75, 207]).

The multiple peaks of SNe Ia host galaxies from Fig. 3.9 are also seen in Fig. 3.10. This provides additional evidence for multiple host galaxy populations with distinct size, brightness, and morphology. Previous studies have shown that SNe Ia occur within a broad range of galaxies [82].

It is possible that these host galaxy differences can be attributed at least in part to differences in red-

shift. The fact that the postage stamp at the peak of our SN Ib/c distribution reveals significantly more morphological information than the postage stamp near the peak of the SLSN distribution seems to verify this prediction, as SLSNe are found at systematically higher redshifts than SNe Ib/c. In addition, the archival data we have used contain observational biases that systematically under-represent the number of supernovae at higher redshifts. While we are unable to completely constrain the redshift dependence of our features, no single magnitude-limited survey to date contains enough spectroscopically confirmed events of each class to construct a redshift-balanced sample. We have found our PCA results to be consistent for a sub-sample of our data consisting of only low- z (< 0.014) host galaxies, but we caution that this effort represents only a first pass toward characterizing supernova host galaxies.

Figure 3.10: The distributions of supernova classes as a function of their loading along the first principal component from our PCA analysis. In this space, a type IIb supernova (SN IIb) is easily differentiated from a superluminous supernova (SLSN). The host properties of IIb, II, and Ib/c are nearly indistinguishable.

Comparing Host Galaxy Distributions with tSNE

While PCA is valuable for visualizing data, it is only able to compose reduced dimensional spaces from linear combinations of features. This renders it unable to identify nonlinear correlations that may be valuable for our analysis. The limitations of this method can be seen in the wide separation between host galaxy magnitude and flux vectors in Fig. 3.9, suggesting no correlation. To explore nonlinear relationships between our host galaxy features, we implement t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (tSNE) [316]. In tSNE, the transformation preserves the distribution of separations between points. This makes it another useful tool for directly comparing multiple classes of objects while preserving nonlinear correlations between features.

Figure 3.11: Distributions of host galaxy features for SNe Ia, SNe Ib/c, and SLSNe along the first dimension of our 2D tSNE, with dashed lines indicating the median of each distribution. Relative positions and shapes of the three distributions are consistent with the results from our principal component analysis given in Fig. 3.10, suggesting different underlying host galaxy populations.

We begin by projecting our data into a three-dimensional tSNE space using the `sklearn` implementation. We select a perplexity of 30 and a learning rate of 200. To compare our results with the PCA analysis completed in §3.4, we project our supernovae along only the first tSNE axis. We present KDEs for our transformed host galaxy data for SNe Ia, SNe Ib/c, and SLSNe along this axis in Fig. 3.11. As before, we see a leftward skew for SLSN host galaxies and rightward skew for SN Ib/c host galaxies. The medians of these distributions occur at significantly different positions along this axis. tSNE is a stochastic algorithm,

and we have verified through multiple iterations that the differences between our distributions are insensitive to the random seed used. These results suggest that the systematic differences between core-collapse, SN Ia, and SLSN host galaxies are robust, with SLSNe preferentially found in small and faint host galaxies and core-collapse supernovae found preferentially in large, bright host galaxies.

To further explore nonlinear correlations, we transform our host galaxy features into a three-dimensional t-SNE space. We find striking visual differences in the distributions of SN IIP, SLSN, and SN I Ib host galaxies along the second and third t-SNE axes, which we plot in Fig. 3.12. SLSN and SN I Ib host galaxies are most easily distinguished in this space, and SN IIP hosts are centered near the middle of the two distributions and span the full space of SN host galaxy features. We have found the separation between SN I Ib and SLSN host galaxies to be robust for a range of perplexities and initial random seeds, suggesting that real discriminatory information exists between these classes. These results also suggest that certain supernova sub-types may be easier to distinguish using host galaxy features than SNe Ia and core-collapse events. Larger sample sizes from upcoming surveys, especially at higher redshifts, will make it possible to investigate the host galaxy correlations of these underrepresented events in greater detail.

Figure 3.9 suggests that our ability to distinguish supernova host galaxies by class is redshift-dependent. This relationship becomes more evident when we plot the redshifts for the same SN IIP, SN I Ib, and SLSN host galaxies described above. In the left panel of Figure 3.12, we find that redshift roughly decreases toward the bottom left of our tSNE space and increases toward the top right. SLSNe events are highly coincident with high-redshift host galaxies and SN I Ib events are highly coincident with low-redshift host galaxies. This reflects previous findings that SLSNe preferentially occur at high- z and core-collapse events have been preferentially observed at low- z , particularly SNe I Ib [258].

We can partially account for these redshift effects by calculating the absolute magnitudes of our host galaxies. First, we convert our PS1 magnitudes to the SDSS photometric system using the model developed by Finkbeiner et al. [138]. We then k -correct our host galaxy magnitudes using the *SDSS* color-conversion from Chilingarian et al. [96] and convert to rest-frame using the galaxy redshifts found in NED. We show g -band rest-frame and absolute magnitudes of these hosts in the right panel of Fig. 3.12. SN I Ib and SLSN host galaxies in g are well-separated by rest-frame magnitude, but after correcting for their redshifts reported in NED we find that the absolute magnitudes of these host galaxies are nearly identical. This supports the evidence from our 2D tSNE plot that previously discovered SNe I Ib and SLSNe occur at distinct redshifts. Though these host galaxies are similar in intrinsic brightness, they can still be distinguished at early times by the redshifts at which they more frequently occur. A volume-limited survey would confirm whether these redshift-dependent rates reflect our observational biases or underlying formation mechanisms for SN I Ib and SLSN events. If these trends persist in future datasets, they could also be used to validate photometric redshifts of these classes.

Figure 3.12: **Left, Above.** The distribution of host features corresponding to three classes of supernovae (SNe IIP, SNe IIb, and SLSNe) along our second and third tSNE axes. SLSN and SN IIb host galaxies are easily separable in this space, whereas SN IIP hosts are centered between the two distributions and span a much wider range of values. **Left, Below.** The same host galaxies as above, colored by redshift. The clustering of SNe IIb and SLSNe in tSNE space is highly redshift-dependent. **Right, Above.** Histograms for the k -corrected g -band Kron magnitudes of the same hosts as in left. Distribution colors match the supernova classes top left. SLSN host galaxies are fainter than nearly all SN IIb host galaxies; SN IIP host galaxies span both distributions. **Right, Below.** Histograms for the g -band absolute Kron magnitudes of these hosts. After correcting for host redshift, the distributions of the three classes are nearly coincident. This implies that the majority of the observed differences between SLSN, SN IIP, and SN IIb host galaxies are caused by redshift-dependent event rates.

3.5 Supernova Classification

Random Forest: Methods

We are now able to quantify the predictive power of host galaxy information in supernova classification. As in our star-galaxy separator, we implement a random forest model for this classification.

First, we remove all host galaxy features from our final table that do not describe physically meaningful information. These include PS1 IDs, PS1 data quality flags and features that reflect the quality of model fits. After removing rows containing missing values, we are left with 11,873 supernovae. In order to ensure

accurate matches for classification, we also drop all rows where the redshift of the associated host differs by greater than 5% from the redshift of the supernova (if both are reported). We then consolidate supernova class labels.

First, we consolidate our training data into two classes: core-collapse supernovae (including SNe Ib/c, SNe II, and all sub-classes of SN II events) and type Ia supernovae (SNe Ia). The vast majority of supernovae within GHOST are SNe Ia, and in a magnitude-limited survey the majority of discovered events will also be SNe Ia. Training our random forest on the observed distribution of events would improve the classification accuracy when tested on data matching this distribution, but the tendency of the classifier to preferentially identify SNe Ia would prevent it from learning fundamental differences between the host galaxies of underrepresented supernova classes. The imbalanced training set would also lead to more wrong classifications for rarer events, as the algorithm would determine that any event with ambiguous host galaxy properties is likely a SN Ia. Further, the intrinsic rates of undersampled supernovae remain poorly understood [473] and therefore poorly constrained [390]. Observed rates also suffer from known systematic effects such as Malmquist bias [292]. Because we are unable to rebalance our dataset to match the intrinsic rates of each class, a model trained on this data would maximize accuracy by predicting on observed population rates. Because we are primarily focused on characterizing host galaxies and not event rates, we re-balance our training set using the package `Imbalanced-learn`.

We first use k -fold cross-validation to generate five samples of equal size. One of these samples is chosen as the test data in our first random forest model, and the remaining 80% of the data is used as our training set. To re-balance our training data, we undersample our largest class (SN Ia) and oversample our smallest class (core-collapse) to a size between these two extremes. This allows us to train on as much data from the majority class as possible, while minimizing the amount of artificial data we generate for the minority class. After re-sampling, our training data contains 3,500 SN Ia events and 3,500 core-collapse events in a single fold. Our test set contains approximately 1,503 SN Ia events and 723 core-collapse events in each fold (because our full test set is not divisible by five, each fold will contain a slightly different number of events). The next model uses a different one of the five sub-samples for testing and the remaining re-balanced 80% of the data for training. This process is repeated for each of the five folds, generating five distinct random forests for our binary classification problem. We plot pie charts comparing the classes of our full dataset and our re-balanced samples in Figure 3.13.

We use the `RandomizedSearchCV` algorithm to determine the optimal hyperparameters for our random forest. Our final model consists of 1,400 trees without bootstrapping, and considers a maximum of 18 features (the square root of the total number of features) when choosing the best split for each node. We use a maximum depth of 90 and a minimum of 2 samples required for splitting. As with the dimensionality reduction described in §3.4, we scale our features to have a mean of 0 and variance of unity before classification.

Random Forest: Results

Because an event’s predicted class is determined by consolidating the predictions of each of the trees, the fraction of final votes belonging to each class can be used as a classification probability. Traditionally, the overall accuracy in a binary classification problem is determined by the fraction of events correctly classified by a majority of trees, corresponding to a decision threshold of 50%; however, different thresholds can be selected to prioritize particular aspects of the model. For example, a higher decision threshold will consider only the events which are classified nearly unanimously by all of the trees, as was the case for our star-galaxy classifier, whereas a low decision threshold will do the opposite. This tradeoff can be conceptualized with a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, which describes the rate of true positive classifications and false positive classifications as a function of the decision threshold (from 0 to 1). The accuracy of our model, which is determined by a majority vote, represents a single point along this curve. The Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC) quantifies the separability of our two classes, with a high AUC indicating a model that achieves a high true positive rate and a low false positive rate. In the limit of perfect classification, the AUC approaches unity. We have constructed a ROC curve in Figure 3.14a to evaluate the binary model described above. We also report the AUC for each class and its standard deviation across our 5-folds. We present the confusion matrix for our model in Figure 3.14b, which lists the mean classification accuracy (corresponding to a probability threshold of 50%) for each class and for the complete test set.

We find that we can predict supernova class with $\sim 70\%$ accuracy without any spectroscopic or photometric information from the explosion itself, using exclusively host galaxy information and the angular offset of the supernova. The model achieves an overall accuracy of $67.9\% \pm 1.7\%$, with a classification accuracy of 72% for SN Ia events. The AUC for our final model is $72\% \pm 2\%$ and $72\% \pm 3\%$ for SN Ia and core-collapse events, respectively. We also achieve a SN Ia model precision of 79%. Imputing missing values using the default mean imputation configuration of SimpleImputer from the sklearn package results in a comparable mean accuracy and a larger standard deviation of $66.8 \pm 4.6\%$.

To assess the predictive power of host galaxies as a function of redshift, we divide our events into 9 equally spaced bins spanning $0 < z < 0.6$. We divide the data for each bin into 5 folds, re-balance our training set, and train and test our models. Because of the small number of observed core-collapse events at high redshift (fewer than 100 above $z = 0.3$), we re-balance in each bin by only undersampling our SNe Ia events. This prevents our training set from being dominated by simulated data. We plot the classification accuracy at each redshift for SNe Ia, core-collapse events, and across all events in Figure 3.15.

Our mean classification accuracy increases roughly monotonically with redshift after $z > 0.1$, and traces the classification accuracy for SNe Ia because they comprise the majority of events in each bin. In addition, our accuracy for each class in the highest redshift sample is nearly 20% higher than our classification accuracy for these classes at the lowest redshift sample. At every redshift, we achieve a higher mean classification accuracy than random guessing. Despite the small number of events within the highest redshift bin (107 branch-normal SNe Ia and 18 core-collapse events for $0.53 < z < 0.60$), we accurately identify 90%

Figure 3.13: **Above.** The fraction of the GHOST database comprised by different classes of supernovae. We show the fraction of core-collapse supernovae comprised by different sub-types at right. **Below.** The total number of supernovae within the training and testing samples for each fold of our two-class model. We have under-sampled our largest class (SN Ia) and over-sampled our smallest class (core-collapse) to generate a balanced dataset for training our algorithm. We list the number of real and augmented core-collapse events for clarity. Due to the small number of peculiar core-collapse, peculiar SN Ia, and SLSN events discovered to date, we are unable to robustly classify these groups by host galaxy properties.

of core-collapse events and 76.7% of SNe Ia. By removing the events classified as core-collapse supernovae across all folds, we increase the SN Ia fraction of our high-redshift ($0.53 < z < 0.60$) sample from 85.6% to 92.2%. This $\sim 7\%$ increase suggests that host galaxy information can be used to increase the purity of SN Ia samples at high- z , but because we are unable to associate the majority of supernovae past $z \sim 0.6$ the accuracy of reported classifications will likely decrease for events more distant than this.

For comparison, we develop two “wishful thinking” classifiers that randomly guess the supernova type of each event. The first classifier guesses each class 50% of the time, and the second guesses “SN Ia” 100% of the time. When applied to our test sample, these classifiers achieve mean accuracies of 50% and 68% respectively. While the latter has a comparable mean accuracy to our random forest classifier, it achieves a model precision of 68% for SNe Ia. This makes our random forest classifier $\sim 20\%$ more accurate than chance and 11% more precise at classifying SNe Ia than a model trained on SN Ia event rates. This study is the first to accurately distinguish thousands of SNe Ia and core-collapse supernovae with the photometric

properties of their host galaxies. We provide a single random forest classifier, trained on the full GHOST database, as a submodule within the `astro_ghost` package.

We have found across several iterations that our models trained on data spanning the full redshift range of the database classify SNe Ia more accurately than core-collapse events. This trend is reversed in our redshift-binned models: we classify core-collapse supernovae more accurately than SNe Ia for the majority of our redshift samples. Although it is possible that our simulated core-collapse events within the full sample were unphysical, it is more likely that the full sample captures more of the diversity of core-collapse events and their host environments [258]. This is supported by the wide spread of SN II in Fig. 3.10, although a larger sample of events is needed to probe these host galaxies in more detail.

The classifier’s improved accuracy with redshift is surprising, as more host galaxy information is available at low- z . In comparing the properties of SN II and SN Ia host galaxies in our highest redshift bin, we find that the high- z SNe Ia extend to significantly higher θ/d_{DLR} values than the high- z SNe II. This parameter is the most significant feature in our high-redshift model, suggesting it is responsible for the model’s improved accuracy. If more supernovae were incorrectly matched to neighboring bright galaxies at high- z because their true host galaxies are faint, they will be overwhelmingly SNe Ia and the reported scaled offsets of this group will be shifted upward. We nevertheless find that this effect remains after considering only supernovae that match their host galaxy’s redshift to within 5%.

Our database has been consolidated from multiple supernova surveys. Supernovae discovered from SDSS-II are included in this analysis, which span the range $0.05 < z < 0.4$. Past $z \sim 0.4$, our samples consist primarily of transients from deeper surveys such as ESSENCE [338] and SNLS [24], which extend past $z \sim 0.7$. These high- z , large-aperture telescope surveys allow us to probe the innermost regions of supernova host galaxies, where faint core-collapse supernovae would typically be masked by galactic extinction. In addition, because many of these high- z surveys are untargeted, we expect to find more SNe Ia in the extended halos of their host galaxies where older stellar populations are found. This effect would also shift the scaled angular offsets of SNe Ia upward. We find by plotting θ/d_{DLR} as a function of redshift that the median scaled angular offsets of both core-collapse and type Ia supernovae in our sample are roughly comparable for $0.0 < z < 0.35$, and past this point the scaled offsets for SNe II shift to systematically lower values. Further, the scaled offsets for SNe Ia rapidly increase following $z \sim 0.4$ and then gradually return to a value comparable to the low- z sample as we begin to reach the observing limits of the high- z surveys. These trends explain both the rapid increase in classification accuracy at $z \sim 0.4$ seen in Fig. 3.15 and the overall increase in accuracy with redshift, as more of the low-offset core-collapse events are considered in our analysis. Nevertheless, with only 18 core-collapse events in our highest-redshift bin, more events are needed to validate and further explore these effects at higher redshifts.

As in §3.4, we can compare the redshift-corrected photometry of these classes to distinguish observational and intrinsic differences between host galaxies. Re-running our classifier using SDSS absolute magnitudes, we find a mean accuracy of $70.5 \pm 1.5\%$ but a lower core-collapse accuracy of $53.4 \pm 8\%$. This

result suggests that redshift information plays a larger role in classifying core-collapse events than SNe Ia.

The accuracy of our classification results suggests that host features can be used to minimize contamination within photometric SNe Ia samples. Because these photometric measurements will be already be made by upcoming surveys, this represents a low-overhead strategy for immediately improving cosmological estimates.

We have found in section 3.4 that each of our host features does not provide unique information, so we can reduce the complexity of our classification model while sacrificing minimal accuracy. We achieve this by considering only the 13 features with high loading from Figure 3.9 in *grizy*. This reduces our parameter space from 317 to 65 features. We use these features to train a new random forest model, and find an accuracy for each class comparable to that reported for the full model.

Despite the differences in host galaxy distributions found in Fig. 3.10, we are unable to construct a random forest that can accurately distinguish between rarer sub-classes of supernovae, even after augmenting these classes as was done for the core-collapse events. These rarer events include SLSNe, SNe IIP, SNe I Ib, and SNe Ib/c. It is likely that there are too few of these events for our random forest to identify meaningful relationships with their host galaxies. At present, GHOST contains under 100 SLSNe. Rubin Observatory in Wide-Fast-Deep mode is predicted to find $\sim 10^4$ SLSNe per year [500], dramatically expanding this dataset and facilitating future studies into the host galaxies of these underrepresented classes.

Because of the strong correlations between the majority of host galaxy features, the variable importances returned by our random forest model may not reveal the most valuable features for supernova classification. Further, the random forest importances presented by `scikit-learn` are known to be biased². We use the package `feature-selector` to remove all features that are greater than 80% linearly correlated and train a gradient boosting model for supernova classification. We use the normalized feature importance, defined as the percentage of times the feature is used within the model, as our metric for feature significance. We list the ten most significant features from our model in Fig. 3.16.

We have additionally calculated the permutation importance of our host galaxy features using the `rfrimp` package. This method identifies the top five features in our model to be $g - r$, second order moments in g and r , *ExtNSigma* in z and *psfMajorFWHM* in i . These results agree with the gradient boosting features and emphasize the importance of color and derived morphological features.

The host galaxy parameters found to be most significant by our gradient boosting model can be grouped into three main categories: radial offset, including θ and θ/d_{DLR} ; color-derived features, including *4DCD*, $g - r$, $g - i$, $r - i$, and $i - z$; and morphological features, including *momentXX* in g and i and *ExtNSigma* in g . The high importance of scaled radial offset indicates that supernova classes may preferentially occur at different locations throughout their host galaxies. The unscaled radial offset also has high importance, but this is likely a consequence of the difference in observed rates of supernova classes at different redshifts. For example, core-collapse events within GHOST are found predominantly at low redshift,

²<https://explained.ai/rf-importance/#intro>

Figure 3.14: **a.** A receiver operator characteristic (ROC) curve for our random forest classifier trained to classify SNe Ia and core-collapse events. Shaded regions describe the sample standard deviation calculated from a 5-fold cross-validation. The dashed line designates the performance of a model that classifies at random, and the area under the curve (AUC) for each class is listed along with its standard deviation across the 5 folds. The total number of supernovae in the training and testing sets (after augmentation) for each fold is listed top left. **b.** The confusion matrix for our classifier, showing the mean true positive rate and mean false positive rate for each class. The overall accuracy is given at top. We accurately distinguish $\sim 70\%$ of SNe Ia and core-collapse events without any information from either the light curve or spectrum.

where their observed angular offsets span a wide range of values due to the decreased distance to the host galaxy.

The morphological features characterize the light profile of the host galaxy, which can reflect the classification of the host galaxy along the Hubble tuning fork [494]. Color features encode host galaxy metallicity, mass, and galactic star formation rate, which are also correlated with supernova type (e.g. [208]). Color is also a useful indicator of early and late-type galaxies ([469]; [357]). These results suggest that the host galaxy features that are most valuable in classifying supernovae reflect many of the correlations that have been previously identified in the literature. The large PCA loadings of light profile metrics from §3.4 further confirm the discriminatory power of host galaxy morphology. Finally, the color with highest importance in our model is $g - r$. This color is strongly correlated with host galaxy magnitude (Fig. 3.8), which also has a strong loading in PCA space.

A Comparison to Previous Classification Efforts Using Host Galaxy Information

A similar study was undertaken by Baldeschi et al. [31] to distinguish SNe Ia and core-collapse events from LOSS [299] and ZTF-BTS [155], and these samples cover $z \leq 0.15$ and $z \leq 0.005$, respectively. The number of total events classified within each sample was ~ 500 , whereas we classify $> 10,000$ total super-

Figure 3.15: The SN Ia (dashed purple line), core-collapse (dotted red line), and combined classification accuracy (solid green line) of our random forest model as a function of redshift. Supernovae are grouped into 9 bins spanning the range $0 < z < 0.6$. The mean classification accuracy increases nearly monotonically for $z > 0.1$; whereas the lowest-redshift events are classified with $\sim 60\%$ accuracy, $\sim 80\%$ of the highest-redshift events are accurately classified. The mean accuracy of the model is higher than random guessing (the solid gray line) for every redshift bin; core-collapse classification does better than random guessing for all but one redshift bin.

novae across all five-folds of our classification scheme. Our train and test sets are randomly selected with replacement across folds, so these are not each unique events; however, we have classified at minimum 2,000 unique supernovae (the number within a single fold). Because our analysis includes significantly more events spanning $z \leq 2$, we have validated the robustness of host-galaxy correlations for supernova classification across a wider range of redshifts and host galaxies than previous studies. Baldeschi et al. [31] also included peculiar Ia events (e.g. Ia-02cx, Ia-91T, Ia-91bg, Ia-SC, Ia-CSM) within their Ia sample; the sample purities for branch-normal events are unknown. Peculiar SN Ia will be unusable for cosmological analysis because of the difficulty of standardizing their photometry. The classification accuracies presented in the current study have only considered branch-normal SNe Ia for classification with the motivation of studying dark energy in upcoming synoptic surveys. Finally, Baldeschi et al. [31] considered only host galaxies with complete Kron information and used g -band Kron radius in PS1-DR2 to associate transients with host galaxies. Because we have developed an association method that is fault-tolerant to faulty PS1 Kron radius estimates (described in §3.2), we are able to accurately identify a host galaxy even when Kron radius values are incorrect or incomplete. Nevertheless, their work reflects the value of using derived host galaxy properties to classify supernovae. We have considered the problem of classification directly from observed photometry (and morphological moments), but derived features such as host metallicity and stellar mass should be the focus of future work. Their released database of Hubble classes and star formation rates for all Pan-STARRS sources is ideal for extending this study.

In constructing a supernovae classifier from host galaxy information, Foley et al. [142] found that the

Figure 3.16: The ten host galaxy features with highest normalized importances in our binary supernova classification model as determined by a gradient boosting model. The features are ordered by importance. The features with highest importance can be broadly categorized by host galaxy color, radial separation, and host galaxy light profile. These features reflect previously-identified host galaxy correlations with supernova type. All of these features are available a-priori or can be calculated immediately following a triggered event.

most significant feature for increasing their FoM (which prioritized SN Ia sample purity) was host morphology. This data increased the FoM by greater than a factor of two over using no host galaxy information. This agrees with our finding that the light profile of a host galaxy (*ExtNSigma* and $m_{Ap,i} - m_{Kron,i}$) adds significant information for supernova classification. After morphology, Foley et al. [142] find that host galaxy color and luminosity slightly increase their FoM and increase the separation between SNe Ia and core-collapse samples. While this is considered less significant than morphology for maintaining pure SN Ia samples, the significance of color and luminosity in distinguishing supernova classes is supported by the results from our random forest model. Finally, Foley et al. [142] found that radial offset information produces only marginal contributions to SN Ia sample purities. It is surprising, then, that our random forest model uses radial offset information as its most important feature set for classification. We hypothesize that this difference can be attributed to our larger number of supernova events, which may show systematic differences in radial offset that may not be apparent in smaller low-redshift samples. In addition, our core-collapse sample consists of a greater number of sub-types (e.g. IIP, IIIn) than were originally considered by

Foley et al. [142], and these sub-types may be more distinguishable by radial offset than SNe Ib/c, SNe II, and SNe Ia only.

Other classifiers have accurately distinguished transient events by their postage stamps alone, and these will inevitably include the photometric properties of the host galaxy; however, these have typically been used to distinguish supernovae from non-explosive transients ([80]; [181]). These works also train neural networks on complete sequences of images taken throughout the duration of a transient event, and as a result their ability to accurately classify events from real-time single-epoch observations remains unclear. Further, the model developed by Carrasco-Davis et al. [80] requires at least three observations in g -band for accurate recall. Although this method is well-equipped for ZTF’s public survey cadence of ~ 3 days in g and r , these observations will span nearly a month of the wide-fast-deep survey’s single-band cadence. This is far too long to be leveraged for early-time follow-up without retraining. These methods will be more valuable for classifying events within archival data without the need to manually extract photometric measurements. They can also be used to validate pre-maximum classifications made by GHOST. In the event that a supernova that was missed by real-time classifiers is later discovered by archival image sequences, GHOST can still be run in tandem with these methods to identify the host galaxy and provide a classification.

GHOST characterizes the nature of a supernova that has already been discovered, but it cannot be used to determine whether an event has occurred or not. A real/bogus classifier operating on real-time postage stamps would extend the work of Carrasco-Davis et al. [80] and provide a necessary pre-processing step to the GHOST pipeline.

Calibrated aperture flux, $psf\ Flux$, adaptive source intensity second moments, and their associated uncertainties will be released for each new source detected by Rubin within 24 hours of detection. Difference image alerts will also provide the radial offset of a transient from a likely host galaxy. From these data, color, morphology, and radial features can be derived and used for transient classification. From our importances above, these measures are critical for classifying transient events with host galaxy information. In addition, Rubin will accompany source alerts with flags to characterize the “extendedness” and “spuriousness” of detected objects, and these can improve the current models for star-galaxy separation and host galaxy association, respectively. Because of the Rubin baseline cadence in a single passband, these features will only be available in $ugrizy$ after the first ~ 6 months of operation. During the initial period of Rubin commissioning, host photometry can be retrieved from PS1. Our association method runs in ~ 1 minute, and classification adds a negligible overhead. This is fast enough to operate on the full Rubin alert stream so that host and preliminary class information can be provided with a source alert well within Rubin’s projected 24 hour window.

3.6 Supernova Siblings

By determining the host galaxies of the majority of spectroscopically confirmed supernovae, we can compare the properties of supernova siblings: supernovae associated with the same host galaxy. Extensive work has been done to compare the light curves of SN Ia siblings ([172, 439]) and conduct a census of supernova siblings ([201, 16]). Our pipeline identifies 304 galaxies in our sample that host 2 supernovae, 37 galaxies that host 3 supernovae, 5 that host 4 supernovae, 4 that host 5 supernovae, and 3 that host 6 supernovae. These are nearly half of the supernova siblings identified by <http://www.rochesterastronomy.org/snimages/sndupe.html>. The majority of missing pairs were dropped from our pipeline because a supernova was located greater than 30° from its host galaxy center; however, increasing our cone search would have increased the number of artifacts in our sample and decreased the accuracy of our matches.

For our identified siblings, we use radial offset θ to explore whether SNe II and SNe Ia probe distinct regions of their host galaxy. For all galaxies hosting multiple supernovae, we take the difference between the radial offsets of two supernova siblings, $\delta\theta$. Next, we generate a probability density function for $\delta\theta$. We compare $\delta\theta$ distributions for two samples: siblings that belong to the same class, where both are SNe II or SNe Ia (the matched sample); and pairs where one sibling is a SN Ia and the other is a SN II (the nonmatched sample). The sizes of these two samples are roughly equal. Because we are comparing the *difference* in θ between matched and nonmatched siblings, we minimize the influence of different galaxy sizes, distances, and redshifts. A Malmquist bias is present within this sample, as supernovae within nearby host galaxies will be more easily detected than distant supernovae, especially for SNe II. These host galaxies allow for a greater range of possible $\delta\theta$ values than distant galaxies, so a SN II/SN II match will likely have a larger relative separation than a SN Ia/SN Ia match. This effect is unlikely to mask a systematic difference between $\delta\theta$ for matched and unmatched siblings.

We perform an Anderson-Darling (AD) test to compare the distributions of $\delta\theta$ for matched and unmatched supernovae, and find that at $> 99.8\%$ confidence we can reject the null hypothesis that these two samples are drawn from the same distribution ($p = 0.002$). A Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test, which weights the distribution tails less heavily than the AD test, also finds a significant difference between these distributions at the 99% level ($p = 0.01$).

Wang et al. [507] makes a similar comparison between the radial offsets (in kpc) of 197 SNe II and 246 SNe Ia using a KS test, rejecting the null hypothesis that these two classes have the same radial distributions at $p = 10\%$ (or at the 90% confidence level). Wang et al. [507] further suggests that the dominant differences between the radial offsets of these two classes arise within the inner 6 kpc of a galaxy. To compare the inner radial distributions of SNe Ia and SNe II between galaxies, we can no longer use $\delta\theta$; instead, we compare the scaled radial offset values θ/d_{DLR} for all events within the GHOST database. We find no significant difference in θ/d_{DLR} between SNe Ia and SNe II, either in the full range of values ($p = 0.47$ for KS and $p > 0.25$ for AD) or within the inner 10% of a supernova's host galaxy ($p = 0.57$ for KS and $p > 0.25$ for AD).

for AD). We have found this result to be consistent for the low- z sample ($z < 0.014$). We caution that we have calculated the DLR for these galaxies using the Kron radius reported for these objects; If this radius is not representative of the true radius of the galaxy, it would decrease the robustness of this comparison.

3.7 Conclusions

We have constructed the largest catalog of supernovae and their host galaxies to date. By augmenting the DLR method with a gradient ascent algorithm that isolates galaxy profiles directly from images, we can associate host galaxies spanning a wide range of redshifts ($0.00015 \leq z \leq 2$) to an accuracy of $> 97\%$. Rubin will have a maximum all-band wide-field-deep depth of $5\sigma > 25.08$, and the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope in deep survey mode is slated to achieve a depth per exposure of 26.2 in J and H [226]. These programs will allow us to study supernova host galaxies in unprecedented detail and further explore the correlations between host galaxy and transient, but it will also exacerbate the host galaxy association issues described in §3.2. A light profile-based association method will allow us to leverage the strengths of these surveys to continue to accurately associate new transients. Our results indicate that host galaxy color and photometry can aid in supernova classification. By projecting our sample into reduced parameter spaces, we can immediately identify visual differences between supernova host galaxies. Using a random forest classifier trained on host galaxy information, we distinguish SNe Ia and core-collapse supernovae with $\sim 70\%$ accuracy. This study builds on previous efforts by incorporating a significantly larger number of host galaxy features than were considered by Foley et al. [142]. Our mean classification accuracy is $\sim 20\%$ higher for high- z events than for low- z events. This likely reflects differences in the survey strategies used to discover supernovae in these two regimes, but at present we do not have enough high-redshift events to statistically compare these two samples. Our publically available classifier is trained on the full dataset, which has a median redshift of 0.07. We predict comparable classification accuracies to those listed above for $z < 0.6$ events. Re-training our algorithm with additional high- z host galaxies, whether simulated or discovered in the first few months of Rubin data, will ensure that our classifier is robust for more distant events. The host galaxy features with the most discriminatory power are radial offset, color, and derived morphological features. The color and morphology of a galaxy are indicative of its metallicity and star formation rate, both of which can be used to distinguish SNe Ia and core-collapse supernovae. Accurate morphology estimates in large surveys will be crucial for taking advantage of these correlations for new events. Further, the importance of radial offset suggests that a transient’s local environment may be even more predictive of supernova class than the global properties of its host galaxy. The strong overlap between global features of SN Ia, SLSN, and SN Ib/c host galaxies in Fig. 3.9 reinforces this need for localized metrics to characterize the local environments of supernovae and more accurately distinguish SN classes.

In addition, we find a statistically significant difference between the differential radial offsets $\delta\theta$ of matched (SN Ia, SN Ia and SN II, SN II) and nonmatched (SN Ia, SN II) supernova siblings, but we do not

find a significant difference in the scaled radial offsets θ/d_{DLR} between SNe Ia and SNe II. Intuitively, one might expect these distributions to differ because core-collapse supernovae are associated with star-forming regions and frequently found in the arms of spiral galaxies. Our result suggests that offset alone may not sufficiently characterize the positions of star forming regions. In addition, the significance of radial offset in our classification model suggests that sub-types of core-collapse events (SNe IIP, SNe Ib/c, SNe IIIn) may differ from SNe Ia in radial offset even if SNe II do not. This result underscores the need for higher resolution imaging to assemble a more complete picture of host galaxy-supernova interactions at the local level. This result may also reflect the limitations of characterizing host galaxy morphology using its PS1 Kron radius. As we discuss in greater detail in §3.2, this value is unphysical or unreported for the largest and smallest host galaxies in our sample, limiting our ability to directly compare SN positions between these galaxies. Finally, we find systematic differences in the host galaxy photometry of underrepresented events such as SLSNe, SNe IIP, and SNe I Ib. By comparing rest-frame and absolute g -band magnitudes, we identify a strong redshift-dependence in the rates of these events. Archival SLSNe are found at higher redshifts than SNe I Ib, and as a result their observed host galaxies will be fainter. This information can be used to distinguish these events and validate photometric redshift estimates. Rubin’s official strategy for host galaxy association has not yet been finalized. We have shown that, where deep surveys limit the ability to de-blend extended sources, the directional light radius is unable to robustly identify supernova host galaxies. In addition, the postage stamps associated with real-time transient alerts for Rubin are unlikely to exceed $6^\circ \times 6^\circ$. This window will exclude many supernova host galaxies within $z \sim 0.1$ (See Figure 3.6a), and make it difficult to use postage stamp gradients for host galaxy association. The gradient ascent method outlined in this chapter will be a valuable resource for validating Rubin’s host galaxy associations and proposing improvements to the pipeline.

Finally, we note that we have only considered the binary classification problem in this study. Preliminary correlations have been identified in recent years for rare classes of events, including a preference of Rapidly-Evolving Transients [RETs; 124, 393] for hosts of intermediate mass between high-mass SN Ia hosts and low-mass SLSN hosts [513]. For observationally rare events [e.g., kilonovae (KNe); 452], correlations remain as yet unconstrained, but may play a decisive role in maximizing the yield of future targeted searches. Upcoming surveys are well-poised to further extend our understanding of these class-specific correlations toward higher redshifts and rare subtypes. However, only a few transient classifiers to date [142, 164, 276] have incorporated host galaxy information. Efforts are stymied by the limited observational data available for training these algorithms; perhaps worse, extant samples are frequently biased toward low-redshift, bright host galaxies, uncharacteristic of the galaxies anticipated from upcoming surveys.

The limitations described above for both the current and prior studies motivate the creation of a homogeneous catalog of transients and the properties of their host galaxies spanning cosmological distances for training automated pipelines. With poorly-understood selection effects plaguing the majority of observed transient catalogues, particularly when combined, a simulated catalog in advance of Rubin first light would

spur additional development in this area. We describe the creation and validation of this catalog in the following chapter.

Chapter 4

The Catalog of Optical Transients and Correlated Hosts (SCOTCH)

This chapter is based on: Lokken, Gagliano, Narayan, Hložek, et al., 2023, *MNRAS*, 520, 2.

Disclaimer: This section of the dissertation was a joint effort between Martine Lokken (a Ph.D. candidate at the University of Toronto) and myself, under the guidance of our respective advisors Prof. Renée Hložek (University of Toronto) and Prof. Gautham Narayan (UIUC). Martine and I jointly developed the analysis pipeline, created the HOSTLIB files, tested and ran the PZFlow code to remove CosmoDC2 artifacts, iterated on the functional forms of the transient-host galaxy correlations encoded in the WGTMAP, ran the SNANA simulations, and wrote the publication. Martine selected the initial CosmoDC2 galaxies, wrote the script to create the hdf5 catalog, and led the comparison with observations. I preprocessed the GHOST catalog, created the initial WGTMAP files, and implemented the ANNOY algorithm to find GHOST-like galaxies in CosmoDC2. I also wrote the Zenodo documentation and the walkthrough tutorials in the associated github repository. Other members of the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (where this publication underwent collaboration-wide review) contributed comments and suggestions.

4.1 Introduction

The previous chapter of this dissertation explored the value of extant optical photometry for distinguishing between SNe Ia and CCSNe. The photometry used was from the Pan-STARRS 3π survey, which has a single-visit and stack 5σ depth of 22.0 and 23.3 in g , respectively¹. In contrast, the Vera C. Rubin Observatory will achieve a single-visit and 10-year co-add depth 25.0 and 27.4, respectively, in g . Rubin's unprecedented depth and synoptic coverage of the Southern sky will permit volume-limited studies of even rare classes of transients and the statistical leverage of their host-galaxy properties.

¹<https://outerspace.stsci.edu/display/PANSTARRS/>

First light from Rubin’s Legacy Survey of Space and Time is scheduled to begin early 2025. While observed transient samples are limited to the local Universe and photometry is comparatively shallow, simulations are vital for developing and testing analysis algorithms that incorporate this information. Such algorithms will need to adapt to faint and high-redshift data in the early days of Rubin, while they are iteratively tested and updated using the incoming data and the corresponding advancements in time-domain theory. This interim period requires high-redshift simulations that extend to fainter magnitudes. These simulated data necessarily employ either untested models for cosmological evolution, or the assumption that the trends observed at low redshift extend to high redshift.

We adopt the latter assumption, and construct in this work the first large-scale simulation of optical transients *and their host galaxies* that extrapolates existing data to high redshifts ($z \sim 3$). These simulations extend those generated for the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge [PLAsTiCC; 263]. PLAsTiCC data were generated by simulation code in the SuperNova ANALysis package [265, SNANA], and the challenge represented the first large-scale effort to realistically simulate a broad diversity of transient phenomena. Simulated host-galaxy information, however, was limited: the dataset only includes the photometric redshifts of host galaxies assigned near the redshift of the transient. This study extends the PLAsTiCC framework with the inclusion of empirical and theoretical host-galaxy correlations for both common and rare transient classes. We embed these correlations using a series of host galaxy libraries (called HOSTLIBs within SNANA) and weight maps (WGTMAPS) that describe the likelihood of a given galaxy to host a transient of a certain class within the simulation.

In this work, we extend the results of Vincenzi et al. [503] by simulating additional classes of supernovae and other non-SN transients, incorporating correlations across a wider range of host galaxy properties, and separately validating hosts of different classes across these properties. We extrapolate information from archival events, mostly at low-redshift, to a high-redshift simulated sample of galaxies via associations in intrinsic — rather than observed — properties. In doing so, we encode correlations for each transient class to significantly higher redshifts ($z \sim 3$) than the ranges spanned by current observations. Due to a lack of high- z evidence, the most practical option is to assume no redshift evolution of the observed transient-host relationships in the local universe and smoothly extrapolate transient rate models measured at low redshifts. Therefore, the simulation is likely to become increasingly inaccurate at higher redshifts, and SCOTCH² by itself should not be used for precision cosmological forecasts or high-redshift transient analyses. However, the catalog can be used to test classifier algorithms and alert broker systems, examine the effects of contamination on cosmological constraints, and model selection biases in current and upcoming transient/host galaxy surveys.

We outline the overall methodology for constructing the catalog in §4.2. We introduce the archival catalogs used to construct our host galaxy sample in §4.3. We describe the SNANA simulation code that we use to generate our transient events and summarize the models underlying each event in §4.4. We present

²https://zenodo.org/record/7563623#.Y8_2my9h2yA

our methods in §4.5 for combining observed and simulated catalogs into a library containing millions of host galaxies. We then describe our process for incorporating additional class-specific transient correlations using WGTMAPs in §4.6. We comment briefly on the inclusion of class-specific radial offsets in §4.7. We validate our results in §4.8 and present the schema of our final catalog in §4.9. We then conclude with a discussion of the limitations of our sample and areas for future research in §4.10.

4.2 Methodology Overview

Because the methods we use to simulate the transients themselves are nearly identical to those described in Kessler et al. [263], this work focuses on our methodology for constructing a set of HOSTLIBS and WGTMAPs for the SNANA simulation code. This allows us to realistically associate a simulated host galaxy with each transient, given its class. We provide a flowchart of this pipeline in Fig. 4.1. The initial input is the CosmoDC2 synthetic galaxy catalog [282, described in §4.3] with slight modifications made via the PZF1ow algorithm [109, described in §4.5]. First, we create four large galaxy libraries: for SNe, by selecting synthetic galaxies matching the rest-frame color and absolute magnitude distributions of three broad categories of transient hosts in observational data; and for non-SNe, by generating a generic catalog of galaxies which will be tailored to match observations at a later stage. For SNe, we utilize the observational data in GHOST [164], a catalog of supernova host galaxy properties described in additional detail in §4.3. Our process for selecting synthetic galaxies matching the statistical properties of the observational data, including the use of the ANNOY³ algorithm, is described in detail in §4.5. The resulting three galaxy libraries include: Type Ia hosts (**I**); Type II, II_n, II_p hosts (**II**); and Type Ib, Ic, II_b hosts (**III**). We construct a fourth library of randomly-selected CosmoDC2 galaxies to serve as the hosts of transients from classes that have little observational data, and for which the correlation between explosion and environment is unconstrained by GHOST. Next, for nine different transient classes including SN and non-SN, we encode the probability that an event of that class will occur in a host galaxy given its mass and star formation rate. These probabilities are motivated by observations and are described in §4.6. Finally, the SNANA simulation (§4.4) is used to generate transient light curves and place each in a realistically-associated host galaxy, with host galaxies selected from one of the four libraries depending on the transient class and the probability of selection given by the class-specific functions described in §4.6.

³<https://github.com/spotify/annoy>

Figure 4.1: Analysis flowchart with section labels. Intermediate catalogs and data products are given in blue text, major software packages in red text, and methodology in green text.

4.3 Galaxy Data

The DC2 Simulations

Our work aims to simulate transient-host associations to higher redshifts and fainter magnitudes than have been previously observed. We also wish to produce a catalog containing valuable derived properties of transient hosts, including morphology, star formation rates and stellar masses. Observed galaxy catalogs are limited in these respects, so we make use of synthetic galaxy data from the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC).

DESC is in the midst of a series of data challenges in preparation for the Rubin Observatory. The goal of the data challenges is to produce realistic end-to-end simulations of LSST survey operations, data reduction, and analysis. For data challenge 2 (DC2), DESC produced a suite of simulated LSST-like datasets, including an extragalactic source catalog and co-added images [307]. We make use of the extragalactic catalog, named the CosmoDC2 Synthetic Sky catalog [282], and its associated DC2 image data.

The CosmoDC2 catalog was constructed from a dark matter only N-body simulation in a 4.225 Gpc^3 volume. This volume is insufficient to probe to $z \sim 3$ as needed for LSST, so to create lightcones, the volume was replicated once per axis. After the lightcone generation, realistic galaxies with Sersic profiles and SEDs were associated with dark matter halos. The resultant galaxy catalog, which is delivered in HEALPix⁴ (Hierarchical Equal Area iso-Latitude Pixelization) format [188], spans 440 deg^2 of the sky and cosmological distances ($z \simeq 3$). The CosmoDC2 data has also undergone rigorous validation to ensure that it matches observed galaxy properties [283]. However, due to necessary compromises made to accommodate the needs of the diverse DESC working groups, the CosmoDC2 distributions of galaxy colors are far from perfect, particularly at higher redshifts ($z > 0.5$). We discuss how these color limitations affect the

⁴<http://healpix.sourceforge.net>

final SCOTCH catalog in §4.8.

We use the `GRCatalogs`⁵ analysis tool [327] to select CosmoDC2 galaxies within 31 neighbouring HEALPixels from an $N_{\text{side}} = 32$ pixelisation, corresponding to 104 square degrees of total area. The selected HEALPixels are chosen to completely overlap with the DC2 image catalogs [308], which contain image properties for CosmoDC2 galaxies as LSST would observe them over 5 years, corresponding to a co-add depth of $r = 28$ (where r is the apparent AB magnitude in the LSST filter). The overlap in coverage between these HEALPixels and the image catalog is shown in Fig. 4.2. To ensure the generality of our final catalog, the sky coverage displayed in the figure is not maintained in SCOTCH (we discuss this in additional detail in §4.4).

Figure 4.2: Selected HEALPixels from CosmoDC2 (diamonds) overlaid on the grayscale footprint of the DC2 image catalogs. We cross-match CosmoDC2 and the DC2 image catalogs for the image properties of extragalactic objects.

Within these HEALPixels, we select CosmoDC2 galaxies with $r < 28$, which removes the majority

⁵<https://github.com/LSSTDESC/gcr-catalogs>

of galaxies that were not detected within the DC2 5-year image co-add catalogs. We further refine this sample by removing objects with unreported image properties. After this cut, $\sim 98\%$ of galaxies have an average r -band surface brightness within the half-light radius of less than 26 mag/arcsec^2 . This selection yields a sample of ~ 40 million galaxies, which represent a realistic magnitude-limited galaxy sample. In Section 4.5, we describe the process of selecting galaxies that match observed properties of transient hosts; this further reduces the sample to ~ 10 million galaxies.

The GHOST Catalog of Transient-Host Galaxies

The GHOST catalog [164] consists of $\sim 16,500$ archival SNe consolidated from the Transient Name Server (TNS) and the Open SN Catalog (OSC), as well as the observed properties of their host-galaxies from the first data release of Pan-STARRS (PS1; [84]). Host galaxies within the catalog were identified and validated through a combination of the established Directional-Light Radius method [DLR; 199] and the Gradient Ascent method [164]. Although this GHOST sample contains realistic statistical correlations between transients and their host galaxies, it does not contain a representative sample of events anticipated from upcoming surveys. First, the catalog comprises a small number of low-redshift ($z < 0.2$) explosions. LSST will dramatically enhance our current discovery rate for luminous SNe, motivating the need to scale the sample sizes in the GHOST catalog for every class. Further, GHOST does not include non-SN transients such as Tidal Disruption Events (TDEs) and Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN), classes whose discovery and characterization are key science drivers for LSST. Finally, because the catalog contains only the photometric properties of SN host galaxies, it lacks an explicit correlation between a transient and the stellar-mass and star formation rate of its host galaxy.

The CosmoDC2 catalog provides photometry in LSST ($ugrizY$) and SDSS ($griz$) filters, while GHOST galaxy photometry is provided only in the PS1 ($grizy$) filter system. To accurately match galaxy photometry between these catalogs, we convert the GHOST photometry from the PS1 to the SDSS system. We use the approximate quadratic conversions defined in Tonry et al. [487] and k -correct the apparent magnitude in each band using the analytic approximations⁶ described in Chilingarian et al. [97] and Chilingarian et al. [96], which were computed according to the SEDs of simple stellar populations ranging from 25 Myr to 16.5 Gyr and $-2.5 < [Fe/H] < +1.0$ dex fit to 170,533 galaxies within SDSS Data Release 7. This transformation allows us to accurately match GHOST galaxies to those in CosmoDC2. Next, we use the spectroscopic redshift of each galaxy’s associated transient (or the spectroscopic redshift of the host, if the former was unreported on TNS) to calculate the absolute rest-frame brightness of each galaxy in SDSS passbands. We use these to compute rest-frame $g - r$, $r - i$, and $i - z$ colors. To ensure that only galaxies with high-SNR photometry are considered, we apply stringent quality cuts to the galaxies in the GHOST sample based on the values of the PS1 `primaryDetection` and `objInfoFlag` flags, as well as the `InfoFlag1`,

⁶<http://kcor.sai.msu.ru/getthecode/#python>

InfoFlag2, and InfoFlag3 values in each band.⁷ While this may limit our observed sample to only low-redshift events, it ensures that the photometric correlations we encode from this regime are accurate. Our final sample after these cuts consists of 8,800 SN host galaxies.

4.4 Generating Transients with the SNANA Simulation

The SNANA Framework for Generating Transients

Our methodology is shaped by the existing framework of the SNANA simulation code [265]. Therefore, although the use of SNANA constitutes the final stage of our pipeline as displayed in Fig. 4.1, we first describe the SNANA simulation and introduce the simulation-specific terminology before detailing our methods for host galaxy association. This simulation reads user-defined transient model SEDs (rest-frame), redshift-dependent rates, and realistic observing conditions, and outputs transient events with realistic light curves and spatial distributions as a function of redshift. The SNANA simulation was used to generate nine distinct classes of extragalactic transients for PLAsTiCC; Figure 1 from Kessler et al. [263] shows example output light curves in *ugrizY* bands from each model. In this work, we distinguish SNe Ib from SNe Ic and SNe IIn from SNe II to simulate 11 classes: AGN, KN, TDE, SLSN-I, SN Ib, SN Ic, SN II, SN IIn, SN Iax, SN Ia-91bg, and SN Ia, with the addition of SN IIb and SN Ic-BL and with some updates to the PLAsTiCC models as described in §4.4. We implement a cosmology of $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, $w_0 = -1$, and $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$. We note that, while these values are slightly different from the *Planck* [386] parameters used in the Outer Rim simulation to generate the CosmoDC2 catalog, the small inconsistencies that this difference introduces are far sub-dominant to the shifts that we apply to galaxy redshifts in §4.5.

The transient models differ in the distributions of emission across bands, the shape of the light curves, and the peak brightness. For example, most of the SN Ib/c model flux is emitted at redder wavelengths; the KN model exhibits a characteristic timescale shorter than most other transients in our sample; and simulated SLSNe-I emit significantly higher flux than the other models.

The SNANA simulation includes the option of associating each simulated transient to a host galaxy from a user-input catalog (the *host library* or ‘HOSTLIB’) that includes redshift and other galaxy properties (§4.5). After each transient is simulated, the algorithm selects a HOSTLIB galaxy that lies within δz of the transient. We set δz to correspond approximately to 100 comoving Mpc, which ranges from 0.02 at $z \sim 0$ to 0.1 at $z = 3$ given the 2018 cosmological parameters from the Planck satellite [386]. Host galaxy selection is further influenced by a user-input *weight map* (WGTMAP) that defines the probability of selecting a galaxy as a function of its properties (§4.6). The WGTMAP framework is flexible, such that the probability can depend on different galaxy properties for different classes—in other words, the parameter space over which the WGTMAP probabilities are defined is not fixed but rather user-defined.

⁷A full list of the imposed quality cuts can be found at the GitHub repository for this work.

Table 4.1: Summary of the HOSTLIB, WGTMAP, and cadence used for each transient class in our simulation. The first three HOSTLIBs contain CosmoDC2 galaxies that extrapolate distributions of observed hosts in GHOST; the fourth is a representative sample from CosmoDC2. P_{class} refers to the probability of each transient class occurring given the properties of a galaxy; these functions are defined in §4.6 and implemented via the WGTMAPs. The cadence refers to the time interval between light curve samples in the simulation.

HOSTLIB	WGTMAP	Class	Cadence (Days)
SN Ia Hosts	P_{Ia}	SN Ia	2.0
SN II Hosts	P_{II}	SN II/IIn/IIP/IIL	2.0
H-Poor SN Hosts	P_{Ibc}	SN Ib/Ic	2.0
	$R_{\text{Ic-BL}}$	SN Ic-BL	2.0
	P_{SLSNI}	SLSN-I	2.0
	P_{II}	SN IIb	2.0
Rand. DC2 Subset	P_{AGN}	AGN	0.1, 2.0
	R_{KN}	KN	0.1–2.0
	P_{TDE}	TDE	0.1–2.0

Following Fig. 4.1, the simulation begins by generating a transient SED and drawing a redshift according to the class-specific rate model. The rate models are detailed in § 4.4 and are entirely responsible for the redshift distributions of events in the final catalog. This may be counterintuitive, as one might expect that the features of the synthetic host galaxy population should determine the transient event rates; however, myriad uncertainties in the transient-host connections make such an approach far more challenging to match observed event rates at low redshifts.

Next, the transient is matched to a host galaxy. The surface brightness profile of each galaxy in cosmoDC2 is a weighted combination of two Sersic profiles: that of an exponential disk (n_0), and that of a deVaucouleurs bulge (n_1). For each galaxy associated with a supernova, one of these profiles is selected using their relative weights. Next, a radius and azimuthal angle are selected (where the radius selection is weighted by the Sersic profile), and this determines the position of the transient with respect to the host center. We further encode simple models for the radial offsets of TDEs, AGN, and KNe as described in § 4.7.

After the transient offset is computed, the host galaxy redshift is set to the redshift of the transient and the host’s apparent magnitudes are updated to reflect the small change in distance (100 comoving Mpc

or less). With this framework, one host galaxy from the HOSTLIB can be used multiple times, which is often necessary given the desired number of transients (5M) that we aim to simulate, the similar size of the HOSTLIBs, and the different redshift distributions for the transient model and the HOSTLIBs. In such a case, the single input galaxy is mapped to multiple host galaxies with slightly different redshifts and apparent magnitudes in the final catalog. Due to this duplication, it is necessary to remove on-sky position information from the galaxies such that duplicated galaxies do not appear at the same sky location. Unfortunately, this loses the initial positioning within realistic large-scale structure from CosmoDC2. We leave an accurate embedding of transients within the cosmic web to future work. In our simulation, the host centers are arbitrarily set to be simulated at (RA,Dec)=(0,0) and positions are not reported in the final catalog.

The transient SED is modified for cosmic expansion, weak lensing magnification, redshift, and host galaxy extinction. The weak lensing model aims to statistically match the average magnification effects as a function of redshift; Kessler et al. [263] describes the model in further detail. We do not explicitly model host extinction from each galaxy’s morphology; rather, we follow the statistical treatment in PLAsTiCC [263]. For the theoretical models (MOSFIT and KNe), extinction is parameterized by A_V . For most models, this parameter is drawn from a Galactic Line-of-Sight distribution with a Gaussian core of $\sigma = 0.1$ and an exponential tail parameterized by $\tau = 0.4$ [427, 43]. Dimming is then computed assuming the Milky Way color law from Fitzpatrick [139]. For TDEs, only the exponential is included in order to simulate significantly higher extinction near the host galaxy centers where these transients occur. For KNe experiencing less host extinction at large offsets (see § 4.7), the exponential tail is reduced by a factor of two. The other transient models have been constructed from observed photometry, which implicitly includes the effects of host-galaxy extinction. This formalism assumes no evolution in dust properties with redshift.

The final SED corresponds to what an observation would look like from a vantage point just outside the Milky Way, without Galactic extinction, because we have not simulated transient locations on the sky. This leaves flexibility for the user to place events within the sky footprint of a preferred survey and apply the corresponding line-of-sight extinction and noise models. Next, the SED is converted to an apparent magnitude in the LSST photometric system ($ugrizY$). We configure SNANA to report all light curves in true LSST magnitudes without applying any threshold for detection. Therefore, very faint magnitudes are included in the transient light curves. Because hosts *are* restricted to $r < 28$, catalog users are encouraged to apply a limiting magnitude equal to or brighter than $r = 28$ to the full catalog to create consistency before use.

We sample most of our simulated light curves from 100 days preceding peak light to 100 days after peak. Due to the rapid rise and decline of KN photometry, we sample the light curve for only 10 days pre-peak and 60 days after-peak. For each transient class, we implement one of three cadence strategies. For SNe Ia, CCSNe (II, IIn, IIP, and IIL), and H-poor SNe (Ib/c, Ic-BL, Iib, SLSN-I), we adopt a sampling of $\delta t = 2.0$ days (so that each light curve has 100 observations each in $ugrizY$). Because of the rarity of high-cadence KN and TDE observations, we aim to preserve as much physical information about these light curves as

Figure 4.3: Left: Number of cumulative observations for the variable-cadence ($0.1d \leq \delta t \leq 2.0d$) light curve sampling method for KNe (turquoise), shown alongside the $\delta t = 0.1d$ (red) and the $\delta t = 2.0d$ (yellow) cadences. The function describing the variable-cadence sampling rate is asymmetric in time to mimic the rapid rise and slow decay of transient phenomena. Right: Sample light curves for events using these cadences. Colors indicate the sampling method used.

possible while keeping file sizes manageable. For these events, we adopt a logarithmic sampling scheme, with $\delta t = 0.1d$ at peak and increasing toward $\delta t = 2.0d$ in either temporal direction. Because the rise of many transient light curves occurs on significantly shorter timescales than a decline powered by emission from radioactive decay, our cadence increases more slowly from peak light to late times than from peak light to pre-explosion epochs (Fig. 4.3). This sampling scheme generates ~ 260 observations per pass-band. The rapidly-evolving stochasticity of AGN light curves cannot be accurately characterized by either of these cadences. For the AGN in our catalog, we provide light curves at cadences of both $\delta t = 0.1d$ (250 events) and $\delta t = 2.0d$ (2,250 events). The choice in light curve can be made by the user, depending on their science goals. We show the cumulative number of observations for our three light curve cadences, along with sample light curves, in Fig. 4.3.

In summary, the key features of the catalog are as follows: top-of-the-galaxy observing conditions, near-perfect transient observing efficiency, host galaxies as faint as $r = 28$ associated in a class-dependent manner, and physically-motivated transient-host separations. We provide an overview of the classes of transients generated in this work, the HOSTLIBs and WGTMAPs used to associate them with hosts, and the sampling method for each class, in Table 4.1.

For completeness, we also summarize here the list of major assumptions and approximations used to construct the SCOTCH catalog:

- **Representative correlations from observed samples:** Limited observational data exists for many of the transient classes we simulate. Nevertheless, we assume that each data set presents a representative sample of that class’s host population. With small sample sizes, this may cause host-transient correlations to be over-confidently inferred.

- **sGRBs and KNe occur in the same host galaxies:** Given the extremely low number of KNe detected to date, and the intense interest from the community in detecting additional events, we choose to include KNe in our simulation framework with host-galaxy properties determined by a sample of well-localized sGRBs (§ 4.6).
- **Galaxy populations have been shifted in redshift space:** We introduce redshift adjustments to host galaxies in several stages of the pipeline: when smoothing over unphysical tracks in color-redshift space in CosmoDC2 (see § 4.5) and when adjusting the host redshift to the transient redshift in SNANA. Thus, while the final host galaxy properties depend on redshift in a broadly similar way as in CosmoDC2, any realistic tight redshift dependencies that were encoded into the original simulation may be lost in SCOTCH.
- **No on-sky positions:** The hosts and their transients are not placed realistically on the sky, and thus the catalog lacks realistic large-scale structure.
- **Similar host-galaxy extinction parameters across cosmic time:** Dust parameters were determined from transient studies at low- z (primarily SNe Ia), and this work extends these properties to $z < 3$. Deep host-galaxy studies will further clarify the dust properties of host galaxies at higher redshifts, which can be used to simulate an evolution in dust properties in future work.
- **k-corrections linked to Simple Stellar Populations:** The k-correction equations used to calculate the rest-frame properties of host galaxies in GHOST [164] were computed by SED fits to SDSS galaxies assuming simple stellar populations. This is done to obviate the need for detailed SED fitting, which would be a valuable independent study but is outside the scope of this work.
- **No evolution in host-galaxy correlations:** We did not attempt to model any evolution of host-transient correlations with redshift, and therefore host populations at high- z in the catalog have similar distributions in intrinsic properties to hosts at low- z . Upcoming high- z surveys will shed more light on any potential evolution in host galaxy populations.
- **Malmquist-like bias:** The necessary $r < 28$ cut on synthetic galaxies causes the hosts at higher redshift to be drawn from an intrinsically brighter population.

Transient Models

We simulate each transient class with a similar setup as that of the PLAsTiCC challenge [see 263, hereafter K19, and references therein]. Unless otherwise noted, the event rate of each class follows the same redshift dependency as in PLAsTiCC. As detailed in K19, the redshift-dependent rates have been measured from existing observations, and thus become increasingly uncertain with redshift. We extrapolate the rates to

Figure 4.4: Light curves for the transient classes simulated in this work. Gray curves show a representative sample of events, and colored curves show one example event for each class. Due to the rapid rise of the kilonova model, few KN light curves feature emission at epochs prior to peak light.

$z = 3$ for SCOTCH, but caution that the rate functions are unlikely to be trustworthy at high redshifts. We are unable to simulate realistic *volumetric* rates with the framework described, as our ideal ‘observing’ conditions and wide redshift range would generate a prohibitively large catalog. Instead, we choose to simulate 5 million events and divide the sample by class based on anticipated interest to users. Table 4.2 displays the number of light curves and model used per class. The sky density of events at any given redshift, and the relative rates of different classes, are therefore inaccurate. Nevertheless, the volumetric rates predicted for each class by the respective rate model in K19 can be calculated using information in the supplementary material, Appendix B, and the corresponding functions provided in the GitHub repository for this work. This information can also be used to over- or under-sample the catalog as needed to generate realistic mock observations.

We simulate normal and peculiar SNe Ia using the same models used in K19. Additionally, the core-collapse SN models suffixed with NMF, Templates, and MOSFIT in Table 4.2 are identical to those detailed in K19. However, several features of our simulation are different from PLAsTiCC. We do not include the parametric SN Ibc MOSFiT model, which was part of PLAsTiCC, because its parameters were drawn from unrealistic flat distributions and the models produce unphysical light curves. We also add the recent core-collapse spectrophotometric templates from Vincenzi et al. [502], which are suffixed by HostXT_V19 in Table 4.2. The V19 models add realistic diversity to our core-collapse sample. The V19 models include templates for SNe I Ib and SNe Ic-BL, which are both new since PLAsTiCC. SNe Ic-BL are energetic Ic events observed with broad lines in their spectra, indicating enhanced absorption velocities of $\sim 15,000$ - $30,000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ [346]. Thus, the Ic-BL templates are distinguishable from the typical Ic model primarily through spectroscopy. As we only simulate photometric light curves for SCOTCH, the only relevant difference from SNe Ic is that SN Ic-BL light curves are brighter.

Table 4.2: Simulated transients in the SCOTCH catalog organized by class and model name. N , the number of transients simulated per class, sums to 5 million.

Class	Model Name	N
Ia (2.2M total)	SALT2-Ia	2M
	Iax	100,000
	91bg-like	100,000
H-Rich Core-Collapse (1,999,000 total)		
SN II (1.9M total)	SNII-Templates	633,000
	SNII-NMF	633,000
	SNII+HostXT_V19	633,000
SN II _n (100,000 total)	SNII _n -MOSFiT	50,000
	SNII _n +HostXT_V19	50,000
Stripped Envelope / H-Poor Core-Collapse (500,000 total)		
Ib (100,000 total)	SNIb-Templates	50,000
	SNIb+HostXT_V19	50,000
Ic (100,000 total)	SNIc-Templates	50,000
	SNIc+HostXT_V19	50,000
IcBL	SNIcBL+HostXT_V19	100,000
Iib	SNIIb+HostXT_V19	100,000
SLSN-I	SLSN-I-MOSFiT	100,000
Non-SN Transients (301,000 total)		
KN (100,000 total)	Kasen 2017	50,000
	Bulla 2019	50,000
TDE	TDE_MOSFiT	101,000
AGN	AGN-LSST	100,000

The SLSN I, TDE, and AGN models are similar to those in K19, the only difference being that we impose an upper redshift limit of $z = 3$ to match the limit of CosmoDC2 galaxies within the HOSTLIBs.

PLAsTiCC included a set of kilonova SED models from Kasen et al. [252]. In this work, we incorporate the Kasen model as well as an SED model by Bulla [62]. Both approaches parametrize the rapidly decompressing ejecta from the merger of two neutron stars that are heated by radioactivity from r-process

nucleosynthesis. The Bulla [62] model⁸ is parameterized by the mass of the ejecta, the half-opening angle of its lanthanide-rich component, and the angle between the line of sight and the plane of merger. The Kasen et al. [252] models consider the SED parameterized by the ejecta mass, the lanthanide fraction, and the ejecta velocity, without an observing angle dependence. In general, larger values of the ejecta mass lead to brighter events, while increasing the lanthanide fraction leads to redder, longer-lived kilonovae. Both models are grid-based, i.e., an SED given on a grid of discrete model parameters. Recently, Chatterjee et al. [89] incorporated the Bulla model into SNANA, and used both these kilonova models to create a classifier to filter kilonovae from other astrophysical transients using photometric and contextual information available from gravitational wave data products. The SED data for both the models are publicly available as part of the SNANA package.⁹

We present the distribution of light curves for a representative sample of each simulated transient class in Fig. 4.4. We further present the volumetric rate evolution of transients within the catalog, re-scaled to the match the model predictions using the values in Table B1, in Fig. 4.5. The re-scaling is necessary because the total event numbers in SCOTCH (Table 4.2) are arbitrary. For comparison, we show the observed volumetric rates for SNe Ia from Rodney et al. [412] and CCSNe from Strolger et al. [473]. We find agreement with the observed volumetric rates, with the deviations dominated by the theoretical fits to the data and not limitations in the simulation pipeline.

4.5 Host Library Creation (HOSTLIB)

Overview

Our first step to realistically associate transients with hosts is to create HOSTLIBs from CosmoDC2 galaxies. In previous work, including Vincenzi et al. [503], HOSTLIBs were constructed of representative field galaxies and correlations with transient class were implemented solely via the WGTMAP schema. However, WGTMAPs that depend on more than a few host properties N are prohibitively memory-intensive and computationally slow, as the SNANA code requires weights to be defined over an evenly-spaced grid across the full N -dimensional parameter space. To incorporate additional galaxy properties in our transient-host association, we generate *tailored* HOSTLIBs for different transient categories containing correlations in host galaxy color and magnitude.

Accounting for CosmoDC2 Artifacts with PZFlow

The distribution of CosmoDC2 galaxies in color-redshift space contains non-physical structure that worsens at higher redshifts. The problem is caused by a mismatch between the color ranges in different compo-

⁸We consider the two-component model here; “BULLA-BNS-M2-2COMP” in the SNANA package data.

⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4728252>

Figure 4.5: Re-scaled volumetric rates in the SCOTCH catalog as a function of redshift for multiple transient classes. The true catalog rates (with the same redshift evolution but arbitrary total event numbers) have been re-scaled to match the predicted volumetric rates given the input model. Stars correspond to observed volumetric rates for SNe Ia and core-collapse SNe, with statistical and systematic uncertainties plotted.

Figure 4.6: **Top:** Observed $g - r$ color versus redshift for galaxies within the CosmoDC2 synthetic sky catalog [282]. Discrete tracks visible in this space are an artifact of the limited number of SED models used to generate the derived properties of these galaxies. **Bottom:** The same $g - r$ values plotted against redshifts drawn from a probability density function estimated using a normalizing flow [109]. There is a one-to-one mapping between the galaxies in the top and bottom image; each galaxy’s redshift is slightly shifted, which smears out many of the non-physical tracks.

Figure 4.7: **Left:** Difference between PZFlow-sampled redshift and original CosmoDC2 redshift as a function of CosmoDC2 redshift for each galaxy in the sample. Shifts are minimal, and the discrete paths at top left and bottom right reflect the bounds of $[0, 3]$ imposed in generating PZFlow samples. **Middle:** Histogram of fractional differences in galaxy redshift before and after the PZFlow-oversampling stage. **Right:** Histogram of fractional differences in absolute magnitude propagated from the PZFlow-shifted redshifts.

nents of the hybrid catalog production pipeline for CosmoDC2 [282], and manifests as discrete ‘tracks’ in color-redshift space across the full redshift range (upper panel of Fig. 4.6). These artifacts limit our ability to test upcoming machine-learning based photometric redshift estimators. Along each track, the dispersion about the color-redshift relation is unrealistically low. Photometric redshift and classification algorithms trained using these data are likely to achieve unrealistically accurate results. As photo- z estimation is an important component of upcoming large-sky transient and galaxy surveys, we mitigate this effect by smearing the streaky color-redshift relationship for selected CosmoDC2 galaxies.

We use the code PZFlow¹⁰ [109] to realistically shift galaxy redshifts and smear the color-redshift tracks. PZFlow uses normalizing flows [241] to efficiently model a multi-dimensional probability density function (PDF). The normalizing flow learns a bijection, a function which maps the PDF to a tractable latent distribution (such as a uniform distribution) in which we can easily sample points and calculate densities. We train a normalizing flow to model the conditional PDF $p(z|\mathbf{m}, M_*, \text{SFR})$, where \mathbf{m} is a vector of LSST $ugrizY$ apparent magnitudes. The latent distribution for the flow is uniform over the range $[-5, 5]$. The bijection consists of two layers: the first layer shifts the redshift range $[0, 3]$ into the range of the latent uniform distribution, $[-5, 5]$; the second layer is a Rational-Quadratic Neural Spline Coupling layer [RQ-NSC; 128], which transforms the redshift distribution into a uniform distribution. The RQ-NSC performs this transformation using splines parameterized by a set of knots. The number of spline knots, K , can be chosen to increase or decrease the resolution of information captured by the flow. We choose a low value of $K = 2$ so that the flow does not learn the discrete tracks in the CosmoDC2 color-redshift space, and instead smooths over them.

We train the normalizing flow on the 40M $r < 28$ CosmoDC2 galaxies for 30 epochs using maximum likelihood estimation. Then, for each galaxy, we sample a new redshift z_{PZFlow} from the normalizing flow. These new redshifts are consistent with the galaxies’ photometry, stellar masses, and star formation rates,

¹⁰<https://github.com/jfcrenshaw/pzflow>

but are slightly perturbed from their original values (see left and middle panels of Fig. 4.7). For 92% of the galaxies, the change in redshift is $\delta z < 0.1$. While 8% of redshifts have more substantial perturbations, we stress that each perturbed redshift is consistent with that galaxy’s observed and derived properties. It should not be surprising that, for some galaxies, a substantially different redshift remains consistent with its other properties [428], particularly if the original distribution contained discrete artifacts.

We next adjust each galaxy’s absolute magnitude to retain the same apparent magnitude given its shifted luminosity distance. The right panel of Fig. 4.7 shows the size of these adjustments. For 93% of galaxies, the absolute magnitude change is $\delta M < 0.2$. We expect the small magnitude perturbations to lie within the realistic scatter of galaxy properties.

We have perturbed the galaxy redshifts with the goal of removing the discrete tracks in color-redshift space that would lead to overly-optimistic photo- z estimates. We present the original and re-sampled redshift distributions in the upper and lower panels of Fig. 4.6, respectively, in which only a fraction of the tracks remain (and these are primarily at very high redshift).

After applying PZFlow, we perform an additional cut to clean the CosmoDC2 rest-frame color distribution. We limit our sample to galaxies with $-0.18 < i - z < 0.5$, which maintains the vast majority of the CosmoDC2 color distribution but removes two unrealistic clumps that were visible on the red and blue extremes after re-sampling.

Selecting a CosmoDC2 Subsample

Ideally, we would sample directly from the CosmoDC2 galaxies, with our selection informed by real data, to populate a catalog of synthetic host galaxies for each transient class. Although the GHOST dataset includes many SN classes, for most classes (e.g., SNe IIn, Ic-BL, and I Ib) the sample size is too small to contain representative information. To combat this issue, before matching we group the hosts of archival GHOST SNe into three broader categories:

1. 6,284 hosts of Type Ia SNe.
2. 1,973 hosts of core-collapse SNe with hydrogen lines in their spectra, including those classified as Type II, IIn, and IIP.
3. 443 hosts of hydrogen-poor SNe, including stripped-envelope core-collapse SNe and hydrogen-poor superluminous SNe (SLSNe-I).

For each group, we select a many-times larger sample of synthetic CosmoDC2 galaxies that approximates the distribution in GHOST galaxy properties while extending to higher redshifts. We construct a HOSTLIB for each of these 3 broad categories.

With insufficient high- z data to model any cosmic evolution of transient-host correlations, a reasonable approach to high-redshift HOSTLIB sampling is to find high- z CosmoDC2 galaxies with similar intrinsic

Figure 4.8: Illustration of CosmoDC2 sampling for HOSTLIB generation. **Left:** We identify GHOST galaxies which hosted transients belonging to a particular category (the three categories are defined in the text). The GHOST sample is observationally biased toward low-redshift, but we assume the rest-frame properties (like color, shown on the y axis) are representative of the true full sample of hosts. **Right:** For every GHOST galaxy, we select k synthetic galaxies from CosmoDC2 nearby in rest-frame color, brightness, and redshift (with small d_{ANNOY} values; see Appendix A from the supplementary materials for details) but extending to $z = 3$. For simplicity, the diagram shows $k = 2$ and a 2-dimensional parameter space; in practice, however, $k = 800 - 18,000$ and 5 parameters are used for matching.

properties as low- z galaxies; e.g., rest-frame absolute magnitudes, rest-frame colors, and morphology. This approach ignores the possible evolution of transient-host correlations over cosmic time.

We employ a nearest-neighbour (NN) technique, illustrated in Fig. 4.8, to achieve this matching. NN algorithms deteriorate in high-dimensional space due to decreased data density (the so-called ‘curse of dimensionality’), so we select a small number of galaxy properties that most strongly correlate with transient properties. We train our NN matching on absolute rest-frame r - and i -band magnitudes, rest-frame $g - r$ and $i - z$ colors, and the PZFlow-shifted redshifts. This combination of properties incorporates information from all $griz$ bands (u and y being unavailable after converting GHOST data to SDSS filters) without redundancy. Although a similar matching could be achieved by simply using the $griz$ magnitudes and allowing color to be implicitly included, doing so would down-weight the importance of color. We choose to explicitly make two of the four dimensions colors, with an even weighting as the magnitudes, because color correlates strongly with a galaxy’s star-formation rate, and consequently the rate of core-collapse SNe; while brightness correlates strongly with stellar mass, and consequently the rate of SNe Ia and SNe II (see § 4.6). We manually down-weight redshift with respect to the colors and magnitudes to allow for neighbour match-

ing across a wide range of redshifts. We considered also matching on morphological information such as galaxy radius and ellipticity, but found the difference between observational and simulated estimates to be prohibitive given the necessary corrections to systematics in the GHOST data (e.g., deconvolving the PSF from ellipticity and radius measurements) and the strong redshift-dependent observational bias towards intrinsically large and face-on galaxies in targeted surveys.

Although exact NN algorithms (e.g., `scikit-learn`'s `KNeighbours`) are sufficient for samples of $N \sim 10^5$, they become increasingly slow when scaling up to $\sim 10^7$ galaxies. Instead, we make use of a rapid approximate NN method called ANNOY, which leverages Locality-Sensitive Hashing [LSH; 113], to rapidly cross-match datasets in parallel. We provide additional information on our use of this method in Appendix A in the supplementary materials accompanying this work, available online. We select k neighbours in CosmoDC2 with low Euclidean distance (d_{ANNOY}) to each GHOST galaxy. Rather than impose a limit on d_{ANNOY} , we set k to a value that produces several million matched CosmoDC2 galaxies. We then remove synthetic galaxies that were matched to multiple GHOST galaxies, creating HOSTLIBs with ~ 3 million objects each. This requires k to range from 800-18,000 across the three host categories.

Using this pipeline, we generate HOSTLIBs of CosmoDC2 galaxies matching the host-galaxy distributions in GHOST for the three groups of transient classes described above. We show the distribution of observed GHOST galaxies, a random subset of CosmoDC2 galaxies, and the final matched sample for the Hydrogen-poor host group in Fig 4.9. In addition to the three HOSTLIBs described above, we create a HOSTLIB consisting of galaxies randomly sampled from CosmoDC2 for transient classes not in the GHOST catalog. The host correlations for events using this unmatched HOSTLIB originate entirely from the transient-specific WGTMAP.

The CosmoDC2 simulation contains many ultra-faint galaxies that were injected into the simulation to account for its finite mass resolution [282]. These galaxies were not assigned properties as rigorously as the normal galaxies in the simulation; as a result, we exclude them from our HOSTLIBs. Our initial $r < 28$ cut on CosmoDC2, as well as the matching to GHOST galaxies (which are generally bright), remove many of these galaxies from our sample. We identify any remaining ultra-faint galaxies by their negative `halo_id` after HOSTLIB creation and cut them from the samples.

4.6 Transient-Host Galaxy Correlations (WGTMAP)

The GHOST database contains only basic photometric properties for SN host galaxies. Additional properties like masses and star formation rates, which can be estimated from galaxy imaging and/or spectra, are not reported in GHOST due to the lack of availability. Thus, the HOSTLIBs of CosmoDC2 galaxies matched to GHOST are realistically distributed in color and brightness, but only contain an implicit dependence on derived properties. There is motivation to fold in explicit dependence on mass and star formation rate: many studies have empirically verified this dependence for multiple transient classes (using smaller samples

Figure 4.9: A representation of how the GHOST-CosmoDC2 matching process produces a larger sample of GHOST-like galaxies from CosmoDC2. Each set of three panels (stacked vertically) show the same steps of the process which creates the H-poor host library. The left three plots show a magnitude-color distribution, the middle show color-color space, while the right show color vs. redshift. **Top:** the GHOST H-poor event host galaxies. **Center:** a random subset of CosmoDC2 galaxies. **Bottom:** nearest-neighbour galaxies selected from CosmoDC2 to match each GHOST galaxy in a multidimensional parameter space. The color bar, applying only to the bottom three plots, signifies the nearest-neighbour Euclidean distance and is truncated at 2 for visual purposes. Red points are CosmoDC2 galaxies that are far from their nearest GHOST neighbour. From the left and center plots, it is apparent that the limited color ranges in CosmoDC2 also limit the effectiveness of matching, as some GHOST galaxies lie beyond the available DC2 color extent. The right plots demonstrates how down-weighting redshift as a matched property allows us to select CosmoDC2 galaxies across a wide range (extending to $z = 3$, but only shown up to $z = 1$).

than GHOST) and found statistically significant differences between classes. To more precisely simulate these correlations, we construct a series of WGTMAPs that explicitly encode the class-specific dependence of host-transient association on a galaxy’s derived properties. These WGTMAPs enable us to fine-tune the host populations of the three matched HOSTLIBs and add in class-specific correlations for events whose hosts will be drawn from the unmatched, randomly-sampled HOSTLIB.

Each WGTMAP consists of a multidimensional grid of host properties, where values in the grid correspond to the probability of a galaxy with those properties being selected to host a given transient event in SNANA. The weightmap values can be scaled arbitrarily, so long as the *relative* weights between galaxies of different properties are preserved. When the SNANA simulation generates a transient at z , a sample of candidate host galaxies within δz are retrieved from the HOSTLIB. SNANA then assigns a corresponding weight to each potential host using the WGTMAP. The simulation creates a cumulative distribution function (CDF) for all galaxies, where the horizontal axis orders the galaxies arbitrarily, and the function is augmented by each galaxy’s weight. The CDF is normalized to have a maximum value of one. The simulation selects a ran-

dom number for the CDF vertical axis, and picks the corresponding galaxy along the horizontal axis, such that highly weighted galaxies have a higher CDF slope and are therefore more likely to be selected. Because the normalization is computed internally within SNANA, only the *proportionality* linking the probability P to the host galaxy parameters must be defined for the WGTMAPs.

We emphasize that the transient rate models, described in § 4.4 and extensively detailed in K19, are entered into the SNANA simulation *independently* of host properties. In other words, the final transient event rate in the simulation is not affected by the associated host galaxies. Transients are generated according to the rate function and the total number desired (Table 4.2), and only then assigned a host. The WGTMAP plays a role only in determining the relative likelihood of one host being selected over another.

The following subsections review the observations that motivate the WGTMAPs of each class. We caution that for several classes (TDEs, KNe, SNe Ic-BL, and SLSNe-I), the data statistics remain limited, and thus the resulting simulations may not capture the full diversity of host galaxies. Fig. 4.10 provides some intuition for the probability equations that follow by showing the SFR-mass distribution of hosts selected by SNANA from these equations for six classes.

SNe Ia

SN Ia explosions are thought to occur when a white dwarf accretes material from a companion star (which may also be degenerate) in a binary system, approaches the Chandrasekhar mass, and ignites in a runaway chain reaction of carbon fusion. SNe Ia occur more frequently in high-mass and highly star-forming galaxies [475, 457, 512]. Their light curves are parameterized in the SNANA simulation using the Spectral Adaptive Lightcurve Template (SALT2/SALT3) frameworks [202, 260].

The probability of SNe Ia as a function of galaxy properties can be written as the product of two components:

$$P_{\text{Ia}}(M_*, \text{SFR}, x_1) = P_{\text{Ia}}^{\text{KDE}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \times P_{\text{Ia}}^*(x_1, M_*) \quad (4.1)$$

where M_* is the host galaxy stellar mass, SFR is its star formation rate, and x_1 is the SALT2 stretch parameter of the SN light curve [202].

The first component of the probability, $P_{\text{Ia}}^{\text{KDE}}$, encodes a dependence on galaxy stellar mass and star formation rate. It has been constructed to replicate the distribution of 200 SN Ia host galaxies from the Dark Energy Survey Supernovae Program [456]. Using the `statsmodel` Python package, we perform kernel density estimation on the DES $\log(M_*)$ and $\log(\text{SFR})$ values to estimate a smooth probability density function in $\log(M_*)$ vs. $\log(\text{SFR})$ space. We use a Gaussian kernel for both parameters and determine the best-fit bandwidths from the KDE fit, finding 0.49 and 0.47 for $\log(M_*)$ and $\log(\text{SFR})$, respectively. Because $P_{\text{Ia}}^{\text{KDE}}$ is a non-parametric estimate for the probability density of observed events, it has no closed form.

The second component represents the anti-correlation between M_* and x_1 as shown in Fig. 4 of Smith

et al. [456]. Based on the fact that few events have been observed with $M_* < 10^{10}$ and negative x_1 , we implement the following model from Vincenzi et al. [503]:

$$P_{\text{Ia}}^*(x_1, M_*) \propto \begin{cases} e^{-x_1^2}, & \text{for } x_1 < 0 \text{ and } M_* < 10^{10} \\ 1, & \text{for } x_1 > 0 \text{ and } M_* < 10^{10} \\ 1, & \text{for } \forall x_1 \text{ and } M_* > 10^{10} \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

Peculiar SNe Ia

In addition to ‘normal’ SNe Ia, our simulated sample includes two classes of peculiar transients: SN2002cx-like SNe [SNe Iax; 145], which are underluminous and red at peak light relative to their Branch-normal counterparts; and SN1991bg-like SNe Ia, which are more rapidly evolving [136]. Although observed samples are small, there are indications that SNe Iax occur almost exclusively in late-type, star forming galaxies [239, 481] and SNe 91bg-like preferentially occur in early-type, passive galaxies [493, 205]. Accordingly, Vincenzi et al. [503] set the SN Iax probability to the SN Ia probability in active hosts and 0 in passive hosts; conversely, they define the SN 91bg-like probability as equal to the SN Ia probability in passive hosts and 0 in active hosts. We adopt a similar approach, and assume that the peculiar SNe Ia originate from similar progenitors as normal SNe Ia, but that their hosts represent opposite ends of a continuum in galaxy age and morphology. However, we exponentially taper the probability of SNe Iax in passive galaxies and 91bg-like events in star-forming galaxies. This is done in order to avoid encoding an unrealistically discrete boundary in our catalog, and to account for the possibility that a sub-population of these events does occur in hosts distinct from those previously discovered.

As in Sullivan et al. [475] and Vincenzi et al. [503], we define a threshold between active and passive galaxies at specific star formation rate (sSFR) values of $\log_{10}(\text{sSFR}/\text{Gyr}^{-1}) = -11.5$; active galaxies lie above this threshold and passive galaxies lie below it. For SNe Iax, our combined probability function adopts the normal SN Ia probability (without x_1 dependence) for active galaxies and tapers the probability below the passive/active threshold as follows:

$$P_{\text{Iax}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \propto \begin{cases} P_{\text{Ia}}(M_*, \text{SFR}), & \text{for } x_s \geq -11.5 \\ P_{\text{Ia}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \times e^{(x_s+11.5)}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

where $x_s = \log_{10}(\text{sSFR}/\text{Gyr}^{-1})$. The SN 91bg-like probability does the opposite, tapering the probability symmetrically above the passive/active threshold:

$$P_{\text{91bg}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \propto \begin{cases} P_{\text{Ia}}(M_*, \text{SFR}), & \text{for } x_s < -11.5 \\ P_{\text{Ia}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \times e^{-(x_s+11.5)}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.4)$$

Because P_{Ia} is *not* symmetric about x_s (it increases with galaxy mass and star formation), we note that this formalism results in a higher probability for 91bg-like events to occur in star-forming host galaxies than SNe Iax to occur in passive host galaxies. SCOTCH contains $\sim 0.1\%$ of SNe Iax in passive hosts and $>25\%$ of SNe 91bg-like in active hosts. This implementation is motivated by previous work [e.g., 205] showing a larger tail of 91bg-like hosts toward spiral-type morphologies than of SNe Iax toward elliptical galaxies.

Types II, Ib, and Ic Supernovae (SNe II, SNe Ib/c)

Type II, Type Ib, and Type Ic are three subclasses of core-collapse SNe. Type II events are characterized by strong Hydrogen emission lines, indicating that an outer Hydrogen shell was present in the progenitor star. Types Ib and Ic lack Hydrogen features, indicating that their outer shell was stripped from the progenitor star prior to explosion. Type Ic also lacks Helium features, indicating that the Helium envelope was also lost. Although SNe IIb are typically grouped with these ‘stripped-envelope’ events, they exhibit weak hydrogen features at early times. As the explosion progresses, the hydrogen emission quickly fades and the light curves begin to resemble those of SNe Ib. Because of their short-lived progenitor systems (typically <50 Myr), core-collapse explosions are predominantly observed in galaxies that are actively forming massive stars. The probability of these events occurring in passive galaxies, in contrast, is suppressed. Active and passive galaxies can be distinguished by their sSFR, defined as the star formation rate of the galaxy per unit of stellar mass.

The probability of these classes of core-collapse supernovae are set to [503]:

$$P_{\text{II}}(M_*, SFR) \propto \begin{cases} (M_*/M_\odot)^{0.16}, & \text{for } x_s \geq -11.5 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.5)$$

$$P_{\text{Ib/c}}(M_*, SFR) \propto \begin{cases} (M_*/M_\odot)^{0.36}, & \text{for } x_s \geq -11.5 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

Additionally, we distinguish the hosts of SNe Ic-BL events from the lower-energy class of SNe Ic explosions through the properties of their host galaxies. To do so, we embed a further correlation with host galaxy metallicity. Additional details concerning this correlation are described in Sec. 4.6.

Type Ic-BL Supernovae (SNe Ic-BL)

It is hypothesized that long-duration gamma ray bursts (IGRBs, lasting longer than ~ 2 seconds) are produced by relativistic jets originating in an SN explosion and interacting with surrounding circumstellar ma-

terial [417]. Broad-Lined SNe Ic (SNe Ic-BL) are the only SNe that have been unambiguously associated with IGRBs, and these explosions have been found to occur in galaxies of lower average metallicity than the less-energetic SNe Ic [345]. A thorough understanding of the host-galaxy correlations of SNe Ic-BL could permit a reconstruction of the physical conditions that give rise to relativistic jets in SNe. To simulate a distinction between SNe Ic and SNe Ic-BL hosts, the WGTMAP probabilities for both SNe Ic and SNe Ic-BL are constructed as the product of two terms. The first term embeds the preference for core-collapse events to occur in active galaxies, which is parameterized by equation 6. For the second term, we consider the metallicity of each galaxy and model the distribution of SN Ic and SN Ic-BL host galaxy metallicities as a set of logistic distributions:

$$P_{\text{Ic}}^{MZR} \propto f(9(Z - 8.9)) \quad (4.7)$$

$$P_{\text{IcBL}}^{MZR} \propto f(10(Z - 8.5)) \quad (4.8)$$

where Z is the metallicity of the galaxy measured as $\log_{10}(12 + O/H)$ and estimated using the modified Mass-Metallicity Relation (MZR) given by Eq. 2 in Mannucci et al. [325] (galaxy metallicity is not included in the CosmoDC2 catalog). The functions f are Gaussians which roughly reproduce both the probability density functions and the cumulative distributions of Ic and Ic-BL hosts shown in Fig. 5 of Modjaz et al. [345].

We note that the SN Ic and Ic-BL light curve models are photometrically similar, and therefore these classes provide a unique opportunity to test the value of host galaxy information in classification.

Type I Superluminous Supernovae (SLSNe-I)

Superluminous SNe (SLSNe) are unusually bright explosions potentially powered by exotic engines [e.g., pair instability or magnetar spin-down; 284, 364]. Type-I SLSNe are hydrogen-poor and have been found to occur predominantly in low-mass, metal-poor, and highly star-forming galaxies [311, 375, 438]. We model their rate based on the observations of ~ 50 SLSN-I hosts from Lunnan et al. [311], Perley et al. [375], and Schulze et al. [438]. All studies report SLSN-I hosts with specific star formation rates greater than 10^{-10} yr^{-1} ; thus, we model the SLSN-I probability to be exponentially suppressed below this threshold.

Based on the observed distribution of host galaxy masses and star formation rates, we further suppress the probability of events in galaxies that are both massive and highly star-forming:

$$P_{\text{SLSNI}} \propto \begin{cases} e^{(x_s+10)}, & \text{for } x_s < -10, x_M < 10 \text{ and } x_f < -0.5 \\ e^{-(x_M-3)}, & \text{for } x_M > 10 \text{ and } x_f > -0.5 \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4.9)$$

where $x_M = \log_{10}(M_*/M_\odot)$, $x_s = \log_{10}(\text{sSFR}/\text{Gyr}^{-1})$, and $x_f = \log_{10}(\text{SFR}/\text{Gyr}^{-1})$. We normalize these probabilities by eye such that hosts in the ‘otherwise’ category all have an equal probability of being selected, hosts beyond the defined boundaries are increasingly less likely to be selected, and the discontinuity at the boundaries is minimized.

Using Short-Duration Gamma-Ray Bursts as a Proxy for Kilonova Correlations

The discovery of gravitational-wave event GW170817 by the LIGO and Virgo collaborations, followed by short-duration ($\lesssim 2$ sec) Gamma-Ray Burst (sGRB) GRB170817A a few seconds later and the optical kilonova (KN) AT2017gfo several hours later, confirmed the association of these signals during a likely neutron star - neutron star merger [3, 2, 180]. The multi-band photometry of AT2017gfo, an event which took place in the nearby ($z \approx 0.00972$) galaxy NGC 4993, provided direct evidence for compact mergers as a site where r-process elements are forged [123]. Nevertheless, many questions remain. Although the color of the emission reveals information on the fraction of lanthanides and actinides produced from the neutron-rich ejecta, more events are needed to understand the relationship between an event’s emission and its precise nucleosynthetic yield. Further, the differences between KNe generated from the merging of a neutron star-black hole system and those originating in a neutron star-neutron star collision remain unknown. Though there have been no observations of KNe from a neutron star-black hole system yet, numerical simulations show differences between these types of KNe [256, 483, 442, 63]. The strength of the subsequent electromagnetic signal also encodes information regarding the neutron-star equation of state [35, 298, 399]. Because our knowledge of these systems starts and ends at this prototypical event, owing to the large sky localization area of gravitational wave observations – especially when events are observed only in some of the existing detectors – and the low intrinsic event rate, additional KN discoveries in upcoming surveys would vastly improve our understanding of these systems.

Because our aim is to improve the ability to accurately identify a diversity of KN events in upcoming survey streams, we do not want to limit our KN host-galaxy model solely to galaxies matching the properties of NGC 4993 (the host of AT2017gfo). Indeed, whereas NGC 4993 is a quiescent galaxy [297], sGRBs have been discovered in a variety of both star-forming and quiescent systems [392, 42]. Based on recent evidence that these signatures share a common astrophysical site [3], for this work, we assume that sGRBs and KNe inhabit host galaxies with similar properties. This assumption has the added benefit that GRBs are regularly observed across the full sky [114], and as a result we have amassed hundreds of GRB detections to date.

We begin constructing the KN WGTMAP by retrieving the positions of reasonably well-localized sGRBs (uncertainty radius $r_e < 0.01^\circ$ and $t_{90} \lesssim 2$ s) from the NASA Fermi GBM Burst catalog [504, 197, 505, 358] and from the GRB Host Studies catalog [433]. Next, we use the `astro_ghost`¹¹ software to identify the most-likely host galaxy associated with these events and retrieve photometric data from these galaxies. Whereas the original implementation of the package considered only northern-hemisphere galaxies within the Pan-STARRs source catalog [140], for this study we have extended the code to query the SkyMapper catalog [369] for southern-hemisphere sources as well. After visually verifying each association, we arrive at a sample of 11 sGRB-hosts, one of which is NGC 4993. Apparent *gri*-band magnitudes are reported for all hosts except two, which lack high-SNR brightness estimates in the *r* band. We then convert apparent magnitudes to absolute magnitudes. We adopt the galaxies’ spectroscopic redshifts as reported in the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database¹² where possible, and use a photo-*z* estimator¹³ for the galaxies without a reported redshift. We generate a kernel density estimate (KDE) to approximate the joint distribution of absolute magnitudes in *gri* for these hosts using the available data. From this KDE and using a Gaussian kernel, we determine best-fit bandwidths of 0.93, 0.62, and 0.57 for *gri*-band absolute magnitudes, respectively.

We then sample from this KDE along a uniformly-spaced grid spanning the apparent magnitudes of a random sample of CosmoDC2 galaxies. This sampling forms the basis of our KN WGTMAP.

To select hosts for our KN simulations, we initially applied this WGTMAP to the HOSTLIB of randomly-sampled cosmoDC2 galaxies. The resulting simulations exhibited an unrealistically small scatter in the host $r - i$ vs. $g - r$ colors. We identified this as a result of tight color correlations in the HOSTLIB coming from the cosmoDC2 color assignment, unrelated to the WGTMAP construction. To correct for this artifact, we shift the apparent magnitudes of cosmoDC2 galaxies in each LSST band by a random number less than or equal to the observational uncertainty in that band. This sample of magnitude-shifted cosmoDC2 galaxies is stored as a distinct HOSTLIB and used only for the KN class. The shifts are effective at smearing the tight color relationship. The KN WGTMAP is unchanged.

Active Galactic Nuclei

The emission from Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN) originates from black holes at the centers of host galaxies in one of various states of active accretion [315]. Multiple theoretical and observational studies have lent support for the co-evolution of supermassive black-holes and the galaxies they inhabit [131, 415], making these bright transients powerful probes both for galaxy formation and black-hole evolution across cosmic time [12]. Kauffmann et al. [255] found by analyzing a sample of 22,623 AGN within $z < 0.3$ that these transients occur predominantly in massive ($> 10^{10} M_\odot$) galaxies. The properties of an AGN, including its

¹¹<https://pypi.org/project/astro-ghost/>

¹²<https://ned.ipac.caltech.edu/>

¹³https://github.com/awe2/easy_photoz/tree/main

overall luminosity and the characteristic timescale of its optical variability, have also been linked to the luminosity and stellar mass of its host, respectively [210, 218, 67].

To simulate the properties of AGN host galaxies, we model the properties of 2,204 AGN hosts from Stemo et al. [468]. While not a volume-limited sample, the catalog provides publicly-available stellar masses and star-formation rates for AGN hosts from SEDs derived using *HST*, *Spitzer*, and *Chandra* data and spans $0.2 < z < 2.5$, nearly the same redshift range considered in this study.

As was done for SNe Ia, we model the joint probability distribution $P_{\text{AGN}}(M_*, \text{SFR})$ by performing kernel density estimation on the observed sample, using a Gaussian kernel for both parameters and the best-fit bandwidth of 0.18 for both parameters.

Tidal Disruption Events

In a Tidal Disruption Event (TDE), material from a star is stripped during close passage to a supermassive black hole [SMBH; 25, 474]. The stripped material circularizes into a debris disk around the SMBH and accretes onto it, resulting in a luminous flare spanning the electromagnetic spectrum. This occurs when the separation between the star and the SMBH falls within the tidal disruption radius of the star and, in some cases, the star is completely destroyed. Early detection and characterization of these events facilitates photometric and spectroscopic follow-up that illuminates the dynamic accretion physics of SMBHs across a range of mass scales [particularly for quiescent black holes; 133]. To date, however, only a few these events have been observed in detail. TDEs are found predominantly in post-starburst galaxies [159, 158], and these correlations can be incorporated into targeted searches in upcoming surveys [522]. We encode these correlations into a TDE WGTMAP by constructing the following functional approximation, which roughly reproduces the distribution of events as a function of host galaxy SFR and M_* as shown in Fig. 3 of French et al. [158].

$$P(M_*, \text{SFR}) \propto \begin{cases} e^{-x_f}, & \text{if } \text{SFR} \geq 10^{-9} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1} \\ & \text{and } M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot \\ e^{-x_M}, & \text{if } \text{SFR} < 10^{-9} M_* \text{yr}^{-1} \\ & \text{and } M_* \geq 10^{11} M_\odot \\ e^{-(x_f + x_M)}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (4.10)$$

We use the HOSTLIB of randomly-selected cosmoDC2 galaxies for this class.

Figure 4.10: Distribution of derived host-galaxy properties for six simulated classes of transients. Galaxies are colored by redshift (with red points for high-redshift galaxies). Marginal distributions are given at the top and right of each sub-plot. NGC 4993, the host of GW170817, is shown as the green diamond.

4.7 Offsets from the Host Center

Transient Offset Model and Validation

Within the SNANA simulation, we select the position of a transient relative to its host galaxy center by randomly sampling from a probability distribution defined by the galaxy’s surface brightness profile. This is motivated by prior studies that, averaging over class, SN surface density profiles roughly trace the surface brightness distribution of the spiral disks that host them [206]. Nevertheless, differences exist between the observed distributions of radial offsets for multiple transient classes. While we have aimed primarily at reproducing *global* transient-host galaxy correlations in this work, we also integrate a basic local model for three classes of transients: AGN, KNe, and TDEs. When post-processing SCOTCH to place events within a survey footprint, care should be taken to preserve the listed offsets.

Because AGN are nuclear transients by definition, we place them closer to their host centers than any

other class. AGN are placed within a radius that encompasses 10% of the total galaxy flux; within this radius, their distribution traces the surface brightness profile. We caution that AGN *have* been detected that are more offset relative to their galaxy centers, but these are rare [$<5\%$; 105] and may be traced back to specific merger events, which is challenging to model with our existing framework.

TDEs, typically discovered as the optical signal from the tidal interaction between a star and a central supermassive black hole, are placed at small offsets in our simulations. However, the recent discovery of a TDE from a candidate intermediate-mass black hole (IMBH) in the nucleus of a dwarf galaxy [18] suggests that future observations may reveal TDEs from IMBHs offset from the nucleus of massive hosts [see 41, for a discussion of wandering IMBHs]. To allow for this possibility, we model the TDE offsets slightly more broadly than AGN, with probability profiles truncated beyond the radius that encompasses 30% of the host galaxy flux.

Conversely to TDE and AGN, we place KNe at broad offsets: their positions are sampled from distributions in which the innermost 20% of a host galaxy is truncated. This is done to encode the prediction that natal kicks prior to explosion eject KNe from the inner regions of their host galaxies [186].

We present the offsets for AGN, KNe, TDEs, and SNe Ia in our catalog in Fig. 4.11, and compare the SNe Ia and TDE offsets to observed SNe from the Young Supernova Experiment (YSE) Data Release 1 [8] and the KN offsets to *Swift* satellite sGRB data [178] that was previously collected and analyzed in Fong et al. [146] and Pan et al. [371]. The qualitative differences in our simulation clearly follow our model prescription: AGN lie closest to their host nucleus, TDE are slightly more offset, KN are evacuated from the central region of the host, and SNe Ia (representative of the treatment for all SN classes) appear throughout the host galaxy with most within the inner few kpc. The observational data shows reasonable agreement to the simulations, despite the fact that our approach for offset prescriptions was approximate, and we did not explicitly aim to replicate observations. We leave a more detailed prescription for individual SN classes to future work.

Hostless Events

Some transient events are reported without a host in SCOTCH. This occurs when the distance of the transient from its host exceeds a particular threshold. After generating the position as described above, SNANA calculates the d_{DLR} , the angular separation from the transient and nucleus (in arcseconds) normalized by the DLR, which is a measure of the galaxy radius in the direction of the transient. If $d_{\text{DLR}} > 4$, the host is rejected to simulate the fact that a realistic survey would be unlikely to match that transient with its host (specifically, the rate of mismatch within $d_{\text{DLR}} < 4$ is expected to be small, $\sim 4\%$ according to [199]). Hostless events due to d_{DLR} rejection do not occur for TDE or AGN due to their inner-galaxy placement; for all other classes, the rate of hostless events is at the few-percent level ($\sim 3 - 8\%$).

In SCOTCH, these transients appear as hostless in the final catalog. A more realistic treatment would be to provide an incorrect host when another galaxy lies closer to the transient than the true host. However,

Figure 4.11: The cumulative distribution functions (CDF) for transient-nucleus offsets for several classes in SCOTCH only (top) and a SCOTCH comparison to observational data from YSE (middle) and Swift data (bottom). **Top:** qualitative differences in our treatment of several classes are visible; AGN and TDE are closest to the center of galaxies while SN Ia and KN are distributed further out. KN are not allowed to exist within the centers of galaxies to simulate the kick effect. Here, SCOTCH data is limited to the range $z < 0.25$, where most YSE data lies, to facilitate a comparison in the middle plot. **Middle:** SCOTCH TDE and SNIa CDFs are duplicated and YSE data is added. The simulated TDE fit the YSE data well; the simulated SNIa are distributed closer to the center than in YSE. **Bottom:** SCOTCH KN data is shown for $z < 1$ and are distributed somewhat further than the distribution of sGRBs from Swift data, which also extend to $z \sim 1$ [146].

because SCOTCH removes all on-sky position information for hosts, including galaxy neighbors as false hosts in this manner is infeasible.

4.8 Validation of Host Galaxy Correlations

To validate the SCOTCH catalog, we first confirm that the correlations described in §4.6 appear in the final sample as expected. Fig. 4.10 displays the SFR vs. M_* relationships for a representative sample of hosts associated with six transient classes. Each matches qualitative trends in host types: SN Ia hosts are massive and highly star-forming, SLSNe-I occur mainly in galaxies with high specific star formation rates (and trace the cosmic star formation rate), and SNe 91bg-like occur in passive, massive galaxies. The generated samples, which used WGTMAP probabilities from Vincenzi et al. [503], match the correlations therein, but extend to lower masses and star formation rates due to our use of CosmoDC2 versus their use of observed DES galaxies. To more directly compare the host-galaxy derived properties for each class, we plot the cumulative density functions (CDFs) for M_* and SFR in Fig. 4.12.

The CDFs show that, of all transients simulated in SCOTCH, TDEs are simulated in the lowest-mass host galaxies, followed by SLSNe-I. Simulated KNe are hosted by the highest-mass galaxies, followed by the host galaxies of stripped-envelope systems (particularly SNe Ic). The star formation rate CDFs indicate an overabundance of TDEs in galaxies of low star formation rate, which is consistent with observations of them in post-starburst galaxies. SNe 91bg-like events in our simulation occur on average in the galaxies with the lowest star formation rates, a feature of our exponential suppression in active galaxies for this class.

Figure 4.12: Cumulative density functions (CDFs) in host galaxy stellar mass (left), star formation rate (middle), and specific star formation rate (right) for a representative sample of transient classes in the catalog. Differences between transient classes reflect a combination of WGTMAP and HOSTLIB effects.

Simulated SNe Iax and KNe occur in galaxies with the highest average star formation rate. For SNe Iax, this reflects the exponential suppression of these events in passive hosts.

Consistent with the fact that we simulated nearly all core-collapse supernovae (besides SNe Ic-BL) with the same WGTMAP and HOSTLIB, the CDFs do not show any clear differences between the host galaxy SFR of different core-collapse subclasses. The exception is the Ic-BL class, which appears more often in the simulation in galaxies of low mean SFR due to the different implemented WGTMAP. We note that, in our models, we can distinguish between statistical samples of SNe Ic and SNe Ic-BL by the mass of their host galaxy, as SNe Ic-BL occur in lower-metallicity host galaxies [345] and therefore in lower-mass hosts on average. A detailed analysis of the typical observational uncertainties associated with these derived properties and how they might obfuscate these differences in observed data is beyond the scope of this study.

Fig. 4.13 shows the distributions of host colors within each class. Redder galaxies appear to the upper-right and bluer to the lower-left. We did not directly encode color correlations into the WGTMAPS for any of these classes; therefore, the differences between distributions stem from the initial GHOST matching in conjunction with the WGTMAPS in which transient probabilities are dependent on galaxy mass and star formation rate. We caution that we have not converted galaxy colors to the rest-frame for Fig. 4.13, and so the redshift-dependent rates for each class affect this comparison.

Qualitatively, the observed color plots display many of the intended comparative attributes. Simulated SLSN-I host galaxies are bluer than other SN hosts, reproducing observations that show that these events occur in highly star-forming galaxies [438]. SN 91bg-like host galaxies are redder than normal SN Ia, as intended. The KN hosts are surprisingly blue; given the broad redshift distribution of simulated events (Fig. 4.13), this may reflect the preference of observed sGRBs for late-type hosts [146]. As GW170817 (diamond in Fig. 4.13) occurred in a lenticular galaxy, its host galaxy is redder than the majority of the simulated sample. The simulated $g - r$ distribution for TDE host galaxies is broader than all others, which is consistent with observations [158]; however, the $i - z$ span may be unrealistically restricted.

Next, we quantitatively compare the colors of SNe Ia (including peculiar) hosts with the observed dis-

tributions reported in Hakobyan et al. [205, H20]. H20 examined $u - r$ colors (SDSS photometry) for a low-redshift sample and found statistically significant differences between the $\langle u - r \rangle$ of ‘normal’ SNe Ia, 91bg-type, and Iax-type host galaxies. The authors reported that galaxies hosting SNe Iax are bluer than normal, while SNe 91bg are redder than normal, with $\Delta\langle u - r \rangle \sim 0.4$ in each case. To investigate this trend in our own data, we calculate the average $u - r$ SDSS rest-frame color among 10,000 random members of the SCOTCH host sample for the same three classes. Although H20 examined hosts with $z < 0.04$, for the comparison we draw the SCOTCH host sample from the entire $z < 3$ redshift range because our simulation methodology treats high- z host selection equivalently to low- z . The results are shown in Table 4.3. Our average mean simulated host color values are significantly bluer than those of the H20 sample for two of the three classes. Our mean SN Iax host color is also bluer, but consistent within 2σ with the H20 observations. The blue trend may be a consequence of unrealistic galaxy colors in CosmoDC2, as demonstrated in Fig. 3 of Kovacs et al. [283]: the CosmoDC2 $u - g$ distribution is significantly bluer than observational data while $g - r$ is consistent with observations, suggesting that $u - r$ tends to be nonphysically blue. The color differences between the Ia classes in SCOTCH are in the same direction as the observed differences and are statistically significant. The magnitudes of the differences are somewhat mismatched from observations. Although qualitatively imperfect, the fact that SCOTCH reproduces the general trend in color differences between the SN Ia subtypes should enable catalog users to test algorithms which include host information for classification.

Table 4.3: A comparison of the mean rest-frame $u - r$ color of observed SN Ia host galaxies (all $z < 0.04$) in [205] (H20) with the simulated catalog (spanning all redshifts) presented here. Each reported uncertainty is the standard error of the mean. Δ -norm is the difference between $\langle u - r \rangle$ of the peculiar SN Ia sample and the normal sample. All simulated hosts are bluer than the observed hosts; SN Ia and SN Ia-91bg-like hosts are significantly bluer, while SN Iax are consistent within 2σ . The qualitative relationship between the classes (SN Iax hosts are bluer, SN 91bg-like hosts are redder) is similar.

	H20		This work	
	$\langle u - r \rangle$	Δ -norm	$\langle u - r \rangle$	Δ -norm
SN Ia (normal)	1.86 ± 0.03		1.372 ± 0.005	
SN Iax	1.47 ± 0.10	-0.39 ± 0.10	1.255 ± 0.006	-0.117 ± 0.008
SN Ia-91bg	2.23 ± 0.05	0.37 ± 0.06	1.908 ± 0.003	0.536 ± 0.007

We also aim to reproduce observed correlations between the photometric light curves of SNe Ia and their host galaxies. These have been extensively studied in the literature due to the use of these events as cosmological distance indicators. We present the SALT2 [202] fitted parameters x_1 and c (describing the stretch and color of an SN Ia light curve, respectively) as a function of the intrinsic properties of our associated hosts in Fig. 4.14. We find similar distributions to those presented in Childress et al. [95], including

Figure 4.13: Density distribution of observed colors for simulated transient classes (combining WGTMAP and HOSTLIB contributions). Marginal histograms are shown at top and at right of each sub-panel. The green diamond indicates NGC 4993, the host of the single kilonova observed. Overdensities near $g-r=0$ reflect remaining discrete tracks in CosmoDC2 galaxy distribution.

Figure 4.14: SALT2 [202] fitted parameters x_1 and c as a function of host galaxy M_* and sSFR. Our simulations reproduce the distribution of events observed in Childress et al. [95].

a mass-step at $10^{10} M_\odot$ (this has been explicitly encoded in our simulations, so its presence is not surprising), and weak anti-correlations between x_1 and both host galaxy M_* and sSFR. We observe a few SALT2 c values above $c=0.2$, and multiple are identified in Childress et al. [95]; although these are anomalous, our model their presence indicates that our correlation model is able to reproduce both the central distribution and the tails of the observed data.

We present SDSS-*griz* histograms of the absolute magnitudes of host galaxies associated with each transient in Fig. 4.15. GHOST data with $z > 0.05$ are shown for several classes with black histograms; the cut is motivated by the fact that SCOTCH has very few events below this redshift. The data reasonably fit the simulation. The impact of our encoded correlations is readily apparent by the variation in median and skew between distributions. However, we caution that the host magnitude differences between classes are not only due to encoded correlations, but also due to two important redshift-dependent effects within SCOTCH: the intrinsic rate of different transients across cosmological distances and the $r < 28$ magnitude cut imposed prior to matching in order to cross-match with the 5-yr DC2 image catalog. The confluence of these effects results in a Malmquist-like bias in the sample, with the distribution of host galaxies for a given class tending toward intrinsically brighter galaxies with increasing redshift (fainter hosts being unavailable to draw from the HOSTLIBs at those redshifts). For events occurring in galaxies ranging in brightness and observed only at low and intermediate redshifts (e.g., TDEs), we observe a realistic skew toward fainter galaxies that dominate the HOSTLIBs at these redshifts. For bright classes (e.g., SLSNe-I) and common ones spanning the full simulated redshift range (SNe II), the majority of events will be simulated at high-redshift where this bias is strongest. As a result, the histograms in Fig. 4.15 reveal a distribution for SNe Ia,

Figure 4.15: Distribution of host-galaxy absolute magnitudes for a representative sample of SCOTCH transients using both HOSTLIBs and WGTMAPs. Host galaxy photometry from the GHOST catalog for classes with statistical samples is shown as a black outline. Photometry is presented in the SDSS filter system.

SNe II, and SLSNe-I skewed toward bright hosts. This effect is especially visible when examining absolute magnitude as a function of redshift for both GHOST data and SCOTCH results (not shown): the distributions match well across the overlapping redshift range, but both the simulated and observed hosts taper rapidly from including a broad range of magnitudes at low- z to a tighter, brighter range of hosts as z increases.

We next compare the distributions of various properties of our final sample to GHOST to examine the combined effects of our two-step host selection process. Fig. 4.16 shows the galaxy color distribution for the hydrogen-poor event HOSTLIB (consisting of SN Ib, Ic, Iib, and SLSN host matches to GHOST) and the distribution of hosts selected by SNANA after WGTMAPS are applied. The WGTMAPS cause the overall $g - r$ distribution to become slightly bluer and more peaked than the GHOST data. Examining the colors for individual host classes reveals how the different WGTMAPS cause the distributions to stratify. The final SLSN-I host sample is bluer than the others, as encoded via SFR. The Ic hosts separate from the Ic-BL hosts in color space due to the implemented metallicity dependence. Overall, the final combined host grouping remains similar to observed data, but the individual host classes within that group are subtly different, demonstrating the combined power of the HOSTLIB + WGTMAP formalism.

To further demonstrate the utility of including both a HOSTLIB and WGTMAP in our simulation, we compare our final results for SN Ia host galaxies with (1) a sample simulated *only* using the GHOST-matched HOSTLIB and no WGTMAP, and (2) a sample simulated using a randomly-selected (unmatched) CosmoDC2 HOSTLIB and the SN Ia WGTMAP. Figure 4.17 demonstrates how the implementation of either a HOSTLIB *or* a WGTMAP results in reasonable distributions for some, but not other, host properties. Implementing both the HOSTLIB and WGTMAP leads to an improved match with data from both DES [456] and GHOST in multidimensional parameter space.

4.9 Catalog Access and Intended Use

The SCOTCH catalogs are presented in HDF5 format and can be accessed at <https://zenodo.org/record/6601211#.Ypjd6pDMLhM>. There are two separate catalogs, one for transients and one for hosts, which can be cross-matched to access the complete associated host-transient information. The properties of the transient and host catalog are listed in Tables 4.4 and 4.5, respectively. Each transient in the catalog is assigned a unique transient ID (TID) and each host a unique galaxy ID (GID), which are reported in both catalogs to enable cross-matching. If an event is unassociated using our pipeline, we populate the host properties with filler values (-999 for most properties, and 99 for photometry in each LSST passband).

We additionally provide the original dc2ID of each galaxy in the CosmoDC2 catalog, so that users can query the CosmoDC2 image simulations¹⁴ for additional properties. For example, although SCOTCH erases the realistic position information of host galaxies due to the necessary repeat use of HOSTLIB galax-

¹⁴CosmoDC2_v1.1.4_image at <https://data.lsstdesc.org/doc/cosmodc2>.

Figure 4.16: Histogram of $g - r$ color for synthetic Hydrogen-poor SN hosts before and after running the SNANA simulation. **Left:** The HOSTLIB of all H-poor (Ib/c, SLSN, Iib) hosts (gray), which was tailored to match the GHOST data (dashed line). The hosts selected after running the SNANA simulation for all H-poor classes with their respective WGTMAPs are shown in yellow. **Right:** SNANA-selected hosts of SLSN, Ic, and Ic-BL events. SLSN hosts are bluest, and Ic-BL hosts are bluer than the rest of the Ic class due to SFR and metallicity correlations. GHOST data are shown with a dashed outline, and we avoid plotting SNe Ic-BL hosts in GHOST due to the small sample size.

Figure 4.17: Simulated SN Ia hosts compared to observational data for simulations using either a HOSTLIB or a WGTMAP (left), and simulations using both (right). Marginal kernel density estimates are shown at top and at right in each panel. The HOSTLIB-only simulation (blue) decently reproduces the color-magnitude spread of SN Ia hosts in GHOST (upper left), although it is worse in $g - r$ than in M_r due to the CosmoDC2 color limitations. The blue points, however, are a poor match to DES data from Smith et al. [456] in SFR-stellar mass (SFR- M_*) space (lower left), especially in the SFR distribution. A random sampling of CosmoDC2 galaxies which is associated with SNANA transients via a realistic WGTMAP (yellow) yields more realistic SFR- M_* results but does worse in color-magnitude space. Notably, the yellow distribution in $g - r$ is in strong disagreement with GHOST. Simulations using both HOSTLIB and WGTMAP (green at right) result in decent matches to both data sets in both parameter spaces. In all plots, the redshift range is limited to $z < 0.85$ to enable fairer comparison with observational data. In the lower plots the simulations are further limited to $r < 23.8$, the $10\text{-}\sigma$ magnitude limit for the DES3YR sample, for optimal comparison.

ies (see §4.4), if a user is interested in the original position and large-scale environment of a galaxy, e.g. to check whether the galaxy was a cluster member, they may retrieve the relevant information from CosmoDC2. A user in need of host galaxy SED information may access the original CosmoDC2 SED, find the amount that the galaxy’s redshift has changed from CosmoDC2 to SCOTCH, and red- or blue-shift the SED accordingly. However, we warn that for *kilonova* hosts in particular, the magnitude and colors of SCOTCH hosts are *not* directly traceable to the CosmoDC2 native values, as the kilonova host galaxy magnitudes in SCOTCH have been shifted (§4.6).

With top-of-the-galaxy observing conditions, users aiming to simulate optical surveys with similar passbands to LSST have a straightforward path to forecasting survey data. The path would include converting the magnitudes accordingly, subselecting events according to expected survey densities, updating transient and host positions to span the survey footprint, and implementing Galactic extinction and atmospheric noise. The ideally-sampled light curves can be degraded by adding noise and by sub-sampling as needed. We provide a series of basic tutorials for querying the catalog and post-processing the data in Appendix B, available in the online supplementary materials.

Due to the increased volumes at higher redshifts in the universe and the fact that we simulate a fixed number of transient events per class, the full $z < 3$ catalog is sparsely populated at very low redshifts. Users wishing to access a larger amount of low- z data may alternatively make use of an additional z -limited catalog that we release. In this catalog, we restrict the maximum z to 0.8 for each transient class so that the same number of events N as the full catalog, as given in Table 4.2, are generated at lower redshifts. The $z < 3$ catalog is named SCOTCH_Z3 and the additional catalog is named SCOTCH_ZLIM.

For users wishing to simulate significantly different surveys, we also provide the HOSTLIBs and WGTMAPs at <https://zenodo.org/record/6601211#.Ypjd6pDMLhM> for re-running the SNANA simulation code.

Table 4.4: Summary of the transient information in the SCOTCH catalog.

Variable	Summary
TID	Transient ID
z	True Redshift (of host and transient)
GID	Host-galaxy ID
MJD	Array of Modified Julian Dates of light curve observations (only spacing is meaningful)
$m_{\langle \text{band} \rangle}$	Apparent brightness in LSST <i>ugrizY</i> bands (AB magnitudes)
Class	Transient class
Model	Simulation model from Table 4.2
Cadence	Time-spacing of light curve samples [days]
RA _{off}	Transient offset from host nucleus in R.A. ["]
ffi _{off}	Transient offset from host nucleus in Dec. ["]
Sep	Total great-circle distance between transient and host nucleus ["]

Table 4.5: Summary of the host galaxy information in the SCOTCH catalog. We note that the original CosmoDC2 catalog contains inaccurate ellipticities due to a bug; in SCOTCH, we report the corrected ellipticity and minor axis values following the corrections from https://github.com/LSSTDESC/gcr-catalogs/blob/ellipticity_bug_fix/GCRCatalogs/cosmodc2.py.

Variable	Summary
GID	Host-galaxy ID
TID	Transient ID
dc2ID	ID of corresponding CosmoDC2 galaxy
$m_{\langle \text{band} \rangle}$	Apparent AB magnitudes in LSST <i>ugrizY</i> bands
$\sigma_{m, \langle \text{band} \rangle}$	10-year estimated apparent AB magnitude errors for LSST
e	Shear ellipticity $(1 - q)/(1 + q)$, where q is the axis ratio
R_d	Disk half-light radius in physical kpc
R_s	Spheroid half-light radius in physical kpc
$\log(M_*)$	Log stellar mass [M_\odot]
$\log(SFR)$	Log star formation rate [M_\odot/yr]
n_i	Sersic index for $i=[0, 1]$; $n_0=1$ (exponential disk) and $n_1=4$ (deVaucouleurs bulge)
w_i	Weight of $i=[0, 1]$ Sersic components (bulge and disk)
a_i	Major-axis half-light size ["] for $i=[0, 1]$ Sersic components
b_i	Minor-axis half-light size ["] for $i=[0, 1]$ Sersic components
e_i	Ellipticity of $i=[0, 1]$ Sersic components
e_{tot}	Luminosity-weighted sum of bulge and disk ellipticities
a_{rot}	Rotation angle of major axis with respect to the +RA coordinate [$^\circ$]

4.10 Conclusions

We have presented our methodology for constructing the SCOTCH catalog, a dataset consisting of multiple classes of simulated transients and their host galaxies. The final catalog includes 5 million light curves for 10 distinct classes of supernovae and 3 additional transient classes, as well as the observed and derived properties of their host galaxies and physically-motivated offsets between the galaxy and transient positions. The cadence of these simulated light curves is class-specific in order to resolve rapidly-evolving features while limiting total data volumes. This catalog significantly advances the framework for simulating the time-domain sky initially constructed for PLAsTiCC, which included minimal host-galaxy information.

This catalog can be used for a broad range of scientific studies. First, teams developing transient classification algorithms for upcoming surveys can test the value of large samples of realistic host information. This added contextual information may help classify transients earlier in their light curves, facilitating rapid

follow-up of interesting objects. Host information can also increase the precision of classifications, of particular value for collecting large uncontaminated samples of Type Ia supernovae for precision dark energy measurements. However, users should take caution when training classifiers on this catalog, as overconfidence in the correlations represented therein could limit classifiers from finding transients in hosts not described by extant samples. We have not attempted to include any anomalies in the catalog to mitigate this problem. Additionally, this catalog is missing some known transient classes, and does not include any mock new classes of transients. Classifier trained for anomaly detection should be able to flag a totally unknown class of event in an upcoming survey, and this will be an important aspect of upcoming surveys.

Beyond classification, this catalog can be used to forecast future population-level studies of transients – e.g., for progenitor studies or cosmological applications – using upcoming survey data. Besides the LSST-specific passbands, the catalog is not tailored to fit the observational limitations of any particular survey. With empirically-derived transient rates extrapolated to $z=3$ and host galaxy magnitudes as faint as $r=28$, users can post-process the catalog to reflect the expected footprint, depth, and observational biases of planned surveys. The catalog can then be used to generate a proof-of-concept for science ideas, forecast results, estimate expected biases, and test new methods to mitigate them.

Although not the focus of this study, the validated correlations between simulated SNe Ia and their host galaxies are encouraging. Because we have linked the properties of observed SN Ia host galaxies to synthetic galaxies in CosmoDC2, myriad intrinsic host properties are available. The authors encourage future catalog users to evaluate the use of synthetic SNe Ia for cosmological analyses, and explore additional correlations between Hubble Residuals and the CosmoDC2 properties of host galaxies.

The realism of this simulated catalog is limited by approximations made during the simulation pipeline and the limitations of pre-existing transient-host galaxy catalogs. Here we re-emphasize several points and discuss opportunities for future improvements.

Generally, we allow the catalog to reflect the trends seen in the existing data, so that developers of classification algorithms can better incorporate host galaxy information where available. The classes with the sparsest currently available data will have the least accurate host property distributions. Thus the transient-host correlations learned by a classifier trained on SCOTCH may be revealed to be too strong, or even fully inaccurate, with future data influxes.

Future updates to the catalog should seek to augment the small samples with recent data. For example, the Transient Host Exchange [394] could be ingested into our simulation framework to incorporate additional data into the existing SCOTCH classes as well as expand to more classes. During the writing of this chapter, the first long-duration GRB (lGRB) was discovered with evidence for coincident kilonova emission [402]. This result underscores our limited understanding of these events. Should additional future events be discovered with joint lGRB-KN emission, upcoming iterations of host galaxy simulations should include the properties of lGRB host galaxies as possible KN sites. The authors will consider incorporating this in future SCOTCH releases given sufficient demand. Finally, while preparing this manuscript,

O’Connor et al. [366] also investigated a series of high-redshift ($z < 2$) sGRB host galaxies and found a potential increase in the number of hostless events with redshift. Given the small number of observed sGRBs considered in this study, additional work should be devoted to identifying and integrating correlations among high- z samples.

In addition, a major approximation in SCOTCH is that the hosts and transients are *not* distributed in a realistic large-scale-structure. Although the relative offsets between transients and their host galaxies are physically motivated, we have avoided placing these systems on the sky so that the catalog may be of general use for generating synthetic transient catalogs for both northern and southern hemisphere surveys by the user. Therefore, the SCOTCH catalog cannot be used to forecast cosmological applications of surveys that rely on realistic positions or velocities within the large-scale structure. Previous studies have found SNe to be highly clustered within the large-scale structure of the universe [490], so at the very least, retaining the locations of the synthetic SNe hosts within their simulated cosmic web environment would be a major improvement in realism. To retain large-scale structure information while matching empirically-determined transient rates, it is necessary to have very large HOSTLIBs. The current computational time required to read the large files into memory many times during the simulation is a bottleneck. In addition, retaining realistic position information would limit the sky area to the 440 sq. deg. currently simulated in CosmoDC2, which is less helpful for creating survey mocks. The future release of 5,000 sq. deg. of CosmoDC2 will present an opportunity for expansion, while other larger-volume synthetic galaxy catalogs could also be explored [e.g., Buzzard, 117].

Another possible extension of this work is to implement correlations between a transient and its location within a galaxy, as multiple studies have revealed local transient correlations (for example, with the amount of host-galaxy extinction for SNe Ia; see [220, 221, 387]). For some classes (e.g., TDEs), this local information may be more valuable in early classification than global host galaxy information [183].

In addition to these catalog-level corrections, our methods could be expanded to produce simulated images. This is a non-trivial issue because the transient image must be overlaid on the host galaxy image as well as surrounded by a realistic background which accurately reflects the galaxy density at the location in the simulation (which would require the preservation of large-scale structure information). Machine learning-based algorithms such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) have shown significant promise in generating galaxy images that are both survey-specific and realistic [163, 119, 64, among others], and conditional networks allow for the encoding of model-specific parameters in generated images [404]. A generative model conditioned on transient and host galaxy correlations, along with local galaxy density, could be used to rapidly generate realistic images for the systems in the SCOTCH sample. This framework would represent a significant milestone toward complete end-to-end validation of survey infrastructure.

4.11 Data Availability

The simulated data are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/6601211#.Ypjd6pDMLhM> [305]. All code used is publicly visible at <https://github.com/LSSTDESC/transient-host-sims>. Users are encouraged to report any catalog problems or bugs in the code via GitHub Issues or by e-mail to the authors. The supplementary materials to this work, available online, include a description of the nearest-neighbors matching from Sec. 4.5 (Appendix A) and a description of the catalog walk-through tutorials (Appendix B).

Chapter 5

First Impressions: Early-Time Classification of Supernovae using Host Galaxy Information and Shallow Learning

This chapter is based on: Gagliano, Contardo, Foreman-Mackey, Malz, et al., 2023, *in review*.

5.1 Introduction

Despite these early successes, real-time transient classification remains in its infancy. Success in practice has been limited by two factors. First, to satiate the data-starved machine learning classifiers currently in use, it has become standard practice to generate and train on a large sample of synthetic light curves. Due to our limited understanding of the underlying physical systems involved, these transient models are driven by observed phenomenology, and so are necessarily simplified. This limits the performance of these classifiers on observed samples, particularly those containing out-of-distribution behavior. Second, the question of early-time classification has to date been explored *post-hoc* through modifications to networks originally developed for full-phase classification. A classifier has yet to be designed explicitly to classify early and to bridge the divide spanning simulation and observation.

Real-time classification will also help enable the discovery of a greater number of rare and rapidly-evolving transients that have eluded discovery within previous surveys. Serendipitous detections among massive survey streams have already revealed multiple transients in this region of parameter space, including Rapidly-Evolving Transients (RETs; [393]); Fast Blue Optical Transients (FBOTs; [376]); and Fast-Evolving Luminous Transients (FELTs; [406]). Because the emission time-scales of most SNe is determined by the radioactive half-life of ^{56}Ni , events evolving more rapidly than this hint at distinct explosion physics and central engines (such as a relativistic jet that interacts with a cloud of dense circumstellar material, as with FBOTs; [190]). Increasing our sample sizes of these events is essential for constructing a

complete picture of stellar death and the nature of the compact remnant that these doomed systems leave behind.

Here, we introduce a recurrent neural network designed end-to-end for *early* classification of explosive transients. In contrast to the rise of deep-learning methods that introduce complex networks at the expense of model interpretability, our model consists of a single recurrent layer and leverages physical information about the explosion site to improve early performance. Because of the simplified architecture and the emphasis on classification with incomplete light curve information, we deem this approach ‘shallow learning’. Our framework extends the initial real-time classification system developed by [355] in four key respects:

1. We implement a temporally-weighted categorical cross-entropy loss function such that early classification is prioritized over full-phase classification.
2. We adopt a flexible Gaussian Process model parameterized by the correlation between filter passbands and observations in time to realistically interpolate observed transient photometry.
3. We utilize a two-component training strategy where the network is first trained on a large sample of simulated light curves, and then re-trained on a curated subset of real observations.
4. We include photometry from the galaxy where a transient occurred (its ‘host galaxy’) to reduce the reliance on sparse transient photometry at early phases.

Host galaxy information is increasingly being considered for its value in early SN classification. The initial work of [142] verified using the Lick Observatory SN Search sample [135] that host galaxy morphology and color could be used to construct photometric SN Ia samples as pure as those constructed using the then-leading light curve methods. [31] extended this work with a random forest classifier to distinguish between low and highly star-forming host galaxies, finding that this metric could serve as an indicator of transient type in the two-class scenario (SNe II versus SNe Ia). A postage-stamp classifier constructed by [79] uses a convolutional neural network to distinguish between SNe, asteroids, variable stars, and bogus alerts with a single detection image (in the case of SNe, this necessarily includes host galaxy information). [164] found that a random forest classifier trained directly on the photometric features of transient host galaxies achieved $\sim 70\%$ accuracy distinguishing between SNe II and SNe Ia. FLEET, a random-forest classifier used to recover SLSNe-I from survey streams, combines a set of full-phase parametric light curve features with host galaxy properties and reports 20 SLSN-I discovered per year with an overall detection purity of 85% [182]. More recent work has extended these insights to additional sub-classes of SNe [276]. None of these methods leverage both host-galaxy and light curve information for *real-time, adaptive* photometric classification.

We leverage the photometric information from two surveys, mimicking the realistic scenario in which heterogeneous data (potentially with observations collected in distinct filter systems) is consolidated from

Figure 5.1: Overview of our analysis pipeline, with relevant sections in this paper labeled. Data are outlined in blue, while analysis steps are given in green.

multiple sources. We consider SN photometry in ZTF-*gr* and host-galaxy photometry in Sloan Digital Sky Survey [SDSS; 426] *griz*, both in our simulated and observed samples.

We provide an overview of our analysis, which mimics the structure of this paper, in Fig. 5.1. In §5.2, we introduce the simulated and observational datasets used. We outline our prescription for pre-processing each of the transient light curves in §5.3, and introduce our recurrent neural network architecture in §5.4. We then describe our training of the model in §5.5. We provide results from our recurrent classification tests and place them in the context of other recently-released photometric classifiers in §5.6. We conclude with a discussion of potential science applications in §5.7.

5.2 Data

Training Data: Simulated Transients with SNANA

We use the SNANA [265] simulation code to simulate the properties of four classes of SNe: SNe Ia, SNe II, SNe Ib, and SNe Ic. SNANA constructs a forward model for a transient event, starting from a rest-frame SED and ending with synthetic observations matching the cadence and depth of a survey of interest. The simulation considers atmospheric distortions, instrument efficiency, and photometric calibration in estimating the uncertainty of each simulated observation. In our simulations, we assume a flat Λ CDM cosmology with $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and $w = -1$.

A common set of SN models used to train the current generation of photometric classifiers are those constructed for the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge [PLAsTiCC; 263]. Since the challenge was run, the models associated with SNe Ia, SNe II, and SNe Ib/c have all been updated, and will soon be released in an updated iteration of the challenge. We use the recently-

released SALT3 model [260], an update of the commonly-used SALT2 model [202], to parameterize the rise, stretch, and color of SNe Ia as a function of their rest-frame SEDs. For SNe II, SNe Ib, and SNe Ic, we use the spectrophotometric templates provided by Vincenzi et al. [502]. These templates have been constructed from observed events of multiple sub-types; we consolidate the templates provided for SNe IIP/III, SNe IIn, and SNe IIb as “SNe II” to reflect the observational diversity of this class.

We generate synthetic light curves in ZTF- g and ZTF- r for $20k$ events of each transient class over the redshift range $0 < z < 0.2$ to match the photometric properties of the data publicly reported in the alert stream of the Zwicky Transient Facility [ZTF; 40]¹. Data from the ZTF public stream are collected using the 47 deg² field-of-view camera mounted atop the Palomar 48-inch Schmidt telescope, which observes in three passbands: ZTF- g , ZTF- r , and ZTF- i . The data collected, which now include forced photometry at the locations of identified events [333], are then processed at the Infrared Processing and Analysis Center (IPAC) to produce public alerts ~ 4 minutes from the time of observation. Now in the second phase of its public survey, which comprises half of its total time on-sky, ZTF scans the entire northern sky with a cadence of ~ 2 nights in ZTF- g and ZTF- r . To prevent confusion between ZTF- gr and SDSS- gr passbands, we will hereafter refer to ZTF- g as X and ZTF- r as Y .

Because we aim to apply our trained network to the ZTF Bright Transient Survey (ZTF BTS), which is magnitude-limited to $Y < 18.5$ (additional detail on the catalog is provided in §5.2), we cut from our simulations any transients without at least a single observation brighter than this limit. We also remove observations with a signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of less than 4 (determined empirically to match the S/N distribution of observations reported in the ZTF BTS). Once we have a dataset of ‘observed’ ZTF SNe, we combine SNe Ib and SNe Ic into a single “SN Ib/c” class (due to the uncertainty surrounding their classification as distinct sub-types) and under-sampling the dominant classes with the Python package `imbalanced-learn` [296] so that the full dataset has the same number of events per class. This results in a sample containing 20,000 ZTF light curves per transient class (SN Ia, SN II, and SN Ib/c), or 60,000 in total. The sky locations of transients in the simulated sample, which convolves a uniform distribution where they occur with the ZTF footprint where they are detected, are used to calculate the expected line-of-sight Galactic extinction assuming $R_V=3.1$, an intrinsic scatter of $\sigma_{E(B-V)}=0.16$, and the dust law from Cardelli et al. [77].

We use the SCOTCH [306] framework within SNANA to realistically associate simulated transients with host galaxies. SCOTCH consists of a series of host galaxy libraries informed by observed samples (e.g., [164]), best-fit scaling relations for the host galaxies of different transient types (e.g., [503]), and the synthetic sky catalog CosmoDC2 [282]. After a transient is simulated, a class-specific galaxy library is selected and candidate host galaxies within a given redshift range δz of the transient are selected. The final association between a transient and its host galaxy is done probabilistically and is weighted by additional encoded host-galaxy correlations with transient types.

¹<http://ztf.caltech.edu>

For SNe Ia, the dominant simulated correlations take the following functional form:

$$P_{\text{Ia}}(M_*, \text{SFR}, x_1) = P_{KDE}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \times P_{\text{Ia}}^*(x_1, M_*) \quad (5.1)$$

where M_* is the stellar mass of a host galaxy candidate, SFR is its star-formation rate, x_1 is the SN’s SALT3 stretch [see 260], and P_{KDE} and P_{Ia} are empirical probability distributions constructed from SN Ia host galaxy properties within the Dark Energy Survey SN Program [456]. The host galaxy selection for the other classes of simulated transients is weighted by M_* and SFR following the prescription outlined in Vincenzi et al. [503]:

$$P_{\text{II}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \propto \begin{cases} (M_*/M_\odot)^{0.16}, & \text{for } x_s \geq -11.5 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5.2)$$

$$P_{\text{Ib/c}}(M_*, \text{SFR}) \propto \begin{cases} (M_*/M_\odot)^{0.36}, & \text{for } x_s \geq -11.5 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

where $x_s = \log_{10}[\text{SFR}M_*^{-1}/\text{Gyr}^{-1}]$. These functions reproduce the relative dearth of these transients in galaxies with low specific star-formation rates, a reflection of their massive, short-lived progenitors.

In the SCOTCH framework, transients are matched to synthetic galaxies from the CosmoDC2 catalog [282]. This gives us access to a wide range of both observed and derived galaxy properties. While we have found in early iterations of our network that simulated host galaxy stellar mass and star-formation rate are highly informative for early classification, these properties are difficult to estimate in real time as they often require Bayesian fitting of multi-band galaxy photometry to a set of template spectral energy distributions [although more rapid machine-learning solutions to this problem have recently been proposed and validated at low redshifts; 204]. To ensure the realism of our model, we consider only the broadband photometry of the host galaxy in our classification network. Our network is trained on host-galaxy brightness in the rest-frame SDSS-*griz* passbands.

We have simulated our transients using 10 Intel Xeon “Haswell” processor nodes on the Cray XC40 “Cori” system at the National Energy Research Scientific Computing (NERSC). The full simulation took a total wall time of 5.2 hours. We then divide our simulated sample into training and test sets comprising 75% and 25% of the original dataset, respectively. We maintain the even class balance in the training set; however, we re-balance the test set to have the approximate class proportions as exist in the ZTF BTS after quality cuts: 80% SNe Ia, 15% SNe II, and 5% SNe Ib/c (where we assume equal proportions of SNe Ib and SNe Ic in the combined SN Ib/c class). This allows us to track the performance of the network on a BTS-like sample of events as it trains. We achieve these proportions by undersampling our SNe II and

SNe Ib/c light curves using `imbalanced-learn`. Our final simulated training set contains 10,000 events of each class, while our simulated test set contains 8,000 SNe Ia, 1,500 SNe II, and 500 SNe Ib/c.

Re-Training & Testing Data: The ZTF Bright Transient Sample

To evaluate the performance of our network on real observations, we use the set of 3,890 SNe from the ZTF BTS² [155, 378], the largest spectroscopic sample of SNe constructed to date. The ZTF BTS is magnitude-limited to $Y < 18.5$ and nearly spectroscopically-complete, containing spectroscopic classifications for 93% of discovered SNe. The catalog (at the time of download on July 25th, 2022) consists of 2,788 SNe Ia, 493 SNe II, and 163 SNe Ib/c, whose photometry was released to alert brokers in near real-time and whose spectra were made public on the Transient Name Server³ within a day of observation. The catalog also contains multiple events belong to rarer classes (including SLSNe-I); we do not consider these additional classes in this study, but note that significant host-galaxy correlations have been identified among these other classes [306] and our model can easily be extended to consider these classes.

We download the photometry of all 3,444 SNe in our three-class sample using the ANTARES alert broker local client⁴ [334]. Photometry for 8 transients could not be found and were dropped. Next, we identify the most-likely host galaxies of these transients in Pan-STARRS (PS1) using the modified directional light-radius [199] method implemented in the GHOST [164] software⁵. The host galaxies of 149 SNe, $\sim 4\%$ of the sample, could not be found using this method and were dropped. Through visual inspection, another 174 were found to have erroneous or ambiguous associations and removed from the sample. 130 systems had unreported host galaxy photometry in at least one PS1 band and were dropped at this stage.

For the host galaxies that were found, SDSS best-fit model magnitudes in *griz*-passbands were retrieved using the `astroquery` package. These magnitudes are determined by integrating the best-fit brightness profile of each galaxy, where the best-fit model is determined in SDSS-*r* between a de Vaucouleurs and an exponential model⁶. Because the PS1 survey spans more of the sky than SDSS, we use linear regression to determine a mapping between PS1-*griz* Kron magnitude (the brightness contained within an aperture twice the size of the first image moment radius) and SDSS-*griz* model magnitude for the galaxies spanning both surveys. We use this function to compute the expected SDSS-*griz* photometry for each host galaxy observed only in PS1.

PS1 photometry was then corrected for Galactic extinction using the `sfdmap` package⁷, which implement the dust maps from Schlafly et al. [436]. Photometric redshifts were estimated for each galaxy using

²<https://sites.astro.caltech.edu/ztf/bts/bts.php>

³<https://www.wis-tns.org>

⁴<https://nsf-noirlab.gitlab.io/csdc/antares/client/installation.html>

⁵<https://pypi.org/project/astro-ghost/>

⁶https://www.sdss.org/dr12/algorithms/magnitudes/#mag_model

⁷<https://github.com/kbarbary/sfdmap>

the multi-layered perceptron model Easy PhotoZ, which was trained on a catalog of spectroscopic galaxies from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey [SDSS; 520] with SDSS photometry retrieved via a cross-matching search in the Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes⁸. By default, Easy PhotoZ returns a posterior probability density function of the most likely host galaxy redshift; the mode of this distribution is taken as the point estimate of the redshift of each galaxy. Additional details concerning this method are provided in Aleo et al. [8]. We then convert from apparent magnitude to flux using an assumed fixed zero-point of $m_{ZP}=27.5$. While each of these systems have spectroscopic redshifts from ZTF, we use the host galaxy photometric redshifts to normalize our light curves as described in the following section. We similarly use the SDSS zero-points and photometric redshifts to convert the host galaxy apparent magnitudes to host galaxy luminosity, which we normalize to be near unity.

Our observed sample before pre-processing contains 2,983 SNe. An additional 649 were dropped during the light curve truncation stage described in §5.3, leaving us with a final observed sample size of 2,334 SNe. While this is a fraction of the initial number in the ZTF BTS ($\sim 68\%$), we note that only a small fraction of the discovered SNe in upcoming surveys will be classified and selected for follow-up observations. By constructing a curated observed dataset, we optimize our classifier’s ability to discover events for which we will be able to extract meaningful scientific insights. We compare the distributions of peak apparent magnitude, redshift, and host galaxy photometry after each of these steps to ensure that we do not encode an additional observational bias into our observed sample with these cuts. We summarize our sample sizes after each of these cuts in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Number of SNe from the ZTF BTS remaining, and fraction removed, after each step in the processing pipeline.

Processing Cut	SNe Remaining	Fraction Cut
Initial Sample	3,444	–
Missing Photometry	3,436	0.2%
No Host Found	3,287	4.3%
Incorrect Host	3,113	5.1%
Unreported Host Phot.	2,983	3.8%
Light Curve Truncation	2,334	18.8%
Final SN Sample	2,334	32.2%

We divide our final spectroscopic sample into a 75% training set and a 25% test set without changing the relative proportions of classes. As a result, our spectroscopic training set consists of 1,512 SNe Ia, 250 SNe II, and 79 SNe Ib/c; our spectroscopic test set consists of 410 SNe Ia 62 SNe II, and 21 SNe Ib/c.

⁸<https://archive.stsci.edu>

Figure 5.2: The training and testing datasets used. **Above:** The composition of simulated events used in phase 1 of training the network. The total number of light curve segments in each sample are listed, and the number of unique transient events in each sample are given in parentheses. **Below:** The composition of spectroscopic events used in the re-training stage (see text for details).

5.3 Data Pre-Processing

Phase Jitter of Synthetic Light Curves

In our model, the date at which ZTF ‘discovers’ a SN (deemed the trigger date, or T_{trigger}) is the epoch when a second observation is taken with $S/N \geq 5$. Because the date at which a transient is discovered is determined by the combination of a transient’s brightness evolution and the survey, this date should not be assumed to be either date of the start of the explosion or a constant offset relative to it. Nevertheless, the simplicity of SN simulations may lead a machine learning model to over-train on unrealistic correlations in the trigger dates of the training set instead of the properties of the light curve. This will limit its use when applied to data collected from a survey with more restrictive, or relaxed, trigger criteria. To mitigate this issue, we remove observations from the first d days of each transient light curve, where d is a number randomly sampled from a truncated Normal distribution with $d \sim \mathcal{N}(T_{\text{trigger}}, 0.25^2)$ and $d \geq T_{\text{trigger}}$. We then re-define the trigger date of each event as the epoch of the first observation in this new truncated light curve. For each light curve in both the simulated and spectroscopic sample, we calculate the phase of each observation relative to trigger in days. We correct these phases for time dilation using the photometric redshifts calculated above and correct light curve flux values for Galactic extinction. We then remove observations from each light curve obtained greater than 30 days after this new trigger date (as we are interested in early classification). We do not k-correct our photometry, as this would encode assumptions about the shape of

the SED of each transient class (and further encode the reliance on accurately determined redshifts, as we describe in §5.3).

Our classifier consists of a recurrent neural network, and these networks were initially constructed to process arrays of uniform length. To prepare irregularly-sampled light curves across multiple passbands for processing, common approaches include padding light curves to a fixed length and mask zero-valued observations in training [e.g., 88]; or interpolating observations onto a grid of uniform length [e.g., 501]. We adopt both approaches, using a Gaussian Process model described in the following section.

Gaussian Process Interpolation and Padding

We use Gaussian Process Regression [GPR; 401] to construct a light curve model for each transient event and interpolate observations in apparent magnitudes onto an evenly-spaced grid in time. In GPR, observations are considered to be realizations of a latent function with Gaussian noise. A function describing the covariance between observations, called the kernel, is constructed and its parameters are chosen to minimize the loss function (and maximize the likelihood of the obtained observations). This results in a continuous posterior distribution for a class of models that describe the data. GPR can additionally consider a mean model for the observations, and this further conditions the subsequent model predictions.

Our model, which is implemented in the lightweight code `tinygp`⁹, uses a Matérn kernel with $\nu=3/2$ that quantifies the correlation in time between observations t_i and t_j as

$$k(t_i, t_j) = (1 + \sqrt{3}r)e^{-\sqrt{3}r} \quad (5.4)$$

In the above equation, $r = \left\| \frac{t_i - t_j}{l} \right\|_1$ parameterizes the time between observations and the scale factor l is a free parameter. In addition to modeling the correlation between single-band observations in time, we model the correlations between *bands*. We construct a $p \times p$ symmetric correlation matrix, where in this case $p=2$ is the number of passbands considered. The diagonal and off-diagonal terms (2 and 1 terms, respectively) are free parameters to be fit.

We use a constant value in each band as our mean model (\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) , and add the uncertainty in each band to the diagonal of the covariance matrix along with an additional free term j_X, j_Y to capture any remaining measurement error. In total, our model consists of 8 free parameters. We transform our data from flux to magnitude space and minimize the negative marginal log probability of the model (our loss function) to determine the best-fit parameters for each event. We optimize our Gaussian Process fit with the `Scipy` package.

There is precedent to a light curve model parameterized by the correlation in both wavelength/frequency and time. A similar method was first introduced by Boone [47] with the photometric classifier `Avocado`, the winning submission of the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge [PLAs-

⁹<https://tinygp.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

Figure 5.3: Best-fit Gaussian Process model for one simulated light curve in ZTF passbands (X in green and Y in red) at three phases in its evolution from the time of trigger (bottom). The best-fit band-wise covariance matrix associated with each fit is shown at top. Because our model is parameterized by the covariance between observations in both time and wavelength, observations taken in a single band inform the model in the other.

TiCC; 263]. In Avocado, the central wavelength of each passband was used as the coordinates of the wavelength dimension of the GP. Villar et al. [499] also used a custom GP model described by a kernel in both wavelength and time, where the distance metric in wavelength space was the Wasserstein-1 distance between each filter’s normalized throughput. Because these two GP methods place physical constraints on the covariance in wavelength, they are specialized cases of our model. A physically-motivated construction of the GP covariance matrix may be desirable when photometry is sparse; we opt instead for a model with greater flexibility to fully characterize both the long-duration and short-duration behavior of each transient.

We show the best-fit GP model for one simulated transient event across three phases of its light curve, in addition to the best-fit passband kernel at that phase, in Fig. 5.3. With few observations, minimal correlation is detected between passbands (left plot). As more data is obtained (middle and right plots), the correlation increases and is used to improve the posterior light curve fits across both passbands. This learned correlation also ensures that the model in each band is robust against low-S/N observations (not shown).

Although a GP model whose hyperparameters are optimized based on a full-phase light curve would best characterize an event’s evolution in time and across passbands, this information will not be available in real-time. We decompose each transient light curve into segments to realistically simulate constructing a model at different phases of observation. From a light curve with N total observations in the simulated sample, we construct a series of $N/2$ segments from the first n observations, where $n=2, 4, \dots, N$. In other words, we generate a unique segment every two observations of the light curve. This cadence was chosen to reduce the volumes of training data without decreasing the number of transient events they contain (and

the associated photometric diversity).

Multiple strategies have been proposed to pre-process unevenly-sampled and multi-variate time-series datasets for use in recurrent neural networks, and it remains unclear which strategy yields the best performance for SN classification. With this in mind, we construct three different data representations of our light segments:

1. **Raw and Pad Model:** In the first approach, we construct an array directly from the light curve observations. This photometry has been corrected for distance, extinction, and time-dilation but has not been interpolated using our GP model. In this method, our temporal array contains the phases at which observations were obtained in any band; the magnitude and magnitude uncertainty arrays are filled with zeros where a given band was unobserved. These arrays are then padded with zeros at the tail end so that the matrices for all events have equal length.
2. **100-Timestep Model:** In the second approach, we construct a GP fit for each light curve segment and compute the mean and standard deviation of the GP posterior distribution at 100 independently-spaced phases spanning the full extent of the segment. We then convert these interpolated observations and their uncertainties from magnitude space back to flux space. We note that, in contrast to prior light curve methods, this interpolation scheme does not maintain uniform spacing in time across light curve segments. One segment may have its 20th observation at $t_n=10$ days, in which case its light curves assume a uniform grid with $\delta t=0.05$ days; while the 20th observation may occur at day 20 days of observation, in which case the spacing between interpolated observations is $\delta t=1.0$ days.
3. **0.2-Day Spacing Model:** In the third approach, we construct a GP fit as above and evaluate the GP model at phases beginning at the time of trigger and occurring every 0.2 days until the end of the segment. We then convert these interpolated observations to flux. While this approach preserves consistent spacing in time, the interpolated light curves will not be equal in length. As in method 1, we pad each light curve array to a consistent length after interpolation.

We have adopted a flexible GP model over a physical light curve model to capture the observed diversity in SN photometry, which allows unexpected phenomenology to be expressed in the interpolated data. When an SN is young, however, this flexibility can be detrimental: with very few observations, the best-fit GP model may not reflect expected early-time SN behavior. To bypass this limitation, we only interpolate our observations after 5 or more total observations have been obtained. Before this phase, we pad the photometry with zeros to a uniform length in all three of our models and pass these arrays directly into the neural network. We note that a more sophisticated approach may be to integrate a physically-motivated light curve model at early times, then transition to a more flexible GP model as more data is obtained. We leave this implementation to future work.

Figure 5.4: **Left:** Comparison between photometric and true redshifts for the galaxies in our simulated and observed samples. Simulated photometric redshifts (represented by the two-dimensional histogram in green) are drawn from a normalizing flow model conditioned on galaxy photometry. Photometric redshifts estimated for galaxies associated with the ZTF BTS are shown as black points. BTS Photometric redshifts are estimated using an MLP model trained on PS1 photometry for a sample of SDSS galaxies. The skew toward higher photometric redshifts reflects the redshift range of the galaxy sample used to train the photo-z estimator.

After obtaining the interpolated or padded representations of each light curve segment, we convert its flux to normalized luminosity using the equation

$$L_{\text{Norm}} = \frac{4\pi d^2 F}{\alpha} \quad (5.5)$$

where F is the GP-interpolated flux in each band; d is the luminosity distance to the transient in parsec, estimated from the photometric redshift of the host galaxy; and $\alpha=10^{23}$ is a normalization constant used to keep the computed luminosities near unity (as neural network performance is often better if the input range is constrained). Photometric uncertainties extracted from the GP fit are similarly converted as $\sigma_{L,\text{Norm}} = L_{\text{Norm}}\sigma_F/F$.

Estimation of Photometric Redshifts (Photo- z s) from Simulated Host Galaxies

Early tests of our classifier revealed a heavy reliance on each transient’s redshift, which we estimate in the observed sample using the host galaxy’s photometry. This dependence is unsurprising, as redshift is a key feature used to estimate the absolute brightness of an explosion, and therefore a key discriminator between SNe Ia and core-collapse events. When trained on simulations, even those with host-galaxy redshifts redrawn from redshift-dependent gaussian distributions to approximate a degradation in our approximators with distance, classification performance suffered. This motivates the need for realistic simulated photometric redshifts (photo- z). We take the first step toward realizing this goal by constructing a normalizing flow to predict the redshift of each CosmoDC2 host galaxy conditioned upon its photometry. Because these same host-galaxy simulations will be used to simulate alerts for the Extended LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge (ELAsTiCC) as a separate work, we condition redshifts upon the photometry of simulated host galaxies in Vera Rubin Observatory passbands: $p(z|ugrizy, \sigma_{ugrizy})$.

Normalizing flows [241] are generative models constructed to approximate and draw from a joint probability density function (PDF) associated with a complex multi-dimensional dataset. They are parameterized by an invertible bijective function (or bijector) that maps a simple distribution (e.g., a multi-dimensional Uniform distribution) to the observed data distribution. New samples can then be drawn from the data distribution by sampling the simple distribution and applying the learned bijective function. A flow can also be constructed to predict one parameter of the dataset conditioned on its other parameters, as is done here. We use the PZFlow¹⁰ package [110] to build our conditional normalizing flow.

We train a conditional flow on the LSST- $u - g, g - r, r - i, i - z$, and $z - y$ colors plus r -band magnitudes of a representative sample of $\sim 300k$ simulated CosmoDC2 galaxies [one-thousandth of the cosmoDC2_v1.1.4_small catalog; 282]. The photometry of these galaxies is estimated from simulated co-added images corresponding to the full 10-year LSST survey. Our bijective function is a Rational-Quadratic Neural Spline Coupling [128], and we train for 100 epochs, confirming convergence of the log-probability. After a transient is associated with a galaxy in our simulation, we condition our learned flow on its $(r, u - g, g - r, r - i, i - z, z - y)$ photometry to generate a posterior PDF for its photometric redshift. Following the recommendation of Malz et al. [321]¹¹, this distribution is discretized across ten equally spaced percentile bins, and the redshift of the 50th percentile (median) of the PDF is used as the point estimate for the galaxy’s redshift. Additional scatter is incorporated into the simulation to account for the peculiar velocities of local galaxies.

We plot the distribution of simulated photometric redshifts as a function of spectroscopic redshift in Fig. 5.4. In comparison, we show the photometric redshifts estimated by Easy PhotoZ for the ZTF BTS sample. Qualitatively, the scatter in photometric redshifts between the two samples are similar for $z < 0.15$; however, we note that multiple catastrophic outliers are predicted by Easy PhotoZ with $z_{\text{Phot.}} > 0.15$.

¹⁰<https://github.com/jfcrenshaw/pzflow>

¹¹<https://github.com/aimalz/qp>

We caution that these models have been constructed using mutually non-representative photometry from different surveys (LSST’s 10-year co-added image depth is $r \sim 26.5$ compared to PS1’s $r \sim 23.2$ ¹²), and a more thorough treatment would aim to adapt the normalizing flow to more closely emulate the statistical properties of the redshifts predicted by Easy PhotOZ. Nevertheless, this approach represents a significant advancement over light curve simulations that estimate photo-zs from interpolating look-up tables of host galaxy colors [see e.g., 193].

5.4 Model Architecture

Overview

A recurrent neural network (RNN) is comprised of multiple connected and directed “units” that are trained to learn a data representation from both the internal states of earlier units as well as a component of the input array. Because gradients propagate through the network, RNNs have traditionally suffered from vanishing and exploding gradients (those tending toward 0 and infinity, respectively) in training. This issue can be alleviated by the use of recurrent units that modulate information flow through the network; for example, Gated Recurrent Units [GRUs; 98] feature coupled “update” and “reset” gates. We have selected the more conventional Long-Short Term Memory cells [LSTM; 219] as our RNN units. LSTMs contain three gates: a “forget” gate that removes information from the cell state; an “input” gate that regulates the adding of new information from the data sequence into the cell state; and an “output”, which regulates the output of the cell state into a subsequent unit. We use LSTMs for their ability to retain insights from the long-term behavior of complex time-series data, where they often achieve superior performance to GRUs [e.g., 69].

The architecture of our neural network is illustrated in Fig. 5.5. It consists of a single LSTM layer of 60 units, with a `sigmoid` activation function defined as

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (5.6)$$

where x is the input tensor to the gate. The next layer is a masking layer, which prevents the network from attempting to learn from the padded zeros in the light curve arrays. This layer is followed by a dense layer to consolidate model outputs into a set of normalized probability scores corresponding to the likelihood of the light curve to belong to the three transient classes considered (SN Ia, SN II, SN Ib/c). Many previous RNN architectures for photometric classification have applied dropout layers that deactivate randomly-selected neurons during training to ensure that all neurons are used; batch normalization is also common to decrease the number of training epochs needed to achieve accurate classification results. We have found that neither modifications significantly increases the accuracy of our model when applied to real data, and

¹²<https://outerspace.stsci.edu/display/PANSTARRS/>

so have excluded them. Our network is implemented in TensorFlow [1] using the Keras [99] interface.

Each interpolated or padded transient light curve segment is represented in our dataset as an $n \times p$ matrix, where n_t is the number of interpolated observations (which is different for each of the three methods) and $p=2$ is the number of passbands (XY). To this matrix, we add the array of interpolated phases $t_n=T - T_{\text{trigger}}$; the GP-derived photometric uncertainties in each band; and n -length arrays contains the fixed repeated values of $E(B - V)_{MW}$, z_{phot} , and host galaxy normalized luminosity in SDSS-*griz* filters. This results in a data matrix containing arrays of dimensionality $n_t \times (2p + 7)$ that is used to both train and validate the network, as is shown in Fig. 5.5.

We consolidate our $n_t \times (2p+7)$ arrays for all SN segments associated with the SNe in our training samples described in 5.2; this forms our training set. The segment arrays associated with the test SNe similarly form our test set. Our target array for prediction is a one-hot encoded representation of our three classes: SNe II are encoded as ‘0’, SNe Ia as ‘1’, and SNe Ib/c as ‘2’. We report the number of unique transient events across the simulated and spectroscopic training and test set, along with the number of light curve segments within each sample, in Fig. 5.2.

Class-Weighted Loss For Accurate Early Predictions

A common choice for the loss function used to train multi-class classification networks is the sparse categorical cross-entropy. For an event belong to true class a , the categorical cross-entropy is calculated as

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = - \sum_{j=0}^M \sum_{i=0}^C y_{ij} \times \log(\hat{y}_{ij}) \quad (5.7)$$

where C is the number of transient classes (in this case, $C=3$), M is the number of events in a training batch, y_{ij} is the true class of event j after one-hot-encoding (with $y_{ij}=1$ where $j=a$, else $y_{ij}=0$), and \hat{y}_{ij} is the set of predicted normalized probabilities output from the softmax layer of the network. The cross-entropy for each event in a given batch is summed at each training epoch to compute the network loss. We modify this framework to weight the contributions of particular segments. The modified cross-entropy loss is constructed as:

$$L(y, \hat{y}) = - \sum_{j=0}^M \sum_{i=0}^C \beta_{ij} y_{ij} \times \log(\hat{y}_{ij}) \quad (5.8)$$

Figure 5.5: Architecture for our RNN, which is composed of a single LSTM layer of 60 units. The photometry in each band (interpolated, padded, or both) is stacked with the photometric redshift, extinction, and host galaxy photometry, which are repeated at each phase. This combined array serves as the input to our RNN, and the network returns a single classification prediction corresponding to the light curve segment processed.

We calculate the weight of each light curve segment as a function of t_N , the final phase covered by the segment:

$$\beta_{ij}(t_N) = \begin{cases} 10, & \text{for } t_N \leq 3 \\ 5, & \text{for } t_N > 3 \text{ and } t_N \leq 15 \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5.9)$$

These weights are constructed so that the network minimizes the loss by prioritizing the classification of SNe using only photometry provided in the first three days following detection. In the re-training stage using observed ZTF light curves (See §5.5 for details), we modulate these values by an additional weight

according to the class of the transient associated with the segment:

$$\beta_{ij}(t_N) = \begin{cases} \beta_{ij}(t_N) \times 2, & \text{for } j=0 \\ \beta_{ij}(t_N) \times 1, & \text{for } j=1 \\ \beta_{ij}(t_N) \times 5, & \text{for } j=2 \end{cases} \quad (5.10)$$

The multiplicative factors are added to make the network more sensitive to identifying SNe II and SNe Ib/c, which are poorly represented in our re-training dataset. SNe II events are more photometrically heterogeneous than SNe Ia, and SNe Ib/c are more easily confused with SNe Ia; the network learns to classify these more challenging minority classes only through explicit weighting. We note that we have tested the performance of the network after using these class weights in the primary training stage (on synthetic data before re-training). We find no significant improvement in performance relative to the early-weighted cross-entropy loss. The same principle we have applied here can be used to adapt publicly-available classifiers for specific science cases (e.g., to prioritize SN Ia classification for cosmological studies, or to prioritize late classification for nebular-phase spectroscopic follow-up).

5.5 Primary and Adaptive Training

Because of the inherent complexity of observational data, classification models trained on simulated data typically under-perform on more realistic datasets. We have attempted to reduce the discrepancy between synthetic and observed samples by simulating photometric redshifts and jittering the early photometry of simulated light curves. We further prepare our trained network for real-time operation with a domain-adaptation step in the training process. There are two primary motivations for this:

- **Encoding a weak dependence on class imbalance and survey systematics:** If the network was fully trained using realistic relative class rates, it may prioritize accurate classification of some classes over others (e.g., only classifying SNe Ia, the most common SN class in observed samples); conversely, a network trained on evenly balanced datasets may predict unrealistically-large numbers of minority classes. A re-training stage allows a reasonably flexible architecture to consider both pieces of information. After learning the underlying phenomenological differences between the light curves of each SN class from the balanced simulated sample, the network in its re-training stage additionally considers the observed distribution of real events in a given survey.
- **Increasing the Realism of Estimated Photo- z s:** Given the reliance of photometric classifiers on the predicted distance to the transient, it is imperative that our model is trained on a set of photometric redshifts with statistical properties comparable to those derived from observed photometry (including the rate of catastrophic outliers, which are not well-simulated by our photo- z treatment).

in §5.3).

First, we train our network on the simulated training sample for 200 epochs. We use the stochastic gradient descent optimizer Adam [275], with a learning rate of $l=10^{-4}$. We then re-train this model for 200 additional epochs and the same learning rate on the observed training sample. The temporal weights used in both training stages are identical; however, we have only used the class weights in the re-training stage, to account for the class imbalance. We use a training batch size of 16 in the simulated training stage and 12 in the spectroscopic training stage to account for the smaller data volumes of the latter dataset. We conducted the primary and secondary training for each of the three models across 24 CPUs of a node of the Flatiron Institute Scientific Computing Hub. The primary training stage was completed in a wall time of 31.2 - 32.1 hours per model, while the secondary training stage was conducted in 9.7 - 11.6 hours of wall time per model.

5.6 Results

In the following section, we evaluate the performance of our three models as a function of phase. We construct ROC curves and PRC curves for each model, and report balanced metrics across the SN classes in our sample.

ROC and Precision-Recall Curves

For both the simulated and the observed samples, we bin our light curve segments into early ($t_N < 3$ days), intermediate ($3 < t_N < 15$ days), and late ($15 > t_N > 30$ days) epochs depending on the phase of the final observation in the segment. The vast majority of events within the ‘early’ bin will still be brightening, while the late events will predominantly be dimming after peak.

For a given phase bin, events correctly classified as belonging to class a are called True Positives (TP). Events incorrectly classified as belonging to class a are called False Positives (FP). Conversely, events correctly and incorrectly classified as *not* belonging to class a are deemed True Negatives (TN) and False Negatives (FN), respectively. Then, the classification precision, also known as its purity, is calculated as

$$p_a = \frac{TP_a}{TP_a + FP_a} \quad (5.11)$$

The classification recall, also known as its completeness, is calculated by

$$r_a = \frac{TP_a}{TP_a + FN_a} \quad (5.12)$$

A common method to evaluate the performance of a binary classifier is to consider the false positive rate FP_a as a function of the true positive rate TP_a ; a well-trained classifier should be able to maximally increase

the rate at which they recover events from class a while minimizing the rate at which they mistakenly identify the alternative class as belonging to class a . The ideal behavior of this $TP - FP$ curve, also known as a Receiver Operator Characteristic Curve [ROC; 380], is to rapidly increase toward a true positive rate of unity with minimal false positives. We quantify this behavior by calculating the Area Under the ROC [AUROC; 374], which is unity in the limit of perfect classification and 0.5 in the case of random guessing.

Another common metric is to plot the recall of the model as a function of its precision; a well-performing classifier exhibits a Precision-Recall (PR) curve with high recall rates (the fraction of recovered events from class a) even as the demanded model precision increases. As in the ROC curve, this trade-off can be quantified by the area under the precision-recall curve [AUPRC; 423], with AUPRC=1 for perfect classification and $AUC=f_a$, the fraction of the test data consisting of class a , for random guessing. The AUROC and the AUPRC provide complementary views of a classifier’s performance.

Our work is motivated by the need for rapid characterization of common events to conduct follow-up with highly limited resources. We will be unable to study the vast majority of discovered transient events in detail, but we must ensure that we do not waste precious resources when we do. For this reason, this and other upcoming SN classifiers will need to optimize a method’s precision over its recall. We note that if an event is intrinsically rare, a classifier’s recall rate should be prioritized over its precision.

We use the `StratifiedKFold` module in `sklearn` to generate five evenly-sized random splits of the test datasets. These data subsets are mutually exclusive: no events are repeated between them. Next, we binarize our classification predictions for each split using the one-versus-all approach (in which the true class a is assigned a value of 1 and the other two classes are assigned a value of 0). We then generate ROC and PR Curves for each data split and each phase range (early, intermediate, and late). Finally, we calculate the mean and standard deviation of the curves across all splits.

The ROC and PR curves for the ‘Raw with Pad’, ‘100-Timestep GP’, and ‘0.2-Day GP’ models are shown in Figures 5.6, 5.7, and 5.8, respectively. We show these curves applied to both the simulated test segments after the first training stage and on the observed test segments after the retraining stage. We report the class-specific AUC and AUPRC values in the figure legends.

On the simulated sample, we achieve near-perfect classification for both SNe II and SNe Ia at late phases ($15 < t_N < 30$): Our AUROC and AUPRC values for the two classes are $\geq 98 \pm 1\%$ across all three models. We observe slightly worse results at late phases for SNe Ib/c: an AUROC of $95 \pm 1\%$ for the GP-100 model, and an associated AUPRC of $63 \pm 6\%$. We attribute this to the class imbalance of the test set, to which the the AUPRC is particularly sensitive: $\sim 5\%$ of the sample are SNe Ib/c.

At early phases, we observe a larger difference than at late phases between the three classifiers tested on the simulated transients. We find the worst performance across all classes with the 100-Timestep GP model, with AUROC values of $91 \pm 1\%$, $83 \pm 2\%$, and $77 \pm 2\%$ for SNe II, SNe Ia, and SNe Ib/c, respectively; and AUPRC values of $73 \pm 4\%$, $93 \pm 1\%$, and $28 \pm 6\%$, respectively. It is possible that this is a reflection of the loss of physically-relevant timescales in pre-processing these light curves: because 100 observations are

generated independent of the duration of the light curve segment, the same rise time could comprise half of one processed array and span the full extent of another. Although we also pass the phase information explicitly to the network, we propose that the physically-motivated spacing between array elements aids the network in learning the temporal evolution of an event. Further, we note that the first five observations were passed in directly for each of the models. Because ZTF observations are taken with a median cadence of ~ 2 days, these observations encode physical information about the phase of the event in the number of array elements. The two networks trained to identify this correlation (the ‘Raw and Pad’ and the ‘0.2-Day GP’ models) are better-adapted to process the raw early data than the 100-Timestep model.

Finally, we note that the AUC and AUPRC values for each class increase monotonically from the early-phase to the late-phase bin. This aligns with our expectation that as more data is taken, our ability to classify an explosion improves. We conclude that the RNN is successfully able to improve its performance according to the temporal evolution of the simulated datasets, regardless of the pre-processing method adopted.

We now consider the performance of our three models on the spectroscopically-confirmed sample of SNe from the ZTF BTS. For the dominant class in the sample, SN Ia, we note surprisingly consistent results when transitioning from simulations to observations: the late-phase classification achieves an AUROC of $81 \pm 2\%$ and an AUPRC of $96 \pm < 1\%$ in the worst case (with the ‘Raw and Pad’ model). The performance on the other two classes is appreciably worse: we observe significantly greater variance among the performance results between the five cross-validation folds for each the three models, particularly for SNe Ib/c. In the worst case, our average AUROC metric for late-phase classification decreases by 26% for SNe Ib/c and 21% for SNe II with the ‘Raw and Pad’ model. When applied to the real data, we find the worst performance with this model: our early-phase AUPRC suggests SN II classification is barely superior to random guessing ($17 \pm 1\%$ compared to its 15% abundance in the dataset).

Although our AUROC and AUPRC values increase with phase for each classifier applied to the simulated SN sample, we do not observe the same trend for all phases in the observed SN sample. Our highest SN II AUROC is achieved only for intermediate-phase light curves ($81 \pm < 1\%$ versus $78 \pm < 1\%$ at late phase), and the difference between the AUPRC values of each class from intermediate to late-phase prediction is not statistically significant. The increase in model performance is more evident among the two GP models applied to the real data. This suggests that our simplified RNN architecture struggles to learn the temporal behavior of the real data without interpolation, emphasizing the need to fit observations to some underlying model as a pre-processing step for real-time classification.

Finally, we find that *only* the 0.2-Day GP model is able to perform on the first three days of observations with AUROC and AUPRC values above random guessing for all three models. We find AUROC values of $\sim 70\%$ across all three classes, and an AUPRC value of 91% for SNe Ia. We additionally find an AUPRC value of $26 \pm 18\%$ for SNe Ib/c and $34 \pm 2\%$ for SNe II. These are encouraging results that the light curve rise of an SN, coupled with its host galaxy photometry, can be used for real-time early classification. We conclude that the ‘0.2-Day GP’ model is better able to incorporate the long-term temporal evolution of

each light curve better than the ‘Raw and Pad’ model, while preserving information about the brightening and dimming of each event better than the ‘100-Timestep GP’ model. Our results also suggest that the application of machine-learning solutions to simulated SN samples alone may suggest overly optimistic performance, and may not be strong indicators of their performance on real data.

Comparison to Previous Classifiers

First, we compare our classifier to pre-existing methods in its approach. Because we have sought to overcome existing barriers to real-time classification using physically-motivated information instead of model complexity, our classifier is simpler in architecture to the majority of comparative leading methods. Earlier RNN methods for photometric classification (e.g., superNNova; [349]) had considered two layers of bi-directional GRUs, in which the RNN representation of the light curve at each unit is informed by information from both earlier and later phases. These architectures are suited for full-phase classification but are ill-suited for classification with an incomplete light curve.

RAPID, the first recurrent neural network to be constructed for real-time classification, consisted of two layers of 100 uni-directional GRUs to avoid leaking information from later phases. It was later updated to use Temporal-Convolutional Neural units [TCNs; 30]. Our method uses a single LSTM layer consisting of 60 uni-directional units. To interpolate observations onto a uniform grid, Muthukrishna et al. [355] interpolated synthetic ZTF observations onto a grid of 50 observations spanning $-70 < t < 80$ days at a 3-day cadence. Model predictions were then wrapped in a TimeDistributed layer to provide a classification output at each interval in phase. In contrast, we process segments of the light curve separately through our network and interpolate each segment separately with a flexible GP model. We have chosen this approach so that our light curve representation improves as additional observations are obtained, contrary to the stationary interpolation scheme considered by Muthukrishna et al. [355]. This mimics model construction in real-time: as additional observations are obtained, our understanding of the shape and evolution of the light curve improves. Muthukrishna et al. [355] also define a pseudo-class to distinguish pre-explosion from post-explosion phases, and use a parametric fit to each light curve in training to estimate the time of explosion relative to trigger. We avoid this framework so that the network does not need to estimate the time of explosion, which in the case of sparse light curves is non-trivial and non-essential for classification. We note that our model can easily be modified to incorporate pre-explosion non-detections, as is done in [355]; this may further improve its performance.

Last year, the real-time classifier SCONE [396] was developed. SCONE uses a convolutional neural network applied to ‘flux-heatmap’ representations of transient light curves for classification, after 2-dimensional Gaussian Process interpolation in wavelength and time. The model consists of 22,606 free parameters for multi-class classification, whereas ours consists of 17,463. We note, however, that our model has only been constructed to distinguish three classes of SNe, whereas theirs includes SNe Iax, SNe 91bg, and SLSNe-I for a total of six possible SN classes.

During the writing of this work, Pimentel et al. [383] released a Deep Attention Model for photometric classification of transients discovered by ZTF. Attention Models [344] are secondary neural networks added to a primary network and tasked with learning the input features most relevant to the output of the primary network. Using a custom time-modulated attention component (called ‘TimeModAttn’), Pimentel et al. [383] uses an auto-encoder to learn a continuous representation of a light curve from discrete observations. Two model approaches are considered: a serial one in which an auto-encoder simultaneously encodes the light curves in $ZTF-g$ and $ZTF-r$ into a single latent vector; and a parallel one in which the light curves of an event in each band are encoded separately, combined, and then compressed with a linear projection to arrive at a dimensionality comparable to that of the serial model. After the partial light curve is encoded, it is processed by a Multi-Layered Perceptron (MLP; [353]) model with two layers, a dropout fraction of 50%, a batch normalization component, and a final softmax layer to convert the output of the model to a series of classification probabilities. We note that this requires more pre-processing than our model, and we require no dropout, batch normalization, or attention component. Nevertheless, the inclusion of the attention component allows for the network to predict the specific photometric observations most significant for classification by the model, a major advancement in the interpretability of machine learning models used for this task.

We now compare the performance of our classifier to prior methods. To better facilitate a comparison to the work of Pimentel et al. [383], we consider the macro-average of the AUROC, AUPRC, precision, and recall between the three classes. These metrics consider the contributions of each class equally, and consequently are not dominated by the network’s performance on the most dominant class in the observed sample (SN Ia). This is in contrast to the micro-average, in which a weighted average is computed using the number of events of each class. We provide these averages for each of our metrics in Table 5.2, where the balanced metrics are denoted with a ‘b-’ prefix. We also introduce an additional metric to our comparison: the balanced- F_1 score, defined as the harmonic mean between the precision and recall of a classifier averaged between classes:

$$F_1 = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=0}^C \frac{2r_i p_i}{r_i + p_i} \quad (5.13)$$

The balanced- F_1 score consolidates multiple performance metrics into a single value for directly comparing two classifiers. We list these values at each phase bin for the simulated and observed SN samples classified with the 0.2-Day GP model in Table 5.2. We acknowledge that few commonly-reported classification metrics are intuitive; for clarity, we also provide the overall accuracy of the network at each phase, although we note that this is equal to the micro-averaged precision and so is sensitive to the class imbalance of the dataset ($\sim 80\%$ SNe Ia).

In Pimentel et al. [383], the authors report the performance of their TimeModAttn models relative to a traditional RNN with LSTM units and a Balanced Random Forest algorithm constructed from 144 features extracted from the light curves. They evaluate these classifiers on a sample of spectroscopically-

Table 5.2: Classification metrics for the 0.2-Day GP RNN model evaluated on synthetic and observed (ZTF BTS) light curves at early ($t_N < 3$ days), intermediate ($3 < t_N < 15$ days), and late phases ($15 < t_N < 30$ days). Upper rows indicate the performance of our model, and the lower rows indicate only its late-phase performance in comparison with the same metrics at full-phase ($t_N = 100$ days) for the BRF, LSTM RNN, and TimeModAttn models from Pimentel et al. [383]. The three models from literature are evaluated on observed ZTF light curves, but the specific SNe considered may vary.

Model	Data	Phase	b-AUROC	b-AUPRC	b-Precision	b-Recall	b-F ₁ Score	Accuracy
0.2-Day GP	Synthetic	<i>Early</i>	$0.91 \pm <0.01$	0.73 ± 0.03	0.62 ± 0.01	$0.74 \pm <0.01$	0.66 ± 0.01	$0.83 \pm <0.01$
		<i>Intermediate</i>	$0.97 \pm <0.01$	0.87 ± 0.07	0.77 ± 0.01	$0.87 \pm <0.01$	0.81 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.01
		<i>Late</i>	$0.99 \pm <0.01$	0.94 ± 0.05	$0.83 \pm <0.01$	$0.94 \pm <0.01$	$0.87 \pm <0.01$	$0.95 \pm <0.01$
	ZTF BTS	<i>Early</i>	0.69 ± 0.07	0.50 ± 0.18	0.42 ± 0.14	$0.44 \pm <0.01$	0.45 ± 0.06	0.83 ± 0.02
		<i>Intermediate</i>	0.85 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.15	0.57 ± 0.15	$0.53 \pm <0.01$	0.55 ± 0.11	0.87 ± 0.03
		<i>Late</i>	0.91 ± 0.03	0.64 ± 0.10	0.57 ± 0.10	$0.54 \pm <0.01$	0.58 ± 0.07	0.89 ± 0.02
0.2-Day GP	ZTF BTS	<i>Late</i>	0.91 ± 0.03	0.64 ± 0.10	0.57 ± 0.10	$0.54 \pm <0.01$	0.58 ± 0.07	0.89 ± 0.02
BRF	ZTF	<i>Full</i>	0.87 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.05	0.53 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.05	0.53 ± 0.04	-
LSTM RNN	ZTF	<i>Full</i>	0.88 ± 0.03	0.65 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.03	0.68 ± 0.04	0.58 ± 0.04	-
TimeModAttn	ZTF	<i>Full</i>	0.90 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.04	0.61 ± 0.03	-

confirmed SNe from ZTF comparable to that used here. We note that these metrics are computed 100 days after detection, 70 days after our longest light curve segment, and so denote them as *Full-Phase*. Using the results from their parallel TimeModAttn network with synthetic pre-training and zero data augmentation, we provide these balanced metrics in Table 5.2.

We find no statistically significant difference between the balanced precision, F₁ score, AUROC, or AUPRC of our classifier at late-phase ($15 < t_N < 30$) and those reported for the TimeModAttn model 100 days from trigger. It is likely that our results also represent lower limits for the full-phase performance of our classifier. We find the TimeModAttn model to be superior to our method only in terms of balanced recall, and we emphasize that this metric is less important than precision for triggering follow-up spectroscopy on targeted events. We find the mean AUROC, AUPRC, precision, and F₁ score of our method at late-phase to be superior to the baseline random forest model considered; however, we caution that our statistical uncertainties across samples are larger than each of their considered methods, and this limits our ability to directly compare them. In addition, Pimentel et al. [383] considered four SN classes (SNe Ia, SNe Ib/c, SNe II, and SLSNe-I), whereas we have excluded SLSNe-I from our sample. Although the light curve and host galaxy photometry of these events are reasonably distinct from the other classes (and performance is often significantly worse on SNe Ib/c and SNe II; these were the two SN classes with the lowest performance across twelve classes considered in [355]), our results may differ when switching to the four-class problem.

Next, we compare the performance of our network to earlier methods at *early-phase* classification. The number of classifiers that report early-time performance on real data is low; as a result, we will begin by comparing the early performance of RAPID and SCONE on synthetic samples. We caution that both of these classifiers considered more SN classes than this work; in addition, whereas RAPID simulated ZTF light curves, the SCONE framework was tested on LSST-simulated photometry from PLAsTiCC [263]. The

impact to classification of the increased spectral coverage but lower cadence of LSST relative to ZTF is an open question, and should be investigated further.

Figure 7 of Muthukrishna et al. [355] shows the recall of the model across all 12 considered transient classes 2 days since trigger. The performance on SNe II and SNe Ib/c is the worst across all classes. Combining these classes into a balanced-recall score, we find a value of 0.36, compared to our value of $0.74 \pm <0.01$. Figure 8 presents these values 40 days from trigger, when the model achieves a balanced-recall of 0.57 across SNe Ia, II, and SNe Ib/c. Our late-phase performance on synthetic ZTF samples is $0.94 \pm <0.01$, evaluated at least ten days earlier in phase. The confusion matrices shown in Muthukrishna et al. [355] indicate that Calcium-rich transients and SNe Iax are significant contaminants for classifying SNe Ib/c; our superior performance is likely partially attributed to not considering these classes. Nevertheless, we find significantly improved performance on the partial-phase light curves of dominant SN classes relative to RAPID.

Next, we consider the partial-phase performance of SCONE [396] on simulated LSST light curves. Fig. 4 of Qu et al. [395] indicates that their model achieves (when using redshift) a balanced-recall of 0.75 ± 0.03 across SNe Ia, SNe II, and SNe Ib/c 5 days from trigger, compared to our comparable recall of $0.74 \pm <0.01$ within the first 3 days. 50 days following trigger, they report a balanced recall of 0.86 ± 0.03 , compared to our value of $0.94 \pm <0.01$ in the first 30 days. Although these results are encouraging, table 5.2 reveals the significant degradation in results when transitioning from synthetic to real samples. We strongly encourage the validation of RAPID, SCONE, and other early-time photometric classifiers on spectroscopic SN samples to better understand the advantages of each approach.

In addition to the full-phase metrics reported by Pimentel et al. [383], plots are provided for the b-AUROC values of their models as a function of phase. At the earliest observation (approximately three days from trigger), they note a maximum b-AUROC of $\sim 50\%$ across all of their models on observed ZTF SNe. Our model achieves a significantly higher b-AUROC of $69 \pm 7\%$ within the first 3 days. They report a b-AUROC of $\sim 75\%$ for their BRF and LSTM RNN models, and $\sim 85\%$ for their TimeModAttn model at ~ 30 days from trigger, compared to our $85 \pm 5\%$. We conclude that a simple architecture is able to achieve comparable or superior performance to more complex methods in distinguishing between SNe Ia, II, and Ib/c at early phases.

5.7 Conclusions

We have shown that an SN classifier leveraging both transient and host-galaxy photometry can achieve comparable performance to machine learning methods with complex architectures. Our algorithm represents one of the first attempts to prepare for real-time SN classification at every stage of the design and implementation pipeline. Below, we outline our primary conclusions:

1. Between the three light curve pre-processing methods we considered (‘Raw and Pad’, ‘0.2-Day GP’, and ‘100-Timestep GP’), the ‘0.2-Day GP’ model performs best in early classification and time-

evolving classification when applied to the ZTF BTS. The AUROC and AUPRC metrics increase with phase more clearly in the GP models than the ‘Raw and Pad’ model, which suggests that the temporal evolution of the photometry is better-captured by an RNN when trained on an interpolated representation of the light curve (instead of just learning the temporal evolution from an array of phase values passed in).

2. Our late-time classification performance (between 15 and 30 days from trigger) is comparable to the leading methods (the balanced random-forest, LSTM RNN, and TimeModAttn networks given in [383]) 100 days from trigger. The balanced-recall of our method is significantly worse than that of the other methods considered, but this is of secondary importance for prioritizing follow-up of common SN classes for upcoming surveys.
3. Our method, with only a single LSTM layer of 60 gated units, achieves $\sim 20\%$ higher balanced-AUROC than prior methods within the first three days of observation. Additional work should be done to evaluate whether this early success can be attributed to the color and rise rate of the transient, or the photometry of its host galaxy.
4. The uncertainty in each metric (estimated with 5-fold cross-validation) is higher with our model applied to the ZTF BTS than on synthetic data, and also higher than that reported by [383] for a comparable observational dataset. We propose that this reflects the variation in the GP model of a single event as more data is collected. If this is indeed the case, it reflects the realistic stochasticity of light curve fitting in real-time.
5. There remains a fundamental mismatch between the performance of simulations and observations. All three models achieve impressive performance on the synthetic light curves, and struggle when applied to real observations. This could be due to overly simplistic host-galaxy correlations and/or overly optimistic redshifts in the simulations, but we predict that classification methods developed with simulated samples (e.g., those for PLAsTiCC and ELAsTiCC) will face an adaptation step to ensure reliable classification on observed samples.

By constructing a normalizing flow to generate redshifts directly from the photometry of each host galaxy in our simulated sample, we have also increased the realism of the current generation of transient simulations. We have used point estimates for photometric redshifts, but our probabilistic approach provides full posterior distributions for each galaxy. These distributions can reveal bimodalities and other complex behavior not captured by a point estimate, and future work should be devoted to developing classification methods that incorporate this information (e.g., by drawing from the redshift distribution multiple times and quantifying how classification results change).

We have found that classification performance suffered when applying our RNN models directly to the observational data after training with synthetic samples. The performance of our network after re-training

suggests that transfer learning can improve the network’s robustness to realistically complex datasets. Transfer learning is rapidly becoming a critical component of photometric classification architectures (with [383] and [66] released while our network was being developed), and will become increasingly valuable in the initial years of upcoming surveys such as LSST.

Our GP interpolation model is implemented in the lightweight and GPU-accelerated code `tinyGP`; as a result, it is competitive with the fastest GP models in the literature. When implementing our network for classification directly on the ZTF or LSST alert streams, our architecture can be further optimized to ensure rapid inference. We leave this model refinement to future work.

We have avoided using our GP to interpolate early phases of our transient light curves, except where enough data has been collected to construct a reasonable model for its evolution. The growth of physics-informed machine learning in recent years [515, 400, 249] represents a promising direction for balancing model flexibility and physically-motivated constraints. Multiple models exist for the photometric evolution of SNe [particularly for SNe Ia; 260, 324], and future work could incorporate one of these models into the mean model of the GP or into a distinct interpolation scheme that is only used at early phases, where limited data is available to condition a model.

The principles explored here have immediate utility for surveys whose science goals include the discovery of young SNe. One of these is the Young SN Experiment [YSE; 246], a 1500 deg² survey that began in 2019 and that uses the Pan-STARRS telescopes to obtain well-sampled *griz* light curves of low-redshift SNe. A primary goal of this survey is the characterization of early-time flux excesses in young SNe and the construction of the low-redshift SN Ia anchor sample for upcoming cosmological analyses with Rubin. Simulations suggest that this survey at full operation will discover ≥ 2 SNe within 3 days of explosion per month, when they can be classified with $\sim 83\%$ accuracy using our method. We aim to re-train our classifier using simulated YSE light curves and adapt the network using the light curves consolidated as part of the First Data Release for YSE [8]. We predict that the increased wavelength coverage and higher cadence achieved by augmenting ZTF light curves with YSE observations will result in early classification results superior to the ones shown.

Although we have considered only the three dominant classes of SNe in training and testing our network, the problem faced by classifiers operating directly on an alert stream such as that served by ZTF and LSST will be more difficult: they will have to classify from among the full diversity of observed transient classes. The SCOTCH framework we have used to generate realistic SN host galaxies also encodes observed correlations for rarer classes, including Tidal Disruption Events [TDEs; 159, 158, 522], Hydrogen-Poor Superluminous SNe [SLSNe-I; 295, 375, 19], and Kilonovae [KNe; 392, 42]. These events will represent a fraction of the full stream, but high-cadence coverage of the early-time behavior of even a few events of these classes will be a significant contribution to the literature. Consequently, additional work should be dedicated to extending our classification schema to include these events.

The broad-band photometry of a galaxy in optical pass-bands is, at best, a limited indicator of its un-

derlying spectral energy distribution. Multiple degeneracies exist between, for example, the distance to the galaxy and the color of its average stellar population, particularly across wide ranges in redshift. We have limited our analysis to the approximate redshift range spanned by the ZTF BTS ($z < 0.2$) in order to validate our methods on observed data, and it is likely that this has allowed us to largely avoid this drawback. LSST will dramatically increase our sample of high-redshift ($z < 1$) SNe, and at these distances it is unlikely that optical host galaxy photometry alone will have high discriminating power. We have begun investigating the value of host galaxy star-formation rate and stellar mass in simulated samples, but additional work should be devoted to rapid estimation of these parameters from host galaxies imaged with LSST [e.g., using Bayesian SED-fitting codes such as Prospector; 242]. Further, the SCOTCH simulations we have used [306] considered the photometry of transient host galaxies in SDSS-simulated passbands; for high-redshift systems discovered by Rubin, the *Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope* [466], and the *James Webb Space Telescope* [176], however, infrared photometry will play an increasing role in precise galaxy characterization. Observed transient host galaxy catalogs are increasingly incorporating photometry spanning ultraviolet and infrared wavelengths [394], and future work should be dedicated to reproducing these observations in a simulated host galaxy sample.

Raw and Pad Model

Figure 5.6: **First Row:** Receiver Operator Characteristic Curves (ROC) for the network trained and tested directly on transient and host photometry (without using a GP interpolation scheme). The performance has been evaluated on light curve segments truncated at early, intermediate, and late times. The mean AU-ROC are reported with $1\text{-}\sigma$ uncertainties in the legend of each panel. **Third Row:** The Precision-Recall Curves for the same model applied to synthetic photometry. The AUPRC with $1\text{-}\sigma$ uncertainties are given in the corresponding legends. **Second and Fourth Rows:** ROC Curves, and Precision-Recall Curves, for the same model after 100 epochs of re-training on observed light curve segments (see text for details).

100-Timestep GP Model

Figure 5.7: Same plot as Fig. 5.6 for the 100-Timestep GP model.

0.2-Day GP Model

Figure 5.8: Same plot as Fig. 5.6 for the 0.2-Day GP model.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and The Road Ahead

We have presented a comprehensive analysis of the nearby Type Ic SN 2020oi, which exhibits both a consistent flux excess across optical and ultraviolet passbands within three days of explosion; and a blue early spectrum inconsistent with the best-fit spectral sequence near and immediately following peak light. Combining stellar evolution libraries in BPASS with Bayesian modeling of pre-explosion cluster photometry with *HST*, we find the most likely progenitor system to be a low-mass binary of terminal mass $27 \pm 7 M_{\odot}$ whose ejecta interacted with $\sim 0.1 M_{\odot}$ of CSM following detonation. This is the first Type Ic SN whose early flux excess is unlikely to be associated with post-shock cooling of the CSM or surrounding stellar envelope, and its characterization is a testament to the high-cadence early observations obtained through the Young Supernova Experiment.

Furthermore, we have investigated the value of globally-integrated host-galaxy photometry in distinguishing between SNe Ia and CCSNe without light curve information. This required a statistical sample of host galaxies, which we have consolidated and publicly released as the Galaxies HOsting Supernovae and other Transients (GHOST) catalog. Further, we have designed a new model-independent host-galaxy association method that is able to identify the hosts of low-redshift transients more accurately than the commonly-adopted DLR method. The Rubin Observatory’s official strategy for host galaxy association has not yet been finalized; we have shown that, where deep surveys limit the ability to de-blend extended sources, DLR is unable to robustly identify supernova host galaxies. In addition, the postage stamps associated with real-time transient alerts for LSST are unlikely to exceed $6 \text{ arcsec} \times 6 \text{ arcsec}$. This window will exclude many supernova host galaxies within $z \sim 0.1$, and make it difficult to use postage stamp gradients alone for host galaxy association. The gradient ascent method will be a valuable resource for externally validating Rubin’s host galaxy associations and proposing improvements to the pipeline. This association method (and the traditional DLR technique) have been released as a pip-installable Python package for use in transient surveys (the code is already a core component of YSE_PZ, the transient management platform associated with the YSE survey [107]).

We have also constructed the largest transient-host-galaxy simulation to date, and released a catalog

of 5 million synthetic optical transients (including SNe, TDEs, and KNe) and the correlated properties of their host galaxies. The correlations presented in SCOTCH have been extensively validated to ensure that they reproduce previously-reported distributions of observed (brightness and color) and derived (star-formation rate, metallicity, and stellar mass) host galaxy properties. This simulation is the foundation for the Extended LSST Astronomical Time-Series Classification Challenge (ELAsTiCC), which is currently validating the ability of alert brokers to process and analyze a stream of LSST-like alerts containing transient and host-galaxy photometry in real-time.

Finally, we have consolidated the insights from these previous studies into a ‘First Impressions’ Classifier, consisting of a single-layered RNN trained on simulated SNe Ia, II, and Ib/c that ingests partial-phase light curve information and the photometry from the host galaxy. This network has been trained on simulations from the SCOTCH catalog, with the addition of a probabilistic photometric redshift estimator, and validated on SNe within the ZTF Bright Transient Sample. After implementing a re-training stage on a small number of observed SNe, we have achieved classification performance within three days of discovery superior to comparable methods (a three-way balanced-AUROC of 0.69 ± 0.07 , compared to ~ 0.5 reported by [383]). With 30 days of event discovery, our classification results are comparable to the current generation of full-phase neural network classifiers (a balanced-AUROC of 0.91 ± 0.03 , compared with 0.90 ± 0.02 for the TimeModAttn model considered in [383]). We attribute the superior performance of our network at early phases to the inclusion of contextual information and the novel retraining stage. Additional tools to interpret the evolving importance of each parameter (such as saliency maps, shapley values, and attention networks) will be explored in upcoming analyses to improve the interpretability of these methods.

Low-latency supernova classification has significant value in prioritizing events for follow-up observations and for analyzing the bulk observational properties of each class (including their explosion sites). We have validated our ‘First Impressions’ network by emulating real-time classification on archival events, but aim to implement it as a ‘filter’ within the ANTARES alert broker. Once in place, classification results will be incorporated into the value-added alert stream and ingested by science teams around the globe (including the Young Supernova Experiment). The La Silla Schmidt Southern Survey (LS4), a high-cadence, multi-band photometric survey of $>2000 \text{ deg}^2$ of the southern hemisphere sky, is scheduled to begin early 2024¹. 90% of the survey data will be publicly broadcast to ANTARES, Lasair, and ALerCE. A valuable extension of our ‘First Impressions’ network would be to re-train it in 2025 on LS4-Rubin combined photometry (or LS4-Rubin-PS1 photometry in the thousands of square degrees of overlap between the northern and southern-hemisphere surveys). The gaussian process model we have developed and publicly released alongside our network is parameterized by the data covariance between passbands, and consequently the inclusion of Rubin izY and LS4 z photometry will improve our ability to rapidly represent (and interpolate) the observed phenomenology. This, combined with the increased depths achieved by Rubin, should further improve early classification performance.

¹https://www.snowmass21.org/docs/files/summaries/CF/SNOWMASS21-CF6_CF4_Peter_Nugent-171.pdf

While exploring the inclusion of host-galaxy information for ‘First Impressions’ network, we found that incorporating host galaxy stellar mass and star-formation rate improved early classification beyond photometry alone. We outline the prospects for the real-time estimation of these host galaxy parameters in § 5.7, but early interaction signatures will only be resolved for transients in the local Universe, whose host galaxies have already been reasonably characterized by extant surveys. For these reasons, the maintenance of a public full-sky galaxy catalogue with best-fit SED models and the physical parameters extracted from them would be a valuable extension of this work. The consolidated optical and IR photometry presented in the TEx host galaxy catalog [394], when augmented with all-sky UV photometry from GALEX, forms an ideal dataset for this analysis.

To deepen our understanding of the underlying *physics* of each explosion requires stepping beyond classification alone. For the vast majority of archival events, physical inference is achieved by fitting the observed multi-band light curve to simple parametric models for the believed source of the emission (including [21] for the radioactive decay of ^{56}Ni , or [240] for CSM-dominated emission). If a parametric model is not available, light curves are compared to a grid of simulations and the properties of the best-fit template are considered by proxy.

A wave of advancements has now made it possible to conduct physical inference both probabilistically (to quantify the confidence in the estimate) and with a fraction of the computing resources required at run-time. This field of *variational inference*, in which the posterior probabilities of physical parameters are estimated iteratively through optimization, will be paramount in scaling transient analysis pipelines to the scores of SNe expected from Rubin. This avenue has been only tentatively explored for supernova science to date, with two implementations reported in the literature: the first, to predict morphological parameters associated with SNe Ia light curves [430]; and the second, to predict the physical properties of synthetic SNe Ic from well-sampled light curves in LSST passbands [498]. The behavior of these techniques on observed photometry (particularly as both cadence and S/N decrease), and the reliability of their predictions on out-of-distribution transient classes, are open questions, and will be the focus of future work.

Due to the limited number of low-redshift transients with resolved explosion site photometry, the connection to the local environment remains poorly understood. While Branch-normal SNe Ia are expected to arise in progenitor systems with median delay times of >0.5 Gyr [419], where the explosion site may be uncorrelated with the explosion, many prompt explosions (CCSNe, SNe Iax) occur in environments that shed light on the nature of the stellar progenitor. The Time-Domain Extragalactic Survey (TiDES) conducted on the 4-metre Multi-Object Spectrograph Telescope (4MOST) and beginning in 2024, will change this. TiDES can simultaneously obtain spectra for ~ 2400 objects distributed over a 4.2 deg^2 field-of-view, and its footprint will be designed to track that of Rubin. The resulting spatially-resolved spectroscopy for the explosion sites of Rubin transients (with tracking of $\sim 10,000$ CCSNe anticipated over its 5-year lifetime) will provide an unprecedented window into the precise stellar populations that surround each transient class. This question will become increasingly relevant for further reducing the systematic sources of uncer-

tainty that are expected to dominate next-generation cosmological studies conducted with Rubin’s tightly-calibrated SN Ia photometry.

The early-time interaction signatures of young SNe, as with SN 2020oi, are valuable for their ability to probe the progenitor’s pre-explosion environment and, consequently, its terminal nature and behavior. Deep multi-year baseline photometry consolidated during the Rubin LSST will allow us to study the progenitor system directly, and statistically, for the first time. In addition to the exciting potential of directly imaging low-redshift CCSN progenitors, this photometry will launch systematic studies of pre-explosion variability and its connection to the surprisingly large number of SNe II discovered with evidence of CSM interaction. This variability will become essential prior information for prioritizing transient follow-up observations. By combining insights from pre-explosion and post-explosion behavior, we will further constrain the role of stellar death in the continuous narrative that begins with a dying star and ends with its compact remnant.

This dissertation has taken a Bayesian approach to the analysis of supernovae, and considered the additional information revealed by the local environment. Over its decade-long survey, Rubin will obtain photometry for 5 billion galaxies, many of which have hosted (or will host) explosive transients. To ignore this rich *a-priori* information while the average light curve cadence decreases would be a waste of valuable resources in analyzing phenomena that are unresolved and faded beyond detectability in weeks (sometimes sooner). An ongoing effort exists in astronomy to identify and account for selection effects in consolidated samples, in order to gain a ‘true’ view of the time-domain sky. The inclusion of contextual ‘biases’ in our classification algorithms may at first appear counterproductive to these efforts. The validation of algorithms for targeted scientific analyses, however, will always specialize their use toward intended science goals and away from others. If contextual information increases the purity of photometrically-identified SNe Ia for cosmology, then this contextual information should not be ignored.

An equally valid and complementary approach to supernova science lies in ‘anomaly detection’: the search for entirely new transient behavior, or events exhibiting unexpected local correlations (although the notion of ‘anomaly’ requires that prior assumptions be made regarding the distribution of the underlying population, and so will be similarly sensitive to extant samples and their corresponding observational biases). Supernova science in the era of Rubin will require advancements along both fronts. Further, the rise of active learning now allows for a powerful union between these two classes of techniques: prior knowledge of likely host galaxies can be used to improve classification metrics, and events manually flagged as anomalous in explosion or host properties can be added to the sample of events used to re-train context-aware classifiers.

Active learning is increasingly being considered to mitigate the losses associated with training on limited and contaminated samples. This technique is used in the Recommendation System for Spectroscopic Follow-up (RESSPECT; [232]): a spectrum is requested for events photometrically classified with highest uncertainties, and the spectroscopically-classified object is added to the dataset used to re-train the system.

Active learning has also been used in anomaly detection to minimize the required number of labels in training [303]. By incorporating direct feedback in limited, high-priority regimes (without excluding it entirely), these algorithms will play an increasing role in real-time transient analysis in the era of synoptic surveys.

The landscape of time-domain astrophysics is evolving at a dizzying pace, driven on one end by synoptic multi-band coverage of the night sky and on the other by the rise of scalable algorithms for automated analysis. As our distance increases from the raw data we collect, our interpretation of it becomes increasingly sensitive to the software we design and the data with which we train them. The terabytes of imaging data soon-to-be collected by Rubin, followed shortly thereafter by the *Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope*, will contain answers to our most pressing questions in supernova physics. Whether we find them (and recognize them as such) will depend on how we ask the questions, and we should wield this subjectivity wisely.

Appendix A

Details Concerning the Construction and Use of the SCOTCH Catalog

A.1 Approximate Nearest-Neighbours Matching of GHOST and CosmoDC2 Galaxies with ANNOY

In LSH methods, a hashing function h is constructed that maps a high-dimensionality observation to a scalar such that, for any three observations a , b , and c for which some distance metric s is defined in the original space, the following criterion is met:

$$d(a, b) < d(b, c) \implies h(a, b) < h(b, c) \tag{A.1}$$

In this example, the two observations a and b with a small relative distance will retain a small relative distance (high relative similarity) after being mapped to a scalar value. Because $d \neq h$, the nearest neighbours returned by LSH methods may vary from those returned by a brute-force distance calculation between all observations; but the ‘approximate’ solution is achieved in significantly less time.

A multitude of methods exist both for constructing the hashing function h and the distance measure d [see 506, for additional details]. In the random projection method employed by ANNOY, a catalog of observations is provided and two are selected at random. A maximum-margin hyperplane is then constructed that separates the two observations [87]. This process is repeated and a decision tree is constructed with each node in the tree corresponding to a hyperplane. The hashing function encodes the side of each separating hyperplane on which the observations fall. Similar to random forest algorithms, multiple decision trees are constructed in ANNOY. The nearest-neighbours returned by an observation query to the space are the indexed observations that fall on the same side of all separating hyperplanes in a combination of decision trees.

In contrast with previous implementations of LSH methods, ANNOY decouples the construction of the indexed space and the querying of the space for individual vectors. Because the indexed space can be saved as a static file and then loaded into shared memory, matching can be achieved in parallel to dramatically reduce matching time.

We construct our indexed space from the following properties of 30M galaxies in CosmoDC2: absolute rest-frame r - and i -band magnitudes, $g-r$ and $i-z$ colors, and redshift. We normalize all properties by the StandardScaler algorithm, after which the distribution for each parameter has a mean of 0 and a variance of 1. Finally, we weight the redshift by 5%, enabling a wider distribution of redshifts in the matched sample than the low- z GHOST data. We select the same parameters from observed galaxies within the GHOST catalog, normalize them, and query the indexed space for k approximate nearest-neighbours in CosmoDC2. For a transient class i , we set $k=2 \times 10^6 / N_{i,\text{Ghost}}$, where $N_{i,\text{Ghost}}$ is the number of galaxies of class i in the GHOST catalog. This allows our matched sample to contain $\sim 2\text{M}$ galaxies for each class.

A.2 Using the SCOTCH Catalog

Figure A.1: A schematic diagram showing the hierarchical organization of the SCOTCH catalog. Only two transient classes are shown for illustrative purposes. The Hierarchical Data Format (HDF5) allows users to read only the desired components of the catalog into memory.

We have released the SCOTCH catalog as an HDF5 file consisting of a transient table and a host galaxy table. We present an overview of the SCOTCH catalog hierarchy in Fig. A.1, and provide Python code for retrieving basic information about transients and host galaxies below. Full tutorials can be found in the repository associated with this release.¹

Properties of Transient Host Galaxies

To load in the SCOTCH catalog, we use the Python package `h5py`²:

```
>> scotch = h5py.File("./scotch.hdf5", "r")
>> print(scotch.keys())
```

```
<KeysViewHDF5 ['HostTable', 'TransientTable']>
```

The host galaxy table is further broken down by transient class:

```
>> scotch_hosts = scotch['HostTable']
>> print(scotch_hosts.keys())
```

```
<KeysViewHDF5 ['AGN', 'KN', 'SLSN-I', 'SNII',
'SNIIb', 'SNIa', 'SNIb', 'SNIc', 'TDE']>
```

The parameters linked to each host galaxy are given by retrieving the hosts of a given class:

```
>> print(scotch_hosts['AGN'].keys())
```

```
<KeysViewHDF5 ['GID', 'T', 'TID', 'a0', 'a1',
'a_rot', 'b0', 'b1', 'dc2ID', 'ellipticity',
'logMstar', 'logSFR', 'mag_Y', 'mag_g', 'mag_i',
'mag_r', 'mag_u', 'mag_z', 'magerr_Y', 'magerr_g',
'magerr_i', 'magerr_r', 'magerr_u', 'magerr_z',
'n0', 'n1', 'w0', 'w1', 'z']>
```

Values for each parameter can then be retrieved for each event:

```
>> print(scotch_hosts['AGN']['logSFR'][0])
```

```
-0.4994781
```

¹https://github.com/LSSTDESC/transient-host-sims/blob/main/notebooks/SCOTCH_walkthroughs.ipynb

²<https://www.h5py.org/>

Recovering Transient Light Curves

We now consider the table of transient properties in SCOTCH, and focus on SNe II in the catalog.

```
>> scotch_transients = scotch['TransientTable']
>> SNII = scotch_transients["SNII"]
```

Each transient table is further broken down by transient model.

```
>> print(SNII.keys())

<KeysViewHDF5 ['SNII+HostXT_V19', 'SNII-NMF',
'SNII-Templates', 'SNIIIn+HostXT_V19',
'SNIIIn-MOSFIT']>
```

The details for these models are provided in § 4.2 of the main text as well as [263].

Below, we retrieve these models and plot the light curves of a single event for each model:

```
>> SNII_models = list(SNII.keys())
>>
>> bands = 'ugrizY'
>> cols_sns = sns.color_palette("colorblind", 10)
>> cols = [cols_sns[4], cols_sns[9], cols_sns[2],
>>         cols_sns[1], 'tab:red', cols_sns[5]]
>>
>> fig, axs = plt.subplots(nrows=3,
>>                          ncols=2, figsize=(10, 10),
>>                          sharex=True, sharey=True)
>> axs[2, 1].set_axis_off()
>> plt.subplots_adjust(hspace=0.25, wspace=0.2)
>>
>> for i in np.arange(len(SNII_models)):
>>     model = SNII_models[i]
>>     SNII_oneModel = SNII[model]
>>     ax = axs.ravel()[i]
>>     for j in np.arange(len(bands)):
>>         ax.plot(SNII_oneModel['MJD'][0],
>>                 SNII_oneModel['mag_%s'
>>                               % bands[j]][0],
```

```

>>         c=cols[j], label=bands[j])
>>     if i==0:
>>         ax.legend(bbox_to_anchor=(2.05, -1.7),
>>                 borderaxespad=0, ncol=2)
>>     ax.set_ylim((35, 23))
>>     ax.set_xlim((53120, 53300))
>>     ax.set_ylabel("mag$_{LSST}$")
>>     ax.set_title(model)
>>     axs.ravel()[4].set_xlabel("MJD");

```

This code produces Fig. A.2.

Figure A.2: Sample light curves from the SCOTCH catalog for each SN II model used.

Survey-Specific Analyses

SCOTCH is intended as a truth catalog, but for many purposes the goal is to simulate observations taken by real surveys with specific footprints and limited efficiency. In the associated tutorials for this work, we provide a basic example of how to emulate observations matching the depths and sky footprint of the LSST Deep Drilling Fields (DDFs), using PLAsTiCC data³ as a comparison.

We plot the results of our magnitude limit cuts in Fig. A.3, where we have also placed SCOTCH SNe realistically on the sky. The redshift distributions for SNe Ia and SLSNe-I now show reasonable agreement to those from the test set of the PLAsTiCC challenge. The remaining discrepancy reflects Milky Way extinction, which is considered in PLAsTiCC and not in SCOTCH; and the difference in how observational limits are incorporated into the SNANA simulated framework (as an efficiency versus SNR curve, and not as an explicit SNR cut as we have imposed here).

Because SCOTCH does not simulate Milky Way extinction or instrument systematics, some additional work is required to more accurately reflect the observed distribution of transients from a survey. We can roughly estimate these observational effects for an observational catalog such as the Zwicky Transient Facility Bright Transient Sample [ZTF BTS; 155]. We download the ZTF BTS, model the distribution of Galactic A_V values across the sample, and draw new values for SCOTCH transients. After mapping the given trigger criterion to LSST-*gr* bands, we arrive at the distribution of SNe Ia and SNe II in Fig. A.4. We find reasonable agreement, despite the facts that the photometric systems used are different and that the precise observing strategy of the survey is unknown.

The number of objects per class in SCOTCH do not represent realistic volumetric rates. However, SNANA provides calculations of the expected number of events per solid angle per survey time given the input volumetric rate models. These are shared in Table A.1 to enable re-sampling the simulation to create realistic volumetric populations.

We provide additional tutorials for comparing the properties of transient light curves and their host galaxies in the associated repository.

³<https://zenodo.org/record/2539456#.YmHSu5LMKNF>

Table A.1: Number of transients per year, n , predicted by each model for the entire sky and for $z < 3$. The relative amounts of core collapse SNe follow the relative rates measured by [444].

Class	Model name	n [yr^{-1}]
Ia	SALT2-Ia	21,773,710
	Iax	15,933,345
	91bg-like	5,035,905
Hydrogen-Rich Core-Collapse (2M total)		
SN II	SNII-Templates	15,652,660
	SNII-NMF	15,652,660
	SNII+HostXT_V19	31,402,045
SN II _n	SNII _n -MOSFiT	2,270,665
	SNII _n +HostXT_V19	2,270,665
Stripped Envelope / H-Poor Core-Collapse		
Ib	SNIb-Templates	5,217,675
	SNIb+HostXT_V19	5,217,675
Ic	SNIc-Templates	3,623,355
	SNIc+HostXT_V19	3,623,355
IcBL	SNIcBL+HostXT_V19	1,062,880
IIb	SNIIb+HostXT_V19	10,531,710
SLSN-I	SLSN-I-MOSFiT	53,290
KN	Kasen 2017	122,640
	Bulla 2019	122,640
TDE	TDE_MOSFiT	38,690

Figure A.3: **Top:** Redshift distributions for SNe simulated within the LSST DDFs. PLAsTiCC data (dashed lines) are compared to SCOTCH SNe after a cut to match the expected 5σ depth of the DDFs. **Bottom:** SCOTCH SNe Ia placed within an LSST DDF field on the sky and colored by redshift. SN Locations were generated by oversampling observations from within a simulated library of DDF observations with PZFlow [109]. The structure observed for SN locations is not physical, but reflects the limited number of observations used for oversampling. Additional details can be found at the repository for this work.

Figure A.4: Distribution for SCOTCH SNe post-processed to match the detection criteria of the ZTF BTS. Observed samples are shown as solid lines.

Appendix B

Consolidated Optical and UV Photometry of SN Ic 2020oi

Table B.1: Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi.

MJD	Phase	Band	Mag.	Uncertainty	Telescope
58856.46	+2.46	UVW2	>13.95	–	<i>Swift</i>
58856.79	+2.79	UVW2	>13.92	–	<i>Swift</i>
58857.45	+3.45	UVW2	>14.17	–	<i>Swift</i>
58858.85	+4.85	UVW2	>13.95	–	<i>Swift</i>
58859.49	+5.49	UVW2	>13.93	–	<i>Swift</i>
58860.38	+6.38	UVW2	>13.96	–	<i>Swift</i>
58861.25	+7.25	UVW2	>13.83	–	<i>Swift</i>
58877.19	+23.19	UVW2	>13.93	–	<i>Swift</i>
58887.68	+33.68	UVW2	>13.98	–	<i>Swift</i>
58898.57	+44.57	UVW2	>14.02	–	<i>Swift</i>
58907.25	+53.25	UVW2	>14.01	–	<i>Swift</i>
58856.46	+2.46	UVM2	>13.75	–	<i>Swift</i>
58857.46	+3.46	UVM2	>13.86	–	<i>Swift</i>
58858.86	+4.86	UVM2	>13.75	–	<i>Swift</i>
58860.38	+6.38	UVM2	>13.81	–	<i>Swift</i>
58861.25	+7.25	UVM2	>13.74	–	<i>Swift</i>
58877.19	+23.19	UVM2	>13.73	–	<i>Swift</i>
58887.68	+33.68	UVM2	>13.79	–	<i>Swift</i>
58898.57	+44.57	UVM2	>13.92	–	<i>Swift</i>
58907.25	+53.25	UVM2	>13.76	–	<i>Swift</i>
58856.45	+2.45	UVW1	>14.08	–	<i>Swift</i>
58856.79	+2.79	UVW1	>14.04	–	<i>Swift</i>
58857.45	+3.45	UVW1	>14.22	–	<i>Swift</i>
58858.84	+4.84	UVW1	>14.03	–	<i>Swift</i>
58859.48	+5.48	UVW1	>14.04	–	<i>Swift</i>
58859.81	+5.81	UVW1	>13.99	–	<i>Swift</i>
58859.97	+5.97	UVW1	>13.99	–	<i>Swift</i>
58860.38	+6.38	UVW1	>14.03	–	<i>Swift</i>
58861.24	+7.24	UVW1	>13.80	–	<i>Swift</i>
58877.19	+23.19	UVW1	>14.06	–	<i>Swift</i>
58887.68	+33.68	UVW1	>14.27	–	<i>Swift</i>
58898.57	+44.57	UVW1	>14.20	–	<i>Swift</i>
58907.25	+53.25	UVW1	>14.22	–	<i>Swift</i>

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58856.39	+2.39	<i>u</i>	15.37	0.06	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>u</i>	15.41	0.09	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>u</i>	15.41	0.09	LCO
58857.32	+3.32	<i>u</i>	15.60	0.07	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>u</i>	15.43	0.06	LCO
58859.05	+5.05	<i>u</i>	15.10	0.04	LCO
58860.05	+6.05	<i>u</i>	14.66	0.04	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>u</i>	14.10	0.04	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>u</i>	>14.72	–	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>u</i>	14.22	0.04	LCO
58864.75	+10.75	<i>u</i>	14.20	0.04	LCO
58866.30	+12.30	<i>u</i>	14.52	0.04	LCO
58867.30	+13.30	<i>u</i>	14.98	0.04	LCO
58868.27	+14.27	<i>u</i>	15.29	0.08	LCO
58869.27	+15.27	<i>u</i>	15.54	0.07	LCO
58870.27	+16.27	<i>u</i>	15.93	0.10	LCO
58871.26	+17.26	<i>u</i>	16.16	0.17	LCO
58872.29	+18.29	<i>u</i>	16.49	0.07	LCO
58872.35	+18.35	<i>u</i>	16.11	0.03	Swope
58873.09	+19.09	<i>u</i>	16.73	0.06	LCO
58874.28	+20.28	<i>u</i>	16.86	0.08	LCO
58875.25	+21.25	<i>u</i>	17.04	0.07	LCO
58876.33	+22.33	<i>u</i>	17.01	0.61	LCO
58876.33	+22.33	<i>u</i>	>14.02	–	LCO
58876.37	+22.37	<i>u</i>	17.46	0.04	Swope
58878.34	+24.34	<i>u</i>	17.14	0.19	LCO
58881.99	+27.99	<i>u</i>	17.10	0.10	LCO
58882.32	+28.32	<i>u</i>	17.99	0.05	Swope
58884.37	+30.37	<i>u</i>	17.32	0.16	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>u</i>	>15.72	–	LCO
58885.36	+31.36	<i>u</i>	18.12	0.08	Swope
58893.29	+39.29	<i>u</i>	16.54	0.03	Swope
58895.29	+41.29	<i>u</i>	18.55	0.09	Swope
58895.29	+41.29	<i>u</i>	>15.44	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58896.29	+42.29	<i>u</i>	18.37	0.11	Swope
58897.32	+43.32	<i>u</i>	17.42	0.04	Swope
58902.24	+48.24	<i>u</i>	>14.81	–	LCO
58903.28	+49.28	<i>u</i>	18.55	0.10	Swope
58904.33	+50.33	<i>u</i>	18.60	0.07	Swope
58905.29	+51.29	<i>u</i>	18.65	0.07	Swope
58906.10	+52.10	<i>u</i>	>15.62	–	LCO
58906.28	+52.28	<i>u</i>	18.77	0.08	Swope
58907.37	+53.37	<i>u</i>	18.38	0.08	Swope
58908.31	+54.31	<i>u</i>	18.65	0.10	Swope
58909.36	+55.36	<i>u</i>	18.59	0.07	Swope
58910.16	+56.16	<i>u</i>	>15.77	–	LCO
58910.25	+56.25	<i>u</i>	18.59	0.10	Swope
58911.20	+57.20	<i>u</i>	18.55	0.09	Swope
58912.27	+58.27	<i>u</i>	18.80	0.11	Swope
58919.14	+65.14	<i>u</i>	>15.81	–	LCO
58921.25	+67.25	<i>u</i>	17.44	0.07	Swope
58923.14	+69.14	<i>u</i>	>16.00	–	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>u</i>	16.94	0.10	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>u</i>	>16.29	–	LCO
58935.62	+81.62	<i>u</i>	>14.88	–	LCO
58935.62	+81.62	<i>u</i>	14.88	0.36	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>u</i>	15.00	0.36	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>u</i>	>15.00	–	LCO
58943.46	+89.46	<i>u</i>	14.67	0.36	LCO
58943.46	+89.46	<i>u</i>	>14.67	–	LCO
58952.44	+98.44	<i>u</i>	>16.07	–	LCO
58966.35	+112.35	<i>u</i>	>16.32	–	LCO
58974.11	+120.11	<i>u</i>	>15.64	–	LCO
58980.76	+126.76	<i>u</i>	>16.87	–	LCO
58988.31	+134.31	<i>u</i>	>16.04	–	LCO
58996.50	+142.50	<i>u</i>	>16.69	–	LCO
59002.74	+148.74	<i>u</i>	>18.18	–	LCO
59007.70	+153.70	<i>u</i>	>18.79	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

59014.79	+160.79	<i>u</i>	>19.02	-	LCO
59026.34	+172.34	<i>u</i>	>17.91	-	LCO
59032.34	+178.34	<i>u</i>	>19.29	-	LCO
59202.09	+348.09	<i>u</i>	>17.83	-	LCO
59208.07	+354.07	<i>u</i>	>17.84	-	LCO
59213.45	+359.45	<i>u</i>	>16.58	-	LCO
59214.05	+360.05	<i>u</i>	>16.73	-	LCO
59220.37	+366.37	<i>u</i>	>17.40	-	LCO
59226.10	+372.10	<i>u</i>	>17.77	-	LCO
59227.71	+373.71	<i>u</i>	>17.74	-	LCO
59232.37	+378.37	<i>u</i>	>17.12	-	LCO
59236.06	+382.06	<i>u</i>	>17.29	-	LCO
59245.42	+391.42	<i>u</i>	>17.76	-	LCO
59252.05	+398.05	<i>u</i>	>18.17	-	LCO
59257.33	+403.33	<i>u</i>	>17.73	-	LCO
59262.22	+408.22	<i>u</i>	>17.55	-	LCO
59267.12	+413.12	<i>u</i>	>16.91	-	LCO
58856.45	+2.45	<i>U</i>	>14.00	-	<i>Swift</i>
58856.79	+2.79	<i>U</i>	>14.00	-	<i>Swift</i>
58857.45	+3.45	<i>U</i>	>14.13	-	<i>Swift</i>
58858.85	+4.85	<i>U</i>	>13.96	-	<i>Swift</i>
58859.49	+5.49	<i>U</i>	>13.84	-	<i>Swift</i>
58860.38	+6.38	<i>U</i>	>13.61	-	<i>Swift</i>
58861.25	+7.25	<i>U</i>	>13.35	-	<i>Swift</i>
58877.19	+23.19	<i>U</i>	>14.31	-	<i>Swift</i>
58887.68	+33.68	<i>U</i>	>14.46	-	<i>Swift</i>
58887.69	+33.69	<i>U</i>	>14.32	-	<i>Swift</i>
58898.56	+44.56	<i>U</i>	>14.68	-	<i>Swift</i>
58898.57	+44.57	<i>U</i>	>14.33	-	<i>Swift</i>
58907.25	+53.25	<i>U</i>	>14.49	-	<i>Swift</i>
58907.26	+53.26	<i>U</i>	>14.36	-	<i>Swift</i>
58856.45	+2.45	<i>B</i>	>14.75	-	<i>Swift</i>
58856.79	+2.79	<i>B</i>	>14.81	-	<i>Swift</i>
58857.30	+3.30	<i>B</i>	15.66	0.41	Synthetic

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58857.45	+3.45	<i>B</i>	>14.79	–	<i>Swift</i>
58858.85	+4.85	<i>B</i>	>14.52	–	<i>Swift</i>
58859.49	+5.49	<i>B</i>	>14.44	–	<i>Swift</i>
58860.38	+6.38	<i>B</i>	>14.25	–	<i>Swift</i>
58861.25	+7.25	<i>B</i>	>13.99	–	<i>Swift</i>
58864.60	+10.60	<i>B</i>	14.30	0.37	Synthetic
58868.60	+14.60	<i>B</i>	14.63	0.38	Synthetic
58869.35	+15.35	<i>B</i>	14.58	0.03	Swope
58869.35	+15.35	<i>B</i>	14.73	0.03	Swope
58870.32	+16.32	<i>B</i>	14.88	0.03	Swope
58870.50	+16.50	<i>B</i>	15.02	0.39	Synthetic
58871.36	+17.36	<i>B</i>	15.13	0.03	Swope
58872.36	+18.36	<i>B</i>	15.30	0.03	Swope
58872.40	+18.40	<i>B</i>	15.14	0.39	Synthetic
58873.09	+19.09	<i>B</i>	>18.09	–	LCO
58875.00	+21.00	<i>B</i>	15.22	0.39	Synthetic
58875.38	+21.38	<i>B</i>	15.82	0.03	Swope
58876.37	+22.37	<i>B</i>	15.94	0.03	Swope
58876.70	+22.70	<i>B</i>	16.10	0.42	Synthetic
58878.06	+24.06	<i>B</i>	>16.25	–	LCO
58879.07	+25.07	<i>B</i>	>15.93	–	LCO
58880.30	+26.30	<i>B</i>	16.10	0.42	Synthetic
58880.40	+26.40	<i>B</i>	15.36	0.40	Synthetic
58880.44	+26.44	<i>B</i>	>18.29	–	Nickel
58882.33	+28.33	<i>B</i>	16.50	0.03	Swope
58883.01	+29.01	<i>B</i>	>17.54	–	LCO
58883.38	+29.38	<i>B</i>	16.55	0.03	Swope
58884.38	+30.38	<i>B</i>	16.54	0.03	Swope
58885.37	+31.37	<i>B</i>	16.62	0.03	Swope
58887.69	+33.69	<i>B</i>	>14.70	–	<i>Swift</i>
58892.00	+38.00	<i>B</i>	17.60	0.45	Synthetic
58893.30	+39.30	<i>B</i>	16.90	0.03	Swope
58894.32	+40.32	<i>B</i>	16.46	0.06	Swope
58895.00	+41.00	<i>B</i>	16.98	0.44	Synthetic

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58895.43	+41.43	<i>B</i>	>18.60	-	Nickel
58897.33	+43.33	<i>B</i>	16.34	0.03	Swope
58898.57	+44.57	<i>B</i>	>14.70	-	<i>Swift</i>
58903.29	+49.29	<i>B</i>	16.89	0.03	Swope
58904.34	+50.34	<i>B</i>	17.05	0.03	Swope
58905.31	+51.31	<i>B</i>	17.03	0.03	Swope
58906.29	+52.29	<i>B</i>	17.08	0.03	Swope
58906.30	+52.30	<i>B</i>	17.07	0.03	Swope
58907.26	+53.26	<i>B</i>	>14.75	-	<i>Swift</i>
58907.38	+53.38	<i>B</i>	17.02	0.03	Swope
58908.32	+54.32	<i>B</i>	17.02	0.03	Swope
58908.33	+54.33	<i>B</i>	17.05	0.03	Swope
58909.37	+55.37	<i>B</i>	17.11	0.03	Swope
58910.26	+56.26	<i>B</i>	17.03	0.03	Swope
58911.21	+57.21	<i>B</i>	17.12	0.03	Swope
58912.28	+58.28	<i>B</i>	17.13	0.03	Swope
58921.26	+67.26	<i>B</i>	16.80	0.10	Swope
58923.29	+69.29	<i>B</i>	16.71	0.04	Swope
58954.16	+100.16	<i>B</i>	>18.31	-	Nickel
58963.19	+109.19	<i>B</i>	>17.82	-	Nickel
58995.60	+141.60	<i>B</i>	16.79	0.45	Synthetic
58543.30	-310.70	<i>g</i>	18.19	0.15	ZTF
58559.31	-294.69	<i>g</i>	19.87	0.35	ZTF
58559.32	-294.68	<i>g</i>	19.83	0.34	ZTF
58575.29	-278.71	<i>g</i>	19.42	0.20	ZTF
58575.29	-278.71	<i>g</i>	18.79	0.19	ZTF
58580.26	-273.74	<i>g</i>	20.02	0.23	ZTF
58586.26	-267.74	<i>g</i>	20.03	0.27	ZTF
58596.23	-257.77	<i>g</i>	19.91	0.24	ZTF
58596.23	-257.77	<i>g</i>	20.13	0.32	ZTF
58600.21	-253.79	<i>g</i>	20.42	0.36	ZTF
58600.21	-253.79	<i>g</i>	20.09	0.28	ZTF
58628.19	-225.81	<i>g</i>	20.13	0.27	ZTF
58635.19	-218.81	<i>g</i>	19.74	0.17	ZTF

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58636.25	-217.75	<i>g</i>	19.47	0.17	ZTF
58639.23	-214.77	<i>g</i>	20.26	0.29	ZTF
58642.20	-211.80	<i>g</i>	20.24	0.32	ZTF
58846.55	-7.45	<i>g</i>	19.60	0.18	ZTF
58849.50	-4.50	<i>g</i>	20.45	0.36	ZTF
58856.31	+2.31	<i>g</i>	15.81	0.04	LCO
58856.33	+2.33	<i>g</i>	15.78	0.03	LCO
58856.33	+2.33	<i>g</i>	15.79	0.03	LCO
58856.35	+2.35	<i>g</i>	15.83	0.03	LCO
58856.37	+2.37	<i>g</i>	15.82	0.04	LCO
58856.41	+2.41	<i>g</i>	15.54	0.03	LCO
58856.73	+2.73	<i>g</i>	15.54	0.03	LCO
58856.73	+2.73	<i>g</i>	15.56	0.03	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>g</i>	15.53	0.40	Synthetic
58857.30	+3.30	<i>g</i>	15.32	0.03	LCO
58857.32	+3.32	<i>g</i>	15.34	0.03	LCO
58857.35	+3.35	<i>g</i>	15.38	0.03	LCO
58857.36	+3.36	<i>g</i>	15.21	0.12	LCO
58857.71	+3.71	<i>g</i>	15.21	0.03	LCO
58857.72	+3.72	<i>g</i>	15.17	0.03	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>g</i>	14.94	0.03	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>g</i>	14.86	0.03	LCO
58858.31	+4.31	<i>g</i>	14.92	0.03	LCO
58858.34	+4.34	<i>g</i>	14.88	0.03	LCO
58859.05	+5.05	<i>g</i>	14.63	0.03	LCO
58859.30	+5.30	<i>g</i>	14.52	0.03	LCO
58859.52	+5.52	<i>g</i>	14.39	0.03	ZTF
58859.69	+5.69	<i>g</i>	14.39	0.03	LCO
58860.05	+6.05	<i>g</i>	14.65	0.07	LCO
58860.05	+6.05	<i>g</i>	>16.55	-	LCO
58860.05	+6.05	<i>g</i>	14.23	0.03	LCO
58860.07	+6.07	<i>g</i>	14.15	0.03	LCO
58860.07	+6.07	<i>g</i>	14.16	0.03	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>g</i>	13.88	0.03	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58861.29	+7.29	<i>g</i>	13.96	0.03	LCO
58861.35	+7.35	<i>g</i>	13.83	0.03	LCO
58861.35	+7.35	<i>g</i>	13.85	0.03	LCO
58861.68	+7.68	<i>g</i>	13.78	0.03	LCO
58862.36	+8.36	<i>g</i>	13.65	0.03	LCO
58862.36	+8.36	<i>g</i>	13.66	0.03	LCO
58862.53	+8.53	<i>g</i>	13.58	0.04	Thacher
58863.53	+9.53	<i>g</i>	12.57	0.03	Thacher
58864.34	+10.34	<i>g</i>	13.51	0.04	Thacher
58864.60	+10.60	<i>g</i>	14.10	0.37	Synthetic
58864.75	+10.75	<i>g</i>	13.57	0.03	LCO
58865.45	+11.45	<i>g</i>	13.57	0.03	Thacher
58866.30	+12.30	<i>g</i>	13.60	0.03	LCO
58866.32	+12.32	<i>g</i>	13.62	0.03	Thacher
58866.57	+12.57	<i>g</i>	13.62	0.03	PS1
58867.30	+13.30	<i>g</i>	13.73	0.03	LCO
58867.30	+13.30	<i>g</i>	13.73	0.03	LCO
58867.30	+13.30	<i>g</i>	13.82	0.03	LCO
58867.35	+13.35	<i>g</i>	13.72	0.03	Thacher
58867.40	+13.40	<i>g</i>	13.77	0.03	LCO
58867.40	+13.40	<i>g</i>	13.79	0.03	LCO
58867.44	+13.44	<i>g</i>	13.87	0.03	ZTF
58868.27	+14.27	<i>g</i>	13.96	0.03	LCO
58868.60	+14.60	<i>g</i>	14.37	0.37	Synthetic
58869.27	+15.27	<i>g</i>	14.11	0.03	LCO
58869.35	+15.35	<i>g</i>	14.18	0.03	Swope
58869.36	+15.36	<i>g</i>	14.11	0.03	LCO
58869.36	+15.36	<i>g</i>	14.10	0.03	LCO
58869.57	+15.57	<i>g</i>	14.10	0.03	PS1
58870.27	+16.27	<i>g</i>	14.39	0.03	LCO
58870.50	+16.50	<i>g</i>	14.70	0.38	Synthetic
58871.27	+17.27	<i>g</i>	14.62	0.03	LCO
58871.32	+17.32	<i>g</i>	14.52	0.03	LCO
58871.32	+17.32	<i>g</i>	14.53	0.03	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58871.33	+17.33	<i>g</i>	14.42	0.03	Thacher
58871.35	+17.35	<i>g</i>	14.52	0.03	Swope
58871.44	+17.44	<i>g</i>	14.59	0.03	ZTF
58872.29	+18.29	<i>g</i>	14.68	0.03	LCO
58872.33	+18.33	<i>g</i>	14.60	0.03	Thacher
58872.35	+18.35	<i>g</i>	14.73	0.03	Swope
58872.35	+18.35	<i>g</i>	14.61	0.03	Swope
58872.40	+18.40	<i>g</i>	14.85	0.38	Synthetic
58873.09	+19.09	<i>g</i>	14.76	0.03	LCO
58873.09	+19.09	<i>g</i>	14.75	0.03	LCO
58873.09	+19.09	<i>g</i>	14.80	0.03	LCO
58873.40	+19.40	<i>g</i>	14.84	0.03	Thacher
58874.28	+20.28	<i>g</i>	14.97	0.03	LCO
58874.29	+20.29	<i>g</i>	14.94	0.03	Thacher
58875.00	+21.00	<i>g</i>	15.02	0.39	Synthetic
58875.25	+21.25	<i>g</i>	15.20	0.03	LCO
58875.38	+21.38	<i>g</i>	15.18	0.03	Swope
58875.46	+21.46	<i>g</i>	15.25	0.03	ZTF
58876.03	+22.03	<i>g</i>	15.23	0.03	LCO
58876.03	+22.03	<i>g</i>	15.21	0.03	LCO
58876.29	+22.29	<i>g</i>	15.16	0.05	Thacher
58876.33	+22.33	<i>g</i>	15.36	0.05	LCO
58876.36	+22.36	<i>g</i>	15.30	0.03	Swope
58876.70	+22.70	<i>g</i>	15.65	0.40	Synthetic
58877.03	+23.03	<i>g</i>	15.35	0.03	LCO
58877.03	+23.03	<i>g</i>	15.37	0.03	LCO
58877.26	+23.26	<i>g</i>	15.44	0.03	LCO
58877.26	+23.26	<i>g</i>	15.40	0.04	LCO
58878.06	+24.06	<i>g</i>	>16.42	–	LCO
58878.34	+24.34	<i>g</i>	15.55	0.03	LCO
58878.49	+24.49	<i>g</i>	15.62	0.03	ZTF
58879.08	+25.08	<i>g</i>	>16.75	–	LCO
58879.40	+25.40	<i>g</i>	14.97	0.39	Synthetic
58880.12	+26.12	<i>g</i>	15.62	0.03	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58880.12	+26.12	<i>g</i>	15.59	0.03	LCO
58880.28	+26.28	<i>g</i>	15.67	0.04	Thacher
58880.30	+26.30	<i>g</i>	15.86	0.41	Synthetic
58880.40	+26.40	<i>g</i>	15.25	0.39	Synthetic
58881.28	+27.28	<i>g</i>	15.75	0.04	Thacher
58881.46	+27.46	<i>g</i>	15.84	0.03	ZTF
58881.99	+27.99	<i>g</i>	15.78	0.03	LCO
58882.09	+28.09	<i>g</i>	15.80	0.03	LCO
58882.09	+28.09	<i>g</i>	15.85	0.03	LCO
58882.32	+28.32	<i>g</i>	15.92	0.03	Swope
58883.01	+29.01	<i>g</i>	15.90	0.04	LCO
58883.01	+29.01	<i>g</i>	15.91	0.04	LCO
58883.01	+29.01	<i>g</i>	>17.66	–	LCO
58883.12	+29.12	<i>g</i>	15.84	0.03	LCO
58883.12	+29.12	<i>g</i>	15.87	0.03	LCO
58883.38	+29.38	<i>g</i>	16.00	0.03	Swope
58883.99	+29.99	<i>g</i>	15.91	0.03	LCO
58884.00	+30.00	<i>g</i>	16.01	0.04	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>g</i>	16.00	0.03	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>g</i>	15.84	0.30	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>g</i>	16.01	0.03	Swope
58884.37	+30.37	<i>g</i>	>17.25	–	LCO
58884.44	+30.44	<i>g</i>	16.07	0.03	ZTF
58885.36	+31.36	<i>g</i>	16.08	0.03	Swope
58885.37	+31.37	<i>g</i>	15.99	0.04	Thacher
58885.38	+31.38	<i>g</i>	>15.89	–	Swope
58886.28	+32.28	<i>g</i>	16.08	0.07	Thacher
58887.43	+33.43	<i>g</i>	16.11	0.03	ZTF
58890.28	+36.28	<i>g</i>	15.78	0.22	Thacher
58892.00	+38.00	<i>g</i>	17.06	0.44	Synthetic
58892.26	+38.26	<i>g</i>	16.21	0.05	Thacher
58892.38	+38.38	<i>g</i>	16.28	0.03	ZTF
58893.25	+39.25	<i>g</i>	16.16	0.03	Thacher
58893.29	+39.29	<i>g</i>	16.33	0.03	Swope

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58894.25	+40.25	<i>g</i>	16.28	0.04	Thacher
58894.31	+40.31	<i>g</i>	16.34	0.03	Swope
58895.00	+41.00	<i>g</i>	16.69	0.43	Synthetic
58895.29	+41.29	<i>g</i>	>16.56	–	LCO
58895.29	+41.29	<i>g</i>	16.37	0.03	Swope
58895.38	+41.38	<i>g</i>	16.34	0.03	ZTF
58896.29	+42.29	<i>g</i>	16.38	0.04	Swope
58897.31	+43.31	<i>g</i>	16.06	0.03	Swope
58898.24	+44.24	<i>g</i>	16.44	0.04	Thacher
58898.42	+44.42	<i>g</i>	16.42	0.03	ZTF
58899.23	+45.23	<i>g</i>	16.44	0.05	Thacher
58899.40	+45.40	<i>g</i>	16.44	0.03	ZTF
58900.34	+46.34	<i>g</i>	16.48	0.05	Thacher
58902.24	+48.24	<i>g</i>	>16.54	–	LCO
58903.27	+49.27	<i>g</i>	16.51	0.03	Swope
58903.29	+49.29	<i>g</i>	16.33	0.04	Thacher
58903.36	+49.36	<i>g</i>	16.47	0.03	ZTF
58904.32	+50.32	<i>g</i>	16.52	0.03	Swope
58904.46	+50.46	<i>g</i>	16.54	0.03	ZTF
58905.29	+51.29	<i>g</i>	16.55	0.03	Swope
58905.31	+51.31	<i>g</i>	16.55	0.03	ZTF
58905.57	+51.57	<i>g</i>	15.93	0.11	Thacher
58906.28	+52.28	<i>g</i>	16.56	0.03	Swope
58906.33	+52.33	<i>g</i>	16.50	0.03	ZTF
58907.36	+53.36	<i>g</i>	16.58	0.03	Swope
58908.31	+54.31	<i>g</i>	16.57	0.03	Swope
58908.31	+54.31	<i>g</i>	16.59	0.03	Swope
58908.34	+54.34	<i>g</i>	16.55	0.03	ZTF
58909.36	+55.36	<i>g</i>	16.66	0.03	Swope
58910.25	+56.25	<i>g</i>	16.67	0.03	Swope
58911.20	+57.20	<i>g</i>	16.67	0.03	Swope
58911.40	+57.40	<i>g</i>	16.73	0.03	ZTF
58912.27	+58.27	<i>g</i>	16.68	0.03	Swope
58913.33	+59.33	<i>g</i>	16.62	0.03	ZTF

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58914.42	+60.42	<i>g</i>	16.76	0.04	ZTF
58915.44	+61.44	<i>g</i>	16.70	0.04	ZTF
58919.14	+65.14	<i>g</i>	16.05	0.04	LCO
58919.14	+65.14	<i>g</i>	>16.37	–	LCO
58923.14	+69.14	<i>g</i>	>17.07	–	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>g</i>	15.88	0.06	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>g</i>	>17.04	–	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>g</i>	16.72	0.36	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>g</i>	>16.72	–	LCO
58936.29	+82.29	<i>g</i>	17.21	0.04	ZTF
58939.34	+85.34	<i>g</i>	17.34	0.04	ZTF
58940.39	+86.39	<i>g</i>	17.32	0.04	ZTF
58941.46	+87.46	<i>g</i>	17.38	0.05	ZTF
58943.46	+89.46	<i>g</i>	>16.66	–	LCO
58943.46	+89.46	<i>g</i>	16.66	0.36	LCO
58952.44	+98.44	<i>g</i>	>17.71	–	LCO
58954.30	+100.30	<i>g</i>	17.82	0.04	ZTF
58955.30	+101.30	<i>g</i>	17.83	0.05	ZTF
58959.34	+105.34	<i>g</i>	>17.38	–	LCO
58962.23	+108.23	<i>g</i>	17.95	0.05	ZTF
58963.31	+109.31	<i>g</i>	18.13	0.05	ZTF
58965.23	+111.23	<i>g</i>	17.99	0.05	ZTF
58966.35	+112.35	<i>g</i>	>16.33	–	LCO
58967.23	+113.23	<i>g</i>	18.12	0.06	ZTF
58968.30	+114.30	<i>g</i>	18.33	0.06	ZTF
58971.28	+117.28	<i>g</i>	18.18	0.07	ZTF
58974.11	+120.11	<i>g</i>	>16.69	–	LCO
58974.21	+120.21	<i>g</i>	18.37	0.11	ZTF
58977.17	+123.17	<i>g</i>	19.41	0.33	ZTF
58980.19	+126.19	<i>g</i>	18.79	0.07	ZTF
58980.76	+126.76	<i>g</i>	>16.81	–	LCO
58986.22	+132.22	<i>g</i>	19.08	0.10	ZTF
58988.32	+134.32	<i>g</i>	>16.91	–	LCO
58991.17	+137.17	<i>g</i>	18.97	0.10	ZTF

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58994.23	+140.23	<i>g</i>	19.42	0.12	ZTF
58995.60	+141.60	<i>g</i>	16.60	0.43	Synthetic
58996.50	+142.50	<i>g</i>	>17.03	–	LCO
58997.20	+143.20	<i>g</i>	19.14	0.12	ZTF
59002.75	+148.75	<i>g</i>	>18.42	–	LCO
59007.71	+153.71	<i>g</i>	>18.14	–	LCO
59014.20	+160.20	<i>g</i>	20.23	0.28	ZTF
59014.80	+160.80	<i>g</i>	>18.73	–	LCO
59020.20	+166.20	<i>g</i>	19.92	0.22	ZTF
59023.22	+169.22	<i>g</i>	20.15	0.31	ZTF
59026.22	+172.22	<i>g</i>	19.02	0.18	ZTF
59026.35	+172.35	<i>g</i>	>16.83	–	LCO
59032.34	+178.34	<i>g</i>	>19.87	–	LCO
59038.72	+184.72	<i>g</i>	>19.25	–	LCO
59173.49	+319.49	<i>g</i>	20.16	0.34	ZTF
59177.53	+323.53	<i>g</i>	19.46	0.17	ZTF
59186.52	+332.52	<i>g</i>	18.81	0.23	ZTF
59193.46	+339.46	<i>g</i>	20.02	0.30	ZTF
59202.09	+348.09	<i>g</i>	>18.12	–	LCO
59203.53	+349.53	<i>g</i>	19.34	0.17	ZTF
59208.07	+354.07	<i>g</i>	>17.92	–	LCO
59214.05	+360.05	<i>g</i>	>17.34	–	LCO
59217.44	+363.44	<i>g</i>	19.46	0.24	ZTF
59220.37	+366.37	<i>g</i>	>17.94	–	LCO
59221.48	+367.48	<i>g</i>	19.45	0.18	ZTF
59226.11	+372.11	<i>g</i>	>17.17	–	LCO
59227.71	+373.71	<i>g</i>	>18.33	–	LCO
59232.37	+378.37	<i>g</i>	>16.88	–	LCO
59236.06	+382.06	<i>g</i>	>17.68	–	LCO
59245.42	+391.42	<i>g</i>	>18.21	–	LCO
59250.36	+396.36	<i>g</i>	20.10	0.36	ZTF
59252.06	+398.06	<i>g</i>	>17.65	–	LCO
59252.49	+398.49	<i>g</i>	20.10	0.25	ZTF
59257.33	+403.33	<i>g</i>	>18.74	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

59262.22	+408.22	<i>g</i>	>17.90	-	LCO
59267.12	+413.12	<i>g</i>	>16.98	-	LCO
58856.46	+2.46	<i>V</i>	>14.17	-	<i>Swift</i>
58856.80	+2.80	<i>V</i>	>14.17	-	<i>Swift</i>
58857.30	+3.30	<i>V</i>	15.29	0.40	Synthetic
58857.45	+3.45	<i>V</i>	>14.05	-	<i>Swift</i>
58858.85	+4.85	<i>V</i>	>13.85	-	<i>Swift</i>
58860.38	+6.38	<i>V</i>	>13.58	-	<i>Swift</i>
58861.25	+7.25	<i>V</i>	>13.40	-	<i>Swift</i>
58864.60	+10.60	<i>V</i>	13.57	0.35	Synthetic
58868.60	+14.60	<i>V</i>	13.78	0.36	Synthetic
58869.35	+15.35	<i>V</i>	13.80	0.03	Swope
58869.36	+15.36	<i>V</i>	13.64	0.03	LCO
58870.32	+16.32	<i>V</i>	13.83	0.03	Swope
58870.32	+16.32	<i>V</i>	13.90	0.03	Swope
58870.50	+16.50	<i>V</i>	14.02	0.36	Synthetic
58871.31	+17.31	<i>V</i>	13.89	0.03	LCO
58871.36	+17.36	<i>V</i>	14.12	0.03	Swope
58872.36	+18.36	<i>V</i>	14.30	0.03	Swope
58872.40	+18.40	<i>V</i>	14.31	0.37	Synthetic
58873.09	+19.09	<i>V</i>	>17.53	-	LCO
58875.00	+21.00	<i>V</i>	14.63	0.38	Synthetic
58875.38	+21.38	<i>V</i>	14.69	0.03	Swope
58876.37	+22.37	<i>V</i>	14.92	0.03	Swope
58876.70	+22.70	<i>V</i>	14.97	0.39	Synthetic
58877.19	+23.19	<i>V</i>	>13.84	-	<i>Swift</i>
58878.06	+24.06	<i>V</i>	>15.76	-	LCO
58879.08	+25.08	<i>V</i>	>15.62	-	LCO
58879.40	+25.40	<i>V</i>	14.87	0.38	Synthetic
58880.12	+26.12	<i>V</i>	>16.86	-	LCO
58880.30	+26.30	<i>V</i>	15.31	0.39	Synthetic
58880.40	+26.40	<i>V</i>	15.10	0.39	Synthetic
58880.44	+26.44	<i>V</i>	>17.76	-	Nickel
58882.33	+28.33	<i>V</i>	15.56	0.03	Swope

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58883.12	+29.12	<i>V</i>	15.26	0.03	LCO
58883.38	+29.38	<i>V</i>	15.67	0.03	Swope
58884.37	+30.37	<i>V</i>	15.63	0.03	Swope
58885.37	+31.37	<i>V</i>	15.73	0.03	Swope
58887.68	+33.68	<i>V</i>	>13.97	–	<i>Swift</i>
58892.00	+38.00	<i>V</i>	16.32	0.42	Synthetic
58893.30	+39.30	<i>V</i>	16.12	0.03	Swope
58894.32	+40.32	<i>V</i>	16.17	0.03	Swope
58895.00	+41.00	<i>V</i>	16.12	0.41	Synthetic
58895.30	+41.30	<i>V</i>	16.11	0.03	Swope
58895.43	+41.43	<i>V</i>	>18.67	–	Nickel
58895.44	+41.44	<i>V</i>	>18.43	–	Nickel
58896.30	+42.30	<i>V</i>	16.08	0.03	Swope
58897.32	+43.32	<i>V</i>	15.80	0.12	Swope
58898.57	+44.57	<i>V</i>	>14.05	–	<i>Swift</i>
58899.32	+45.32	<i>V</i>	>18.54	–	Nickel
58900.38	+46.38	<i>V</i>	>18.18	–	Nickel
58903.28	+49.28	<i>V</i>	16.27	0.03	Swope
58904.34	+50.34	<i>V</i>	16.40	0.03	Swope
58904.35	+50.35	<i>V</i>	>18.08	–	Nickel
58905.30	+51.30	<i>V</i>	16.41	0.03	Swope
58906.29	+52.29	<i>V</i>	16.43	0.03	Swope
58907.25	+53.25	<i>V</i>	>14.10	–	<i>Swift</i>
58907.37	+53.37	<i>V</i>	16.39	0.03	Swope
58908.32	+54.32	<i>V</i>	16.39	0.03	Swope
58908.32	+54.32	<i>V</i>	16.41	0.03	Swope
58909.37	+55.37	<i>V</i>	16.51	0.03	Swope
58910.26	+56.26	<i>V</i>	16.45	0.03	Swope
58911.21	+57.21	<i>V</i>	16.46	0.03	Swope
58912.28	+58.28	<i>V</i>	16.58	0.03	Swope
58921.26	+67.26	<i>V</i>	16.50	0.05	Swope
58923.29	+69.29	<i>V</i>	16.34	0.03	Swope
58963.20	+109.20	<i>V</i>	>17.59	–	Nickel
58995.60	+141.60	<i>V</i>	16.32	0.85	Synthetic

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58558.22	-295.78	<i>r</i>	18.58	0.18	ZTF
58575.37	-278.63	<i>r</i>	18.63	0.28	ZTF
58580.35	-273.65	<i>r</i>	20.23	0.33	ZTF
58583.28	-270.72	<i>r</i>	19.41	0.22	ZTF
58584.32	-269.68	<i>r</i>	20.14	0.34	ZTF
58588.34	-265.66	<i>r</i>	19.48	0.30	ZTF
58589.27	-264.73	<i>r</i>	18.89	0.29	ZTF
58597.33	-256.67	<i>r</i>	19.87	0.24	ZTF
58633.20	-220.80	<i>r</i>	20.12	0.36	ZTF
58634.26	-219.74	<i>r</i>	20.29	0.28	ZTF
58637.19	-216.81	<i>r</i>	20.25	0.28	ZTF
58638.23	-215.77	<i>r</i>	20.10	0.28	ZTF
58834.52	-19.48	<i>r</i>	18.72	0.20	ZTF
58855.54	+1.54	<i>r</i>	16.96	0.03	ZTF
58856.31	+2.31	<i>r</i>	15.98	0.04	LCO
58856.31	+2.31	<i>r</i>	>16.51	–	LCO
58856.33	+2.33	<i>r</i>	16.15	0.03	LCO
58856.33	+2.33	<i>r</i>	16.15	0.03	LCO
58856.37	+2.37	<i>r</i>	15.54	0.04	LCO
58856.41	+2.41	<i>r</i>	>16.44	–	LCO
58856.41	+2.41	<i>r</i>	16.62	0.28	LCO
58856.41	+2.41	<i>r</i>	15.79	0.04	LCO
58856.70	+2.70	<i>r</i>	15.92	0.04	LCO
58856.74	+2.74	<i>r</i>	15.74	0.03	LCO
58856.74	+2.74	<i>r</i>	15.74	0.03	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>r</i>	15.45	0.03	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>r</i>	15.39	0.03	Synthetic
58857.30	+3.30	<i>r</i>	15.20	0.03	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>r</i>	>16.84	–	LCO
58857.32	+3.32	<i>r</i>	>17.03	–	LCO
58857.32	+3.32	<i>r</i>	15.51	0.03	LCO
58857.35	+3.35	<i>r</i>	>17.23	–	LCO
58857.35	+3.35	<i>r</i>	15.48	0.03	LCO
58857.37	+3.37	<i>r</i>	15.66	0.18	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58857.72	+3.72	<i>r</i>	15.24	0.03	LCO
58857.72	+3.72	<i>r</i>	15.09	0.03	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>r</i>	14.87	0.04	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>r</i>	14.96	0.03	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>r</i>	14.97	0.03	LCO
58858.31	+4.31	<i>r</i>	15.00	0.03	LCO
58858.34	+4.34	<i>r</i>	14.91	0.03	LCO
58859.05	+5.05	<i>r</i>	14.80	0.03	LCO
58859.30	+5.30	<i>r</i>	14.58	0.03	LCO
58859.48	+5.48	<i>r</i>	14.39	0.03	ZTF
58859.69	+5.69	<i>r</i>	14.46	0.03	LCO
58860.05	+6.05	<i>r</i>	14.33	0.03	LCO
58860.08	+6.08	<i>r</i>	14.31	0.03	LCO
58860.08	+6.08	<i>r</i>	14.32	0.03	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>r</i>	14.04	0.03	LCO
58861.29	+7.29	<i>r</i>	14.00	0.03	LCO
58861.35	+7.35	<i>r</i>	14.00	0.03	LCO
58861.35	+7.35	<i>r</i>	14.05	0.03	LCO
58861.68	+7.68	<i>r</i>	13.98	0.03	LCO
58862.36	+8.36	<i>r</i>	13.87	0.03	LCO
58862.37	+8.37	<i>r</i>	13.88	0.03	LCO
58864.31	+10.31	<i>r</i>	13.58	0.04	LCO
58864.34	+10.34	<i>r</i>	13.62	0.03	Thacher
58864.60	+10.60	<i>r</i>	13.54	0.03	Synthetic
58864.75	+10.75	<i>r</i>	13.54	0.03	LCO
58864.75	+10.75	<i>r</i>	13.62	0.03	LCO
58864.75	+10.75	<i>r</i>	13.54	0.03	LCO
58865.46	+11.46	<i>r</i>	13.56	0.04	Thacher
58866.31	+12.31	<i>r</i>	13.50	0.03	LCO
58866.32	+12.32	<i>r</i>	13.57	0.03	Thacher
58867.30	+13.30	<i>r</i>	13.56	0.03	LCO
58867.35	+13.35	<i>r</i>	13.57	0.03	Thacher
58867.40	+13.40	<i>r</i>	13.56	0.03	LCO
58867.40	+13.40	<i>r</i>	13.59	0.03	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58867.48	+13.48	<i>r</i>	13.51	0.03	ZTF
58868.27	+14.27	<i>r</i>	13.68	0.03	LCO
58868.27	+14.27	<i>r</i>	13.50	0.03	LCO
58868.60	+14.60	<i>r</i>	13.65	0.03	Synthetic
58869.27	+15.27	<i>r</i>	13.82	0.03	LCO
58869.35	+15.35	<i>r</i>	13.75	0.03	Swope
58869.35	+15.35	<i>r</i>	13.62	0.03	Swope
58869.36	+15.36	<i>r</i>	13.67	0.03	LCO
58869.36	+15.36	<i>r</i>	13.68	0.03	LCO
58869.57	+15.57	<i>r</i>	13.63	0.03	PS1
58870.27	+16.27	<i>r</i>	14.00	0.03	LCO
58870.31	+16.31	<i>r</i>	13.69	0.03	Swope
58870.50	+16.50	<i>r</i>	13.82	0.03	Synthetic
58871.27	+17.27	<i>r</i>	14.00	0.03	LCO
58871.32	+17.32	<i>r</i>	13.86	0.03	LCO
58871.32	+17.32	<i>r</i>	13.92	0.03	LCO
58871.32	+17.32	<i>r</i>	13.93	0.03	LCO
58871.34	+17.34	<i>r</i>	13.88	0.03	Thacher
58871.35	+17.35	<i>r</i>	13.79	0.03	Swope
58871.50	+17.50	<i>r</i>	13.86	0.03	ZTF
58872.29	+18.29	<i>r</i>	13.96	0.03	LCO
58872.33	+18.33	<i>r</i>	13.99	0.03	Thacher
58872.35	+18.35	<i>r</i>	14.06	0.03	Swope
58872.40	+18.40	<i>r</i>	14.02	0.03	Synthetic
58873.09	+19.09	<i>r</i>	14.09	0.03	LCO
58873.10	+19.10	<i>r</i>	14.16	0.03	LCO
58873.10	+19.10	<i>r</i>	14.14	0.03	LCO
58873.40	+19.40	<i>r</i>	14.09	0.03	Thacher
58874.28	+20.28	<i>r</i>	14.22	0.03	LCO
58874.29	+20.29	<i>r</i>	14.26	0.03	Thacher
58874.37	+20.37	<i>r</i>	14.28	0.03	Swope
58875.00	+21.00	<i>r</i>	14.34	0.03	Synthetic
58875.26	+21.26	<i>r</i>	14.46	0.03	LCO
58875.37	+21.37	<i>r</i>	14.33	0.03	Swope

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58875.52	+21.52	<i>r</i>	14.38	0.03	ZTF
58876.03	+22.03	<i>r</i>	14.52	0.03	LCO
58876.03	+22.03	<i>r</i>	14.54	0.03	LCO
58876.29	+22.29	<i>r</i>	14.45	0.04	Thacher
58876.34	+22.34	<i>r</i>	14.62	0.03	LCO
58876.36	+22.36	<i>r</i>	14.49	0.03	Swope
58876.70	+22.70	<i>r</i>	14.57	0.03	Synthetic
58877.03	+23.03	<i>r</i>	14.64	0.03	LCO
58877.03	+23.03	<i>r</i>	>17.96	–	LCO
58877.03	+23.03	<i>r</i>	14.62	0.03	LCO
58877.26	+23.26	<i>r</i>	14.65	0.03	LCO
58877.26	+23.26	<i>r</i>	14.68	0.03	LCO
58878.28	+24.28	<i>r</i>	14.60	0.04	Thacher
58878.34	+24.34	<i>r</i>	14.83	0.03	LCO
58878.36	+24.36	<i>r</i>	14.80	0.03	ZTF
58879.40	+25.40	<i>r</i>	14.92	0.03	Synthetic
58880.12	+26.12	<i>r</i>	14.96	0.03	LCO
58880.12	+26.12	<i>r</i>	>17.30	–	LCO
58880.12	+26.12	<i>r</i>	15.02	0.03	LCO
58880.29	+26.29	<i>r</i>	15.03	0.03	Thacher
58880.30	+26.30	<i>r</i>	15.02	0.03	Synthetic
58880.40	+26.40	<i>r</i>	15.03	0.03	Synthetic
58880.44	+26.44	<i>r</i>	>18.07	–	Nickel
58881.28	+27.28	<i>r</i>	15.11	0.03	Thacher
58881.54	+27.54	<i>r</i>	15.02	0.03	ZTF
58882.00	+28.00	<i>r</i>	15.27	0.03	LCO
58882.09	+28.09	<i>r</i>	15.20	0.03	LCO
58882.09	+28.09	<i>r</i>	15.20	0.03	LCO
58882.32	+28.32	<i>r</i>	15.31	0.03	Swope
58883.01	+29.01	<i>r</i>	15.24	0.03	LCO
58883.12	+29.12	<i>r</i>	15.28	0.03	LCO
58883.12	+29.12	<i>r</i>	15.34	0.03	LCO
58883.37	+29.37	<i>r</i>	15.40	0.03	Swope

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58884.00	+30.00	<i>r</i>	15.42	0.03	LCO
58884.00	+30.00	<i>r</i>	15.39	0.03	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>r</i>	>18.20	–	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>r</i>	15.32	0.03	Swope
58884.37	+30.37	<i>r</i>	15.42	0.03	LCO
58884.52	+30.52	<i>r</i>	15.34	0.03	ZTF
58885.35	+31.35	<i>r</i>	15.43	0.03	Swope
58886.28	+32.28	<i>r</i>	15.51	0.04	Thacher
58887.52	+33.52	<i>r</i>	15.46	0.03	ZTF
58890.28	+36.28	<i>r</i>	15.61	0.06	Thacher
58892.00	+38.00	<i>r</i>	15.83	0.03	Synthetic
58892.27	+38.27	<i>r</i>	15.85	0.04	Thacher
58892.32	+38.32	<i>r</i>	15.77	0.03	ZTF
58893.25	+39.25	<i>r</i>	15.89	0.03	Thacher
58893.29	+39.29	<i>r</i>	15.98	0.03	Swope
58894.26	+40.26	<i>r</i>	16.00	0.03	Thacher
58894.31	+40.31	<i>r</i>	15.99	0.03	Swope
58895.00	+41.00	<i>r</i>	15.96	0.03	Synthetic
58895.24	+41.24	<i>r</i>	16.56	0.26	Swope
58895.28	+41.28	<i>r</i>	15.91	0.03	Swope
58895.29	+41.29	<i>r</i>	>16.39	–	LCO
58895.43	+41.43	<i>r</i>	15.99	0.17	Nickel
58895.44	+41.44	<i>r</i>	>19.01	–	Nickel
58895.44	+41.44	<i>r</i>	15.84	0.03	ZTF
58896.29	+42.29	<i>r</i>	15.97	0.03	Swope
58897.31	+43.31	<i>r</i>	16.15	0.03	Swope
58897.31	+43.31	<i>r</i>	15.91	0.08	Swope
58898.24	+44.24	<i>r</i>	16.17	0.04	Thacher
58898.37	+44.37	<i>r</i>	15.90	0.03	ZTF
58899.23	+45.23	<i>r</i>	16.05	0.04	Thacher
58899.44	+45.44	<i>r</i>	16.01	0.03	ZTF
58900.34	+46.34	<i>r</i>	16.11	0.04	Thacher
58900.38	+46.38	<i>r</i>	16.13	0.31	Nickel
58900.44	+46.44	<i>r</i>	16.04	0.03	ZTF

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58901.42	+47.42	<i>r</i>	16.08	0.03	ZTF
58902.24	+48.24	<i>r</i>	>16.54	–	LCO
58902.26	+48.26	<i>r</i>	16.01	0.04	Thacher
58903.27	+49.27	<i>r</i>	16.24	0.04	Swope
58903.27	+49.27	<i>r</i>	16.16	0.03	Swope
58903.29	+49.29	<i>r</i>	16.24	0.04	Thacher
58904.32	+50.32	<i>r</i>	16.19	0.03	Swope
58904.35	+50.35	<i>r</i>	>18.74	–	Nickel
58904.47	+50.47	<i>r</i>	16.21	0.03	ZTF
58905.28	+51.28	<i>r</i>	16.23	0.03	Swope
58905.28	+51.28	<i>r</i>	16.34	0.03	Swope
58905.57	+51.57	<i>r</i>	16.28	0.07	Thacher
58906.27	+52.27	<i>r</i>	16.24	0.03	Swope
58906.45	+52.45	<i>r</i>	16.25	0.03	ZTF
58907.36	+53.36	<i>r</i>	16.34	0.03	Swope
58908.30	+54.30	<i>r</i>	16.41	0.03	Swope
58908.30	+54.30	<i>r</i>	16.45	0.03	Swope
58908.45	+54.45	<i>r</i>	16.26	0.03	ZTF
58909.35	+55.35	<i>r</i>	16.37	0.03	Swope
58910.16	+56.16	<i>r</i>	>17.32	–	LCO
58910.24	+56.24	<i>r</i>	16.39	0.03	Swope
58911.20	+57.20	<i>r</i>	16.41	0.03	Swope
58911.45	+57.45	<i>r</i>	16.42	0.03	ZTF
58912.27	+58.27	<i>r</i>	16.19	0.12	Swope
58912.45	+58.45	<i>r</i>	16.45	0.03	ZTF
58913.45	+59.45	<i>r</i>	16.42	0.03	ZTF
58914.27	+60.27	<i>r</i>	>17.17	–	LCO
58914.38	+60.38	<i>r</i>	16.53	0.03	ZTF
58915.40	+61.40	<i>r</i>	16.49	0.04	ZTF
58919.14	+65.14	<i>r</i>	>16.41	–	LCO
58923.14	+69.14	<i>r</i>	>17.24	–	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>r</i>	>17.02	–	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>r</i>	>13.08	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58935.64	+81.64	<i>r</i>	16.52	0.36	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>r</i>	>16.52	–	LCO
58936.41	+82.41	<i>r</i>	17.20	0.04	ZTF
58939.36	+85.36	<i>r</i>	17.58	0.10	ZTF
58942.51	+88.51	<i>r</i>	17.22	0.05	PS1
58943.46	+89.46	<i>r</i>	16.16	0.36	LCO
58943.46	+89.46	<i>r</i>	>16.16	–	LCO
58952.44	+98.44	<i>r</i>	>17.75	–	LCO
58954.18	+100.18	<i>r</i>	>19.56	–	Nickel
58954.26	+100.26	<i>r</i>	17.79	0.04	ZTF
58955.27	+101.27	<i>r</i>	17.77	0.04	ZTF
58955.28	+101.28	<i>r</i>	18.21	0.07	ZTF
58959.34	+105.34	<i>r</i>	>17.53	–	LCO
58962.28	+108.28	<i>r</i>	18.17	0.06	ZTF
58963.21	+109.21	<i>r</i>	>19.12	–	Nickel
58964.27	+110.27	<i>r</i>	18.06	0.05	ZTF
58965.29	+111.29	<i>r</i>	18.14	0.05	ZTF
58966.35	+112.35	<i>r</i>	>16.59	–	LCO
58968.20	+114.20	<i>r</i>	18.12	0.05	ZTF
58971.21	+117.21	<i>r</i>	18.37	0.07	ZTF
58974.11	+120.11	<i>r</i>	>16.83	–	LCO
58974.25	+120.25	<i>r</i>	19.40	0.30	ZTF
58976.42	+122.42	<i>r</i>	17.96	0.16	PS1
58978.29	+124.29	<i>r</i>	19.55	0.24	ZTF
58980.25	+126.25	<i>r</i>	19.19	0.12	ZTF
58980.76	+126.76	<i>r</i>	>16.86	–	LCO
58988.32	+134.32	<i>r</i>	>16.91	–	LCO
58994.21	+140.21	<i>r</i>	19.35	0.14	ZTF
58995.60	+141.60	<i>r</i>	16.22	0.05	Synthetic
58996.50	+142.50	<i>r</i>	>17.18	–	LCO
59002.75	+148.75	<i>r</i>	>18.54	–	LCO
59007.71	+153.71	<i>r</i>	>18.50	–	LCO
59014.23	+160.23	<i>r</i>	20.08	0.28	ZTF
59014.80	+160.80	<i>r</i>	>18.73	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

59017.24	+163.24	<i>r</i>	20.33	0.32	ZTF
59020.24	+166.24	<i>r</i>	20.00	0.28	ZTF
59032.34	+178.34	<i>r</i>	>20.04	–	LCO
59038.72	+184.72	<i>r</i>	>19.34	–	LCO
59175.50	+321.50	<i>r</i>	18.75	0.33	ZTF
59193.54	+339.54	<i>r</i>	19.91	0.27	ZTF
59202.10	+348.10	<i>r</i>	>18.46	–	LCO
59203.50	+349.50	<i>r</i>	19.89	0.34	ZTF
59208.07	+354.07	<i>r</i>	>18.22	–	LCO
59214.05	+360.05	<i>r</i>	>17.97	–	LCO
59217.41	+363.41	<i>r</i>	19.58	0.28	ZTF
59220.37	+366.37	<i>r</i>	>17.88	–	LCO
59225.51	+371.51	<i>r</i>	18.98	0.30	ZTF
59226.11	+372.11	<i>r</i>	>17.59	–	LCO
59227.72	+373.72	<i>r</i>	>18.37	–	LCO
59232.38	+378.38	<i>r</i>	>16.59	–	LCO
59236.06	+382.06	<i>r</i>	>17.78	–	LCO
59245.42	+391.42	<i>r</i>	>18.30	–	LCO
59252.06	+398.06	<i>r</i>	>17.81	–	LCO
59252.33	+398.33	<i>r</i>	20.21	0.30	ZTF
59257.33	+403.33	<i>r</i>	>18.84	–	LCO
59262.23	+408.23	<i>r</i>	>18.25	–	LCO
59267.12	+413.12	<i>r</i>	>17.02	–	LCO
59275.38	+421.38	<i>r</i>	19.55	0.22	ZTF
58873.25	+19.25	<i>G</i>	14.29	0.20	Gaia
58547.44	-306.56	<i>i</i>	19.47	0.32	ZTF
58856.31	+2.31	<i>i</i>	17.52	0.12	LCO
58856.34	+2.34	<i>i</i>	16.47	0.04	LCO
58856.34	+2.34	<i>i</i>	16.57	0.04	LCO
58856.37	+2.37	<i>i</i>	16.15	0.05	LCO
58856.41	+2.41	<i>i</i>	16.12	0.04	LCO
58856.70	+2.70	<i>i</i>	>14.68	–	LCO
58856.70	+2.70	<i>i</i>	15.11	0.05	LCO
58856.70	+2.70	<i>i</i>	15.75	0.07	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58856.74	+2.74	<i>i</i>	16.08	0.06	LCO
58856.74	+2.74	<i>i</i>	16.06	0.03	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>i</i>	15.93	0.04	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>i</i>	15.55	0.40	Synthetic
58857.32	+3.32	<i>i</i>	15.82	0.03	LCO
58857.35	+3.35	<i>i</i>	15.74	0.03	LCO
58857.72	+3.72	<i>i</i>	15.30	0.04	LCO
58857.72	+3.72	<i>i</i>	>16.74	–	LCO
58857.72	+3.72	<i>i</i>	15.39	0.04	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>i</i>	15.28	0.03	LCO
58858.30	+4.30	<i>i</i>	15.29	0.03	LCO
58858.31	+4.31	<i>i</i>	15.31	0.03	LCO
58858.34	+4.34	<i>i</i>	15.18	0.03	LCO
58859.05	+5.05	<i>i</i>	14.97	0.03	LCO
58859.30	+5.30	<i>i</i>	14.88	0.03	LCO
58859.69	+5.69	<i>i</i>	14.75	0.03	LCO
58860.05	+6.05	<i>i</i>	14.58	0.03	LCO
58860.08	+6.08	<i>i</i>	14.63	0.03	LCO
58860.08	+6.08	<i>i</i>	14.59	0.03	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>i</i>	14.34	0.03	LCO
58861.05	+7.05	<i>i</i>	14.28	0.03	LCO
58861.29	+7.29	<i>i</i>	14.31	0.03	LCO
58861.35	+7.35	<i>i</i>	14.38	0.03	LCO
58861.35	+7.35	<i>i</i>	14.35	0.03	LCO
58861.69	+7.69	<i>i</i>	14.20	0.03	LCO
58861.69	+7.69	<i>i</i>	>15.85	–	LCO
58861.69	+7.69	<i>i</i>	14.00	0.03	LCO
58862.37	+8.37	<i>i</i>	14.08	0.03	LCO
58862.37	+8.37	<i>i</i>	14.07	0.03	LCO
58862.53	+8.53	<i>i</i>	14.02	0.04	Thacher
58864.31	+10.31	<i>i</i>	13.87	0.04	LCO
58864.34	+10.34	<i>i</i>	13.83	0.03	Thacher
58864.60	+10.60	<i>i</i>	13.79	0.35	Synthetic
58864.76	+10.76	<i>i</i>	13.89	0.03	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58865.46	+11.46	<i>i</i>	13.76	0.05	Thacher
58866.31	+12.31	<i>i</i>	13.73	0.03	LCO
58866.33	+12.33	<i>i</i>	13.79	0.03	Thacher
58866.56	+12.56	<i>i</i>	13.76	0.03	PS1
58867.30	+13.30	<i>i</i>	13.84	0.03	LCO
58867.35	+13.35	<i>i</i>	13.82	0.03	Thacher
58867.40	+13.40	<i>i</i>	13.79	0.03	LCO
58868.28	+14.28	<i>i</i>	14.00	0.03	LCO
58868.60	+14.60	<i>i</i>	13.84	0.35	Synthetic
58869.27	+15.27	<i>i</i>	13.98	0.03	LCO
58869.35	+15.35	<i>i</i>	13.85	0.03	Swope
58869.36	+15.36	<i>i</i>	13.92	0.03	LCO
58869.36	+15.36	<i>i</i>	13.94	0.03	LCO
58870.27	+16.27	<i>i</i>	14.25	0.03	LCO
58870.32	+16.32	<i>i</i>	13.97	0.03	Swope
58870.32	+16.32	<i>i</i>	13.88	0.03	Swope
58870.50	+16.50	<i>i</i>	13.91	0.35	Synthetic
58871.32	+17.32	<i>i</i>	14.13	0.03	LCO
58871.32	+17.32	<i>i</i>	14.06	0.03	LCO
58871.34	+17.34	<i>i</i>	14.06	0.03	Thacher
58871.35	+17.35	<i>i</i>	14.03	0.03	Swope
58872.29	+18.29	<i>i</i>	14.07	0.03	LCO
58872.29	+18.29	<i>i</i>	14.15	0.03	LCO
58872.29	+18.29	<i>i</i>	14.07	0.03	LCO
58872.33	+18.33	<i>i</i>	14.12	0.03	Thacher
58872.35	+18.35	<i>i</i>	14.28	0.03	Swope
58872.40	+18.40	<i>i</i>	13.79	0.35	Synthetic
58873.09	+19.09	<i>i</i>	14.30	0.03	LCO
58873.10	+19.10	<i>i</i>	14.22	0.03	LCO
58873.10	+19.10	<i>i</i>	14.23	0.03	LCO
58873.40	+19.40	<i>i</i>	14.24	0.03	Thacher
58874.29	+20.29	<i>i</i>	>16.62	–	LCO
58874.29	+20.29	<i>i</i>	14.36	0.03	LCO
58874.29	+20.29	<i>i</i>	14.34	0.03	Thacher

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58874.29	+20.29	<i>i</i>	14.53	0.08	LCO
58875.00	+21.00	<i>i</i>	14.25	0.36	Synthetic
58875.26	+21.26	<i>i</i>	14.56	0.03	LCO
58875.38	+21.38	<i>i</i>	14.46	0.03	Swope
58876.03	+22.03	<i>i</i>	14.60	0.03	LCO
58876.03	+22.03	<i>i</i>	14.61	0.03	LCO
58876.29	+22.29	<i>i</i>	14.39	0.04	Thacher
58876.34	+22.34	<i>i</i>	14.60	0.04	LCO
58876.36	+22.36	<i>i</i>	14.62	0.03	Swope
58876.70	+22.70	<i>i</i>	14.04	0.36	Synthetic
58877.03	+23.03	<i>i</i>	14.75	0.03	LCO
58877.03	+23.03	<i>i</i>	14.71	0.03	LCO
58877.27	+23.27	<i>i</i>	14.70	0.03	LCO
58878.07	+24.07	<i>i</i>	14.75	0.03	LCO
58878.07	+24.07	<i>i</i>	14.75	0.03	LCO
58878.07	+24.07	<i>i</i>	>15.15	–	LCO
58878.29	+24.29	<i>i</i>	14.77	0.04	Thacher
58878.34	+24.34	<i>i</i>	14.84	0.03	LCO
58879.40	+25.40	<i>i</i>	14.97	0.38	Synthetic
58880.12	+26.12	<i>i</i>	15.08	0.03	LCO
58880.12	+26.12	<i>i</i>	15.05	0.03	LCO
58880.29	+26.29	<i>i</i>	15.06	0.03	Thacher
58880.30	+26.30	<i>i</i>	14.99	0.38	Synthetic
58880.40	+26.40	<i>i</i>	15.13	0.39	Synthetic
58880.44	+26.44	<i>i</i>	>17.34	–	Nickel
58881.28	+27.28	<i>i</i>	15.16	0.03	Thacher
58882.00	+28.00	<i>i</i>	>18.24	–	LCO
58882.00	+28.00	<i>i</i>	15.26	0.03	LCO
58882.00	+28.00	<i>i</i>	15.19	0.10	LCO
58882.09	+28.09	<i>i</i>	15.31	0.03	LCO
58882.09	+28.09	<i>i</i>	15.28	0.03	LCO
58882.32	+28.32	<i>i</i>	15.38	0.03	Swope
58883.12	+29.12	<i>i</i>	15.34	0.03	LCO
58883.12	+29.12	<i>i</i>	15.31	0.03	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58883.37	+29.37	<i>i</i>	15.48	0.03	Swope
58884.00	+30.00	<i>i</i>	15.44	0.03	LCO
58884.00	+30.00	<i>i</i>	15.41	0.03	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>i</i>	15.50	0.03	LCO
58884.37	+30.37	<i>i</i>	15.22	0.03	Swope
58885.35	+31.35	<i>i</i>	15.53	0.03	Swope
58886.28	+32.28	<i>i</i>	15.57	0.04	Thacher
58890.28	+36.28	<i>i</i>	15.62	0.06	Thacher
58892.00	+38.00	<i>i</i>	15.25	0.39	Synthetic
58892.27	+38.27	<i>i</i>	15.89	0.04	Thacher
58893.25	+39.25	<i>i</i>	15.90	0.03	Thacher
58893.29	+39.29	<i>i</i>	15.97	0.03	Swope
58894.26	+40.26	<i>i</i>	16.03	0.04	Thacher
58894.31	+40.31	<i>i</i>	16.08	0.03	Swope
58895.00	+41.00	<i>i</i>	15.92	0.41	Synthetic
58895.29	+41.29	<i>i</i>	16.01	0.03	Swope
58895.29	+41.29	<i>i</i>	>16.20	–	LCO
58895.43	+41.43	<i>i</i>	15.31	0.07	Nickel
58895.44	+41.44	<i>i</i>	>18.83	–	Nickel
58896.29	+42.29	<i>i</i>	15.45	0.04	Swope
58897.31	+43.31	<i>i</i>	15.75	0.03	Swope
58898.24	+44.24	<i>i</i>	16.01	0.04	Thacher
58899.24	+45.24	<i>i</i>	16.24	0.05	Thacher
58900.35	+46.35	<i>i</i>	16.06	0.04	Thacher
58900.38	+46.38	<i>i</i>	>18.23	–	Nickel
58902.24	+48.24	<i>i</i>	>16.52	–	LCO
58902.26	+48.26	<i>i</i>	16.12	0.06	Thacher
58903.27	+49.27	<i>i</i>	16.25	0.03	Swope
58903.29	+49.29	<i>i</i>	16.10	0.04	Thacher
58904.32	+50.32	<i>i</i>	16.30	0.04	Swope
58904.35	+50.35	<i>i</i>	>19.00	–	Nickel
58905.29	+51.29	<i>i</i>	16.41	0.03	Swope
58905.58	+51.58	<i>i</i>	16.25	0.16	Thacher
58906.10	+52.10	<i>i</i>	>17.05	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58906.10	+52.10	<i>i</i>	15.61	0.04	LCO
58906.28	+52.28	<i>i</i>	16.49	0.03	Swope
58907.36	+53.36	<i>i</i>	16.39	0.03	Swope
58908.30	+54.30	<i>i</i>	16.54	0.03	Swope
58908.30	+54.30	<i>i</i>	16.55	0.03	Swope
58909.36	+55.36	<i>i</i>	16.60	0.03	Swope
58911.20	+57.20	<i>i</i>	16.51	0.04	Swope
58912.27	+58.27	<i>i</i>	16.53	0.04	Swope
58919.14	+65.14	<i>i</i>	>16.37	–	LCO
58923.14	+69.14	<i>i</i>	>17.26	–	LCO
58923.27	+69.27	<i>i</i>	16.36	0.03	Swope
58929.50	+75.50	<i>i</i>	>12.78	–	LCO
58929.50	+75.50	<i>i</i>	>16.73	–	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>i</i>	16.52	0.36	LCO
58935.64	+81.64	<i>i</i>	>16.52	–	LCO
58943.46	+89.46	<i>i</i>	>15.74	–	LCO
58943.46	+89.46	<i>i</i>	15.74	0.36	LCO
58952.44	+98.44	<i>i</i>	>17.70	–	LCO
58954.18	+100.18	<i>i</i>	>18.80	–	Nickel
58959.34	+105.34	<i>i</i>	>17.52	–	LCO
58963.21	+109.21	<i>i</i>	>18.28	–	Nickel
58966.35	+112.35	<i>i</i>	>16.49	–	LCO
58974.11	+120.11	<i>i</i>	>16.62	–	LCO
58980.76	+126.76	<i>i</i>	>16.62	–	LCO
58988.32	+134.32	<i>i</i>	>16.70	–	LCO
58995.60	+141.60	<i>i</i>	16.23	0.52	Synthetic
58996.50	+142.50	<i>i</i>	>17.25	–	LCO
59002.75	+148.75	<i>i</i>	>18.46	–	LCO
59007.71	+153.71	<i>i</i>	>18.41	–	LCO
59014.80	+160.80	<i>i</i>	>18.49	–	LCO
59026.35	+172.35	<i>i</i>	>17.34	–	LCO
59032.34	+178.34	<i>i</i>	>19.96	–	LCO
59038.72	+184.72	<i>i</i>	>19.58	–	LCO
59202.10	+348.10	<i>i</i>	>18.22	–	LCO

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

59208.07	+354.07	<i>i</i>	>17.68	–	LCO
59214.05	+360.05	<i>i</i>	>17.97	–	LCO
59220.37	+366.37	<i>i</i>	>17.76	–	LCO
59226.11	+372.11	<i>i</i>	>16.87	–	LCO
59227.72	+373.72	<i>i</i>	>18.22	–	LCO
59232.38	+378.38	<i>i</i>	>16.44	–	LCO
59236.06	+382.06	<i>i</i>	>17.02	–	LCO
59245.42	+391.42	<i>i</i>	>18.28	–	LCO
59252.06	+398.06	<i>i</i>	>17.33	–	LCO
59257.33	+403.33	<i>i</i>	>18.78	–	LCO
59262.23	+408.23	<i>i</i>	>18.13	–	LCO
59267.12	+413.12	<i>i</i>	>16.71	–	LCO
58857.30	+3.30	<i>z</i>	15.56	0.40	Synthetic
58862.53	+8.53	<i>z</i>	14.08	0.04	Thacher
58864.34	+10.34	<i>z</i>	13.84	0.03	Thacher
58864.60	+10.60	<i>z</i>	13.82	0.35	Synthetic
58866.33	+12.33	<i>z</i>	13.79	0.04	Thacher
58867.36	+13.36	<i>z</i>	13.78	0.04	Thacher
58868.60	+14.60	<i>z</i>	13.83	0.35	Synthetic
58870.50	+16.50	<i>z</i>	13.82	0.35	Synthetic
58871.34	+17.34	<i>z</i>	14.00	0.04	Thacher
58872.34	+18.34	<i>z</i>	14.06	0.03	Thacher
58873.41	+19.41	<i>z</i>	14.11	0.03	Thacher
58874.29	+20.29	<i>z</i>	14.23	0.04	Thacher
58876.29	+22.29	<i>z</i>	14.35	0.05	Thacher
58878.29	+24.29	<i>z</i>	14.45	0.06	Thacher
58880.29	+26.29	<i>z</i>	14.76	0.04	Thacher
58880.40	+26.40	<i>z</i>	14.74	0.37	Synthetic
58881.29	+27.29	<i>z</i>	14.82	0.04	Thacher
58886.29	+32.29	<i>z</i>	15.04	0.04	Thacher
58890.29	+36.29	<i>z</i>	15.30	0.06	Thacher
58892.27	+38.27	<i>z</i>	15.23	0.05	Thacher
58893.25	+39.25	<i>z</i>	15.31	0.05	Thacher

Table B.1 Optical and UV Photometry of SN 2020oi (Continued).

58894.26	+40.26	\approx	15.24	0.04	Thacher
58898.25	+44.25	\approx	15.33	0.04	Thacher
58899.24	+45.24	\approx	15.35	0.05	Thacher
58900.35	+46.35	\approx	15.32	0.04	Thacher
58903.30	+49.30	\approx	15.59	0.05	Thacher
58905.58	+51.58	\approx	15.41	0.15	Thacher
58942.52	+88.52	\approx	16.77	0.06	PS1

References

- [1] Martín Abadi et al. *TensorFlow: Large-Scale Machine Learning on Heterogeneous Systems*. Software available from tensorflow.org. 2015.
- [2] B. P. Abbott et al. “Gravitational Waves and Gamma-Rays from a Binary Neutron Star Merger: GW170817 and GRB 170817A”. *Astrophysical Journal* 848.2, L13 (Oct. 2017), p. L13. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa920c](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa920c).
- [3] B. P. Abbott et al. “Multi-messenger Observations of a Binary Neutron Star Merger”. *Astrophysical Journal* 848.2, L12 (Oct. 2017), p. L12. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa91c9](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa91c9).
- [4] Tatiana Acero-Cuellar et al. “There’s no difference: Convolutional Neural Networks for transient detection without template subtraction”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2203.07390 (Mar. 2022), arXiv:2203.07390. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2203.07390](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.07390).
- [5] Niloufar Afsariardchi et al. “The Nickel Mass Distribution of Stripped-envelope Supernovae: Implications for Additional Power Sources”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 918.2, 89 (Sept. 2021), p. 89. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac0aeb](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac0aeb).
- [6] G. Aldering et al. “SN 1993J: The Optical Properties of its Progenitor”. *Astronomical Journal* 107 (Feb. 1994), p. 662. DOI: [10.1086/116886](https://doi.org/10.1086/116886).
- [7] Greg Aldering et al. “Overview of the Nearby Supernova Factory”. *Survey and Other Telescope Technologies and Discoveries*. Ed. by J. Anthony Tyson et al. Vol. 4836. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. Dec. 2002, pp. 61–72. DOI: [10.1117/12.458107](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.458107).
- [8] P. D. Aleo et al. “The Young Supernova Experiment Data Release 1 (YSE DR1): Light Curves and Photometric Classification of 1975 Supernovae”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2211.07128 (Nov. 2022), arXiv:2211.07128.
- [9] Patrick D. Aleo et al. “On the Iron Abundance Anomaly in K-dwarf and Hyades Stars”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 846.1, 24 (Sept. 2017), p. 24. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa83b6](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa83b6).
- [10] E. L. Allard et al. “Cool Gas and Massive Stars: The Nuclear Ring in M100”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 633.1 (Nov. 2005), pp. L25–L28. DOI: [10.1086/498264](https://doi.org/10.1086/498264).

- [11] E. L. Allard et al. “The star formation history and evolution of the circumnuclear region of M100”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 371.3 (Sept. 2006), pp. 1087–1105. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2006.10751.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2006.10751.x).
- [12] M. Sol Alonso et al. “Active galactic nuclei and galaxy interactions”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 375.3 (Mar. 2007), pp. 1017–1024. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11367.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.11367.x).
- [13] Sivaram Ambikasaran et al. “Fast Direct Methods for Gaussian Processes”. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* 38 (June 2015), p. 252. DOI: [10.1109/TPAMI.2015.2448083](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2015.2448083).
- [14] J. P. Anderson. “A meta-analysis of core-collapse supernova ^{56}Ni masses”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 628, A7 (Aug. 2019), A7. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201935027](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201935027).
- [15] J. P. Anderson et al. “Comparisons of the radial distributions of core-collapse supernovae with those of young and old stellar populations”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 399.2 (Oct. 2009), pp. 559–573. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15324.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15324.x).
- [16] J. P. Anderson et al. “On the multiplicity of supernovae within host galaxies”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 550, A69 (Feb. 2013), A69. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201220600](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201220600).
- [17] J. P. Anderson et al. “Progenitor mass constraints for core-collapse supernovae from correlations with host galaxy star formation”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 424.2 (Aug. 2012), pp. 1372–1391. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21324.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21324.x).
- [18] C. R. Angus et al. “A fast-rising tidal disruption event from a candidate intermediate-mass black hole”. *Nature Astronomy* (Nov. 2022). DOI: [10.1038/s41550-022-01811-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-022-01811-y).
- [19] C. R. Angus et al. “A Hubble Space Telescope survey of the host galaxies of Superluminous Supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 458.1 (May 2016), pp. 84–104. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw063](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw063).
- [20] L. S. Aramyan et al. “Supernovae and their host galaxies - IV. The distribution of supernovae relative to spiral arms”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 459.3 (July 2016), pp. 3130–3143. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw873](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw873).
- [21] W. D. Arnett. “Type I supernovae. I - Analytic solutions for the early part of the light curve”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 253 (Feb. 1982), pp. 785–797. DOI: [10.1086/159681](https://doi.org/10.1086/159681).
- [22] W. David Arnett et al. “Supernova 1987A.” *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophysics* 27 (Jan. 1989), pp. 629–700. DOI: [10.1146/annurev.aa.27.090189.003213](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.aa.27.090189.003213).
- [23] Martin Asplund et al. “The Chemical Composition of the Sun”. *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophysics* 47.1 (Sept. 2009), pp. 481–522. DOI: [10.1146/annurev.astro.46.060407.145222](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.astro.46.060407.145222).

- [24] P. Astier et al. “The Supernova Legacy Survey: measurement of Ω_M , Ω_Λ and w from the first year data set”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 447.1 (Feb. 2006), pp. 31–48. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20054185](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20054185).
- [25] Shai Ayal et al. “Tidal Disruption of a Solar-Type Star by a Supermassive Black Hole”. *Astrophysical Journal* 545.2 (Dec. 2000), pp. 772–780. DOI: [10.1086/317835](https://doi.org/10.1086/317835).
- [26] Jazeel H. Azeez et al. “Kennicutt-Schmidt Law in the Central Region of NGC 4321 as Seen by ALMA”. *Scientific Reports* 6, 26896 (June 2016), p. 26896. DOI: [10.1038/srep26896](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep26896).
- [27] W. Baade. “B Cassiopeiae as a Supernova of Type I.” *Astrophysical Journal* 102 (Nov. 1945), p. 309. DOI: [10.1086/144761](https://doi.org/10.1086/144761).
- [28] W. Baade et al. “Remarks on Super-Novae and Cosmic Rays”. *Physical Review* 46.1 (July 1934), pp. 76–77. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRev.46.76.2](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.46.76.2).
- [29] W. Baade et al. “SUPERNOVAE AND CALIFORNIUM 254”. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific* 68.403 (1956), pp. 296–300. ISSN: 00046280, 15383873.
- [30] Shaojie Bai et al. “An Empirical Evaluation of Generic Convolutional and Recurrent Networks for Sequence Modeling”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1803.01271 (Mar. 2018), arXiv:1803.01271.
- [31] A. Baldeschi et al. “Star Formation and Morphological Properties of Galaxies in the Pan-STARRS 3π Survey. I. A Machine-learning Approach to Galaxy and Supernova Classification”. *Astrophysical Journal* 902.1, 60 (Oct. 2020), p. 60. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abb1c0](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abb1c0).
- [32] C. Barbarino et al. “LSQ14efd: observations of the cooling of a shock break-out event in a type Ic Supernova”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 471.2 (Oct. 2017), pp. 2463–2480. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx1709](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx1709).
- [33] C. Barbarino et al. “Type Ic supernovae from the (intermediate) Palomar Transient Factory”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2010.08392 (Oct. 2020), arXiv:2010.08392.
- [34] E. Baron et al. “Spectral Models of the Type IC Supernova SN 1994I in M51”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 527.2 (Dec. 1999), pp. 739–745. DOI: [10.1086/308107](https://doi.org/10.1086/308107).
- [35] Andreas Bauswein et al. “Neutron-star Radius Constraints from GW170817 and Future Detections”. *Astrophysical Journal* 850.2, L34 (Dec. 2017), p. L34. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa9994](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa9994).
- [36] Róbert Beck et al. “PS1-STRM: neural network source classification and photometric redshift catalogue for PS1 3π DR1”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 500.2 (Jan. 2021), pp. 1633–1644. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa2587](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa2587).
- [37] A. C. Becker et al. “The Deep Lens Survey Transient Search. I. Short Timescale and Astrometric Variability”. *Astrophysical Journal* 611.1 (Aug. 2004), pp. 418–433. DOI: [10.1086/421994](https://doi.org/10.1086/421994).

- [38] Andrew Becker. *HOTPANTS: High Order Transform of PSF ANd Template Subtraction*. Apr. 2015.
- [39] Eric F. Bell et al. “Nearly 5000 Distant Early-Type Galaxies in COMBO-17: A Red Sequence and Its Evolution since $z \sim 1$ ”. *Astrophysical Journal* 608.2 (June 2004), pp. 752–767. DOI: [10.1086/420778](https://doi.org/10.1086/420778).
- [40] Eric C. Bellm et al. “The Zwicky Transient Facility: Surveys and Scheduler”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.1000 (June 2019), p. 068003. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/ab0c2a](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/ab0c2a).
- [41] Jillian Bellovary et al. “Where are the Intermediate Mass Black Holes?” *Bulletin of the AAS* 51.3, 175 (May 2019), p. 175.
- [42] E. Berger. “The Host Galaxies of Short-Duration Gamma-Ray Bursts: Luminosities, Metallicities, and Star-Formation Rates”. *Astrophysical Journal* 690.1 (Jan. 2009), pp. 231–237. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/690/1/231](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/690/1/231).
- [43] J. P. Bernstein et al. “Supernova Simulations and Strategies for the Dark Energy Survey”. *Astrophysical Journal* 753.2, 152 (July 2012), p. 152. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/753/2/152](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/753/2/152).
- [44] Melina C. Bersten et al. “Early Ultraviolet/Optical Emission of The Type Ib SN 2008D”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 767.2, 143 (Apr. 2013), p. 143. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/767/2/143](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/767/2/143).
- [45] Emmanuel Bertin. *SWarp: Resampling and Co-adding FITS Images Together*. Oct. 2010.
- [46] Stéphane Blondin et al. “Determining the Type, Redshift, and Age of a Supernova Spectrum”. *Astrophysical Journal* 666.2 (Sept. 2007), pp. 1024–1047. DOI: [10.1086/520494](https://doi.org/10.1086/520494).
- [47] Kyle Boone. “Avocado: Photometric Classification of Astronomical Transients with Gaussian Process Augmentation”. *Astronomical Journal* 158.6, 257 (Dec. 2019), p. 257. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ab5182](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab5182).
- [48] Kyle Boone. “ParSNIP: Generative Models of Transient Light Curves with Physics-enabled Deep Learning”. *Astronomical Journal* 162.6, 275 (Dec. 2021), p. 275. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ac2a2d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac2a2d).
- [49] Larry Bradley et al. *astropy/photutils: 1.0.1*. Version 1.0.1. Sept. 2020. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4049061](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4049061).
- [50] David Branch et al. “Comparative Direct Analysis of Type Ia Supernova Spectra. II. Maximum Light”. *Publications of the ASP* 118.842 (Apr. 2006), pp. 560–571. DOI: [10.1086/502778](https://doi.org/10.1086/502778).
- [51] David Branch et al. *Supernova explosions*. Springer, 2017.
- [52] Iris Breda et al. “Stellar age gradients and inside-out star formation quenching in galaxy bulges”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 635, A177 (Mar. 2020), A177. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201937193](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201937193).

- [53] Leo Breiman. “Random Forests.” *Machine Learning* 45 (Jan. 2001), pp. 5–32. DOI: [10.1023/A:1010933404324](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324).
- [54] Dillon Brout et al. “It’s Dust: Solving the Mysteries of the Intrinsic Scatter and Host-galaxy Dependence of Standardized Type Ia Supernova Brightnesses”. *Astrophysical Journal* 909.1, 26 (Mar. 2021), p. 26. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abd69b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abd69b).
- [55] Dillon Brout et al. “The Pantheon+ Analysis: Cosmological Constraints”. *Astrophysical Journal* 938.2, 110 (Oct. 2022), p. 110. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac8e04](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac8e04).
- [56] David I. Brown. *WFPC2 Science Capability Report*. Space Telescope WFPC2 Instrument Science Report. Jan. 1992.
- [57] P. J. Brown et al. “SOUSA: the Swift Optical/Ultraviolet Supernova Archive”. *Astrophysics and Space Science* 354 (Nov. 2014), pp. 89–96. DOI: [10.1007/s10509-014-2059-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10509-014-2059-8).
- [58] P. J. Brown et al. “Ultraviolet Light Curves of Supernovae with the Swift Ultraviolet/Optical Telescope”. *Astronomical Journal* 137 (May 2009), pp. 4517–4525. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/137/5/4517](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/137/5/4517).
- [59] T. M. Brown et al. “Las Cumbres Observatory Global Telescope Network”. *Publications of the ASP* 125.931 (Sept. 2013), p. 1031. DOI: [10.1086/673168](https://doi.org/10.1086/673168).
- [60] Warren R. Brown et al. “Most Double Degenerate Low-mass White Dwarf Binaries Merge”. *Astrophysical Journal* 824.1, 46 (June 2016), p. 46. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/824/1/46](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/824/1/46).
- [61] G. Bruzual et al. “Stellar population synthesis at the resolution of 2003”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 344.4 (Oct. 2003), pp. 1000–1028. DOI: [10.1046/j.1365-8711.2003.06897.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-8711.2003.06897.x).
- [62] M. Bulla. “POSSIS: predicting spectra, light curves, and polarization for multidimensional models of supernovae and kilonovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 489.4 (Nov. 2019), pp. 5037–5045. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz2495](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz2495).
- [63] M. Bulla et al. “Polarized kilonovae from black hole-neutron star mergers”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 501.2 (Feb. 2021), pp. 1891–1899. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa3796](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa3796).
- [64] Brandon Buncher et al. “Survey2Survey: a deep learning generative model approach for cross-survey image mapping”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 503.1 (May 2021), pp. 777–796. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab294](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab294).
- [65] E. Margaret Burbidge et al. “Synthesis of the Elements in Stars”. *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 29 (4 1957), pp. 547–650. DOI: [10.1103/RevModPhys.29.547](https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.29.547).
- [66] Umar. F. Burhanudin et al. “Pan-chromatic photometric classification of supernovae from multiple surveys and transfer learning for future surveys”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2208.01328 (Aug. 2022), arXiv:2208.01328.

- [67] Colin J. Burke et al. “A characteristic optical variability time scale in astrophysical accretion disks”. *Science* 373.6556 (Aug. 2021), pp. 789–792. DOI: [10.1126/science.abg9933](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abg9933).
- [68] J. Burke et al. “Early Lightcurves of Type Ia Supernovae are Consistent with Nondegenerate Progenitor Companions”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2207.07681 (July 2022), arXiv:2207.07681. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2207.07681](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2207.07681).
- [69] Roberto Cahuantzi et al. “A comparison of LSTM and GRU networks for learning symbolic sequences”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2107.02248 (July 2021), arXiv:2107.02248.
- [70] Yongzhi Cai et al. “Gap Transients Interacting with Circumstellar Medium”. *Universe* 8.10 (Sept. 2022), p. 493. DOI: [10.3390/universe8100493](https://doi.org/10.3390/universe8100493).
- [71] Daniela Calzetti et al. “The Dust Content and Opacity of Actively Star-forming Galaxies”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 533.2 (Apr. 2000), pp. 682–695. DOI: [10.1086/308692](https://doi.org/10.1086/308692).
- [72] Zach Cano. “A new method for estimating the bolometric properties of Ibc supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 434.2 (Sept. 2013), pp. 1098–1116. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stt1048](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt1048).
- [73] Yi Cao et al. “Discovery, Progenitor and Early Evolution of a Stripped Envelope Supernova iPTF13bvn”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 775.1, L7 (Sept. 2013), p. L7. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/775/1/L7](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/775/1/L7).
- [74] M. Cappellari et al. “Adaptive spatial binning of integral-field spectroscopic data using Voronoi tessellations”. *MNRAS* 342 (2003), pp. 345–354. DOI: [10.1046/j.1365-8711.2003.06541.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-8711.2003.06541.x).
- [75] E. Cappellaro et al. “A new determination of supernova rates and a comparison with indicators for galactic star formation”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 351 (Nov. 1999), pp. 459–466.
- [76] Enrico CAPPELLARO et al. “AUTOMATIC OBJECTIVE CLASSIFICATION OF SUPERNOVAE” (2008).
- [77] Jason A. Cardelli et al. “The Relationship between Infrared, Optical, and Ultraviolet Extinction”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 345 (Oct. 1989), p. 245. DOI: [10.1086/167900](https://doi.org/10.1086/167900).
- [78] B. W. Carney. “Spectrophotometry of SN 1979 C in M 100.” *Publications of the ASP* 92 (Feb. 1980), pp. 56–59. DOI: [10.1086/130614](https://doi.org/10.1086/130614).
- [79] R. Carrasco-Davis et al. “Alert Classification for the ALerCE Broker System: The Real-time Stamp Classifier”. *Astronomical Journal* 162.6, 231 (Dec. 2021), p. 231. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ac0ef1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac0ef1).
- [80] Rodrigo Carrasco-Davis et al. “Deep Learning for Image Sequence Classification of Astronomical Events”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.1004 (Oct. 2019), p. 108006. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aaef12](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aaef12).

- [81] A. Castillo-Morales et al. “Non-circular motion evidence in the circumnuclear region of M100 (NGC 4321)”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 380.2 (Sept. 2007), pp. 489–498. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12104.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12104.x).
- [82] Ana I Gómez de Castro et al. *Fundamental Questions in Astrophysics: Guidelines for Future UV Observatories*. Springer, 2006.
- [83] Gilles Chabrier. “Galactic Stellar and Substellar Initial Mass Function”. *Publications of the ASP* 115.809 (July 2003), pp. 763–795. DOI: [10.1086/376392](https://doi.org/10.1086/376392).
- [84] K. C. Chambers et al. “The Pan-STARRS1 Surveys”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1612.05560 (Dec. 2016), arXiv:1612.05560.
- [85] Poonam Chandra. “Circumstellar Interaction in Supernovae in Dense Environments—An Observational Perspective”. *Space Science Reviews* 214.1, 27 (Feb. 2018), p. 27. DOI: [10.1007/s11214-017-0461-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-017-0461-6).
- [86] Vedant Chandra et al. “The SN Ia runaway LP 398-9: detection of circumstellar material and surface rotation”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 512.4 (June 2022), pp. 6122–6133. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stac883](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac883).
- [87] Moses S Charikar. “Similarity estimation techniques from rounding algorithms”. *Proceedings of the thirty-fourth annual ACM symposium on Theory of computing*. 2002, pp. 380–388.
- [88] Tom Charnock et al. “Deep Recurrent Neural Networks for Supernovae Classification”. *Astrophysical Journal, Letters* 837.2, L28 (Mar. 2017), p. L28. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa603d](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa603d).
- [89] Deep Chatterjee et al. “El-CID: a filter for gravitational-wave electromagnetic counterpart identification”. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 509.1 (Oct. 2021), pp. 914–930. ISSN: 1365-2966. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab3023](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab3023).
- [90] Ting-Wan Chen et al. “THE HOST GALAXY OF THE SUPER-LUMINOUS SN 2010gx AND LIMITS ON EXPLOSIVE ^{56}Ni PRODUCTION”. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* 763.2 (2013), p. L28. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/763/2/L28](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/763/2/L28).
- [91] Wen-Cong Chen et al. “On the Progenitors of Super-Chandrasekhar Mass Type Ia Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 702.1 (Sept. 2009), pp. 686–691. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/702/1/686](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/702/1/686).
- [92] R. A. Chevalier. “Self-similar solutions for the interaction of stellar ejecta with an external medium.” *The Astrophysical Journal* 258 (July 1982), pp. 790–797. DOI: [10.1086/160126](https://doi.org/10.1086/160126).
- [93] R. A. Chevalier et al. “Circumstellar Emission from Type Ib and Ic Supernovae”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 651 (Nov. 2006), pp. 381–391. DOI: [10.1086/507606](https://doi.org/10.1086/507606).

- [94] Roger A. Chevalier. “Synchrotron Self-Absorption in Radio Supernovae”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 499.2 (May 1998), pp. 810–819. DOI: [10.1086/305676](https://doi.org/10.1086/305676).
- [95] M. Childress et al. “Host Galaxies of Type Ia Supernovae from the Nearby Supernova Factory”. *Astrophysical Journal* 770.2, 107 (June 2013), p. 107. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/770/2/107](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/770/2/107).
- [96] Igor V. Chilingarian et al. “A universal ultraviolet-optical colour-colour-magnitude relation of galaxies”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 419.2 (Jan. 2012), pp. 1727–1739. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19837.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19837.x).
- [97] Igor V. Chilingarian et al. “Analytical approximations of K-corrections in optical and near-infrared bands”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 405.3 (July 2010), pp. 1409–1420. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.16506.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.16506.x).
- [98] Kyunghyun Cho et al. “Learning Phrase Representations using RNN Encoder–Decoder for Statistical Machine Translation”. *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*. Doha, Qatar: Association for Computational Linguistics, Oct. 2014, pp. 1724–1734. DOI: [10.3115/v1/D14-1179](https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/D14-1179).
- [99] François Chollet et al. *Keras*. <https://keras.io>. 2015.
- [100] Roberto Cid Fernandes et al. “Semi-empirical analysis of Sloan Digital Sky Survey galaxies - I. Spectral synthesis method”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 358.2 (Apr. 2005), pp. 363–378. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2005.08752.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2005.08752.x).
- [101] J. Christopher Clemens et al. “The Goodman spectrograph”. *Ground-based Instrumentation for Astronomy*. Ed. by Alan F. M. Moorwood et al. Vol. 5492. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. Sept. 2004, pp. 331–340. DOI: [10.1117/12.550069](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.550069).
- [102] Agnes M. Clerke. *The System of the Stars*. 1890.
- [103] Stirling A. Colgate et al. “Early Supernova Luminosity”. *Astrophysical Journal* 157 (Aug. 1969), p. 623. DOI: [10.1086/150102](https://doi.org/10.1086/150102).
- [104] J. D. Colvin et al. “An empirical study of the nuclear explosion-induced lightning seen on IVY-MIKE”. *Journal of Geophysics Research* 92.D5 (May 1987), pp. 5696–5712. DOI: [10.1029/JD092iD05p05696](https://doi.org/10.1029/JD092iD05p05696).
- [105] Julia M. Comerford et al. “Offset Active Galactic Nuclei as Tracers of Galaxy Mergers and Supermassive Black Hole Growth”. *Astrophysical Journal* 789.2, 112 (July 2014), p. 112. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/789/2/112](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/789/2/112).
- [106] Jeff Cooke et al. “Superluminous supernovae at redshifts of 2.05 and 3.90”. *Nature* 491.7423 (Nov. 2012), pp. 228–231. DOI: [10.1038/nature11521](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11521).

- [107] D. A. Coulter et al. “YSE-PZ: A Transient Survey Management Platform that Empowers the Human-in-the-Loop”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2303.02154 (Mar. 2023), arXiv:2303.02154. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2303.02154](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.02154).
- [108] K. R. Covey et al. “Stellar SEDs from 0.3 to 2.5 μm : Tracing the Stellar Locust and Searching for Color Outliers in the SDSS and 2MASS”. *Astronomical Journal* 134.6 (Dec. 2007), pp. 2398–2417. DOI: [10.1086/522052](https://doi.org/10.1086/522052).
- [109] J. F. Crenshaw et al. “PZFlow: normalizing flows for cosmology, with applications to forward modeling galaxy photometry”. *American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts*. Vol. 53. American Astronomical Society Meeting Abstracts. June 2021, 230.01, p. 230.01.
- [110] J. F. Crenshaw et al. “Statistical Modeling of Galaxy Catalogues with Normalizing Flows”. *in prep.* (2022).
- [111] R. Mark Crockett et al. “The Birth Place of the Type Ic Supernova 2007gr”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 672.2 (Jan. 2008), p. L99. DOI: [10.1086/527299](https://doi.org/10.1086/527299).
- [112] N. Dallaporta. “On the Frequency of Type I and Type II Supernovae”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 29 (Dec. 1973), p. 393.
- [113] Mayur Datar et al. “Locality-sensitive hashing scheme based on p-stable distributions”. *Proceedings of the twentieth annual symposium on Computational geometry*. 2004, pp. 253–262.
- [114] P. D’Avanzo. “Short gamma-ray bursts: A review”. *Journal of High Energy Astrophysics* 7 (2015). Swift 10 Years of Discovery, a novel approach to Time Domain Astronomy, pp. 73–80. ISSN: 2214-4048. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jheap.2015.07.002>.
- [115] K. De et al. “A hot and fast ultra-stripped supernova that likely formed a compact neutron star binary”. *Science* 362.6411 (Oct. 2018), pp. 201–206. DOI: [10.1126/science.aas8693](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aas8693).
- [116] Debabrata Deb et al. “Anisotropic Magnetized White Dwarfs: Unifying Under- and Overluminous Peculiar and Standard Type Ia Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 926.1, 66 (Feb. 2022), p. 66. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac410b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac410b).
- [117] Joseph DeRose et al. “The Buzzard Flock: Dark Energy Survey Synthetic Sky Catalogs”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1901.02401 (Jan. 2019), arXiv:1901.02401.
- [118] Luc Dessart et al. “Core-collapse explosions of Wolf-Rayet stars and the connection to Type IIb/Ib/Ic supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 414.4 (July 2011), pp. 2985–3005. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18598.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18598.x).
- [119] M. Dia et al. “Galaxy Image Simulation Using Progressive GANs”. *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems XXIX*. Ed. by R. Pizzo et al. Vol. 527. Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series. Jan. 2020, p. 175.

- [120] Paul Dierckx. *Curve and surface fitting with splines*. Oxford University Press, 1995.
- [121] G. Dimitriadis et al. “K2 Observations of SN 2018oh Reveal a Two-component Rising Light Curve for a Type Ia Supernova”. *Astrophysical Journal, Letters* 870, L1 (Jan. 2019), p. L1. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aaedb0](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aaedb0).
- [122] Alan Dressler et al. “Spectroscopy and Photometry of Elliptical Galaxies. I. New Distance Estimator”. *Astrophysical Journal* 313 (Feb. 1987), p. 42. DOI: [10.1086/164947](https://doi.org/10.1086/164947).
- [123] M. R. Drout et al. “Light curves of the neutron star merger GW170817/SSS17a: Implications for r-process nucleosynthesis”. *Science* 358.6370 (Dec. 2017), pp. 1570–1574. DOI: [10.1126/science.aag0049](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag0049).
- [124] M. R. Drout et al. “Rapidly Evolving and Luminous Transients from Pan-STARRS1”. *Astrophysical Journal* 794.1, 23 (Oct. 2014), p. 23. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/794/1/23](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/794/1/23).
- [125] M. R. Drout et al. “The Double-peaked SN 2013ge: A Type Ib/c SN with an Asymmetric Mass Ejection or an Extended Progenitor Envelope”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 821.1, 57 (Apr. 2016), p. 57. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/821/1/57](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/821/1/57).
- [126] Maria R. Drout et al. “The First Systematic Study of Type Ibc Supernova Multi-band Light Curves”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 741.2, 97 (Nov. 2011), p. 97. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/741/2/97](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/741/2/97).
- [127] Dmitry A. Duvet et al. “Real-bogus classification for the Zwicky Transient Facility using deep learning”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 489.3 (Nov. 2019), pp. 3582–3590. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz2357](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz2357).
- [128] Conor Durkan et al. “Neural Spline Flows”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1906.04032 (June 2019), arXiv:1906.04032.
- [129] J. J. Eldridge et al. “Binary Population and Spectral Synthesis Version 2.1: Construction, Observational Verification, and New Results”. *Publications of the Astron. Soc. of Australia* 34, e058 (Nov. 2017), e058. DOI: [10.1017/pasa.2017.51](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2017.51).
- [130] John J. Eldridge et al. “The effect of massive binaries on stellar populations and supernova progenitors”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 384.3 (Mar. 2008), pp. 1109–1118. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12738.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12738.x).
- [131] Sara L. Ellison et al. “Galaxy pairs in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey - IV. Interactions trigger active galactic nuclei”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 418.3 (Dec. 2011), pp. 2043–2053. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19624.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.19624.x).
- [132] Bruce G. Elmegreen et al. “Regularly Spaced Infrared Peaks in the Dusty Spirals of Messier 100”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 863.1, 59 (Aug. 2018), p. 59. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aacf9a](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aacf9a).

- [133] Charles R. Evans et al. “The Tidal Disruption of a Star by a Massive Black Hole”. *Astrophysical Journal* 346 (Nov. 1989), p. L13. DOI: [10.1086/185567](https://doi.org/10.1086/185567).
- [134] R. Ferretti et al. “Probing gas and dust in the tidal tail of NGC 5221 with the type Ia supernova iPTF16abc”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 606, A111 (Oct. 2017), A111. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201731409](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201731409).
- [135] Alexei V. Filippenko et al. “The Lick Observatory Supernova Search with the Katzman Automatic Imaging Telescope”. *IAU Colloq. 183: Small Telescope Astronomy on Global Scales*. Ed. by Bohdan Paczynski et al. Vol. 246. Astronomical Society of the Pacific Conference Series. Jan. 2001, p. 121.
- [136] Alexei V. Filippenko et al. “The Subluminous, Spectroscopically Peculiar Type Ia Supernova 1991bg in the Elliptical Galaxy NGC 4374”. *Astronomical Journal* 104 (Oct. 1992), p. 1543. DOI: [10.1086/116339](https://doi.org/10.1086/116339).
- [137] Alexei V. Filippenko et al. “The Type IC Supernova 1994I in M51: Detection of Helium and Spectral Evolution”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 450 (Sept. 1995), p. L11. DOI: [10.1086/309659](https://doi.org/10.1086/309659).
- [138] Douglas P. Finkbeiner et al. “Hypercalibration: A Pan-STARRS1-based Recalibration of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Photometry”. *Astrophysical Journal* 822.2, 66 (May 2016), p. 66. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/822/2/66](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/822/2/66).
- [139] Edward L. Fitzpatrick. “Correcting for the Effects of Interstellar Extinction”. *Publications of the ASP* 111.755 (Jan. 1999), pp. 63–75. DOI: [10.1086/316293](https://doi.org/10.1086/316293).
- [140] H. A. Flewelling et al. “The Pan-STARRS1 Database and Data Products”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 251.1, 7 (Nov. 2020), p. 7. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/abb82d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/abb82d).
- [141] Gastón Folatelli et al. “Disappearance of the Progenitor of Supernova iPTF13bvn”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 825.2, L22 (July 2016), p. L22. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8205/825/2/L22](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8205/825/2/L22).
- [142] Ryan J. Foley et al. “Classifying Supernovae Using Only Galaxy Data”. *Astrophysical Journal* 778.2, 167 (Dec. 2013), p. 167. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/778/2/167](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/778/2/167).
- [143] Ryan J. Foley et al. “SN 2008ha: An Extremely Low Luminosity and Exceptionally Low Energy Supernova”. *Astronomical Journal* 138.2 (Aug. 2009), pp. 376–391. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/138/2/376](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/138/2/376).
- [144] Ryan J. Foley et al. “The Foundation Supernova Survey: motivation, design, implementation, and first data release”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 475.1 (Mar. 2018), pp. 193–219. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx3136](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx3136).
- [145] Ryan J. Foley et al. “Type Iax Supernovae: A New Class of Stellar Explosion”. *Astrophysical Journal* 767.1, 57 (Apr. 2013), p. 57. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/767/1/57](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/767/1/57).

- [146] W. Fong et al. “Demographics of the Galaxies Hosting Short-duration Gamma-Ray Bursts”. *Astrophysical Journal* 769.1, 56 (May 2013), p. 56. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/769/1/56](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/769/1/56).
- [147] Daniel Foreman-Mackey et al. “emcee: The MCMC Hammer”. *Publications of the ASP* 125.925 (Mar. 2013), p. 306. DOI: [10.1086/670067](https://doi.org/10.1086/670067).
- [148] F. Förster et al. “ALeRCE/ZTF Transient Discovery Report for 2020-01-07”. *Transient Name Server Discovery Report* 2020-67 (Jan. 2020), p. 1.
- [149] F. Förster et al. “The Automatic Learning for the Rapid Classification of Events (ALeRCE) Alert Broker”. *Astronomical Journal* 161.5, 242 (May 2021), p. 242. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/abe9bc](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/abe9bc).
- [150] Ori D. Fox et al. “A Spitzer survey for dust-obscured supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 506.3 (Sept. 2021), pp. 4199–4209. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab1740](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab1740).
- [151] Ori D. Fox et al. “Late-time Circumstellar Interaction in a Spitzer Selected Sample of Type II_n Supernovae”. *Astronomical Journal* 146.1, 2 (July 2013), p. 2. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/146/1/2](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/146/1/2).
- [152] Ori D. Fox et al. “On the nature of Type II_n/Ia-CSM supernovae: optical and near-infrared spectra of SN 2012ca and SN 2013dn”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 447.1 (Feb. 2015), pp. 772–785. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu2435](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu2435).
- [153] Wendy L. Freedman et al. “Distance to the Virgo cluster galaxy M100 from Hubble Space Telescope observations of Cepheids”. *Nature* 371.6500 (Oct. 1994), pp. 757–762. DOI: [10.1038/371757a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/371757a0).
- [154] Wendy L. Freedman et al. “First Hubble Space Telescope Observations of the Brightest Stars in the Virgo Galaxy M100 = NGC 4321”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 435 (Nov. 1994), p. L31. DOI: [10.1086/187587](https://doi.org/10.1086/187587).
- [155] C. Fremling et al. “The Zwicky Transient Facility Bright Transient Survey. I. Spectroscopic Classification and the Redshift Completeness of Local Galaxy Catalogs”. *Astrophysical Journal* 895.1, 32 (May 2020), p. 32. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab8943](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab8943).
- [156] C. Fremling et al. “ZTF18aalrxas: A Type II_b Supernova from a Very Extended Low-mass Progenitor”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 878.1, L5 (June 2019), p. L5. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/ab218f](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ab218f).
- [157] Christoffer Fremling et al. “SNIascore: Deep-learning Classification of Low-resolution Supernova Spectra”. *Astrophysical Journal Letters* 917.1, L2 (Aug. 2021), p. L2. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/ac116f](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ac116f).

- [158] K. Decker French et al. “The Host Galaxies of Tidal Disruption Events”. *Space Science Reviews* 216.3, 32 (Mar. 2020), p. 32. DOI: [10.1007/s11214-020-00657-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-020-00657-y).
- [159] K. Decker French et al. “The Post-starburst Evolution of Tidal Disruption Event Host Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 835.2, 176 (Feb. 2017), p. 176. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/835/2/176](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/835/2/176).
- [160] C. Frohmaier et al. “The volumetric rate of normal type Ia supernovae in the local Universe discovered by the Palomar Transient Factory”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 486.2 (June 2019), pp. 2308–2320. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz807](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz807).
- [161] Antonella Fruscione et al. “CIAO: Chandra’s data analysis system”. *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*. Ed. by David R. Silva et al. Vol. 6270. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. June 2006, 62701V, p. 62701V. DOI: [10.1117/12.671760](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.671760).
- [162] T. Fusco et al. “Reconstruction of the ground-layer adaptive-optics point spread function for MUSE wide field mode observations”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 635, A208 (Mar. 2020), A208. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202037595](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202037595).
- [163] Levi Fussell et al. “Forging new worlds: high-resolution synthetic galaxies with chained generative adversarial networks”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 485.3 (May 2019), pp. 3203–3214. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz602](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz602).
- [164] Alex Gagliano et al. “GHOST: Using Only Host Galaxy Information to Accurately Associate and Distinguish Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 908.2, 170 (Feb. 2021), p. 170. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abd02b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abd02b).
- [165] Alexander Gagliano et al. “An Early-time Optical and Ultraviolet Excess in the Type-Ic SN 2020oi”. *Astrophysical Journal* 924.2, 55 (Jan. 2022), p. 55. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac35ec](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac35ec).
- [166] Avishay Gal-Yam. “Luminous Supernovae”. *Science* 337.6097 (Aug. 2012), p. 927. DOI: [10.1126/science.1203601](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1203601).
- [167] Avishay Gal-Yam. “Observational and Physical Classification of Supernovae”. *Handbook of Supernovae*. Ed. by Athem W. Alsabti et al. 2017, p. 195. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-21846-5_35](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21846-5_35).
- [168] T. J. Galama et al. “An unusual supernova in the error box of the γ -ray burst of 25 April 1998”. *Nature* 395.6703 (Oct. 1998), pp. 670–672. DOI: [10.1038/27150](https://doi.org/10.1038/27150).
- [169] L. Galbany et al. “Characterizing the environments of supernovae with MUSE”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 455.4 (Feb. 2016), pp. 4087–4099. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv2620](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv2620).
- [170] L. Galbany et al. “PISCO: The PMAS/PPak Integral-field Supernova Hosts Compilation”. *Astrophysical Journal* 855.2, 107 (Mar. 2018), p. 107. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aaaf20](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aaaf20).

- [171] Lluís Galbany et al. “Type Ia Supernova Properties as a Function of the Distance to the Host Galaxy in the SDSS-II SN Survey”. *Astrophysical Journal* 755.2, 125 (Aug. 2012), p. 125. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/755/2/125](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/755/2/125).
- [172] C. Gall et al. “Two transitional type Ia supernovae located in the Fornax cluster member NGC 1404: SN 2007on and SN 2011iv”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 611, A58 (Mar. 2018), A58. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201730886](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201730886).
- [173] E. E. E. Gall et al. “A comparative study of Type II-P and II-L supernova rise times as exemplified by the case of LSQ13cuw”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 582, A3 (Oct. 2015), A3. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201525868](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201525868).
- [174] G. Gamow et al. “Neutrino Theory of Stellar Collapse”. *Phys. Rev.* 59 (7 1941), pp. 539–547. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRev.59.539](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.59.539).
- [175] S. Garcia-Burillo et al. “Molecular gas in the barred spiral M 100. II. (12)CO(1-0) interferometer observations and numerical simulations”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 333 (May 1998), pp. 864–876.
- [176] Jonathan P. Gardner et al. “The James Webb Space Telescope”. *Space Science Reviews* 123.4 (Apr. 2006), pp. 485–606. DOI: [10.1007/s11214-006-8315-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-006-8315-7).
- [177] P. M. Garnavich et al. “Shock Breakout and Early Light Curves of Type II-P Supernovae Observed with Kepler”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 820.1, 23 (Mar. 2016), p. 23. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/820/1/23](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/820/1/23).
- [178] N. Gehrels et al. “The Swift Gamma-Ray Burst Mission”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 611 (Aug. 2004), pp. 1005–1020. DOI: [10.1086/422091](https://doi.org/10.1086/422091).
- [179] Avishai Gilkis et al. “Effects of winds on the leftover hydrogen in massive stars following Roche lobe overflow”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 486.3 (July 2019), pp. 4451–4462. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz1134](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz1134).
- [180] A. Goldstein et al. “An Ordinary Short Gamma-Ray Burst with Extraordinary Implications: Fermi-GBM Detection of GRB 170817A”. *Astrophysical Journal* 848.2, L14 (Oct. 2017), p. L14. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa8f41](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa8f41).
- [181] Catalina Gómez et al. “Classifying Image Sequences of Astronomical Transients with Deep Neural Networks”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* (Oct. 2020). DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa2973](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa2973).
- [182] Sebastian Gomez et al. “FLEET: A Redshift-agnostic Machine Learning Pipeline to Rapidly Identify Hydrogen-poor Superluminous Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 904.1, 74 (Nov. 2020), p. 74. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abbf49](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abbf49).

- [183] Sebastian Gomez et al. “Identifying Tidal Disruption Events with an Expansion of the FLEET Machine Learning Algorithm”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2210.10810 (Oct. 2022), arXiv:2210.10810.
- [184] Sebastian Gomez et al. “Luminous Supernovae: Unveiling a Population between Superluminous and Normal Core-collapse Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 941.2, 107 (Dec. 2022), p. 107. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac9842](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac9842).
- [185] Sebastian Gomez et al. “The Search for Thermonuclear Transients from the Tidal Disruption of a White Dwarf by an Intermediate Mass Black Hole”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2302.14070 (Feb. 2023), arXiv:2302.14070. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2302.14070](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.14070).
- [186] B. P. Gompertz et al. “A Search for Neutron Star-Black Hole Binary Mergers in the Short Gamma-Ray Burst Population”. *Astrophysical Journal* 895.1, 58 (May 2020), p. 58. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab8d24](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab8d24).
- [187] S. Gonzaga et al. *The DrizzlePac Handbook*. 2012.
- [188] K. M. Górski et al. “HEALPix: A Framework for High-Resolution Discretization and Fast Analysis of Data Distributed on the Sphere”. *Astrophysical Journal* 622.2 (Apr. 2005), pp. 759–771. DOI: [10.1086/427976](https://doi.org/10.1086/427976).
- [189] Y. Götberg et al. “Stars Stripped in Binaries: The Living Gravitational-wave Sources”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 904.1, 56 (Nov. 2020), p. 56. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abbd5](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abbd5).
- [190] Ore Gottlieb et al. “Shocked jets in CCSNe can power the zoo of fast blue optical transients”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 513.3 (July 2022), pp. 3810–3817. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stac910](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac910).
- [191] Matthew J. Graham et al. “The Zwicky Transient Facility: Science Objectives”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.1001 (July 2019), p. 078001. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/ab006c](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/ab006c).
- [192] Melissa Graham et al. “Discovery Frontiers of Explosive Transients: An ELT and LSST Perspective”. *Bulletin of the AAS* 51.3, 339 (May 2019), p. 339. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.1904.05957](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1904.05957).
- [193] Melissa L. Graham et al. “Photometric Redshifts with the LSST: Evaluating Survey Observing Strategies”. *Astronomical Journal* 155.1, 1 (Jan. 2018), p. 1. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/aa99d4](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/aa99d4).
- [194] Or Graur et al. “LOSS Revisited. II. The Relative Rates of Different Types of Supernovae Vary between Low- and High-mass Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 837.2, 121 (Mar. 2017), p. 121. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa5eb7](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa5eb7).
- [195] Or Graur et al. “Stripped-envelope supernova rates and host-galaxy properties”. *IAU Focus Meeting 29B* (Jan. 2016), pp. 257–258. DOI: [10.1017/S1743921316005238](https://doi.org/10.1017/S1743921316005238).

- [196] Jose H. Groh et al. “Progenitors of supernova Ibc: a single Wolf-Rayet star as the possible progenitor of the SN Ib iPTF13bvn”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 558, L1 (Oct. 2013), p. L1. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201322369](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201322369).
- [197] David Gruber et al. “The Fermi GBM Gamma-Ray Burst Spectral Catalog: Four Years of Data”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 211.1, 12 (Mar. 2014), p. 12. DOI: [10.1088/0067-0049/211/1/12](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/211/1/12).
- [198] James Guillochon et al. “MOSFiT: Modular Open Source Fitter for Transients”. *The Astrophysical Journals* 236.1, 6 (May 2018), p. 6. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/aab761](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/aab761).
- [199] Ravi R. Gupta et al. “Host Galaxy Identification for Supernova Surveys”. *Astronomical Journal* 152.6, 154 (Dec. 2016), p. 154. DOI: [10.3847/0004-6256/152/6/154](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-6256/152/6/154).
- [200] Ravi Ryan Gupta. “Understanding Type Ia supernovae through their host galaxies using the SDSS-II Supernova Survey”. *Publicly Accessible Penn Dissertations* 758 (2013).
- [201] B. N. G. Guthrie. “Multiple supernova events in spiral galaxies.” *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 234 (Aug. 1990), p. 84.
- [202] J. Guy et al. “SALT2: using distant supernovae to improve the use of type Ia supernovae as distance indicators”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 466.1 (Apr. 2007), pp. 11–21. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20066930](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20066930).
- [203] Izumi Hachisu et al. “A Wide Symbiotic Channel to Type IA Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 522.1 (Sept. 1999), pp. 487–503. DOI: [10.1086/307608](https://doi.org/10.1086/307608).
- [204] ChangHoon Hahn et al. “Accelerated Bayesian SED Modeling using Amortized Neural Posterior Estimation”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2203.07391 (Mar. 2022), arXiv:2203.07391.
- [205] A. A. Hakobyan et al. “Supernovae and their host galaxies - VII. The diversity of Type Ia supernova progenitors”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 499.1 (Nov. 2020), pp. 1424–1440. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa2940](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa2940).
- [206] A. A. Hakobyan et al. “The radial distribution of core-collapse supernovae in spiral host galaxies”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 508.3 (Dec. 2009), pp. 1259–1268. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/200912795](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/200912795).
- [207] Mario Hamuy. “Observed and Physical Properties of Core-Collapse Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 582.2 (Jan. 2003), pp. 905–914. DOI: [10.1086/344689](https://doi.org/10.1086/344689).
- [208] K. S. Alexander Hansson et al. “Observed versus modelled u-, g-, r-, i-, z-band photometry of local galaxies - evaluation of model performance”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 427.3 (Dec. 2012), pp. 2376–2391. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21659.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21659.x).

- [209] Ramin Hasani et al. “Closed-form Continuous-time Neural Models”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2106.13898 (June 2021), arXiv:2106.13898. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2106.13898](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.13898).
- [210] T. M. Heckman. “An optical and radio survey of the nuclei of bright galaxies. Activity in normal galactic nuclei.” *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 500 (July 1980), pp. 187–199.
- [211] Francois Henault et al. “MUSE: a second-generation integral-field spectrograph for the VLT”. *Instrument Design and Performance for Optical/Infrared Ground-based Telescopes*. Ed. by Masanori Iye et al. Vol. 4841. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. Mar. 2003, pp. 1096–1107. DOI: [10.1117/12.462334](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.462334).
- [212] Olivier Hernandez et al. “On the Relevance of the Tremaine-Weinberg Method Applied to an H α Velocity Field: Pattern Speed Determination in M100 (NGC 4321)”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 632.1 (Oct. 2005), pp. 253–265. DOI: [10.1086/431964](https://doi.org/10.1086/431964).
- [213] F. William High et al. “Stellar Locus Regression: Accurate Color Calibration and the Real-Time Determination of Galaxy Cluster Photometric Redshifts”. *Astronomical Journal* 138.1 (July 2009), pp. 110–129. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/138/1/110](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/138/1/110).
- [214] R. J. Hill et al. “The Calibration of WFPC2 and Its Application to M100”. *Calibrating Hubble Space Telescope. Post Servicing Mission*. Ed. by Anuradha P. Koratkar et al. Jan. 1995, p. 360.
- [215] Geoffrey Hinton. “The Forward-Forward Algorithm: Some Preliminary Investigations”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2212.13345 (Dec. 2022), arXiv:2212.13345. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2212.13345](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2212.13345).
- [216] Daichi Hiramatsu et al. “The electron-capture origin of supernova 2018zd”. *Nature Astronomy* 5 (June 2021), pp. 903–910. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-021-01384-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-021-01384-2).
- [217] R. Hložek et al. “Results of the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-series Classification Challenge (PLAsTiCC)”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2012.12392 (Dec. 2020), arXiv:2012.12392. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2012.12392](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2012.12392).
- [218] Luis C. Ho et al. “A Search for “Dwarf” Seyfert Nuclei. III. Spectroscopic Parameters and Properties of the Host Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 112.2 (Oct. 1997), pp. 315–390. DOI: [10.1086/313041](https://doi.org/10.1086/313041).
- [219] Sepp Hochreiter et al. “Long short-term memory”. *Neural computation* 9.8 (1997), pp. 1735–1780.
- [220] B. W. Holwerda. “Host galaxy extinction of Type Ia supernovae: co-evolution of interstellar medium structure and the extinction law with star formation”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 386.1 (May 2008), pp. 475–480. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13050.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13050.x).

- [221] B. W. Holwerda et al. “SN Ia host galaxy properties and the dust extinction distribution”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 446.4 (Feb. 2015), pp. 3768–3775. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu2345](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu2345).
- [222] A. Horesh et al. “An Initial Analysis of the VLA Observation of the Nearby Supernova SN2020oi in M100”. *Transient Name Server AstroNote* 9 (Jan. 2020), p. 1.
- [223] Assaf Horesh et al. “A Non-equipartition Shock Wave Traveling in a Dense Circumstellar Environment around SN 2020oi”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 903.2, 132 (Nov. 2020), p. 132. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abbd38](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abbd38).
- [224] Michael Hoskin. “Harlow Shapley: The making of an observatory director”. *Journal for the History of Astronomy* 47.3 (2016), pp. 317–331.
- [225] Griffin Hosseinzadeh et al. “Bumpy Declining Light Curves Are Common in Hydrogen-poor Superluminous Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 933.1, 14 (July 2022), p. 14. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac67dd](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac67dd).
- [226] R. Hounsell et al. “Simulations of the WFIRST Supernova Survey and Forecasts of Cosmological Constraints”. *Astrophysical Journal* 867.1, 23 (Nov. 2018), p. 23. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aac08b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aac08b).
- [227] D. Andrew Howell et al. “The type Ia supernova SNLS-03D3bb from a super-Chandrasekhar-mass white dwarf star”. *Nature* 443.7109 (Sept. 2006), pp. 308–311. DOI: [10.1038/nature05103](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05103).
- [228] Steve B. Howell et al. “The K2 Mission: Characterization and Early Results”. *Publications of the ASP* 126.938 (Apr. 2014), p. 398. DOI: [10.1086/676406](https://doi.org/10.1086/676406).
- [229] F. Hoyle et al. “Nucleosynthesis in Supernovae.” *Astrophysical Journal* 132 (Nov. 1960), p. 565. DOI: [10.1086/146963](https://doi.org/10.1086/146963).
- [230] M. Huber et al. “The Pan-STARRS Survey for Transients (PSST) - first announcement and public release”. *The Astronomer’s Telegram* 7153 (Feb. 2015), p. 1.
- [231] E. E. O. Ishida et al. “Kernel PCA for Type Ia supernovae photometric classification”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 430.1 (Mar. 2013), pp. 509–532. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sts650](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sts650).
- [232] E. E. O. Ishida et al. “Optimizing spectroscopic follow-up strategies for supernova photometric classification with active learning”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 483.1 (Feb. 2019), pp. 2–18. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty3015](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty3015).
- [233] Željko Ivezic et al. “LSST: From Science Drivers to Reference Design and Anticipated Data Products”. *Astrophysical Journal* 873.2, 111 (Mar. 2019), p. 111. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab042c](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab042c).

- [234] Kohichi Iwamoto et al. “Theoretical Light Curves for the Type IC Supernova SN 1994I”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 437 (Dec. 1994), p. L115. DOI: [10.1086/187696](https://doi.org/10.1086/187696).
- [235] L. Izzo et al. “Signatures of a jet cocoon in early spectra of a supernova associated with a γ -ray burst”. *Nature* 565.7739 (Jan. 2019), pp. 324–327. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-018-0826-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0826-3).
- [236] W. V. Jacobson-Galán et al. “Final Moments. I. Precursor Emission, Envelope Inflation, and Enhanced Mass Loss Preceding the Luminous Type II Supernova 2020tlf”. *Astrophysical Journal* 924.1, 15 (Jan. 2022), p. 15. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac3f3a](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac3f3a).
- [237] Wynn V. Jacobson-Galán et al. “SN 2019ehk: A Double-peaked Ca-rich Transient with Luminous X-Ray Emission and Shock-ionized Spectral Features”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 898.2, 166 (Aug. 2020), p. 166. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab9e66](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab9e66).
- [238] Jacob E. Jencson et al. “The SPIRITS Sample of Luminous Infrared Transients: Uncovering Hidden Supernovae and Dusty Stellar Outbursts in Nearby Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 886.1, 40 (Nov. 2019), p. 40. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab4a01](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab4a01).
- [239] Saurabh W. Jha. “Type Iax Supernovae”. *Handbook of Supernovae*. Ed. by Athem W. Alsabti et al. Springer, Cham, 2017, p. 375. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-21846-5_42](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21846-5_42).
- [240] Brighten Jiang et al. “Extended Self-similar Solution for Circumstellar Material-supernova Ejecta Interaction”. *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society* 4.1, 16 (Jan. 2020), p. 16. DOI: [10.3847/2515-5172/ab7128](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/ab7128).
- [241] Danilo Jimenez Rezende et al. “Variational Inference with Normalizing Flows”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1505.05770 (May 2015), arXiv:1505.05770.
- [242] Benjamin D. Johnson et al. “Stellar Population Inference with Prospector”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 254.2, 22 (June 2021), p. 22. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/abef67](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/abef67).
- [243] Hugh M. Johnson et al. “The Spatial Distribution of Supernovae in Galaxies”. *Publications of the ASP* 75.443 (Apr. 1963), p. 123. DOI: [10.1086/127915](https://doi.org/10.1086/127915).
- [244] D. O. Jones et al. “Measuring Dark Energy Properties with Photometrically Classified Pan-STARRS Supernovae. II. Cosmological Parameters”. *Astrophysical Journal* 857.1, 51 (Apr. 2018), p. 51. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aab6b1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aab6b1).
- [245] D. O. Jones et al. “The Foundation Supernova Survey: Measuring Cosmological Parameters with Supernovae from a Single Telescope”. *Astrophysical Journal* 881.1, 19 (Aug. 2019), p. 19. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab2bec](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab2bec).
- [246] D. O. Jones et al. “The Young Supernova Experiment: Survey Goals, Overview, and Operations”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 908.2, 143 (Feb. 2021), p. 143. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abd7f5](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abd7f5).

- [247] P. M. W. Kalberla et al. “The Leiden/Argentine/Bonn (LAB) Survey of Galactic HI. Final data release of the combined LDS and IAR surveys with improved stray-radiation corrections”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 440 (Sept. 2005), pp. 775–782. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20041864](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20041864).
- [248] N. V. Karpenka et al. “A simple and robust method for automated photometric classification of supernovae using neural networks”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 429.2 (Feb. 2013), pp. 1278–1285. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sts412](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sts412).
- [249] Platon I. Karpov et al. “Physics-Informed Machine Learning for Modeling Turbulence in Supernovae”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2205.08663 (May 2022), arXiv:2205.08663.
- [250] Daniel Kasen. “Secondary Maximum in the Near-Infrared Light Curves of Type Ia Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 649.2 (Oct. 2006), pp. 939–953. DOI: [10.1086/506588](https://doi.org/10.1086/506588).
- [251] Daniel Kasen. “Seeing the Collision of a Supernova with Its Companion Star”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 708.2 (Jan. 2010), pp. 1025–1031. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/708/2/1025](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/708/2/1025).
- [252] Daniel Kasen et al. “Origin of the heavy elements in binary neutron-star mergers from a gravitational-wave event”. *Nature* 551.7678 (Oct. 2017), pp. 80–84. ISSN: 1476-4687. DOI: [10.1038/nature24453](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24453).
- [253] M. M. Kasliwal et al. “The GROWTH Marshal: A Dynamic Science Portal for Time-domain Astronomy”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.997 (Mar. 2019), p. 038003. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aafbc2](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aafbc2).
- [254] Mansi M. Kasliwal et al. “PTF 10fq: A Luminous Red Nova in the Spiral Galaxy Messier 99”. *Astrophysical Journal* 730.2, 134 (Apr. 2011), p. 134. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/730/2/134](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/730/2/134).
- [255] Guinevere Kauffmann et al. “The host galaxies of active galactic nuclei”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 346.4 (Dec. 2003), pp. 1055–1077. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2003.07154.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2003.07154.x).
- [256] Kyohei Kawaguchi et al. “Models of Kilonova/Macronova Emission from Black Hole-Neutron Star Mergers”. *Astrophysical Journal* 825.1, 52 (July 2016), p. 52. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/825/1/52](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/825/1/52).
- [257] Patrick L. Kelly et al. “Constraints on the Progenitor System of the Type Ia Supernova 2014J from Pre-explosion Hubble Space Telescope Imaging”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 790.1, 3 (July 2014), p. 3. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/790/1/3](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/790/1/3).
- [258] Patrick L. Kelly et al. “Core-collapse Supernovae and Host Galaxy Stellar Populations”. *Astrophysical Journal* 759.2, 107 (Nov. 2012), p. 107. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/759/2/107](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/759/2/107).

- [259] Jr. Kennicutt Robert C. “Star Formation in Galaxies Along the Hubble Sequence”. *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophysics* 36 (Jan. 1998), pp. 189–232. DOI: [10.1146/annurev.astro.36.1.189](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.astro.36.1.189).
- [260] W. D. Kenworthy et al. “SALT3: An Improved Type Ia Supernova Model for Measuring Cosmic Distances”. *Astrophysical Journal* 923.2, 265 (Dec. 2021), p. 265. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac30d8](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac30d8).
- [261] Wolfgang Kerzendorf et al. *Tardis-Sn/Tardis: Tardis V2.0.2 Release*. Version v2.0.2. June 2018. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.1292315](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1292315).
- [262] Wolfgang E. Kerzendorf et al. “A spectral synthesis code for rapid modelling of supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 440.1 (May 2014), pp. 387–404. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stu055](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stu055).
- [263] R. Kessler et al. “Models and Simulations for the Photometric LSST Astronomical Time Series Classification Challenge (PLAsTiCC)”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.1003 (Sept. 2019), p. 094501. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/ab26f1](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/ab26f1).
- [264] Richard Kessler et al. “Results from the Supernova Photometric Classification Challenge”. *Publications of the ASP* 122.898 (Dec. 2010), p. 1415. DOI: [10.1086/657607](https://doi.org/10.1086/657607).
- [265] Richard Kessler et al. “SNANA: A Public Software Package for Supernova Analysis”. *Publications of the ASP* 121.883 (Sept. 2009), p. 1028. DOI: [10.1086/605984](https://doi.org/10.1086/605984).
- [266] David K. Khatami et al. “Physics of Luminous Transient Light Curves: A New Relation between Peak Time and Luminosity”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 878.1, 56 (June 2019), p. 56. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab1f09](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab1f09).
- [267] D. Khazov et al. “Flash Spectroscopy: Emission Lines from the Ionized Circumstellar Material around <10-day-old Type II Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 818.1, 3 (Feb. 2016), p. 3. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/818/1/3](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/818/1/3).
- [268] A. M. Khokhlov. “Delayed detonation model for type IA supernovae”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 245.1 (May 1991), pp. 114–128.
- [269] T L Killestein et al. “Transient-optimized real-bogus classification with Bayesian convolutional neural networks – sifting the GOTO candidate stream”. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 503.4 (Mar. 2021), pp. 4838–4854.
- [270] Charles D. Kilpatrick et al. “A Cool and Inflated Progenitor Candidate for the Type Ib Supernova 2019yvr at 2.6 Years Before Explosion”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2101.03206 (Jan. 2021), arXiv:2101.03206.
- [271] Charles D. Kilpatrick et al. “A potential progenitor for the Type Ic supernova 2017ein”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 480.2 (Oct. 2018), pp. 2072–2084. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty2022](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty2022).

- [272] Charles D. Kilpatrick et al. “Connecting the progenitors, pre-explosion variability and giant outbursts of luminous blue variables with Gaia16cfr”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 473.4 (Feb. 2018), pp. 4805–4823. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx2675](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx2675).
- [273] Charles D. Kilpatrick et al. “On the progenitor of the Type IIb supernova 2016gkg”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 465.4 (Mar. 2017), pp. 4650–4657. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw3082](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw3082).
- [274] Akisato Kimura et al. “Single-epoch supernova classification with deep convolutional neural networks”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1711.11526 (Nov. 2017), arXiv:1711.11526.
- [275] Diederik P. Kingma et al. “Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1412.6980 (Dec. 2014), arXiv:1412.6980.
- [276] Marina Kisley et al. “Classifying Astronomical Transients Using Only Host Galaxy Photometry”. *Astrophysical Journal* 942.1, 29 (Jan. 2023), p. 29. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aca532](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aca532).
- [277] J. H. Knapen et al. “Kinematics of Ionized and Molecular Hydrogen in the Core of M100”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 528.1 (Jan. 2000), pp. 219–235. DOI: [10.1086/308162](https://doi.org/10.1086/308162).
- [278] J. H. Knapen et al. “The Striking Near-Infrared Morphology of the Inner Region in M100”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 443 (Apr. 1995), p. L73. DOI: [10.1086/187839](https://doi.org/10.1086/187839).
- [279] C. S. Kochanek et al. “Supernova progenitors, their variability and the Type IIP Supernova ASASSN-16fq in M66”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 467.3 (May 2017), pp. 3347–3360. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx291](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx291).
- [280] C. S. Kochanek et al. “The All-Sky Automated Survey for Supernovae (ASAS-SN) Light Curve Server v1.0”. *Publications of the ASP* 129.980 (Oct. 2017), p. 104502. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aa80d9](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aa80d9).
- [281] E. C. Kool et al. “SN 2020bjj: A Type Ibn supernova with a long-lasting peak plateau”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 652, A136 (Aug. 2021), A136. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202039137](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039137).
- [282] Danila Korytov et al. “CosmoDC2: A Synthetic Sky Catalog for Dark Energy Science with LSST”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 245.2, 26 (Dec. 2019), p. 26. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/ab510c](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ab510c).
- [283] Eve Kovacs et al. “Validating Synthetic Galaxy Catalogs for Dark Energy Science in the LSST Era”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2110.03769 (Oct. 2021), arXiv:2110.03769.
- [284] Alexandra Kozyreva et al. “Can pair-instability supernova models match the observations of superluminous supernovae?” *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 454.4 (Dec. 2015), pp. 4357–4365. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv2287](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv2287).

- [285] Alexandra Kozyreva et al. “The role of radioactive nickel in shaping the plateau phase of Type II supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 483.1 (Feb. 2019), pp. 1211–1223. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty3185](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty3185).
- [286] Aditi S. Krishnapriyan et al. “Characterizing possible failure modes in physics-informed neural networks”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2109.01050 (Sept. 2021), arXiv:2109.01050. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2109.01050](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.01050).
- [287] S. R. Kulkarni et al. “The Redshift Completeness of Local Galaxy Catalogs”. *Astrophysical Journal* 860.1, 22 (June 2018), p. 22. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aabf85](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aabf85).
- [288] Hubert Lampeitl et al. “The Effect of Host Galaxies on Type Ia Supernovae in the SDSS-II Supernova Survey”. *Astrophysical Journal* 722.1 (Oct. 2010), pp. 566–576. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/722/1/566](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/722/1/566).
- [289] Dustin Lang et al. “Astrometry.net: Blind Astrometric Calibration of Arbitrary Astronomical Images”. *Astronomical Journal* 139.5 (May 2010), pp. 1782–1800. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/139/5/1782](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/139/5/1782).
- [290] E. Laplace et al. “The expansion of stripped-envelope stars: Consequences for supernovae and gravitational-wave progenitors”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 637, A6 (May 2020), A6. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201937300](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201937300).
- [291] Nicholas M. Law et al. “The Palomar Transient Factory: System Overview, Performance, and First Results”. *Publications of the ASP* 121.886 (Dec. 2009), p. 1395. DOI: [10.1086/648598](https://doi.org/10.1086/648598).
- [292] Jesse Leaman et al. “Nearby supernova rates from the Lick Observatory Supernova Search - I. The methods and data base”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 412.3 (Apr. 2011), pp. 1419–1440. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18158.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18158.x).
- [293] Kaela J. Lee et al. “A Single Binary May Host Recurrent Thermonuclear Supernovae”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2212.12596 (Dec. 2022), arXiv:2212.12596. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2212.12596](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2212.12596).
- [294] Joel Leja et al. “Deriving Physical Properties from Broadband Photometry with Prospector: Description of the Model and a Demonstration of its Accuracy Using 129 Galaxies in the Local Universe”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 837.2, 170 (Mar. 2017), p. 170. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa5ffe](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa5ffe).
- [295] G. Leloudas et al. “Spectroscopy of superluminous supernova host galaxies. A preference of hydrogen-poor events for extreme emission line galaxies”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 449.1 (May 2015), pp. 917–932. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv320](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv320).

- [296] Guillaume Lemaître et al. “Imbalanced-learn: A Python Toolbox to Tackle the Curse of Imbalanced Datasets in Machine Learning”. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 18.17 (2017), pp. 1–5.
- [297] A. J. Levan et al. “The Environment of the Binary Neutron Star Merger GW170817”. *Astrophysical Journal* 848.2, L28 (Oct. 2017), p. L28. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa905f](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa905f).
- [298] Ang Li et al. “Constraints on the Maximum Mass of Neutron Stars with a Quark Core from GW170817 and NICER PSR J0030+0451 Data”. *Astrophysical Journal* 913.1, 27 (May 2021), p. 27. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abf355](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abf355).
- [299] W. D. Li et al. “The Lick Observatory Supernova Search”. *Cosmic Explosions: Tenth AstroPhysics Conference*. Ed. by Stephen S. Holt et al. Vol. 522. American Institute of Physics Conference Series. June 2000, pp. 103–106. DOI: [10.1063/1.1291702](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1291702).
- [300] Weidong Li et al. “Nearby supernova rates from the Lick Observatory Supernova Search - II. The observed luminosity functions and fractions of supernovae in a complete sample”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 412.3 (Apr. 2011), pp. 1441–1472. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18160.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.18160.x).
- [301] Chris Lintott et al. “Galaxy Zoo 1: data release of morphological classifications for nearly 900 000 galaxies”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 410.1 (Jan. 2011), pp. 166–178. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17432.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17432.x).
- [302] Zheng-Wei Liu et al. “The interaction of core-collapse supernova ejecta with a companion star”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 584, A11 (Dec. 2015), A11. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201526757](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201526757).
- [303] M. Lochner et al. “ASTRONOMALY: Personalised active anomaly detection in astronomical data”. *Astronomy and Computing* 36, 100481 (July 2021), p. 100481. DOI: [10.1016/j.ascom.2021.100481](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ascom.2021.100481).
- [304] Michelle Lochner et al. “Photometric Supernova Classification with Machine Learning”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 225.2, 31 (Aug. 2016), p. 31. DOI: [10.3847/0067-0049/225/2/31](https://doi.org/10.3847/0067-0049/225/2/31).
- [305] Martine Lokken et al. *SCOTCH Catalogue and Associated Data Files*. Version 1.0. June 2022. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6601211](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6601211).
- [306] Martine Lokken et al. “The Simulated Catalogue of Optical Transients and Correlated Hosts (SCOTCH)”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2206.02815 (June 2022), arXiv:2206.02815.
- [307] LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration et al. “DESC DC2 Data Release Note”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2101.04855 (Jan. 2021), arXiv:2101.04855.

- [308] LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (LSST DESC) et al. “The LSST DESC DC2 Simulated Sky Survey”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 253.1, 31 (Mar. 2021), p. 31. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/abd62c](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/abd62c).
- [309] L. B. Lucy. “Nonthermal Excitation of Helium in Type Ib Supernovae”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 383 (Dec. 1991), p. 308. DOI: [10.1086/170787](https://doi.org/10.1086/170787).
- [310] Knut Lundmark. “Was the Crab Nebula formed by a Supernova in 1054 A. D.?” *Professor & Ouml;sten Bergstrand Vetenskapsmannen Och Läraren*. Jan. 1938, p. 89.
- [311] R. Lunnan et al. “Hydrogen-poor Superluminous Supernovae and Long-duration Gamma-Ray Bursts Have Similar Host Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 787.2, 138 (June 2014), p. 138. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/787/2/138](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/787/2/138).
- [312] R. Lunnan et al. “Zooming In on the Progenitors of Superluminous Supernovae With the HST”. *Astrophysical Journal* 804.2, 90 (May 2015), p. 90. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/804/2/90](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/804/2/90).
- [313] J. D. Lyman et al. “Bolometric light curves and explosion parameters of 38 stripped-envelope core-collapse supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 457.1 (Mar. 2016), pp. 328–350. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv2983](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv2983).
- [314] J. D. Lyman et al. “Investigating the diversity of supernovae type Iax: a MUSE and NOT spectroscopic study of their environments”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 473.1 (Jan. 2018), pp. 1359–1387. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx2414](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx2414).
- [315] D. Lynden-Bell. “Galactic Nuclei as Collapsed Old Quasars”. *Nature* 223.5207 (Aug. 1969), pp. 690–694. DOI: [10.1038/223690a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/223690a0).
- [316] Laurens van der Maaten et al. “Visualizing data using t-SNE”. *Journal of machine learning research* 9.Nov (2008), pp. 2579–2605.
- [317] Keiichi Maeda et al. “Progenitors of type Ia supernovae”. *International Journal of Modern Physics D* 25.10, 1630024 (July 2016), p. 1630024. DOI: [10.1142/S021827181630024X](https://doi.org/10.1142/S021827181630024X).
- [318] M. R. Magee et al. “An investigation of ^{56}Ni shells as the source of early light curve bumps in type Ia supernovae”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 642, A189 (Oct. 2020), A189. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202037870](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202037870).
- [319] M. R. Magee et al. “Modelling the early time behaviour of type Ia supernovae: effects of the ^{56}Ni distribution”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 614, A115 (June 2018), A115. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201832675](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201832675).
- [320] Eugene A. Magnier et al. “Pan-STARRS Pixel Analysis : Source Detection and Characterization”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1612.05244 (Dec. 2016), arXiv:1612.05244.

- [321] A. I. Malz et al. “Approximating Photo-z PDFs for Large Surveys”. *Astronomical Journal* 156.1, 35 (July 2018), p. 35. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/aac6b5](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/aac6b5).
- [322] A. I. Malz et al. “The Photometric LSST Astronomical Time-series Classification Challenge PLAsTiCC: Selection of a Performance Metric for Classification Probabilities Balancing Diverse Science Goals”. *Astronomical Journal* 158.5, 171 (Nov. 2019), p. 171. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ab3a2f](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab3a2f).
- [323] Ilya Mandel et al. “Binary population synthesis with probabilistic remnant mass and kick prescriptions”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 500.1 (Jan. 2021), pp. 1380–1384. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa3390](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa3390).
- [324] Kaisey S. Mandel et al. “A hierarchical Bayesian SED model for Type Ia supernovae in the optical to near-infrared”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 510.3 (Mar. 2022), pp. 3939–3966. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab3496](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab3496).
- [325] F. Mannucci et al. “A fundamental relation between mass, star formation rate and metallicity in local and high-redshift galaxies”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 408.4 (Nov. 2010), pp. 2115–2127. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17291.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.17291.x).
- [326] F. Mannucci et al. “The supernova rate per unit mass”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 433.3 (Apr. 2005), pp. 807–814. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361:20041411](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361:20041411).
- [327] Yao-Yuan Mao et al. “DESCQA: An Automated Validation Framework for Synthetic Sky Catalogs”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 234.2, 36 (Feb. 2018), p. 36. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/aaa6c3](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/aaa6c3).
- [328] D. Maoz et al. “Type-Ia Supernova Rates and the Progenitor Problem: A Review”. *Publications of the Astron. Soc. of Australia* 29.4 (Jan. 2012), pp. 447–465. DOI: [10.1071/AS11052](https://doi.org/10.1071/AS11052).
- [329] Dan Maoz et al. “Observational Clues to the Progenitors of Type Ia Supernovae”. *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophysics* 52 (Aug. 2014), pp. 107–170. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-082812-141031](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-082812-141031).
- [330] R. Margutti et al. “Inverse Compton X-Ray Emission from Supernovae with Compact Progenitors: Application to SN2011fe”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 751, 134 (June 2012), p. 134. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/751/2/134](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/751/2/134).
- [331] R. Margutti et al. “Relativistic Supernovae have Shorter-lived Central Engines or More Extended Progenitors: The Case of SN 2012ap”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 797, 107 (Dec. 2014), p. 107. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/797/2/107](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/797/2/107).
- [332] R. A. Marino et al. “The O3N2 and N2 abundance indicators revisited: improved calibrations based on CALIFA and T_e -based literature data”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 559, A114 (Nov. 2013), A114. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201321956](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201321956).

- [333] Frank J. Masci et al. “The Zwicky Transient Facility: Data Processing, Products, and Archive”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.995 (Jan. 2019), p. 018003. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aae8ac](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aae8ac).
- [334] Thomas Matheson et al. “The ANTARES Astronomical Time-domain Event Broker”. *Astronomical Journal* 161.3, 107 (Mar. 2021), p. 107. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/abd703](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/abd703).
- [335] Curtis McCully et al. “Real-time processing of the imaging data from the network of Las Cumbres Observatory Telescopes using BANZAI”. *Software and Cyberinfrastructure for Astronomy V*. Ed. by Juan C. Guzman et al. Vol. 10707. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. July 2018, 107070K, 107070K. DOI: [10.1117/12.2314340](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2314340).
- [336] L. Mestel. “On the Theory of White Dwarf Stars: I. The Energy Sources of White Dwarfs”. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 112.6 (Dec. 1952), pp. 583–597. ISSN: 0035-8711. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/112.6.583](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/112.6.583).
- [337] Michał J. Michałowski et al. “Connection of supernovae 2002ap, 2003gd, 2013ej, and 2019krl in M 74 with atomic gas accretion and spiral structure”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 638, A47 (June 2020), A47. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202037692](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202037692).
- [338] G. Miknaitis et al. “The ESSENCE Supernova Survey: Survey Optimization, Observations, and Supernova Photometry”. *Astrophysical Journal* 666.2 (Sept. 2007), pp. 674–693. DOI: [10.1086/519986](https://doi.org/10.1086/519986).
- [339] D. Milisavljevic et al. “Metamorphosis of SN 2014C: Delayed Interaction between a Hydrogen Poor Core-collapse Supernova and a Nearby Circumstellar Shell”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 815.2, 120 (Dec. 2015), p. 120. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/815/2/120](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/815/2/120).
- [340] Jennifer Millard et al. “Direct Analysis of Spectra of the Type IC Supernova SN 1994I”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 527.2 (Dec. 1999), pp. 746–756. DOI: [10.1086/308108](https://doi.org/10.1086/308108).
- [341] J. S. Miller et al. “Lick Obs. Tech. Rep. 66.” *LOTRM* (1993).
- [342] E. A. Milne. “The analysis of stellar structure”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 91 (Nov. 1930), pp. 4–55. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/91.1.4](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/91.1.4).
- [343] R. Minkowski. “Spectra of Supernovae”. *Publications of the ASP* 53.314 (Aug. 1941), p. 224. DOI: [10.1086/125315](https://doi.org/10.1086/125315).
- [344] Volodymyr Mnih et al. “Recurrent Models of Visual Attention”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1406.6247 (June 2014), arXiv:1406.6247.
- [345] Maryam Modjaz et al. “Host Galaxies of Type Ic and Broad-lined Type Ic Supernovae from the Palomar Transient Factory: Implications for Jet Production”. *Astrophysical Journal* 892.2, 153 (Apr. 2020), p. 153. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab4185](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab4185).

- [346] Maryam Modjaz et al. “The Spectral SN-GRB Connection: Systematic Spectral Comparisons between Type Ic Supernovae and Broad-lined Type Ic Supernovae with and without Gamma-Ray Bursts”. *Astrophysical Journal* 832.2, 108 (Dec. 2016), p. 108. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/832/2/108](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/832/2/108).
- [347] M MÓDOLO et al. “An expert supernova spectral classification using artificial neural networks”. *J Comp Int* 6.2 (2015), pp. 81–90.
- [348] Maxwell Moe et al. “Mind Your Ps and Qs: The Interrelation between Period (P) and Mass-ratio (Q) Distributions of Binary Stars”. *The Astrophysical Journals* 230.2, 15 (June 2017), p. 15. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/aa6fb6](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/aa6fb6).
- [349] A. Möller et al. “SuperNNova: an open-source framework for Bayesian, neural network-based supernova classification”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 491.3 (Jan. 2020), pp. 4277–4293. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz3312](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz3312).
- [350] Anais Möller et al. “FINK, a new generation of broker for the LSST community”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 501.3 (Mar. 2021), pp. 3272–3288. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa3602](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa3602).
- [351] Viktoriya Morozova et al. “Unifying Type II Supernova Light Curves with Dense Circumstellar Material”. *Astrophysical Journal* 838.1, 28 (Mar. 2017), p. 28. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa6251](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa6251).
- [352] J. C. Muñoz-Mateos et al. “Radial Distribution of Stars, Gas, and Dust in Sings Galaxies. II. Derived Dust Properties”. *Astrophysical Journal* 701.2 (Aug. 2009), pp. 1965–1991. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/701/2/1965](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/701/2/1965).
- [353] Fionn Murtagh. “Multilayer perceptrons for classification and regression”. *Neurocomputing* 2.5 (1991), pp. 183–197. ISSN: 0925-2312. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-2312\(91\)90023-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-2312(91)90023-5).
- [354] Daniel Muthukrishna et al. “DASH: Deep Learning for the Automated Spectral Classification of Supernovae and Their Hosts”. *Astrophysical Journal* 885.1, 85 (Nov. 2019), p. 85. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab48f4](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab48f4).
- [355] Daniel Muthukrishna et al. “RAPID: Early Classification of Explosive Transients Using Deep Learning”. *Publications of the ASP* 131.1005 (Nov. 2019), p. 118002. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/ab1609](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/ab1609).
- [356] D. K. Nadyozhin. “The Properties of NI CO Fe Decay”. *The Astrophysical Journals* 92 (June 1994), p. 527. DOI: [10.1086/192008](https://doi.org/10.1086/192008).
- [357] Preethi B. Nair et al. “A Catalog of Detailed Visual Morphological Classifications for 14,034 Galaxies in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 186.2 (Feb. 2010), pp. 427–456. DOI: [10.1088/0067-0049/186/2/427](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/186/2/427).

- [358] P. Narayana Bhat et al. “The Third Fermi GBM Gamma-Ray Burst Catalog: The First Six Years”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 223.2, 28 (Apr. 2016), p. 28. DOI: [10.3847/0067-0049/223/2/28](https://doi.org/10.3847/0067-0049/223/2/28).
- [359] James D. Neill et al. “THE EXTREME HOSTS OF EXTREME SUPERNOVAE”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 727.1 (2010), p. 15. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/727/1/15](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/727/1/15).
- [360] Yuan Qi Ni et al. “Infant-phase reddening by surface Fe-peak elements in a normal type Ia supernova”. *Nature Astronomy* 6 (Feb. 2022), pp. 568–576. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-022-01603-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-022-01603-4).
- [361] M. Nicholl et al. “On the diversity of superluminous supernovae: ejected mass as the dominant factor”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 452.4 (Oct. 2015), pp. 3869–3893. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv1522](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv1522).
- [362] Matt Nicholl. “SuperBol: A User-friendly Python Routine for Bolometric Light Curves”. *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society* 2.4, 230 (Dec. 2018), p. 230. DOI: [10.3847/2515-5172/aaf799](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/aaf799).
- [363] Matt Nicholl et al. “An extremely energetic supernova from a very massive star in a dense medium”. *Nature Astronomy* 4 (Apr. 2020), pp. 893–899. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-020-1066-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-020-1066-7).
- [364] Matt Nicholl et al. “The Magnetar Model for Type I Superluminous Supernovae. I. Bayesian Analysis of the Full Multicolor Light-curve Sample with MOSFiT”. *Astrophysical Journal* 850.1, 55 (Nov. 2017), p. 55. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa9334](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa9334).
- [365] K. Nomoto et al. “A carbon-oxygen star as progenitor of the type Ic supernova 1994I”. *Nature* 371.6494 (Sept. 1994), pp. 227–229. DOI: [10.1038/371227a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/371227a0).
- [366] B. O’Connor et al. “A deep survey of short GRB host galaxies over $z \sim 0 - 2$: implications for offsets, redshifts, and environments”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2204.09059 (Apr. 2022), arXiv:2204.09059.
- [367] J. B. Oke et al. “The Keck Low-Resolution Imaging Spectrometer”. *Publications of the ASP* 107 (Apr. 1995), p. 375. DOI: [10.1086/133562](https://doi.org/10.1086/133562).
- [368] D. O’Neill et al. “A progenitor candidate for the type II-P supernova SN 2018aoq in NGC 4151”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 622, L1 (Feb. 2019), p. L1. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201834566](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201834566).
- [369] Christopher A. Onken et al. “SkyMapper Southern Survey: Second data release (DR2)”. *Publications of the Astron. Soc. of Australia* 36, e033 (Aug. 2019), e033. DOI: [10.1017/pasa.2019.27](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2019.27).

- [370] R. Pakmor et al. “Normal Type Ia Supernovae from Violent Mergers of White Dwarf Binaries”. *Astrophysical Journal, Letters* 747.1, L10 (Mar. 2012), p. L10. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/747/1/L10](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/747/1/L10).
- [371] Y. C. Pan et al. “The Old Host-galaxy Environment of SSS17a, the First Electromagnetic Counterpart to a Gravitational-wave Source”. *Astrophysical Journal* 848.2, L30 (Oct. 2017), p. L30. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa9116](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa9116).
- [372] Fiona H. Panther et al. “SN1991bg-like supernovae are associated with old stellar populations”. *Publications of the Astron. Soc. of Australia* 36, e031 (Aug. 2019), e031. DOI: [10.1017/pasa.2019.24](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2019.24).
- [373] Cecilia Payne Gaposchkin. “On the Physical Condition of the Supernovae”. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* 22.6 (June 1936), pp. 332–336. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.22.6.332](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.22.6.332).
- [374] Margaret Sullivan Pepe et al. “Combining predictors for classification using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve”. *Biometrics* 62.1 (2006), pp. 221–229.
- [375] D. A. Perley et al. “Host-galaxy Properties of 32 Low-redshift Superluminous Supernovae from the Palomar Transient Factory”. *Astrophysical Journal* 830.1, 13 (Oct. 2016), p. 13. DOI: [10.3847/0004-637X/830/1/13](https://doi.org/10.3847/0004-637X/830/1/13).
- [376] Daniel A. Perley et al. “The fast, luminous ultraviolet transient AT2018cow: extreme supernova, or disruption of a star by an intermediate-mass black hole?” *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 484.1 (Mar. 2019), pp. 1031–1049. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty3420](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty3420).
- [377] Daniel A. Perley et al. “The Type Icn SN 2021csp: Implications for the Origins of the Fastest Supernovae and the Fates of Wolf-Rayet Stars”. *Astrophysical Journal* 927.2, 180 (Mar. 2022), p. 180. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac478e](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac478e).
- [378] Daniel A. Perley et al. “The Zwicky Transient Facility Bright Transient Survey. II. A Public Statistical Sample for Exploring Supernova Demographics”. *Astrophysical Journal* 904.1, 35 (Nov. 2020), p. 35. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abbd98](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abbd98).
- [379] S. Perlmutter et al. “Measurements of Ω and Λ from 42 High-Redshift Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 517.2 (June 1999), pp. 565–586. DOI: [10.1086/307221](https://doi.org/10.1086/307221).
- [380] WWTG Peterson et al. “The theory of signal detectability”. *Transactions of the IRE professional group on information theory* 4.4 (1954), pp. 171–212.
- [381] M. M. Phillips. “The Absolute Magnitudes of Type IA Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal, Letters* 413 (Aug. 1993), p. L105. DOI: [10.1086/186970](https://doi.org/10.1086/186970).

- [382] M. M. Phillips et al. “The Peculiar SN 2005hk: Do Some Type Ia Supernovae Explode as Deflagrations?1,” *Publications of the ASP* 119.854 (Apr. 2007), pp. 360–387. DOI: [10.1086/518372](https://doi.org/10.1086/518372).
- [383] Óscar Pimentel et al. “Deep Attention-Based Supernovae Classification of Multi-Band Light-Curves”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2201.08482 (Jan. 2022), arXiv:2201.08482.
- [384] Anthony L. Piro. “Using Double-peaked Supernova Light Curves to Study Extended Material”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 808.2, L51 (Aug. 2015), p. L51. DOI: [10.1088/2041-8205/808/2/L51](https://doi.org/10.1088/2041-8205/808/2/L51).
- [385] Anthony L. Piro et al. “Shock Cooling Emission from Extended Material Revisited”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 909.2, 209 (Mar. 2021), p. 209. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abe2b1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abe2b1).
- [386] Planck Collaboration et al. “Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 641, A6 (Sept. 2020), A6. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201833910](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833910).
- [387] Brodie Popovic et al. “The Pantheon+ Analysis: Forward-Modeling the Dust and Intrinsic Colour Distributions of Type Ia Supernovae, and Quantifying their Impact on Cosmological Inferences”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2112.04456 (Dec. 2021), arXiv:2112.04456.
- [388] Dovi Poznanski et al. “An empirical relation between sodium absorption and dust extinction”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 426.2 (Oct. 2012), pp. 1465–1474. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21796.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21796.x).
- [389] Dovi Poznanski et al. “Bayesian Single-Epoch Photometric Classification of Supernovae”. *Astronomical Journal* 134.3 (Sept. 2007), pp. 1285–1297. DOI: [10.1086/520956](https://doi.org/10.1086/520956).
- [390] S. Prajs et al. “The volumetric rate of superluminous supernovae at $z \sim 1$ ”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 464.3 (Jan. 2017), pp. 3568–3579. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stw1942](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stw1942).
- [391] S. J. Prentice et al. “Investigating the properties of stripped-envelope supernovae; what are the implications for their progenitors?” *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 485.2 (May 2019), pp. 1559–1578. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty3399](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty3399).
- [392] J. X. Prochaska et al. “The Galaxy Hosts and Large-Scale Environments of Short-Hard Gamma-Ray Bursts”. *Astrophysical Journal* 642.2 (May 2006), pp. 989–994. DOI: [10.1086/501160](https://doi.org/10.1086/501160).
- [393] M. Pursiainen et al. “Rapidly evolving transients in the Dark Energy Survey”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 481.1 (Nov. 2018), pp. 894–917. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/sty2309](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/sty2309).
- [394] Yu-Jing Qin et al. “Linking Extragalactic Transients and Their Host Galaxy Properties: Transient Sample, Multiwavelength Host Identification, and Database Construction”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 259.1, 13 (Mar. 2022), p. 13. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4365/ac2fa1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ac2fa1).

- [395] Helen Qu et al. “Photometric Classification of Early-time Supernova Light Curves with SCONE”. *Astronomical Journal* 163.2, 57 (Feb. 2022), p. 57. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ac39a1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac39a1).
- [396] Helen Qu et al. “SCONE: Supernova Classification with a Convolutional Neural Network”. *Astronomical Journal* 162.2, 67 (Aug. 2021), p. 67. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ac0824](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac0824).
- [397] R. Quimby et al. “Supernova 2006X in NGC 4321”. *Central Bureau Electronic Telegrams* 393 (Feb. 2006), p. 1.
- [398] Robert Michael Quimby. “The Texas Supernova Search”. PhD thesis. University of Texas, Austin, Jan. 2006.
- [399] G. Raaijmakers et al. “Constraints on the Dense Matter Equation of State and Neutron Star Properties from NICER’s Mass-Radius Estimate of PSR J0740+6620 and Multimessenger Observations”. *Astrophysical Journal* 918.2, L29 (Sept. 2021), p. L29. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/ac089a](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ac089a).
- [400] Chengping Rao et al. “Physics-informed deep learning for incompressible laminar flows”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2002.10558 (Feb. 2020), arXiv:2002.10558.
- [401] Carl Edward Rasmussen. “Gaussian processes for machine learning”. MIT Press, 2006.
- [402] J. C. Rastinejad et al. “A Kilonova Following a Long-Duration Gamma-Ray Burst at 350 Mpc”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2204.10864 (Apr. 2022), arXiv:2204.10864.
- [403] Jillian C. Rastinejad et al. “A kilonova following a long-duration gamma-ray burst at 350 Mpc”. *Nature* 612.7939 (Dec. 2022), pp. 223–227. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-022-05390-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-022-05390-w).
- [404] Siamak Ravanbakhsh et al. “Enabling Dark Energy Science with Deep Generative Models of Galaxy Images”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1609.05796 (Sept. 2016), arXiv:1609.05796.
- [405] Gibson Reaves. “NOTES ON EXTRAGALACTIC SUPERNOVAE”. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific* 65.386 (1953), pp. 242–245. ISSN: 00046280, 15383873.
- [406] A. Rest et al. “A fast-evolving luminous transient discovered by K2/Kepler”. *Nature Astronomy* 2 (Mar. 2018), pp. 307–311. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-018-0423-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-018-0423-2).
- [407] A. Rest et al. “Testing LMC Microlensing Scenarios: The Discrimination Power of the SuperMACHO Microlensing Survey”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 634.2 (Dec. 2005), pp. 1103–1115. DOI: [10.1086/497060](https://doi.org/10.1086/497060).
- [408] Mehdi Rezaeian Zadeh et al. “Daily outflow prediction by multi layer perceptron with logistic sigmoid and tangent sigmoid activation functions”. *Water resources management* 24 (2010), pp. 2673–2688.

- [409] J. Rho et al. “Near-infrared and Optical Observations of Type Ic SN 2020oi and Broad-lined Type Ic SN 2020bvc: Carbon Monoxide, Dust, and High-velocity Supernova Ejecta”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 908.2, 232 (Feb. 2021), p. 232. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abd850](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abd850).
- [410] M. W. Richmond et al. “UBVRI Photometry of the Type IC SN 1994I in M51”. *Astronomical Journal* 111 (Jan. 1996), p. 327. DOI: [10.1086/117785](https://doi.org/10.1086/117785).
- [411] Alex Rimoldi et al. “Simulations of stripped core-collapse supernovae in close binaries”. *Computational Astrophysics and Cosmology* 3, 2 (Mar. 2016), p. 2. DOI: [10.1186/s40668-016-0015-4](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40668-016-0015-4).
- [412] Steven A. Rodney et al. “Type Ia Supernova Rate Measurements to Redshift 2.5 from CANDELS: Searching for Prompt Explosions in the Early Universe”. *Astronomical Journal* 148.1, 13 (July 2014), p. 13. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/148/1/13](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/148/1/13).
- [413] M. Roman et al. “Dependence of Type Ia supernova luminosities on their local environment”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 615, A68 (July 2018), A68. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201731425](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201731425).
- [414] P. W. A. Roming et al. “The Swift Ultra-Violet/Optical Telescope”. *Space Science Reviews* 120 (Oct. 2005), pp. 95–142. DOI: [10.1007/s11214-005-5095-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-005-5095-4).
- [415] D. J. Rosario et al. “The host galaxies of X-ray selected active galactic nuclei to $z = 2.5$: Structure, star formation, and their relationships from CANDELS and Herschel/PACS”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 573, A85 (Jan. 2015), A85. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201423782](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201423782).
- [416] B. M. Rose et al. “Think Global, Act Local: The Influence of Environment Age and Host Mass on Type Ia Supernova Light Curves”. *Astrophysical Journal* 874.1, 32 (Mar. 2019), p. 32. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab0704](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab0704).
- [417] Arpita Roy. “Progenitors of Long-Duration Gamma-ray Bursts”. *Galaxies* 9.4 (Oct. 2021), p. 79. DOI: [10.3390/galaxies9040079](https://doi.org/10.3390/galaxies9040079).
- [418] Yulia Rubanova et al. “Latent ODEs for Irregularly-Sampled Time Series”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1907.03907 (July 2019), arXiv:1907.03907. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.1907.03907](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1907.03907).
- [419] Ashley J. Ruiter et al. “Rates and Delay Times of Type Ia Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 699.2 (July 2009), pp. 2026–2036. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/699/2/2026](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/699/2/2026).
- [420] David E Rumelhart et al. “Learning representations by back-propagating errors”. *nature* 323.6088 (1986), pp. 533–536.
- [421] Stuart D. Ryder et al. “Circumnuclear Star Formation in M100”. *Astrophysics and Space Science* 276 (Mar. 2001), pp. 405–412. DOI: [10.1023/A:1017578713184](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1017578713184).

- [422] D. K. Sahu et al. “Broad-line Type Ic supernova SN 2014ad”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 475.2 (Apr. 2018), pp. 2591–2604. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx3212](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx3212).
- [423] Takaya Saito et al. “The precision-recall plot is more informative than the ROC plot when evaluating binary classifiers on imbalanced datasets”. *PloS one* 10.3 (2015), e0118432.
- [424] Kazushi Sakamoto et al. “Bar-Driven Gas Structure and Star Formation in the Center of M100”. *Astronomical Journal* 110 (Nov. 1995), p. 2075. DOI: [10.1086/117670](https://doi.org/10.1086/117670).
- [425] Masao Sako et al. “Photometric Type Ia Supernova Candidates from the Three-year SDSS-II SN Survey Data”. *Astrophysical Journal* 738.2, 162 (Sept. 2011), p. 162. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/738/2/162](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/738/2/162).
- [426] Masao Sako et al. “The Data Release of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey-II Supernova Survey”. *Publications of the ASP* 130.988 (June 2018), p. 064002. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aab4e0](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aab4e0).
- [427] Masao Sako et al. “The Sloan Digital Sky Survey-II Supernova Survey: Search Algorithm and Follow-up Observations”. *Astronomical Journal* 135.1 (Jan. 2008), pp. 348–373. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/135/1/348](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/135/1/348).
- [428] Mara Salvato et al. “The many flavours of photometric redshifts”. *Nature Astronomy* 3 (June 2019), pp. 212–222. DOI: [10.1038/s41550-018-0478-0](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-018-0478-0).
- [429] H. Sana et al. “Binary Interaction Dominates the Evolution of Massive Stars”. *Science* 337.6093 (July 2012), p. 444. DOI: [10.1126/science.1223344](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1223344).
- [430] Alexis Sánchez et al. “Amortized variational inference for type ia supernova light curves”. *Machine Learning and the Physical Sciences Workshop, 35th Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*. 2021.
- [431] Nir Sapir et al. “UV/Optical Emission from the Expanding Envelopes of Type II Supernovae”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 838.2, 130 (Apr. 2017), p. 130. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa64df](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa64df).
- [432] D. N. Sauer et al. “The properties of the ‘standard’ Type Ic supernova 1994I from spectral models”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 369.4 (July 2006), pp. 1939–1948. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2006.10438.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2006.10438.x).
- [433] S. Savaglio et al. “GRB Host Studies (GHostS)”. *Gamma-Ray Bursts in the Swift Era*. Ed. by S. S. Holt et al. Vol. 836. American Institute of Physics Conference Series. May 2006, pp. 540–545. DOI: [10.1063/1.2207951](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2207951).
- [434] R. A. Scalzo et al. “Nearby Supernova Factory Observations of SN 2007if: First Total Mass Measurement of a Super-Chandrasekhar-Mass Progenitor”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 713.2 (Apr. 2010), pp. 1073–1094. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/713/2/1073](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/713/2/1073).

- [435] Paul L. Schechter et al. “DoPHOT, A CCD Photometry Program: Description and Tests”. *Publications of the ASP* 105 (Nov. 1993), p. 1342. DOI: [10.1086/133316](https://doi.org/10.1086/133316).
- [436] Edward F. Schlafly et al. “Measuring Reddening with Sloan Digital Sky Survey Stellar Spectra and Recalibrating SFD”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 737.2, 103 (Aug. 2011), p. 103. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/737/2/103](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/737/2/103).
- [437] Brian P. Schmidt et al. “The unusual supernova SN1993J in the galaxy M81”. *Nature* 364.6438 (Aug. 1993), pp. 600–602. DOI: [10.1038/364600a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/364600a0).
- [438] S. Schulze et al. “Cosmic evolution and metal aversion in superluminous supernova host galaxies”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 473.1 (Jan. 2018), pp. 1258–1285. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx2352](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx2352).
- [439] D. Scolnic et al. “Supernova Siblings: Assessing the Consistency of Properties of Type Ia Supernovae that Share the Same Parent Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 896.1, L13 (June 2020), p. L13. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/ab8735](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ab8735).
- [440] D. M. Scolnic et al. “The Complete Light-curve Sample of Spectroscopically Confirmed SNe Ia from Pan-STARRS1 and Cosmological Constraints from the Combined Pantheon Sample”. *Astrophysical Journal* 859.2, 101 (June 2018), p. 101. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aab9bb](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aab9bb).
- [441] Ken J. Shen et al. “Three Hypervelocity White Dwarfs in Gaia DR2: Evidence for Dynamically Driven Double-degenerate Double-detonation Type Ia Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 865.1, 15 (Sept. 2018), p. 15. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aad55b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aad55b).
- [442] Masaru Shibata et al. “Merger and Mass Ejection of Neutron Star Binaries”. *Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science* 69 (Oct. 2019), pp. 41–64. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-nucl-101918-023625](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-nucl-101918-023625).
- [443] Joshua H. Shiode et al. “Setting the Stage for Circumstellar Interaction in Core-Collapse Supernovae. II. Wave-driven Mass Loss in Supernova Progenitors”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 780.1, 96 (Jan. 2014), p. 96. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/780/1/96](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/780/1/96).
- [444] Isaac Shivvers et al. “Revisiting the Lick Observatory Supernova Search Volume-limited Sample: Updated Classifications and Revised Stripped-envelope Supernova Fractions”. *Publications of the ASP* 129.975 (May 2017), p. 054201. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aa54a6](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aa54a6).
- [445] M. R. Siebert et al. “Investigating the diversity of Type Ia supernova spectra with the open-source relational data base KAEPORA”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 486.4 (July 2019), pp. 5785–5808. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz1209](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz1209).
- [446] M. R. Siebert et al. “UCSC Transient Classification Report for 2020-01-09”. *Transient Name Server Classification Report* 2020-90 (Jan. 2020), p. 1.

- [447] Matthew R. Siebert et al. “Strong Calcium Emission Indicates that the Ultraviolet-flashing SN Ia 2019yvq Was the Result of a Sub-Chandrasekar-mass Double-detonation Explosion”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 900.2, L27 (Sept. 2020), p. L27. DOI: [10.3847/2041-8213/abae6e](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/abae6e).
- [448] Jeffrey M. Silverman et al. “After the Fall: Late-Time Spectroscopy of Type IIP Supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 467.1 (May 2017), pp. 369–411. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx058](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx058).
- [449] Jeffrey M. Silverman et al. “Berkeley Supernova Ia Program - I. Observations, data reduction and spectroscopic sample of 582 low-redshift Type Ia supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 425.3 (Sept. 2012), pp. 1789–1818. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21270.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2012.21270.x).
- [450] Colin T. Slater et al. “Morphological Star-Galaxy Separation”. *Astronomical Journal* 159.2, 65 (Feb. 2020), p. 65. DOI: [10.3847/1538-3881/ab6166](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ab6166).
- [451] S. J. Smartt. “Observational Constraints on the Progenitors of Core-Collapse Supernovae: The Case for Missing High-Mass Stars”. *Publications of the Astron. Soc. of Australia* 32, e016 (Apr. 2015), e016. DOI: [10.1017/pasa.2015.17](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2015.17).
- [452] S. J. Smartt et al. “A kilonova as the electromagnetic counterpart to a gravitational-wave source”. *Nature* 551.7678 (Nov. 2017), pp. 75–79. DOI: [10.1038/nature24303](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24303).
- [453] S. J. Smartt et al. “Mass limits for the progenitor star of supernova 2001du and other Type II-P supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 343.3 (Aug. 2003), pp. 735–749. DOI: [10.1046/j.1365-8711.2003.06718.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-8711.2003.06718.x).
- [454] Stephen J. Smartt. “Progenitors of Core-Collapse Supernovae”. *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophysics* 47.1 (Sept. 2009), pp. 63–106. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-082708-101737](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-082708-101737).
- [455] Ken Smith. “Lasair: The transient alert broker for LSST:UK”. *The Extragalactic Explosive Universe: the New Era of Transient Surveys and Data-Driven Discovery*. Oct. 2019, 51, p. 51. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3478098](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3478098).
- [456] M. Smith et al. “First cosmology results using type Ia supernovae from the Dark Energy Survey: the effect of host galaxy properties on supernova luminosity”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 494.3 (May 2020), pp. 4426–4447. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa946](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa946).
- [457] Mathew Smith et al. “The SDSS-II Supernova Survey: Parameterizing the Type Ia Supernova Rate as a Function of Host Galaxy Properties”. *Astrophysical Journal* 755.1, 61 (Aug. 2012), p. 61. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/755/1/61](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/755/1/61).
- [458] Nathan Smith. “Mass Loss: Its Effect on the Evolution and Fate of High-Mass Stars”. *Annual Review of Astron and Astrophysics* 52 (Aug. 2014), pp. 487–528. DOI: [10.1146/annurev-astro-081913-040025](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-astro-081913-040025).

- [459] Nathan Smith et al. “Observed fractions of core-collapse supernova types and initial masses of their single and binary progenitor stars”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 412.3 (Apr. 2011), pp. 1522–1538. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.17229.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2011.17229.x).
- [460] A. M. Soderberg et al. “A relativistic type Ibc supernova without a detected γ -ray burst”. *Nature* 463 (Jan. 2010), pp. 513–515. DOI: [10.1038/nature08714](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08714).
- [461] A. M. Soderberg et al. “Late-Time Radio Observations of 68 Type Ibc Supernovae: Strong Constraints on Off-Axis Gamma-Ray Bursts”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 638 (Feb. 2006), pp. 930–937. DOI: [10.1086/499121](https://doi.org/10.1086/499121).
- [462] A. M. Soderberg et al. “Relativistic ejecta from X-ray flash XRF 060218 and the rate of cosmic explosions”. *Nature* 442 (Aug. 2006), pp. 1014–1017. DOI: [10.1038/nature05087](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05087).
- [463] A. M. Soderberg et al. “The Afterglow, Energetics, and Host Galaxy of the Short-Hard Gamma-Ray Burst 051221a”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 650 (Oct. 2006), pp. 261–271. DOI: [10.1086/506429](https://doi.org/10.1086/506429).
- [464] J. Sollerman et al. “Two stripped envelope supernovae with circumstellar interaction. But only one really shows it”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 643, A79 (Nov. 2020), A79. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/202038960](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202038960).
- [465] Joshua S. Speagle. “DYNESTY: a dynamic nested sampling package for estimating Bayesian posteriors and evidences”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 493.3 (Apr. 2020), pp. 3132–3158. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa278](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa278).
- [466] D. Spergel et al. “Wide-Field Infrared Survey Telescope-Astrophysics Focused Telescope Assets WFIRST-AFTA 2015 Report”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1503.03757 (Mar. 2015), arXiv:1503.03757.
- [467] Niharika Sravan et al. “Real-time, Value-driven Data Augmentation in the Era of LSST”. *Astrophysical Journal* 893.2, 127 (Apr. 2020), p. 127. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab8128](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab8128).
- [468] Aaron Stemo et al. “A Catalog of AGN Host Galaxies Observed with HST/ACS: Correlations between Star Formation and AGN Activity”. *Astrophysical Journal* 888.2, 78 (Jan. 2020), p. 78. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab5f66](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab5f66).
- [469] Iskra Strateva et al. “Color Separation of Galaxy Types in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey Imaging Data”. *Astronomical Journal* 122.4 (Oct. 2001), pp. 1861–1874. DOI: [10.1086/323301](https://doi.org/10.1086/323301).
- [470] R. A. Street et al. “General-purpose software for managing astronomical observing programs in the LSST era”. *Software and Cyberinfrastructure for Astronomy V*. Ed. by Juan C. Guzman et al. Vol. 10707. Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series. July 2018, 1070711, p. 1070711. DOI: [10.1117/12.2312293](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2312293).

- [471] M. D. Stritzinger et al. “The Carnegie Supernova Project I. Methods to estimate host-galaxy reddening of stripped-envelope supernovae”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 609, A135 (Feb. 2018), A135. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201730843](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201730843).
- [472] Louis-Gregory Strolger et al. “Delay Time Distributions of Type Ia Supernovae from Galaxy and Cosmic Star Formation Histories”. *Astrophysical Journal* 890.2, 140 (Feb. 2020), p. 140. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab6a97](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab6a97).
- [473] Louis-Gregory Strolger et al. “The Rate of Core Collapse Supernovae to Redshift 2.5 from the CANDELS and CLASH Supernova Surveys”. *Astrophysical Journal* 813.2, 93 (Nov. 2015), p. 93. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/813/2/93](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/813/2/93).
- [474] Linda E. Strubbe et al. “Optical flares from the tidal disruption of stars by massive black holes”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 400.4 (Dec. 2009), pp. 2070–2084. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15599.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2009.15599.x).
- [475] M. Sullivan et al. “Rates and Properties of Type Ia Supernovae as a Function of Mass and Star Formation in Their Host Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 648.2 (Sept. 2006), pp. 868–883. DOI: [10.1086/506137](https://doi.org/10.1086/506137).
- [476] M. Sullivan et al. “The dependence of Type Ia Supernovae luminosities on their host galaxies”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 406.2 (Aug. 2010), pp. 782–802. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.16731.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2010.16731.x).
- [477] Ning-Chen Sun et al. “A UV census of the environments of stripped-envelope supernovae”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2209.05283 (Sept. 2022), arXiv:2209.05283. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2209.05283](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.05283).
- [478] F. Taddia et al. “Analysis of broad-lined Type Ic supernovae from the (intermediate) Palomar Transient Factory”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 621, A71 (Jan. 2019), A71. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201834429](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201834429).
- [479] F. Taddia et al. “iPTF15dtg: a double-peaked Type Ic supernova from a massive progenitor”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 592, A89 (Aug. 2016), A89. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201628703](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201628703).
- [480] F. Taddia et al. “The Carnegie Supernova Project I. Analysis of stripped-envelope supernova light curves”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 609, A136 (Feb. 2018), A136. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201730844](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201730844).
- [481] Tyler Takaro et al. “Constraining Type Iax supernova progenitor systems with stellar population age dating”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 493.1 (Mar. 2020), pp. 986–1002. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa294](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa294).

- [482] G. A. Tammann. “On the Frequency of Supernovae as a Function of the Integral Properties of Intermediate and Late Type Spiral Galaxies”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 8 (Oct. 1970), p. 458.
- [483] Masaomi Tanaka et al. “Radioactively Powered Emission from Black Hole-Neutron Star Mergers”. *Astrophysical Journal* 780.1, 31 (Jan. 2014), p. 31. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/780/1/31](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/780/1/31).
- [484] Stefan Taubenberger. “The Extremes of Thermonuclear Supernovae”. *Handbook of Supernovae*. Ed. by Athem W. Alsabti et al. 2017, p. 317. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-21846-5_37](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21846-5_37).
- [485] Samaporn Tinyanont et al. “Infrared Spectropolarimetric Detection of Intrinsic Polarization from a Core-Collapse Supernova”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2102.02075 (Feb. 2021), arXiv:2102.02075.
- [486] J. L. Tonry et al. “ATLAS: A High-cadence All-sky Survey System”. *Publications of the ASP* 130.988 (June 2018), p. 064505. DOI: [10.1088/1538-3873/aabadf](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/aabadf).
- [487] J. L. Tonry et al. “The Pan-STARRS1 Photometric System”. *Astrophysical Journal* 750.2, 99 (May 2012), p. 99. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/750/2/99](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/750/2/99).
- [488] A. Tornambé et al. “Pre-explosive observational properties of Type Ia supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 431.2 (May 2013), pp. 1812–1822. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stt295](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt295).
- [489] Tomonori Totani et al. “Delay Time Distribution Measurement of Type Ia Supernovae by the Subaru/XMM-Newton Deep Survey and Implications for the Progenitor”. *Publications of the ASJ* 60 (Dec. 2008), p. 1327. DOI: [10.1093/pasj/60.6.1327](https://doi.org/10.1093/pasj/60.6.1327).
- [490] Eleni Tsaprazi et al. “The large-scale environment of thermonuclear and core-collapse supernovae”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 510.1 (Feb. 2022), pp. 366–372. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab3525](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab3525).
- [491] S. Valenti et al. “Supernova 2013by: a Type IIL supernova with a IIP-like light-curve drop”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 448.3 (Apr. 2015), pp. 2608–2616. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stv208](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stv208).
- [492] S. Valenti et al. “The broad-lined Type Ic supernova 2003jd”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 383.4 (Feb. 2008), pp. 1485–1500. DOI: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12647.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2007.12647.x).
- [493] Sidney van den Bergh et al. “Classifications of the Host Galaxies of Supernovae, Set III”. *Publications of the ASP* 117.834 (Aug. 2005), pp. 773–782. DOI: [10.1086/431435](https://doi.org/10.1086/431435).
- [494] Arjen van der Wel. “The Dependence of Galaxy Morphology and Structure on Environment and Stellar Mass”. *Astrophysical Journal* 675.1 (Mar. 2008), p. L13. DOI: [10.1086/529432](https://doi.org/10.1086/529432).
- [495] Schuyler D. Van Dyk et al. “SN 2017ein and the Possible First Identification of a Type Ic Supernova Progenitor”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 860.2, 90 (June 2018), p. 90. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aac32c](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aac32c).
- [496] Schuyler D. Van Dyk et al. “The Type IIb Supernova 2013df and its Cool Supergiant Progenitor”. *Astronomical Journal* 147.2, 37 (Feb. 2014), p. 37. DOI: [10.1088/0004-6256/147/2/37](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-6256/147/2/37).

- [497] V. A. Villar et al. “Supernova Photometric Classification Pipelines Trained on Spectroscopically Classified Supernovae from the Pan-STARRS1 Medium-deep Survey”. *Astrophysical Journal* 884.1, 83 (Oct. 2019), p. 83. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab418c](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab418c).
- [498] V. Ashley Villar. “Amortized Bayesian Inference for Supernovae in the Era of the Vera Rubin Observatory Using Normalizing Flows”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2211.04480 (Nov. 2022), arXiv:2211.04480. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.2211.04480](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.04480).
- [499] V. Ashley Villar et al. “Anomaly Detection for Multivariate Time Series of Exotic Supernovae”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:2010.11194 (Oct. 2020), arXiv:2010.11194.
- [500] V. Ashley Villar et al. “Superluminous Supernovae in LSST: Rates, Detection Metrics, and Light-curve Modeling”. *Astrophysical Journal* 869.2, 166 (Dec. 2018), p. 166. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aeee6a](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aeee6a).
- [501] V. Ashley Villar et al. “SuperRAENN: A Semisupervised Supernova Photometric Classification Pipeline Trained on Pan-STARRS1 Medium-Deep Survey Supernovae”. *Astrophysical Journal* 905.2, 94 (Dec. 2020), p. 94. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abc6fd](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abc6fd).
- [502] M. Vincenzi et al. “Spectrophotometric templates for core-collapse supernovae and their application in simulations of time-domain surveys”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 489.4 (Nov. 2019), pp. 5802–5821. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stz2448](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz2448).
- [503] M. Vincenzi et al. “The Dark Energy Survey supernova programme: modelling selection efficiency and observed core-collapse supernova contamination”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 505.2 (Aug. 2021), pp. 2819–2839. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab1353](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab1353).
- [504] A. von Kienlin et al. “The Fourth Fermi-GBM Gamma-Ray Burst Catalog: A Decade of Data”. *Astrophysical Journal* 893.1, 46 (Apr. 2020), p. 46. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/ab7a18](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab7a18).
- [505] Andreas von Kienlin et al. “The Second Fermi GBM Gamma-Ray Burst Catalog: The First Four Years”. *Astrophysical Journal, Supplement* 211.1, 13 (Mar. 2014), p. 13. DOI: [10.1088/0067-0049/211/1/13](https://doi.org/10.1088/0067-0049/211/1/13).
- [506] Jingdong Wang et al. “Hashing for Similarity Search: A Survey”. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv:1408.2927 (Aug. 2014), arXiv:1408.2927.
- [507] Lifan Wang et al. “Supernovae and Their Host Galaxies”. *Astrophysical Journal* 483.1 (July 1997), pp. L29–L32. DOI: [10.1086/310737](https://doi.org/10.1086/310737).
- [508] R. M. West et al. “Astrometry of SN 1987A and Sanduleak -69 202.” *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 177 (May 1987), pp. L1–L3.
- [509] John Whelan et al. “Binaries and Supernovae of Type I”. *Astrophysical Journal* 186 (Dec. 1973), pp. 1007–1014. DOI: [10.1086/152565](https://doi.org/10.1086/152565).

- [510] Fred L. Whipple et al. “Theoretical Synthesis of Supernova Spectra”. *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 84 (Jan. 1941), p. 1.
- [511] Marc Williamson et al. “Modeling Type Ic Supernovae with TARDIS: Hidden Helium in SN 1994I?” *The Astrophysical Journal* 908.2, 150 (Feb. 2021), p. 150. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/abd244](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abd244).
- [512] P. Wiseman et al. “Rates and delay times of Type Ia supernovae in the Dark Energy Survey”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 506.3 (Sept. 2021), pp. 3330–3348. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stab1943](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stab1943).
- [513] P. Wiseman et al. “Supernova host galaxies in the dark energy survey: I. Deep coadds, photometry, and stellar masses”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 495.4 (July 2020), pp. 4040–4060. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa1302](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa1302).
- [514] P. Wiseman et al. “The host galaxies of 106 rapidly evolving transients discovered by the Dark Energy Survey”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 498.2 (Oct. 2020), pp. 2575–2593. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/staa2474](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/staa2474).
- [515] Jin-Long Wu et al. “Physics-informed machine learning approach for augmenting turbulence models: A comprehensive framework”. *Physical Review Fluids* 3.7, 074602 (July 2018), p. 074602. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevFluids.3.074602](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.3.074602).
- [516] Danfeng Xiang et al. “Observations of SN 2017ein Reveal Shock Breakout Emission and a Massive Progenitor Star for a Type Ic Supernova”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 871.2, 176 (Feb. 2019), p. 176. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aaf8b0](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aaf8b0).
- [517] S. C. Yoon et al. “Type Ib/c Supernovae in Binary Systems. I. Evolution and Properties of the Progenitor Stars”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 725.1 (Dec. 2010), pp. 940–954. DOI: [10.1088/0004-637X/725/1/940](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/725/1/940).
- [518] Sung-Chul Yoon. “Evolutionary Models for Type Ib/c Supernova Progenitors”. *Publications of the Astron. Soc. of Australia* 32, e015 (Apr. 2015), e015. DOI: [10.1017/pasa.2015.16](https://doi.org/10.1017/pasa.2015.16).
- [519] Sung-Chul Yoon. “Towards a better understanding of the evolution of Wolf-Rayet stars and Type Ib/Ic supernova progenitors”. *Monthly Notices of the RAS* 470.4 (Oct. 2017), pp. 3970–3980. DOI: [10.1093/mnras/stx1496](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stx1496).
- [520] Donald G. York et al. “The Sloan Digital Sky Survey: Technical Summary”. *Astronomical Journal* 120.3 (Sept. 2000), pp. 1579–1587. DOI: [10.1086/301513](https://doi.org/10.1086/301513).
- [521] S. Yu et al. “The gravitational wave signal from diverse populations of double white dwarf binaries in the Galaxy”. *Astronomy and Astrophysics* 521, A85 (Oct. 2010), A85. DOI: [10.1051/0004-6361/201014827](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201014827).

- [522] Ann Zabludoff et al. “Distinguishing Tidal Disruption Events from Impostors”. *Space Science Reviews* 217.4, 54 (June 2021), p. 54. DOI: [10.1007/s11214-021-00829-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-021-00829-4).
- [523] E. Zapartas et al. “Predicting the Presence of Companions for Stripped-envelope Supernovae: The Case of the Broad-lined Type Ic SN 2002ap”. *The Astrophysical Journal* 842.2, 125 (June 2017), p. 125. DOI: [10.3847/1538-4357/aa7467](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa7467).
- [524] F. Zwicky. “Characteristic Temperatures in Super-Novae”. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science* 22.9 (Sept. 1936), pp. 557–561. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.22.9.557](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.22.9.557).
- [525] F. Zwicky. “Some Results of the Search for Super-Novae”. *Phys. Rev.* 53 (12 1938), pp. 1019–1020. DOI: [10.1103/PhysRev.53.1019](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.53.1019).